

**A CRITICAL COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE
NATIONAL ACCREDITATION STANDARDS FOR
HOSPITALS OF INDIA, AUSTRALIA, DENMARK
AND SOUTH AFRICA**

**A Thesis submitted to
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY,
MANGALORE, KARNATAKA STATE, INDIA**

**For the award of
Doctor of Letters (D. Litt.) Degree
In
Business Management / Commerce**

**By
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**Academic Year
June 2019**

VOLUME - I

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “*A Critical Comparative Study On The National Accreditation Standards For Hospitals of India, Australia, Denmark And South Africa*” is a genuine research work done by Dr. Zuber Mujeeb Shaikh under my guidance and supervision and submitted for the award of the degree of *Doctor of Literature (D. Litt.)* in *Business Management Science* under the Faculty of *Management Studies* as per the requirements of Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka State, India.

This has not been previously submitted for any degree of this or any other university.

Dr. Praveen B.M
(Research Director)

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the research thesis entitled “*A Critical Comparative Study On The National Accreditation Standards For Hospitals of India, Australia, Denmark And South Africa*”, is an independent and original research work done by me and submitted for the award of the degree of *Doctor of Literature (D. Litt.)* in *Business Management Science* under the Faculty of *Management Studies* as per the requirements of Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka State, India.

I also declare that it has not formed previously the basis for the award of any degree, diploma or other similar titles.

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Place : Nanded, India

Date : May 27th, 2019

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I bow before Almighty, Most Gracious and Most Merciful for enabling me to complete this Thesis.

I am thankful to vice-chancellor **Dr. P. S. Aithal**, Dr. Praveen B.M Research Director of Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka State, India.

I am thankful to Dr. Manisha Saxena, Ph.D., Principal, Department of Hospital Management, Deccan School of Management, Hyderabad (A.P., India), Prof. Feroz Iqbal, Ph.D., TISS Mumbai, India, and Prof. Yuhua Su, PhD (Statistics), North Carolina State University, United States of America for the kindness they have shown to me in helping to complete my research work.

It is an honour for me to place my deepest regards to Dr. M. Habeeb Ghatala, Ph.D., Dean of Apollo Hospital Education and Research Foundation, Hyderabad, India, for the scholarly suggestions provided to me.

I would also like to place my sincere gratitude to the Staff of Srinivas University, Mangalore, Indira institute of Management Sciences, Sahayog campus, Vishnupuri, British Council Library, Hyderabad, India.

My teachers at Department of Hospital Management, Deccan School of Management, Hyderabad, India always encouraged in my research pursuits and I express my profound gratitude to them.

My parents have been a great source of inspiration in all my endeavors of my life. It is my responsibility to place my regards deep from my heart to them. I would like to thank my mother Mrs. Zaheda Shaikh, my father (late) Mr. Mujeeb Shaikh, my wife Dr. Gazala Khan, PhD (Management Science), my brother Mr. Zakir Shaikh, PhD (Computer Science and Engineering), my kids Master Ayaan Shaikh and Master Areeb Shaikh for their moral support and courage they provided to me during the testing times of completing this research work.

Several of my friends supported me in my academic and research pursuits and I am grateful to them. I would also like to place my gratitude to all my well wishers who helped me directly or indirectly.

My heartiest thanks to the staff who worked on DTP for their excellent computer work, data feeding, typing and completing the work well in time meticulously and untiringly.

Lastly, I would like to thank my colleagues and supervisors at Dr. Sulaiman Al-Habib Medical Group, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia for their co-operation to me in completing this research work.

Dr. Zuber M. Shaikh, FISQua, PhD

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ABBREVIATIONS & ACRONYMS

Acronym & Abbreviations	Expanded Form or Full Form
ACC	Access, Assessment and Continuity of Care
AAHC	Accreditation Association for Ambulatory Health Care
ACC	Access to Care and Continuity of Care
ACHC	Accreditation Commission for Health Care
ACHs	Australian Council on Healthcare standards
ACS	American College of Surgeons
ACsQHC's	Australian Commission on safety and Quality in Health Care's
AHA	Academy of Hospital Administration
AHRQ	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality
AIDS	Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome
AIMS	Advanced Incident Management System
ANMs	Auxiliary Nursing and Midwifery
AOP	Assessment of Patient
ARV	anti-retroviral
ASC	Anesthesia and Surgical Care
AUD	Australian Dollars
BIS	Bureau of Indian Standards
BMS	Blood Management Standard
BOD	Burden Of Disease
CCS	Comprehensive Care Standard
CGHS	Central Government Health Scheme
CGS	Clinical Governance Standard
CHAP	Community Health Accreditation Program
COHSASA	Council for Health Service Accreditation of Southern Africa
COP	Care of Patients
COPD	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease
CoQIS	COHSASA Quality Information System
CQI	Continuous Quality Improvement
CSS	Communicating for Safety Standard
CSSD	Central Sterile Supply Department
eA	extensive Achievement
ECHS	Ex-Servicemen Contributory Health Scheme
ED	Emergency Department
eQuiP	evaluation and Quality improvement Program
ESI	Employee's State Insurance
FM	Fully Met
FMS	Facility Management and Safety
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHS	General Household Survey

Acronym & Abbreviations	Expanded Form or Full Form
GLD	Governance Leadership and Direction
GNP	Gross National Product
GPs	general practitioners
HCQI	Health Care Quality Indicators
Hib	Heamophilus Influenzae Type B
HIC	Hospital Infection Control
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
HPCSA	Health Professions Council of South Africa
HQAA	Healthcare Quality Association on Accreditation
HR	Human Resource
HRH	Human Resources for Health
HRM	Human Resource Management
HSP	health service package
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
IAP	International Accreditation Programme
ICHA	Indian Confederation for Healthcare Accreditation
IHI	Institute for Healthcare Improvement
IKAS	Danish Institute for Quality and Accreditation in Healthcare
IMR	Infant Mortality Rate
IMS	Information Management System
INR	Indian Rupees
IOM	Institute of Medicine
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISQua	International Society for Quality in Health Care
JCAH	Joint Commission on Accreditation of Hospitals
JCAHO	Joint Commission on Accreditation of Hospitals
JCI	Joint Commission International
KEM	King Edward Memorial
LA	Little Achievement
LAB	Laboratory
LHNs	Local Hospital Networks
MA	Marked Achievement
MaPSaF	Manchester Patient Safety Framework
MBBS	Bachelor of Medicine and Bachelor of Surgery
MBS	Medicare Benefits Scheme
MD	Doctor of Medicine
MEC	Mental Health Care Act
MOI	Management of Information
MOM	Management of Medication
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
MSS	Medication Safety Standard

Acronym & Abbreviations	Expanded Form or Full Form
NABH	National Accreditation Board for Hospitals and Healthcare Providers
NCQA	National Committee for Quality Assurance
NDH	National District Hospital
NDoH	National Department of Health
NGOs	Non Government Offices
NHI	National Health Insurance
NHP	National Health Policy
NHP	National Health Portal
NHS	National Health Service
NIDS	National Income Dynamics Survey
NM	Not Met
NSQHS	National Safety and Quality Health Service
NSQHS	National Safety and Quality Health Service Standards
oA	outstanding Achievement
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OHSC	Office of Health Standards Compliance
OOP	Out-of-pocket
ows	organisation-wide survey
PBS	Pharmaceutical Benefits Scheme
PCHAIS	Preventing and Controlling Healthcare-Associated Infection Standard
PCI	Prevention and Control of Infection
PCMH	Patient-Centered Medical Homes
PCS	Partnering with Consumers Standard
PFE	Patient and Family Education
PFR	Patient and Family Rights
PHARM	Pharmacy
PM	Partially Met
Pr	Periodic review
PRE	Patient Rights and Education
PSC	Patient Safety Culture
QCI	Quality Council of India
QI	Quality Improvement
QuIC	Quality Interagency Coordination Task Force
R	South African Rands(currency)
RAD	Radiology
ROM	Responsibilities of Management
RRADS	Recognizing and Responding to Acute Deterioration Standard
RSBY	Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojna
sA	some Achievement

Acronym & Abbreviations	Expanded Form or Full Form
SA	South Africa
SAHRC	South African Human Rights Commission
TB	tuberculosis
TQM	Total Quality Management
UHC	Universal Health Coverage
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States Of America
USD	United States Dollars
USSR	Union Of Soviet Socialist Republics
WHO	World Health Organisation

CHAPTER-1

INTRODUCTION

Quality has become a fundamental requirement for healthcare organizations in order to survive and succeed in the competitive, demanding and challenging healthcare service industry. Total Quality Management (TQM) is considered to be an essential way to achieve the required excellence in business practice, as it provides customer satisfaction through continuous quality improvement. TQM is a promising management approach which focuses on the customers, improvement of the structures, processes and outcome. The implementation of TQM concepts is a world-wide phenomenon in all sectors and industries for-improving the quality of services offered, reducing the cost, gaining the trust of customers, attracting the new customers and sustaining in the competitive market environment.

In this modern era of science, technology and quality, the healthcare service industry is a thriving sector, which is continuously on high demand in all the continents of the world. The healthcare service industry is decades behind when compared to other industries in terms of creating safer systems. Today, developed and developing nations are working towards continuous quality improvement and patient safety by achieving the national and or international healthcare accreditation and providing safe, effective, patient-centered, timely, efficient and equitable health care services to all their patients and families. These national and or international healthcare accrediting organizations do follow the principles of TQM to improve quality and patient safety.

Even where healthcare systems are well developed and resourced, there is clear evidence that quality remains a serious concern, with expected outcomes, not predictably achieved and with wide variations in standards of healthcare delivery within and between healthcare systems. In every country, there is an opportunity to improve the quality and performance of the healthcare system, as well as growing awareness and public pressure to do so. The use of accreditation in various countries does not follow a standardized methodology, and therefore the results achieved by each country are not always directly comparable.¹

Accreditation of a health care organization is an external evaluation of the level of compliance against a set of organizational standards². The United States (US) American College of Surgeons (ACS), first developed quality standards for hospitals & other health care facilities and introduced the “Minimum Standard for Hospitals” in 1917. Increased world trade in manufactured goods after the World War II, leads to the creation of the Geneva, Switzerland based International Standards Organization (ISO) in 1947. In 1951 the Joint Commission on Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations (JCAHO) was formed in the United States.³ This concept was exported to Canada and Australia in the 1960s and 1970s and reached Europe in the 1980s. Accreditation programs spread all over the world in the 1990s.⁴

The healthcare accreditation is usually a voluntary program, sponsored by a *Non-Governmental Organization* (NGO), in which educated, experienced and trained personnel evaluate the compliance of a health care organization with pre-established performance standards.⁵

Healthcare accreditation standards are advocated as an important means of improving structure, process and outcome. The accrediting organizations assert that their methodologies are effective and efficient in improving the structure, process, outcome and maintaining the quality of the healthcare industry.

Now, most health care managers and policy makers review & evaluate and control and improve in quality, as an imperative⁶. Therefore, with this demand for improved quality, a growing interest and expansion in accreditation programs has occurred worldwide during the past decade⁷. In a variety of industries, accreditation is recognized as a symbol of quality indicating that the organization meets certain performance standards⁸, and provides an opportunity for that organization to evaluate their operation against national standards⁹.

Today, we have various national accrediting organizations for hospitals all over the world. These healthcare accrediting organizations have developed their own set of standards, which are accredited by the Ireland based International Society for Quality in Health Care (*ISQua*), which is the only organization to 'accredit the accreditors'.

However, when we compare critically with the national accreditation standards (ISQua accredited) of the countries in all the continents of the world, there are variations in the number, names of the chapters, number of standards and evidence of compliance or measurable elements of the standards. Despite of the common needs, glitches and errors in the healthcare service industry all over the world, we have different sets of healthcare standards for the hospitals accredited by ISQua. Moreover, till date no one has even thought about having a unique set of healthcare standards applicable for all the general hospitals of the world.

The researcher has considered the seven-continent model for this research study, which is usually taught in China, India, the Philippines, parts of Western Europe and most English-speaking countries, including Australia¹⁰ and England.¹¹

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines “**Health**” as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity, and “**Healthcare**” is the prevention, treatment, and management of illness and the preservation of mental and physical well-being through the services offered by the medical and allied health professions.

Health care is the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of disease, illness, injury, and other physical and mental impairments in humans. Health care is delivered by practitioners in medicine, chiropractic, dentistry, nursing, pharmacy, allied health, and other care providers. It refers to the work done in providing primary care, secondary care and tertiary care, as well as in public health.

Access to health care varies across countries, groups and individuals, largely influenced by social and economic conditions as well as the health policies in place. Countries and jurisdictions have different policies and plans in relation to the personal and population-based health care goals within their societies. Health care systems are organizations established to meet the health needs of target populations. Their exact configuration varies from country to country. In some countries and jurisdictions, health care planning is distributed among market participants, whereas in others planning is made more centrally among governments or other coordinating bodies. In all cases, according to the World Health Organization (WHO), a well-functioning health care system requires a robust financing mechanism; a well-trained and adequately-paid workforce; reliable information on which to base decisions and policies; and well maintained facilities and logistics to deliver quality medicines and technologies.

The increased international focus on improving patient outcomes, safety and quality of care has led stakeholders, policy makers and healthcare provider organizations adopt standardized processes for evaluating health care organizations.¹² The World Health Organization has published several documents, policies on quality since 1990, but hasn't published the standards for the hospitals till now.¹³ Patient safety and patient centered care are emerging as key drivers in health care reform.¹⁴

In the related literature, accreditation brings the idea of an easy-to-understand and feasible methodology, as it uses medical terminology. It addresses the appropriate conduct commonly known by the professionals in the practice, guiding, however, towards an optimal organization, which standardizes the procedures to allow the creation of viable indicators of comparison and recommends the written recording of policies and procedures of the institution that has become a candidate to the process.¹⁵

Healthcare has become increasingly more complex, and with this increased complexity, the number of medical errors and adverse events has also increased, reaching an alarming level. Since the publication of the "To Err is Human report",¹⁶ there has been a national drive towards addressing the hidden issue of medical errors and patient safety by examining their prevalence and underlying causes. Based on this premise, healthcare providers have implemented national and international healthcare accreditation standards in order to prevent errors. Advancements in technologies have included new safety features to ensure that medical errors ranging from the operating room to the charting of pharmaceutical information are minimized.¹⁷ Yet, even with

these innovations and precautions, there have been no major improvements in the rate of medical errors.¹⁸

The current estimate of total annual deaths by medical errors in the United States is now 400, 000 in comparison to the previous estimate from 1999 of 44,000 to 98, 000 in the famous Institute of Medicine (IOM) report “to Err is Human”.¹⁹ Also, while minor changes have been made, there have been no major systematic changes to our healthcare system to prevent or to more efficiently detect harmful events or adverse events. However, the national and international accreditations reduced number of such errors.²⁰

The researcher reviewed all available and accessible literatures related to the research topic and objectives in research related text books, journals, articles, published research papers, all relevant government plans and reports, literature of external agencies, published academic literature and web portals etc. as per the objectives of this study.

Significance of the problem:

Healthcare is the fundamental need and right of every single human being on this planet. The healthcare quality needs are the same all over the world, and providing the quality healthcare services is the vision of each public and private healthcare service provider, for which they follow the National and or International Healthcare Accreditation Standards for their hospitals. Unfortunately, the World Health Organization (WHO), who monitors the health issues in the public sector of the world doesn't have a unique, comprehensive set of hospital quality standards applicable, available and accessible for all general hospitals in the private and public sectors of the world till date.

1. There are variations in the chapters of National Healthcare Accreditation Standards for hospitals.
2. There are variations in the standards (and content) of National Healthcare Accreditation Standards for hospitals.
3. There is variation in the sub-standards or measurable elements of National Healthcare Accreditation Standards.
4. At present there is no unique, comprehensive set of hospital quality standards applicable, available and accessible for all general hospitals in the world.

Objectives:

1. To identify the main distinguishing standards and measurable elements in the selected national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals in India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa.
2. Compare and analyse critically the national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals in India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa.
3. To propose an outline of “The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals”.

Originality and expected contribution of the research:

The need for such research arises because there are variations in the national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals of different countries from selected continents of the world, no one has conducted such a unique research till date and there are no universal standards for the general hospitals. Hence, the researcher will come up with an outline of “The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals”. This study will be helpful to improve the NABH Standards of India and the rest of the countries in the world as well. Also, the WHO can adopt the proposed outline of the “The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals”.

Limitations:

1. This research study is limited to one country from each continent of the globe with the highest GDP in that continent in the year 2018.²¹
2. This research study is limited to the national healthcare accreditation standards of selected countries from selected continents only.
3. This research study is limited to the latest edition of National Healthcare Accreditation Standards for Hospitals of selected countries which will be available on the registration date of this research proposal.
4. This research study is limited to the availability and accessibility of the national healthcare standards for hospitals of selected countries in English language only.
5. This research study is limited to the National Healthcare Accreditation Standards for Hospitals accredited by the Ireland based International Society for Quality in Health Care (*ISQua*).²²
6. The researcher has not selected any country from South America, North America and Antarctica continents as they did not fit into the sample selection criterion.

Research Methodology:

Research refers to search for knowledge. It is an art of scientific investigation. According to Clifford Woody “research comprises defining and redefining problems, formulating hypothesis or suggested solutions; collecting, organizing and evaluating data; making deductions and reaching conclusions; and at last carefully testing the conclusions to determine whether they fit the formulated hypothesis”. Research provides the needed information that guides managers make informed decisions to successfully deal with problems.

Research is essentially a systematic enquiry seeking facts through objective, verifiable methods in order to discover the relationship among them and to deduce from them broad principles or laws. It is really a method of critical thinking.

Research is defined as ‘*A careful investigation or inquiry specially through the search for new facts in any branch of knowledge.*’ Research is a systematic and refined technique of thinking. Research starts with the Problems, collect data or facts, analyses them critically and reaches decisions based on the actual evidence.

Nature of the study:

This is a systematic and empirical research study, which critically analyses the national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals in India, National Accreditation Board for Hospitals and Healthcare Providers (NABH), Australia- National Safety and Quality Health Service Standards (NSQHS), Denmark- Danish Institute for Quality and Accreditation in Healthcare (DDKM) and South Africa- Council for Health Service Accreditation of Southern Africa (COHSASA).

Data Collection:

Data collection is the process of gathering and measuring information on variables of interest, in an established systematic fashion that enables one to answer stated research questions, test hypotheses, and evaluate outcomes. The data collection component of research is common to all fields of study, including physical and social sciences, humanities, business, etc. While methods vary by discipline, the emphasis on ensuring accurate and honest collection remains the same. The goal for all data collection is to capture quality evidence that then translates to rich data analysis and allows the building of a convincing and credible answer to questions that have been posed.

Regardless of the field of study or preference for defining data (quantitative, qualitative), accurate data collection is essential to maintaining the integrity of research. Both the selection of appropriate data collection instruments (existing, modified, or newly developed) and clearly delineated instructions for their correct use reduce the likelihood of errors occurring.

A formal data collection process is necessary as it ensures that data gathered are both defined and accurately and that subsequent decisions based on arguments embodied in the findings are valid. The process provides both a baseline from which to measure and in certain cases a target on what to improve.

The researcher has collected his data from the latest available edition of national accreditation standards for hospitals of India (NABH), Australia (NSQHS), Denmark (DDKM) and South Africa (COHSASA). Utmost care was exercised while collecting data because the quality of the research results depends upon the reliability of the data. For decision making, the input data must be appropriate. The data may be classified as primary and secondary data.

The researcher has also collected the secondary data from the available books, research journals, published papers, literature of external agencies, published academic literature, web portals on healthcare accreditations, patient safety, culture of patient safety, hospital management and total quality management, available and relevant national / international journals on healthcare accreditations, patient safety, culture of patient safety, total quality management, infection control and human resource management etc.

Sample Size:

The researcher has selected the sample based on the below selection criterion:

1. One country from each continent of the globe with highest GDP in that continent in the year 2018.
2. The selected country must have National Accreditation System or Program in English language which must be available and accessible.
3. The selected National Accreditation System or Program must be accredited by Ireland based International Society for Quality in Health Care (*ISQua*).

Hence, the researcher has selected the following countries as per the above selection criterion from each continent of the globe:

1. **India** is selected from Asia Continent,
2. **South Africa** is selected from Africa Continent,
3. **Denmark** is selected from Europe Continent
4. **Australia** is selected from Oceania or Australia Continent

Statement of Hypotheses:

1. H₁₀: There is a decrease in the number of Chapters, Standards and Measurable Elements after mapping, filtration and merging of Standards and Measurable Elements in NABH, DDKM, NSQHS and COHSASA standards for hospitals.

H1₁: There is no decrease in the number of Chapters, Standards and Measurable Elements after mapping, filtration and merging of Standards and Measurable Elements in NABH, DDKM, NSQHS and COHSASA standards for hospitals.

2. H2₀: The national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa are the same.

H2₁: The national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa are not the same.

3. H3₀: The NABH Standards for Hospitals of India are the best amongst the selected countries' Healthcare Standards for Hospitals.

H3₁: The NABH Standards for Hospitals of India are not the best amongst the selected countries' Healthcare Standards for Hospitals.

4. H4₀: The highest numbers of common Measurable Elements are not in COHSASA standards.

H4₁: The highest numbers of common Measurable Elements are in COHSASA Standards.

5. H5₀: The highest numbers of repeated Measurable Elements are not in COHSASA standards.

H5₁: The highest numbers of repeated Measurable Elements are in COHSASA Standards.

Data Analysis:

The researcher has used following statistical tools and methods for analysis and interpretation of data- collection, classification, tabulation, arithmetic mean, percentages, graphic presentation and application of various test (ANOVA) wherever necessary. The SPSS software was used for computerized calculations of this study.

Statistical tools used for data analysis:

Editing of Data:

Editing is the first stage in data processing. Editing may be broadly defined to be a procedure, which uses available information and assumptions to substitute inconsistent values in a data set. While editing, the researcher has taken care to see that the data are as accurate and complete as possible, units of observations and number of decimal places are the same for the same variable.

Classification of Data:

Once the data are collected and edited, the next step towards further processing the data is classification. The researcher has collected the voluminous data through various methods for her research study and arranged in the homogeneous groups different groups or classes according to their similarities and dissimilarities for meaningful analysis. Classification condenses huge amount of data and helps in understanding the important underlying features. It enables to make comparisons, draw inferences, locate facts and also helps in bringing out relationships, so as to draw meaningful conclusions. In fact classification of data provides a basis for tabulation and analysis of data.

Tabulation of Data:

Presentation of collected data in the tabular form is one of the techniques of data presentation. Arranging the data in an orderly manner in rows and columns is called tabulation of data. Sometimes data collected by survey or even from publications of official bodies are so numerous that it is difficult to understand the important features of the data. Therefore, the researcher has summarized the data through tabulation to an easily intelligible form. The data presented in tabular form are much easier to read and understand than the data presented in the text. The tabulation is the process of recording the classified facts in rows and columns.

Statistical Derivatives:

Statistical derivatives are the quantities obtained by simple computation from the given data. Though very easy to compute, they often give meaningful insight into the data. The researcher has used the following most often-used measures: percentage and rate. These measures point out an existing relationship among factors and thereby help in better interpretation.

Percentage:

As we have noted earlier, the frequency distribution may be regarded as simply counting and checking as to how many cases are in each group or class. The relative frequency distribution gives the proportion of cases in individual classes. On multiplication by 100, the percentage frequencies are obtained. Converting to percentages has some advantages - it is now more easily understood and comparisons become simpler because it standardizes data. Percentages are quite useful in other tables also, and are particularly important in case of bivariate tables.

Mean and Weighted Mean:

Most of the time, when we refer to the average of something, we are talking about the arithmetic mean. This is the most important measure of central tendencies which is commonly called mean.

Median:

The median is another measure of central tendency. The median represents the middle value of the data that measures the central item in the data. Half of the items lie above the median, and the other half lie below it.

Mode:

The mode is also a measure of central tendency. This measure is different from the arithmetic mean, to some extent like the median because it is not really calculated from the normal process of arithmetic. The mode, of the data, is the value that appears the maximum number of times.

ANOVA:

In statistics, **one-way analysis of variance** (abbreviated **one-way ANOVA**) is a technique used to compare means of two or more samples (using the F distribution). This technique can be used only for numerical data.

The ANOVA tests the null hypothesis that samples in two or more groups are drawn from populations with the same mean values. To do this, two estimates are made of the population variance. These estimates rely on various assumptions. The ANOVA produces an F-statistic, the ratio of the variance calculated among the means to the variance within the samples. If the group means are drawn from populations with the same mean values, the variance between the group means should be lower than the variance of the samples, following the central limit theorem. A higher ratio therefore implies that the samples were drawn from populations with different mean values.

Typically, however, the one-way ANOVA is used to test for differences among at least three groups, since the two-group case can be covered by a t-test (Gosset, 1908). When there are only two means to compare, the t-test and the F-test are equivalent; the relation between ANOVA and t is given by $F = t^2$.²³

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CHAPTER- 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This chapter is an overview of previous studies relating to the research topic and objectives of the research. However, there is very minimal information or data available on this research topic and objectives.

This review of the literature focuses on all the objectives and problems of this research. The researcher has taken the sincere efforts in reviewing all available and accessible relevant literatures based on the objectives of the research. Also, the information on the healthcare systems, quality improvement, patient safety and accreditations also reviewed for India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa. The national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals of India, National Accreditation Board for Hospitals and Healthcare Providers (NABH), Australia- National Safety and Quality Health Service Standards (NSQHS), Denmark- Danish Institute for Quality and Accreditation in Healthcare (DDKM) and South Africa- Council for Health Service Accreditation of Southern Africa (COHSASA) were microscopically studied.

The literature contains a variety of definitions of healthcare, quality, accreditations, patient safety and related concepts.

Hospital:

A hospital, in the modern sense, is an institution for health care, providing patient treatment by specialized staff and equipment, and often, but not always providing for longer-term patient stays. Its historical meaning, until relatively recent times, was “a place of hospitality”, for example the Chelsea Royal Hospital, established in 1681 to house veteran soldiers.

Today, hospitals are usually funded by the public sector, by health organizations (for profit or non-profit), health insurance companies or charities, including by direct charitable donations. There are over 17,261 hospitals in the world as of now.²

Healthcare Industry:

The healthcare industry (also called the medical industry or health economy) is an aggregation and integration of sectors within the economic system that provides goods and services to treat patients with curative, preventive, rehabilitative, and palliative care. It includes the generation and commercialization of goods and services lending themselves to maintaining and re-establishing health.¹ The modern healthcare industry is divided into many sectors and depends on the interdisciplinary teams of trained professionals and paraprofessionals to meet health needs of individuals and populations.² The healthcare industry is one of the world's largest and fastest-growing industries.³ Consuming over 10 percent of gross domestic

product (GDP) of most developed nations, health care can form an enormous part of a country's economy.

Concept of Quality

The concept of quality has been defined as- “Totality of features and characteristics of a product or service that bear on its ability to satisfy stated or implied needs.” Quality Gurus have also defined the concept differently. Such as, Crosby- It is conformance to requirements, not as goodness, Juran- Fitness for use, Figenbaum- Meeting customer expectations and Deming- Reduction in variations.

The concept of quality in healthcare has recently emerged. According to Dr. Adeis Donabedian, PhD, MPH, the late Quality Guru in U.S., Quality in Health Care is encompassed of three critical attributes- (1) Structure, (2) Process and (3) Outcome. In any hospital, a customer/ patient can access the quality of service provided on these three dimensions:

Structure

The structure includes the physical layout, facility cleanliness, medical and technological facilities provided by the hospitals.

Process

The process includes the operational part (it includes but not limited to clinical, non- clinical and support services) of service delivery. Scheduling of appointments, admissions, triage in the Emergency Department/ Casualty, allocation of beds, collection of sample, delivery of reports, clearance of bills, discharges are a few processes that a patient undergoes in a hospital and it is a major area where he measures quality of service delivery. Waiting time in the queue itself is a major parameter by which patient decides quality in service delivery.

Outcome

For a patient and his/ her attendants, the outcome is the factor that matters most. A patient can leave a hospital after being cured, against medical advice or even death.

Quality in Health Care is classified in two specific parts -

(a) Clinical

- Clinical Credentialing
- Clinical Audit
- Clinical Risk Management
- Clinical Outcome Measurement
- Clinical Care Pathways

(b) Non-Clinical

- Infrastructure & Facilities Management Equipment Management
- Supplies & consumable Management

- IT Infrastructure & Management
- Support Services (including housekeeping services)
- Patient Satisfaction, Accreditation

In modern management, we say, “Customer is King”, and in healthcare, patient is the ‘customer’. Gone are the days of the quiet and compliant patient who dared not to speak, much less challenge the care providers. Today’s better educated, more sophisticated health care consumer can and does make judgments and discriminations about quality of care and services.

Earlier health care was a seller’s market, but now it is a buyer’s market and will continue to be so in the future with the competition getting intensified. Healthcare customers easily discriminate between the way they are treated medically and treated personally, as they are willing to pay more for better care. Today’s patients want to be more actively involved in the decision making process concerning their care and treatment.

Changing an organization's culture is one of the biggest challenges of a TQM or accreditation programme. A firm’s survival may depend on how it adapts its culture to a rapidly changing business environment and to the new demands of its internal and external customers.

TQM demands the implementation of new systems. The quality delivery process involves determining internal and external customer requirements. Customer satisfaction plays a pivotal role in quality management or in hospital accreditation, as in management we say; a satisfied employee is a productive employee. Productive, satisfied employees create successful businesses. The customer (internal and external) satisfaction can be measured by interview/ questionnaire (direct means) or by counting/ analysing the number of complaints and returns received (indirect means). The first step in the quality delivery process is to create a mission statement.

A Growing Healthcare Sector

Healthcare is one of India’s largest sectors, in terms of revenue and employment, and the sector is expanding rapidly. During the 1990s, Indian health care grew at a compound annual rate of 16%. Today, the total value of the sector is more than \$34 billion. This translates to \$34 per capita, or roughly 6% of GDP. By the end of 2012, India’s healthcare sector is projected to grow to nearly \$40 billion. The private sector accounts for more than 80% of total healthcare spending in India. Unless there is a decline in the combined federal and state government deficit, which currently stands at roughly 9%, the opportunity for significantly higher public health spending will be limited. Growing population and economy One driver of growth in the healthcare sector is India’s booming population, currently 1.1 billion and increasing at a 2% annual rate. By 2030, India is expected to surpass China as the

world's most populous nation. By 2050, the population is projected to reach 1.6 billion.

This population increase is due in part to a decline in infant mortality, the result of better health care facilities and the government's emphasis on eradicating diseases such as hepatitis and polio among infants. In addition, life expectancy is rapidly approaching the levels of the western world. By 2025, an estimated 189 million Indians will be at least 60 years of age—triple the number in 2004, thanks to greater affluence and better hygiene. The growing elderly population will place an enormous burden on India's healthcare infrastructure.

The Indian economy, estimated at roughly \$1 trillion, is growing in tandem with the population. Goldman Sachs predicts that the Indian economy will expand by at least 5% annually for the next 45 years (see chart), and that it will be the only emerging economy to maintain such a robust pace of growth.

Quality in Health Care Services

The issue of quality is very broad and correlated with practically every sphere of human activity. However, quality is very important in the health care sector, as it is a basic human right to get the best quality of health care, given the circumstances of the existing economic situation of the country. I shall also explore the historical development of quality in the health sector, different dimensions of quality of health services, philosophy of quality management and finally the relationship between quality and marketing.

'Quality' according to Webster's New World Dictionary is 'the degree of excellence, which a thing possesses'. This definition implies that the term 'Quality' is related to the characteristics which a product or service may possess. Health services have different features. Quality in health services has many facets and dimensions relating to factors and perspectives such as economic, regulatory, social, organisational, political, technical, human, ethical, scientific, and cultural environment. Some of these elements may be elusive, intangible, immeasurable or, at least difficult to measure. Therefore, the meaning of quality in health services has a number of dimensions and aspects, correlated with judgment about the definition, competence and the measurement of quality.

Definition of Quality in Health Services

There is no specific definition of quality, because it means different things to different people and "its content varies according to the situational and substance factors,"⁴ and different definitions are suitable under different circumstances. The roots of quality definitions were discussed by Greek philosophers who defined quality as 'art or excellence'.⁵

Quality can also be defined as 'value', as in the mid-1700s the orientation was to the customers and market relative to the price and by the 1800s the lack of quality

was being lamented, thus there was interest in both 'price and quality in a competitive market'.⁶

McLaughlin and Kaluzny (1994)⁷ also defined quality as "conforming to specifications; having a product or service that meets predetermined standards".

Youssef, Boyd and Williams (1996)⁸ defined quality as "successfully meeting internal and external customer expectations.

From the manufacturing point of view, Morgan and Murgatroyd (1994)⁹ also agreed with the previous definitions as they provided many views of quality definition, which include products, conformance to specification, customer and value.

As the various definitions of Quality in housekeeping, the Researcher has gone through the significance of defining and observed the Strengths and Weaknesses of each of the definitions of Quality.

Considering the different definitions of 'Quality' in housekeeping, the Researcher has gone through the strengths and weaknesses of definition of quality are as shown in Table 2.1.

Health is not a unitary concept. Ideally, it includes all possible dimensions as well as biological, physical environment social, economic and cultural environment. The World Health Organisation (WHO) defined health as "a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease and infirmity."¹⁰ The term 'health' has been used to mention the health services organisation in tertiary level private and public hospitals.

It becomes clear from the previous section that both 'quality' and 'health' have many dimensions that makes it difficult to define quality in health care. It is important when quality is defined in this study to consider the characteristic of services such as "intangibility, heterogeneity and inseparability. Intangibility is used to describe services, which may be difficult to be counted, measured, inventoried, tested or verified in advance of delivery to ensure quality. Services have customers with very heterogeneous needs, inseparability means that the consumer not separate from production, rather quality occurs during the delivery of service."¹¹

Graham (1990b)¹² says that the definition of quality in health care includes technical, scientific and artistic elements.

Donabedian (1986) defined quality as, the maximisation of patient satisfaction considering all profits and losses to be faced in a health care procedure. Although Donabedian's contributions to the improving quality is high, but his definition tends to be considered static as all the fields towards a continuous improvement of quality.¹³

Patients may judge the quality by the standards of technical care, which includes accurate diagnosis and the best possible treatment. It also includes the artistic concept of quality, which means a good interpersonal relationship between providers and patients, and for amenities of care such as cleanliness.¹⁴

Providers include physicians and other technical person's administrator's owners and the third-party payers. Physicians and other technical staff may be interested in accurate diagnosis and the best possible treatment and current available medical knowledge and technology. The health care administrators are interested in delivering the greatest number of services within their budget. The third-party payers such as government and insurance agencies interested to provide the best possible services at the lowest possible cost.¹⁵

The Institute of Medicine (IOM) of the National Academy of Sciences (1990) defined quality of health care from 100 different definitions of quality collected from various sources as "the degree to which health services for individuals and populations increase the likelihood of desired health outcomes and are consistent with current professional knowledge."¹⁶ In this definition, IOM avoided to mention any financial constraint.

In general, the definition of quality in health care was developed from conformance to specifications and included not just patients but all stakeholders and many elements such as continuously improving processes, culture, human resources and included all the health services provided as suggested from the pioneers of TQM. Whichever definition of quality adopted, it must be operational, measurable and acceptable.

It has become clear from reviewing previous definitions of quality; defining quality has many aspects and different dimensions. It includes many concepts as management clinical, sociability, behaviour and technical.

For the purpose of the dissertation, the definition of quality of healthcare will be used as suggested from Saudi Health Care System perspective:

'The degree to which effective and efficient health services attempt to improve the 'health status' and 'satisfaction' of the community, given the current state of knowledge, and technical and financial constraints.

Properties of the above definition are:

The Degree

Quality is a dynamic attribute, shows commitment to continuous improvement and quality as an ongoing activity.

Effective and Efficient Health Services

The probability that the benefits of health services under average conditions of use, the goal being to achieve maximum efficiency without lowering effects.

Health Status

As defined by the patients, government, physicians and other major agencies of the health sector.

Satisfaction

A comprehensive vision that takes all the perspectives of the internal and external customers.

Knowledge and Technical and Financial Constraints

Implies a dynamic state for each of the three conditions and holds both government and physicians responsible for using the best available knowledge, technical and financial resources to improve the health status and the satisfaction of the community.

This definition implies that there should be a net benefit to the target population through the improvement in structure, process and outcome, reflected in an improvement in health status, satisfaction and other outcomes. Health authorities to adopt this definition should decide on their target population, gaps and deficiencies in the structure, process and outcome measures the existing state of knowledge and technical and financial constraints. In general, the definition is in line with the principles of TQM and contributes to the aims of the research such as focusing on the consumer resources and improvement.

Accreditations and Quality Assurance Systems

There are various accreditations and quality assurance systems presently available. These accreditations and quality assurance systems help organizations to streamline their processes, provide timely services and thereby enhance patient outcomes. Evidence from JCI has indicated that accreditation tends to help enhance the overall quality of patient care services, based on select case studies from across the globe. Unfortunately there is little documented evidence about the effectiveness of NABH in improving patient outcomes and quality.

Health Care Quality and Cost¹⁷

With recent advances in healthcare, quality has become a pertinent issue. As the demand for healthcare is rapidly rising with increasing population base and increasing levels of affordability, so is the demand for quality healthcare services. Superior quality of medical care is often associated with higher costs of hospitalization.

Rapidly rising costs in healthcare is an increasing cause of concern across the world. Indian health care is also experiencing a change, with increasing focus on

better quality of medical care services. With a large section of healthcare practitioners in the private sector, the government has realized the need to improve medical care services and has stepped in to regulate the quality of medical care services by the introduction of various quality accreditation norms like the NABH and NABL.

As per available information (Care Continuum, 2005), the healthcare spending per capita per annum in India was about \$109, with total healthcare spending in the range of 4.9% of the country's GDP. Most of the spending occurs from the private sector to public sector contributing to a mere \$ 19 per capita per annum. Concurrently, the average spending per capita per annum in the United States during the same time frame was approximately \$4271 whilst United Kingdom the spending was \$ 1675. These figures clearly indicate that healthcare in India is fairly cheap, a strong reason for a growing medical tourism market in the country. However, when compared with paying power parity and affordability, the cost of medical care is escalating. It is worthwhile to note that as per World Bank (2005) estimates more than 44% of Indian population earns less than one dollar a day.

As per the Finance Ministry, the overall inflation rate in India was about 9.4 percent during April- December 2010, while inflation in medical expenses was in excess of 10 percent for the fourth year in a row (Business Today, 2011). There are several other factors that have been contributing to the escalation in cost of medical care. These factors include increasing demand for medical care services with consistently limited supply, increased penetration of health insurance, improvement in medical technology with new innovations improving diagnostic capabilities and increasing dependence of doctors on diagnostic procedures. Increasing demand for quality in medical care services plays a critical role in increasing the overall cost of medical care services.

While empirical evidence suggests that there is an increasing demand for healthcare services across India, affordability remains a pertinent issue. This has resulted in market segmentation (Shah, Mohanty, 2010), where on one hand there is an increasing demand for quality medical care services while on the other hand there is a demand for medical care services at affordable cost. The demand for the latter has inevitably resulted in poor quality of medical care services with poor health outcomes.

It is simple to compute the direct costs for various medical services, however to compute the cost of quality is not only difficult but rather elusive, which has resulted in over dependence on subjective criteria (Klint, Long, 1989). Various modalities like manpower ratios, infrastructure, medical technological capabilities, accreditation and quality assurance policies and mortality rates, have been considered as quality indicators and have been used to evaluate the quality of health care services. The paper attempts to explore the implication of these quality indicators on the direct expenses incurred by patients whilst seek health care services across India.

Quality Indicators¹⁸

As per the Joint Commission International, the organization's leaders should identify key measures in the organization's structures, processes, and outcomes to be used in the organizational quality improvement and patient safety plan. Quality improvement and patient safety are data driven. Effective use of the data is best accomplished in the broader context of evidence-based clinical practices and evidence-based management practices. Because most organizations have limited resources, they cannot collect data to measure everything they want.

Thus, each organization must choose which clinical and management processes and outcomes are most important to measure based on its mission, patient needs, and services. Measurement often focuses on those processes that are high risk to patients, provided in high volume, high cost to the organization or patient, or are problem prone. An organization's leaders are responsible for making the final selection of key measures to be included in the organization's quality activities.

In healthcare, health outcomes play a crucial role in determining quality. However, the importance of customer experience and customer delight can't be underestimated. Hospitals and Healthcare institutions have consistently focused on improving the patients experience and providing services in timely and orderly fashion. However it is often difficult to rate the quality of services (both clinical and non clinical), using similar indicators.

Healthcare providers often use patient satisfaction surveys to understand the lacunae in quality of care provided and identify critical areas of improvement. Patient satisfaction surveys can be used to measure the quality of services from the prospective of subjective opinion of the patients/beneficiaries. As per a study conducted in Taiwan (Cheng, *et al.*, 2001), it was concluded that patients lack the ability to judge the quality of care in healthcare institutions are in general lack awareness regarding the various quality indicators. The study indicated that patients are not able to rate the infrastructural and technological capabilities of the institution or the technical competencies of their physicians or medical staff.

Asset value is indicative of the medical technology along with the other infrastructural amenities like elevators, air conditioning units, fire fighting services, etc. These services will implicate the overall quality of medical care as it directly impacts on patient safety, infection control rates and the ability of the institution to provide critical care services, etc. In a study conducted in Mexico (Aguilera, Marrufo, 2007), it was observed that the infrastructure of the hospital determines the mortality rate among its beneficiaries. In another study conducted across 87 hospitals in Massachusetts (Levitt, 1994), a clear positive correlation between the investment in plant, machinery and property was observed with the quality of care and patient outcomes.

Hospitals and healthcare institutions are human resource intensive units. Higher nurse to bed and higher staff to bed ratio are indicative of a reduced burden on the staff, which in turn directly enhances their ability to pay greater attention to detail of patient care. In a study conducted (Grujic, *et al.*, 1989) it was observed that the educational qualification, attitude and behaviour of the staff impacted their overall ability to provide medical services and fulfilling patient expectations. The Joint Commission on Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations (JCAHO) found that staffing levels have been a factor in 24% of sentinel adverse events that resulted in death, injury, or permanent loss of function (SHS, 2005). Another research study conducted in the United States (Rothberg *et al.*, 2005) indicated that a ratio of 8 patients to one nurse was less expensive but associated with higher patient mortality and the effectiveness of the staff increased with improvement in the ratio. These studies reiterate the importance of better staff to patient ratios and their significance in enhancing quality of medical care.

In the era of consumerism, the role of patient experience is undisputed and impacts the assessment of the total quality of medical care. Timely service provision, promptly addressing patient grievances, etc. plays a crucial role in the impression the hospital management creates for patients and thereby influences the perception of the patient about the overall health care services provided by the institution (Cleary, 1999). However the use of patient satisfaction should be ideally limited to a few parameters aimed at enhancing patient experience.

The cost of health care depends upon a host of modalities including the disease condition, insurance coverage, age of the individual, etc. In addition, the cost of health care is influenced by other institutional factors namely the service mix, the treatment modalities, the brand image of the institution, etc. Whilst defining quality of care is difficult and subjective, quality parameters can be used to assess the overall quality of medical care services.

Studies have shown that there is a nonlinear U shaped association between quality and hospital charges. This implies that for the lowest quality will have the lowest price and as quality improves the hospitalization charges are bound to increase (Peabody, *et al.*, 2010). In another study conducted in the United States, it was observed that there was no relation between patient satisfaction levels and the expenditure made on health care services (Fu, Wang, 2008). Taking lessons from the United States and Cuba example, optimum utilization of resources plays a crucial role in controlling costs in a health care institution.

Quality indicators namely manpower ratios, infrastructure and asset value, accreditation and quality control procedures can be used to ascertain of the quality of health care services. Patient satisfaction surveys also play a crucial role in assessing the quality of care provided by the healthcare institutions (Express Healthcare, 2007). Patients appreciate better quality of medical care services (Express Healthcare, 2007).

Though several organizations use patient satisfaction reports to evaluate the quality of medical care services, the findings are often not very compelling. Patients are often considerably biased towards reporting satisfaction depending upon various factors including their underlying condition, ethnicity, age, improvement in the condition, etc. (Thiedke. C., 2007). However, careful and appropriate evaluation of patient satisfaction surveys could also act as a vital quality indicator can provide insights into areas of improvement. Though other factors like disease standardized mortality rates may be used, their application is constrained due to technical issues and statistical limitations.

The asset value of hospitals, implying the infrastructure, medical equipment technology, basic amenities and additional services provided play a crucial role in cost of hospitalization. This study observes that with higher asset value the average cost of hospitalization increases. Reports indicate that hospitals with centralized air conditioning units are associated with higher cost of hospitalization (Times of India, 2011).

Nurse to patient ratios and staff to bed ratios also influence the quality of care. Though it may appear that higher staff would increase the cost of medical care borne by the common man, the findings of the study indicate otherwise. The rationale for higher staff to bed ratio, results in the provision of better quality of care, which in turn reduces the average length of stay and hence average hospitalization cost. Higher staff to bed ratio reduce the need for intensive care services and medical equipment support, which in turn reduce the cost of hospitalization.

Accreditations and quality assurance systems have also been observed to reduce the average cost of hospitalization. This clearly indicates that accreditations and quality assurance systems help hospitals to streamline their functions and processes, minimize wastage and thereby aid in enhancing quality and reducing cost of care.

History and Development of Quality Management in Health Services

The history of quality of care in health services goes back to the time of Hammurabi (1700 BC)¹⁹ who promulgated a legal code which included “specific and drastic penalties for surgical incompetence also determined the salaries of physicians” (Ellis and Whittington, 1993);²⁰ Reerink, (1990)²¹; Shihatta, (1995b),²² Shihatta, (1995c).²³ The idea of quality of care as a management system began in the first decade of the twentieth century. It is rooted in the industrial field and applies scientific methods and tools to the health sector.

In the UK, the Royal College of Physicians in 1518, supported the idea to “uphold the standards of medicine for providers and patients.”²⁴ In 1908, Groves evaluated the results of surgery to study the rates of mortality in 50 hospitals. His

study showed the necessity to investigate some diseases and to improve and classify the norms of operations and disease.²⁵

Florence Nightingale (1820-1910) provided her study that contributed to the establishment of the idea of quality. She advocated a uniform system for collecting and evaluating hospital statistics. Her study drew attention to the relationship between nursing care and the rates of mortality during the war. It included the need to improve cleanliness, health, nutrition, and organised operations and daily process in the hospitals.²⁶

In the USA, Flexner published a report in 1910 about the standards of medical colleges. This report led to the closure of 60 medical colleges in the USA in 1920 as a result of poor standards of theoretical and practical education of medical care.²⁷

In 1915, the American College of Surgeons developed the “Hospital Standard Programme.” One of the objectives of this programme was to establish an official method for the approval of hospitals and to verify the quality of the rendered health services therein. The Programme is composed of five main points: assuring the importance of organising the personnel, monthly meetings, examining the medical records, effective supervision and accreditation of doctors for practicing in the medical profession.²⁸ In 1916, Ernest Codman advocated the evaluation of the end results of care, not just as clinical efficiency, but also as economic, social, organisational and managerial activities.²⁹ In 1918, the American College of Surgeons “inaugurated the hospital standardisation programme”, that aimed to devise official methods to sanction hospitals, and to assure good care in hospitals.³⁰

In 1950, Paul Lembecke published the idea and term of “Medical Audit.” His studies showed the importance of “feedback” of medical information to physicians to improve their performance and patients “benefits.”

In 1984, JCAHO adopted the idea of approving the methods of QA for the assessment and supervision of healthcare services. In 1985, JCAHO developed a ten step process to help hospitals to develop the quality assurance programmes. In 1988, JCAHO defined and described the indicators to be supervised and assessed. In 1989, JCAHO published the required features in the activities of risk control and provided the index for hospital approval.³¹

In 1992, JCAHO modified the name “quality assurance” to “continuous quality improvement”, and “quality assessment and improvement” and the terms “continuous quality improvement” and “total quality management” became widespread. Standards were developed for management, leadership, and statistical methods, and for the development of a national system of accreditation of hospital such as in Australia and France.³²

Philosophy of Quality Management

There are many different philosophies related to quality management such as quality control, quality assessment quality assurance, TQM, continuous quality improvement etc. These philosophies were developed through many stages for achieving quality. These philosophies are discussed below, briefly.

Quality Audit:

A quality audit is a “systematic and independent examination to determine whether quality activities and related results comply with planned arrangements and whether these arrangements are implemented effectively and are suitable to achieve objectives.”³³

The UK NHS defined a quality audit as the systematic process and referred to it respectively as routine and regular.³⁴ Quality audits can be categorised as follows: “audits of policies and objectives; audits of performance against company objectives; audits of plans, system and procedures and audits of execution.”³⁵

There were similar terms in health care such as “medical audit”, which can be defined as “the systematic, critical analysis of the quality of medical care, including the procedures used for diagnosis and treatment, the use of resources, and the resulting outcome and quality of life for patients.”³⁶

Quality Control (QC):

The term ‘Quality Control’ can be defined as a “system that aims to minimize variation of product or services and process from standard.”³⁷ Wilson (1987)³⁸ following list of QC system that would be found in place in most hospitals.

Quantity control (QC) necessarily implies that the worker should be able to produce products at the specified standards. Therefore, QC requires setting standards of service or process, monitoring its achievement and using inspection and statistical quality control techniques that accept some variation³⁹

Quality Assessment:

Quality assessment can be defined as “a judgment concerning the process of care, based on the extent to which that care contributes to valued outcome.”⁴⁰ Quality assessment means measuring the level of quality by using standards, answering what are the strengths or weaknesses in the quality of health services, but without any endeavour to modify or improve the system. Donabedian contributed to the measuring and evaluation quality of healthcare when he provided his model which includes structure, process and outcome. He has known fondly by his students as “Mr. Structure-Process-Outcome.”⁴¹

Donabedian (1990a)⁴² considers quality assessment as “an administrative device used to monitor performance to determine whether it continues to remain

within acceptable bounds.” The purpose of assessment is to improve the outcome or effectiveness of the programme as it shows accomplishments and the difficulty of the programme..⁴³

Quality Assurance (QA):

The British Standards Institute defined quality assurance as “a management system designed to give the maximum confidence that a given acceptable level of quality of services is being achieved with the minimum of total expenditure.”⁴⁴

QA contributes to the effective use of the resources, the outcome of health services and is closely related to marketing. QA is an important element of the planning, management and evaluation process for healthcare.⁴⁵

The Development of Total Quality Management in Health Services and Concept of Total Quality Management (TQM)

TQM is one of the methods that can be used to improve the performance and the management of the hospitals. The essential idea is comprehensiveness and integrity in order to achieve consumer satisfaction and the continuous improvement in every aspect of the hospital. “Comprehensiveness” includes all clinical services, supporting services and managerial services. It includes all patients and all types of providers. It also includes different processes and activities in the hospitals. ‘Integral’ means cooperation between all departments, secondary systems and their programmes for improving the level of quality of all health services (clinical services, supporting services and managerial services). TQM is a “management philosophy based on a number of principles, such as customer focus, continuous improvement, process orientation, everybody’s commitment, fast response, result orientation and learning from others.”⁴⁶

TQM is a system for never-ending improvement in health services and it is achieved through long term strategies, which are applied using many principles and tools, such as consumers’ satisfaction, teamwork, leadership, measuring systems, processes.⁴⁷

It is evident from the above, that TQM is not a mere process, technique, managerial style, or tool. It is all that together. It is quality in all the services available in the hospital. It is based on the concept of comprehensiveness and integration, through consolidation and implementation of the appropriate principles of TQM for continuous improvement in the quality of the health services.

Definition of Total Quality Management (TQM)

It is more than the definition of TQM which represents a sort of difficulty when discussing the subject. It seems that there is no consensus, so far, as to what the term TQM precisely means.⁴⁸ Even though TQM is relatively new its literature is full of definitions that often reflect author’s concepts and their own comprehension of the

term, however, may be noticed in the differences in the idioms used not the language. Below is a brief outline of those definitions:

The British Quality Association put forward three alternative definitions of TQM:⁴⁹ the first is interested in the ‘soft qualitative characteristics, customers’ satisfaction, culture of excellence, teamwork, training, involving all employees, competitive edge and performance barriers. The second focuses on the ‘hard’ production management view such as measurement, standards, using statistical tools to control the work and assess quality. The third is a ‘mixture of hard and soft’ this includes three elements: an obsession with quality, scientific orientation and teamwork. However, perhaps the managers focus on tools and measurements and not on the softer characteristics. Maybe categorising TQM into hard and soft techniques is a more practical perspective. From the viewpoint of the proponents of TQM.

The American Federal Office of Management and Budget Circular 1990 (Cited in Milakovich, 1990)⁵⁰ defined TQM as “a total organisational approach for meeting customer needs and expectations that involves all managers and employees in using quantitative methods to continuously improve the organisation’s processes, products, and services. This definition includes a number of points such as: total approach, total management, the application of TQM and a coordinated and committed overall management philosophy.

TQM can be defined in accordance with the Japanese concept “Kaizen” which means “continuous search for opportunities for all processes to get better.”⁵¹ There are many definitions of TQM, which place more emphasis more on the output of care; TQM is the “opportunity to achieve better outcomes with fewer resources.”⁵²

Crosby defined TQM as a “systematic way of guaranteeing that organised activities happen the way they are planned. It is a management discipline concerned with preventing problems occurring by creating the attitudes and controls that make prevention possible.”⁵³

National Health Services (NHS) Management Executive (1993)⁵⁴ defines TQM as a strategy that maximises the efficiency and effectiveness of an organisation, which may be reached through creative applications and unconventional implementation. Ideally, the TQM environment features: customer oriented, well-trained and efficient human resources, continuous improvement and change is subject to scientific methods.

Joint Commission Accreditation of Health Care Organisation (JACHO) uses the term CQI which he defines as an organisational framework within which the health institutions and their employees are committed to monitoring and evaluating all the activities in these institutions (input, process, and output) to continuously improve these activities.⁵⁵ This definition highlights the importance of total approach, continuous improvement, commitment, process and evaluation. Shortell, Levin and

O'Brien (1995)⁵⁶ defined TQM as “an ongoing effort to provide care that meet or exceeds customer expectations.”

In spite of the differences in their views to TQM elements, most definitions have commonly focused on:

- Leadership commitment and top management
- Quality culture
- Statistical analysis and measurement
- Focusing on customers' satisfaction (internal and external customers)
- Participation of all employees in the function of continuous quality
- Improvement
- Focusing on continuous improvement the performance of all process, products and activities
- Participation of management with the employees
- Using many methods and tools in implementing principles to realize TQM
- Some of the definitions added elements such as the financial aspect
- Planning, prevention, competitive and people

Accreditation of Hospitals:

Today, every patient or family visiting to any healthcare facility or provider first ensures that the facility is accredited by national or international healthcare accreditation organization, which gives the positive impact on the mindset of the patient or family about that particular healthcare facility, as healthcare accreditation is the seal of patient safety and total quality management in healthcare industry. The Joint Commission International has been defined accreditation as “A self-assessment and external peer assessment process used by health care organizations to accurately assess their level of performance in relation to established standards and to implement ways to continuously improve”. Critically, accreditation is not just about standard setting, but there are analytical, counseling and self-improvement dimensions to the process. There are parallel issues around evidence-based medicine, quality assurance, medical ethics, patient safety and the reduction of errors and variations is a key role in the accreditation process. Hospital accreditation is therefore the basic and pivotal component in the maintenance of patient safety.

Responding to the need for accreditation of health services, especially in the private sector, the Eleventh Five Year Plan (2007-12) provided for setting up of National Accreditation Board for Hospitals and Healthcare Providers (NABH), which was established in Quality Council of India (QCI) for accreditation of private and public health centres. The Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) also developed an ISO certification for quality management systems which includes healthcare facilities as well. Both private as well as public facilities are encouraged to obtain an International Organization for Standardization (ISO) certification.

The accreditation process is designed to create a culture of safety and quality within an organization that strives to continually improve patient care processes and results. In doing so, organizations;

- Improve public trust that the organization is concerned for patient safety and the quality of care;
- Provide a safe and efficient work environment that contributes to worker satisfaction;
- Negotiate with sources of payment for care with data on the quality of care;
- Listen to patients and their families, respect their rights, and involve them in the care process as partners;
- Create a culture that is open to learning from the timely reporting of adverse events and safety concerns; and
- Establish collaborative leadership that sets priorities for and continuous leadership for quality and patient safety at all levels.

Accreditation is a synonym of Total Quality Management (TQM) in healthcare industry, which is usually a voluntary programme sponsored by a non governmental agency (NGO), in which trained external peer reviewers evaluate a health care organization's compliance with pre established performance standards. Accreditation addresses organizational rather than individual practitioner, capability of performance, unlike licensure. Accreditation focus on continuous improvement strategies and achievements of optimal quality standards, rather than adherence to minimal standards. There are two types of accreditations, national and international.

Hospitals and healthcare services are vital components of any well-ordered and humane society, and will indisputably be the recipients of societal resources. That hospital should be places of safety, not only for patients but also for the staff and for the general public, is of the greatest importance. Quality of hospitals and healthcare services is also of great interest to many other bodies, including governments, NGOs targeting healthcare and social welfare, professional organizations representing doctors, patient organizations, shareholders of companies providing healthcare services, etc. However, accreditation schemes are not the same thing as government-controlled initiatives set up to assess healthcare providers with only governmental objectives in mind - ideally, the functioning and finance of hospital accreditation schemes should be independent of governmental control.

How quality is maintained and improved in hospitals and healthcare services is the subject of much debate. Hospital surveying and accreditation is one recognised means by which this can be achieved.

International Healthcare Accreditation Schemes:

Some accreditation schemes also undertake international healthcare accreditation work outside of their base country. One of the large numbers of

accreditation schemes in the USA, the Joint Commission currently being the best known, has created the Joint Commission International, or JCI. In 2012, *National Accreditation Board for Hospitals & Healthcare Providers (NABH)*, an Indian based health care accrediting organization launched its international standards. Quality Council of India made National Accreditation Board for Hospitals & Healthcare Providers (NABH) accreditation mandatory for all healthcare providers who want to be a *Central Government Health Scheme (CGHS) Empanelment Hospital or Healthcare Provider*.

Health care quality:

Health care quality is a level of value provided by any health care resource, as determined by some measurement. As with quality in other fields, it is an assessment of whether something is good enough and whether it is suitable for its purpose. The goal of health care is to provide medical resources of high quality to all who need them; that is, to ensure good quality of life, to cure illnesses when possible, to extend life expectancy, and so on. Researchers use a variety of quality measures to attempt to determine health care quality, including counts of a therapy's reduction or lessening of diseases identified by medical diagnosis, a decrease in the number of risk factors which people have following preventive care, or a survey of health indicators in a population who are accessing certain kinds of care.

Health care quality is the degree to which health care services for individuals and populations increase the likelihood of desired health outcomes.⁵⁷ Quality of care plays an important role in describing the iron triangle of health care, which defines the intricate relationships between quality, cost, and accessibility of health care within a community.⁵⁸ Researchers measure health care quality to identify problems caused by overuse, underuse, or misuse of health resources.⁵⁹ In 1999, the Institute of Medicine released six domains to measure and describe quality of care in health:⁶⁰

1. Safe – avoiding injuries to patients from care that is intended to help them.
2. Effective – avoiding overuse and misuse of care.
3. Patient-Centered – providing care that is unique to a patient's needs.
4. Timely – reducing wait times and harmful delays for patients and providers.
5. Efficient – avoiding waste of equipment, supplies, ideas and energy.
6. Equitable – providing care that does not vary across intrinsic personal characteristics.

While essential for determining the effect of health services research interventions, measuring quality of care poses some challenges due to the limited number of outcomes that are measurable.⁶¹ Structural measures describe the providers' ability to provide high quality care, process measures describe the actions taken to maintain or improve community health, and outcome measures describe the impact of a health care intervention.⁶² Furthermore, due to strict regulations placed on health services research, data sources are not always complete.⁶³

Assessment of health care quality may occur on two different levels: that of the individual patient and that of populations. At the level of the individual patient, or micro-level, assessment focuses on services at the point of delivery and its subsequent effects. At the population level, or macro-level, assessments of health care quality include indicators such as life expectancy, infant mortality rates, incidence, and prevalence of certain health conditions.⁶⁴

Quality assessments measure these indicators against an established standard. The measures can be difficult to define in health care.⁶⁵ Quality assurance is distinct from quality assessment and is based on the principles of total quality management (TQM). It is a method of using quality assessment measures in a system-wide manner to deliver high-quality care that is continually improving.⁶⁶

Methods to assess and improve:

The Donabedian model is a common framework for assessing health care quality and identifies three domains in which health care quality can be assessed: structure, process, and outcomes.⁶⁷ All three domains are tightly linked and build on each other. Improvements in structure and process are often observed in outcomes. Some examples of improvements in process are: clinical practice guidelines, analysis of cost efficiency, and risk management, which consists of proactive steps to prevent medical errors.

History in the United States:

As early as the 19th century, healthcare quality improvement interventions were implemented in an effort to improve healthcare outcomes.⁶⁸ Healthcare quality improvement further developed in the 1900s, with notable improvements for the modern field of quality improvement taking place in the late 1960s.

In the early 1900s, Dr. Ernest Codman of Massachusetts General Hospital suggested a measure that tracked each patient of the hospital to determine effectiveness of their treatment. His proposal of a system to track patient care to determine quality and standard of hospital care dubbed him one of the earliest advocates of healthcare quality.⁶⁹ Shortly after, influenced by the work of Dr. Codman, the American College of Surgeons (ACS) was founded. In 1918, the ACS developed the Minimum Standard for Hospitals, which was one page. As a result of the 1918 Minimum Standard for Hospitals, ACS began performing on-site inspections of hospitals to determine if they were up to par. During the first on-site inspections of 692 hospitals, only 13% met the minimum standard.⁷⁰

In 1945, Joseph Juran and Edwards Deming established Quality Improvement (QI) as a formal approach to analyzing systematic efforts to improve performance.⁷¹ Specifically, Deming, a philosopher, placed emphasis on the macro level of organizational management and improvement via a systems approach. Juran, on the other hand, strategized quality planning, control, and improvement at the micro

level. He encouraged questions, believing they deepened understanding of problems and led to increased effectiveness in planning and taking action. Together, their work influenced quality of both American public and private organizations in fields from healthcare and industry to government and education.

The Joint Commission on Accreditation of Hospitals (JCAH) was established in 1951 as an independent and non-profit organization that provided voluntary accreditation to hospitals that met minimum quality standards.⁷² JCAH was formed by the combined forces of the American College of Physicians, the American College of Surgeons, the American Hospital Association, the American Medical Association, and the Canadian Medical Association. In 1952, the ACS formally transferred its Hospital Standardization Program to JCAH. JCAH began to charge a fee for surveys in 1964.

The Social Security Amendments of 1965 were passed by Congress in an attempt to grant hospitals accredited by JCAH "deemed status". As such, those same hospitals were said to meet the necessary requirements to participate in Medicare and Medicaid.⁷³ Until 1966, when Avedis Donabedian, MD published his "Evaluating the Quality of Medical Care", the study of health care quality was based on structure (e.g., licensing, staffing levels, accreditation). Donabedian demonstrated a new perspective on analyzing healthcare quality that was based on structure, process, and outcome.

The National Academy of Sciences established the Institute of Medicine (IOM) in 1970. The IOM, a non-profit and independent scientific advisor, was created to improve health on a national scale. The Accreditation Association for Ambulatory Health Care (AAAHHC) formed in 1970 to improve healthcare quality for patients served by ambulatory health care organizations by setting standards for ambulatory healthcare accreditation, similar to JCAH. The Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) was created in 1989 in order to improve quality, safety, efficiency, and effectiveness of health care through research.

In 1990, the National Committee for Quality Assurance (NCQA) was entrusted to offer accreditation programs for managed care organizations. The NCQA was established as an independent non-profit dedicated to improving health care quality through accreditation and performance measurement.⁷⁴ In 1991, Dr. Don Berwick's non-profit Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) was founded. Rather than only focus on national health care quality improvement, IHI campaigned but nationally and worldwide. Directing the focus onto the patient as a consumer, the National Patient Safety Foundation was established in 1996. In 1998, by presidential directive, the Quality Interagency Coordination Task Force (QuIC) was created to increase coordination of federal agencies that work toward improving quality care.^[25] When the IOM published *To Err is Human* in 1999, revealing high medical error mortality rates, the QuIC published a report that inventoried regulatory and legislative initiatives that sought to improve issues surrounding medical error. Also in 1999, the National Quality Forum was founded. The private, non-profit forum

aims to standardize health care delivery and measurements of quality.⁷⁵ In response to the patient safety concerns discussed in *To Err is Human*, the United States enacted the Patient Safety and Quality Improvement Act in 2005.

More recently, the focus of quality improvement has been emerging health information technology (e.g., electronic health records and patient-centered care).⁷⁶ As a result, the formation of Patient-Centered Medical Homes (PCMH) began to gain popularity in 2007. Under PCMH, care among personal primary care physicians and specialists increased coordination and integration of care for the patient. Furthermore, technology was used to maintain personal health information and enhance quality and safety. Since 2007, various studies have demonstrated the wide array of benefits of PCMHs in healthcare quality improvement.⁷⁷

Organizations which determine quality:

Organizations which work to set standards and measures for health care quality include Government health systems; private health systems, accreditation programs such as those for hospital accreditation, health associations, or those who wish to establish international healthcare accreditation; philanthropic foundations; and health research institutions. These organizations seek to define the concept of quality in healthcare, measure that quality, and then encourage the regular measurement of quality so as to provide evidence that health interventions are effective.⁷⁸

Healthcare and Hospital Accreditation:

Fundamentally healthcare and hospital accreditation is about improving how care is delivered to patients and the quality of the care they receive. Accreditation has been defined as "A self-assessment and external peer assessment process used by health care organizations to accurately assess their level of performance in relation to established standards and to implement ways to continuously improve" Interest in hospital accreditation ascends as far as the World Health Organisation. Accreditation is one important component in patient safety. However, there is limited and contested evidence supporting the effectiveness of accreditation programs.⁷⁹

In the USA in the early 20th century, there was concern over how to best create an appropriate environment in which clinicians could work. Standards to improve the control of the hospital environment were thus generated, and these subsequently grew into accreditation schemes with the remit to facilitate and improve organisational development. Part of the process is not only about assessing quality, but also about promoting and improving quality. Similar accreditation schemes were soon developed elsewhere in the world.

In countries such as the United Kingdom, the USA, Australia, New Zealand and Canada, sophisticated accreditation groups have grown up to survey hospitals (and, in some cases, healthcare in the community). Furthermore, other accreditation groups have been set up with openly declared remits to look after just

one particular area of healthcare, such as laboratory medicine or psychiatric services or sexual health.

Accreditation systems are structured so as to provide objective measures for the external evaluation of quality and quality management. Accreditation schemes should ideally focus primarily on the patient and their pathway through the healthcare system – this includes how they access care, how they are cared for after discharge from hospital, and the quality of the services provided for them. At the heart of these schemes is a list of standards which, ideally, serve to assess evaluate in a systematic and comprehensive way the standards of professional performance in a hospital. This includes not only hand-on patient care but also training and education of staff, credentials, clinical governance and audit, research activity, ethical standards etc. The standards can also be used internally by hospitals to develop and improve their quality standards and quality management. Some international accreditation schemes believe that the standards applied should be fixed and are non-negotiable, while others operate a system of negotiation over standards - however, whatever approach is taken the every aspect of the process should be evidence-based.

International standardization groups also exist, but it must be pointed out that the mere achieving of set standards is not the only factor involved in quality accreditation - there is also the significant matter of the incorporating into participating hospitals systems of self-examination, problem solving and self-improvement, and hence there is more to accreditation than following some sort of overall "standardization" process.

As governments and the general public have increasingly come to demand more and more openness about health care and its delivery, including and especially hospital quality and safety and the clinical performance of doctors, and these accreditation systems have generally adapted to fulfill this extended role.

However, accreditation should ideally be independent of governmental control, and accreditation groups should assess hospitals “holistically”, and not just some isolated facet of the hospital’s activities or services such as the laboratories, pharmacy services, infection control, financial health or information technology services (indeed, partial accreditation of this type should be publicly acknowledged as such by both the accreditation scheme and the hospital). The best accreditation schemes also assess academic and intellectual activity (such as teaching and research) within those hospitals that they survey (see later) and have a clear and declared interest in medical ethics.

In some parts of the world, accessing healthcare can be very expensive, even prohibitively so. While some countries have elected to provide comprehensive healthcare services for all of their populations, others appear to be satisfied with leaving portions of their population without access to healthcare. When it comes to

who pays the bills for healthcare, it may be the government or it may be the individual (sometimes either by direct payment, and sometimes through employer-run schemes, insurance companies etc.), or a combination of both. However, healthcare can never be truly “free” – someone somewhere will always have to pay, and the payer will always want the best value for money possible. "Affordability" of healthcare can be the insurmountable hurdle for some human beings. Value for money is hence another factor in assessing the true quality of healthcare.

A number of larger countries engage in hospital accreditation that is provided internally. Taking the USA as an example, numerous groups provide accreditation for internal healthcare organizations, including the AAAHC Accreditation Association for Ambulatory Health Care, Community Health Accreditation Program (CHAP), the Joint Commission, DNV, the Accreditation Commission for Health Care, Inc. (ACHC), the "Exemplary Provider Program" of The Compliance Team, American Accreditation Council (AAC), and the Healthcare Quality Association on Accreditation (HQAA).

Some other countries have looked towards accessing the services of the major international healthcare accreditation groups based in other countries to assess their healthcare services. There are many reasons for this, including cost, a desire to improve healthcare quality for one's own citizens (good governance is at the basis of all high-quality healthcare), or a desire to market one's healthcare services to “medical tourists” (see below). Some hospitals go for international healthcare accreditation as a *de facto* form of advertising.

In response to this marketing opportunity, some national accreditation groups have expanded their wings internationally, and gone on to survey and accredit hospitals outside of their own national borders. When they choose to do this, such groups can be said to be providing "international healthcare accreditation".

This process of accreditation has been made increasingly complicated by the fact that in many parts of the world, more and more human beings are choosing to cross international borders to access healthcare, a phenomenon known as “medical tourism” or "Global Healthcare". Medical tourism/Global Healthcare cannot be ignored as a key issue in international healthcare accreditation - it is becoming increasingly important as millions of (especially) Europeans and Americans seek healthcare overseas outside of their own countries for a variety of reasons (including and especially affordability), and it represents a growing multi-billion euro/dollar/pound business of increasing importance to the economies of many countries, such as Singapore, Thailand, India, Hong Kong, Malaysia and the Philippines. The importance of medical tourism /Global Healthcare to the economy of developing countries is increasingly the subject of academic study⁸⁰ and this synergy has a clear "knock-on" effect for those organizations based within the

developed world who are seeking to develop the medical tourism/Global Healthcare market.

The different accreditation schemes vary in approach, quality, size, intent, sourcing of surveyors and the skill of their marketing. They also vary in terms of how much they charge hospitals and healthcare institutions for their services. They all have web sites.

Accreditation Services:

If a hospital or clinic simply wishes to improve its services to patients wherever those patients come from (locally or from further afield), or wishes to attract medical tourists, how do they choose who to go to when contemplating accessing external peer review by an accreditation group such as those listed above.

No one healthcare system has a monopoly of excellence and no one provider country or scheme can claim to be the total arbiter of quality. The same is true of healthcare accreditation schemes.

For example, some countries (such as the USA) perform very poorly when it comes to providing anything close to universal access to healthcare of adequate quality to the population living within their own borders, while others (such as the UK) have tried to create state-funded systems which provide everything without the assistance of the private sector. Other differences exist – for example, general medical practice ("GP", also sometimes known as Family Medicine) is strong in the UK but weak in the USA, while US hospitals generally have greater expertise in marketing and billing. Different accreditation schemes are sourced out of different parts of the world, for example JCI out of the USA and North America, QHA Trent out of Europe, and ACHSI out of Oceania (see map). As no single international accreditation scheme enjoys exclusive rights to be seen as an overall world-wide-relevant scheme, some hospitals are looking towards multiple accreditation to achieve performance credibility in different parts of the world.

With respect to the cost of accreditation, this can vary enormously and it can be hard to find out precise data; in the case of JCI, the costs can be substantial.

With respect to hospital work, ISO (the International Organization for Standardization) is often mistakenly considered to be an international healthcare accreditation scheme. It is not.

Hospital accreditation is defined as “A self-assessment and external peer assessment process used by health care organizations to accurately assess their level of performance in relation to established standards and to implement ways to continuously improve”. Critically, accreditation is not just about standard-setting: there are analytical, counseling and self-improvement dimensions to the process.

There are parallel issues around evidence - based medicine, quality assurance and medical ethics (see below), and the reduction of medical error is a key role of the accreditation process. Hospital accreditation is therefore one component in the maintenance of patient safety. However, there is limited and contested evidence supporting the effectiveness of accreditation programs.⁸¹

Broadly speaking, there exist two types of hospital accreditation:

1. National healthcare accreditation
2. International healthcare accreditation.

Hospitals and healthcare services are vital components of any well-ordered and humane society, and will indisputably be the recipients of societal resources. That hospitals should be places of safety, not only for patients but also for the staff and for the general public, is of the greatest importance. Quality of hospitals and healthcare services is also of great interest to many other bodies, including governments, NGOs targeting healthcare and social welfare, professional organisations representing doctors, patient organisations, shareholders of companies providing healthcare services, etc. However, accreditation schemes are not the same thing as government-controlled initiatives set up to assess healthcare providers with only governmental objectives in mind - ideally, the functioning and finance of hospital accreditation schemes should be independent of governmental control.

How quality is maintained and improved in hospitals and healthcare services is the subject of much debate. Hospital surveying and accreditation is one recognised means by which this can be achieved.

It is not just an issue of hospital quality. There are financial factors as well. For example, in the USA, up until recently the Joint Commission exercised a *de facto* veto over whether or not US hospitals and other health providers were able to participate, and therefore earn from, the Medicare and Medicaid programs. This situation has changed in recent years.

National Healthcare Accreditation:

The national healthcare accreditation program is offered by the national level healthcare accreditation organizations. Such accreditation programs are limited to the nation only.

International Healthcare Accreditation:

The international healthcare accreditation programs are offered by the international level healthcare accreditation organizations which are not for profit.

Due to the near-universal desire for safe and good quality healthcare, there is a growing interest in international healthcare accreditation.⁸² Providing healthcare, especially of an adequate standard, is a complex and challenging process. Healthcare

is a vital and emotive issue—its importance pervades all aspects of societies, and it has medical, social, political, ethical, business, and financial ramifications. In any part of the world healthcare services can be provided either by the public sector or by the private sector, or by a combination of both, and the site of delivery of healthcare can be located in hospitals or be accessed through practitioners working in the community, such as general medical practitioners and dentists.

This is occurring in most parts of the developed world in a setting in which people are expressing ever-greater expectations of hospitals and healthcare services. This trend is especially strong where socialised medical systems exist. For example, in the European Union "... patients have ever-greater expectations of what health systems ought to deliver," although there has been a "... continuous rise in costs of services determined by scientific and technological innovation."⁸³ And in one particular EU member state, the United Kingdom, "... People are going to increase demand and they have also got an increased expectation of what the NHS can deliver."⁸⁴ The USA manifests some differences here, and is an unusual and distinct oddity among developed Western countries. In 2007, 45.7 million of the overall US population (i.e. 15.3%) had no health insurance whatsoever⁸⁵ yet in 2007 the USA spent nearly \$2.3 trillion on healthcare, or 16% of the country's gross domestic product, more than twice as much per capita as the OECD average.⁸⁶ Because of this, some US citizens are having to look outside of their country to find affordable healthcare, through the medium of medical tourism, also known as "Global Healthcare".

Apart from using hospitals and healthcare services to regain their health if it has become impaired, or to prevent ill health occurring in the first place, people the world over may also use them for a wide variety of other services, for example "improving upon nature"⁸⁷ or acquiring help to overcome difficulties with becoming a parent.

International Society for Quality in Health Care (ISQua):

The International Society for Quality in Health Care (ISQua) is a global organization responsible for assessing the standards of organizations who set the benchmarks in healthcare safety and quality and is the only organization to 'accredit the accreditors'. ISQua also promotes improvement in quality and safety through its education programme, international conferences and global partnerships. ISQua undertook a major review and development of its Quality and Safety Management System (QSMS) in order to ensure it was providing its services to the highest level and to fulfil its own International Accreditation Programme (IAP) Organisational Standards.

The International Society for Quality in Health Care (ISQua) is an umbrella organisation for such organisations providing international healthcare accreditation. Its offices are based in the Republic of Ireland. ISQua is a small non-profit limited

company with members in over 70 countries. ISQua works to provide services to guide health professionals, providers, researchers, agencies, policy makers and consumers, to achieve excellence in healthcare delivery to all people, and to continuously improve the quality and safety of care. ISQua does not actually survey or accredit hospitals or clinics itself. “The ISQua International Accreditation Programme provides a mechanism for external evaluation and standard-settings organisations to assure themselves that their standards, their surveyor training programmes and that they, themselves, as an external evaluation organisation, meet international best practice requirements and to demonstrate this to their clients, funders and stakeholders.”⁸⁸

National Accreditation Board for Hospitals & Healthcare Providers (NABH):

National Accreditation Board for Hospitals & Healthcare Providers is a constituent board of Quality Council of India, set up to establish and operate accreditation programme for healthcare organizations. Formed in 2005, it is the principal accreditation for hospitals in India.⁸⁹

Organisations like the Quality Council of India (QCI) and its National Accreditation Board for Hospitals & Healthcare Providers have designed an exhaustive healthcare standard for hospitals and healthcare providers. This standard consists of stringent 600 plus objective elements for the hospital to achieve in order to get the NABH accreditation. These standards are divided between patient centered standards and organization centred standards.

To comply with these standard elements, the hospital will need to have a process-driven approach in all aspects of hospital activities – from registration, admission, pre-surgery, peri-surgery and post-surgery protocols, discharge from the hospital to follow up with the hospital after discharge. Not only the clinical aspects but the governance aspects are to process driven based on clear and transparent policies and protocols. In a nutshell, NABH aims at streamlining the entire operations of a hospital.

NABH standards have been accredited by ISQUA the apex body accrediting the accreditors hence making NABH accreditation at par with the world’s most leading hospital accreditation. The Quality Council of India works under the guidance of Ministry of Commerce.

The NABH accreditation system was established in 2006 as a constituent of Quality Council of India (QCI). The first edition of standards was released in 2006 and after that the standards has been revised every 3 years. Currently the 4th edition of NABH standards, released in December 2015 is in use.

The first hospital to be accredited by NABH is 'Malabar Institute of Medical Sciences (MIMS), Kerala' which is a 650-bed multispeciality hospital and was

accredited in 2007 and till date more than 350 hospitals in India has achieved accreditation by NABH. In public hospitals, Gandhinagar General hospital was the first to get NABH accreditation in 2009.

National Safety and Quality Health Service (NSQHS):

The National Safety and Quality Health Service (NSQHS) Standards were developed by the Australian Commission on Safety and Quality in Health Care with the Australian Government, state and territory partners, consumers and the private sector. The primary aim of the NSQHS Standards is to protect the public from harm and improve the quality of health care. They describe the level of care that should be provided by health service organisations and the systems that are needed to deliver such care.

The first edition of the NSQHS Standards, which was released in 2011, has been used to assess health service organisations since January 2013. Using the NSQHS Standards, health service organisations have put in place safety and quality systems that have improved patient safety. For example, the rates of healthcare-associated infections have decreased, in-hospital cardiac arrests have decreased, adverse drug reactions and medication histories are better documented and less antibiotics are prescribed due to improvements in antibiotic stewardship.

The second edition of the NSQHS Standards were released in November 2017, and health service organisations will be assessed against the new standards from January 2019. Health service organisations will be informed of the transition arrangements for accreditation well in advance of implementation. The second edition was developed by the Commission in consultation with a wide range of stakeholders, including the Australian Government, state and territory partners, health service organisations, consumers, peak bodies and interest groups. The second edition of the NSQHS Standards addresses gaps identified in the first edition, including mental health and cognitive impairment, health literacy, end-of-life care, and Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander health. It also updates the evidence for actions, consolidates and streamlines standards and actions to make them clearer and easier to implement, and reduces duplication.

Danish Institute for Quality and Accreditation in Healthcare (DDKM):⁹⁰

The Danish Institute for Quality and Accreditation in Healthcare, develops, plans and runs the Danish accreditation programme for healthcare providers, called the Danish Healthcare Quality Programme (DDKM). DDKM is an independent institution financed partially by public means, while private clients cover the costs related to their accreditation. It was established in 2005 and is supervised by a board of directors, including representatives from the Danish Health Authority, Danish Regions, the Ministry of Interior and Health, Local Government Denmark, The Association of Danish Pharmacies, and The Danish Chamber of Commerce,

representing private hospitals. The first accreditation surveys were conducted in late 2009 in pharmacies and 2010 in hospitals.

DDKM offers a range of accreditation programmes, tailored for private hospitals, community pharmacies, community health care, primary care physicians (general practice), specialist physicians practicing outside of a hospital setting and chiropractors. Programmes will be launched for other out-of-hospital based healthcare practitioners over the next years.

A new accreditation programme is developed, when the parties involved in providing publically financed healthcare in the sector in question have made the decision to launch such a programme and have agreed on the overall framework, including the economic framework. As an example, the programme for general practitioners was launched based on a clause in the agreement between the Organisation of General Practitioners in Denmark and the Danish Regions, regulating provision of general primary care medicine. The programme for private hospitals enables the regions to fulfill their regulatory duty to ensure the quality of services provided at their expense; while access to public hospitals is free, citizens have a statutory right to free care in the private sector, if the public sector cannot deliver timely care.

For health care practitioners, participation in DDKM is, with a few well defined exceptions, mandated for those working under the agreement in questions. Others, working in same field without any public financing, can join the programme. In such cases, a fee covering the expenses to DDKM, will be charged. For pharmacies and municipalities, participation is voluntary. While a large majority of pharmacies are enrolled, the uptake among the municipalities is modest. The public hospitals have completed two full three year cycles of accreditation, and the prehospital care (ambulance services) will in 2016 have completed two cycles as well. The Government and the Danish Regions have decided to discontinue accreditation of these providers in favour of other strategies to promote quality improvement. DDKM is committed to pursue the idea of accreditation as a fair and transparent peer evaluation, intended to promote and support continuous quality improvement, while at the same time keeping providers accountable for delivering safe care to patients and for complying with fundamental patients' rights. DDKM participates in ISQua's International Accreditation Programme is represented on the Accreditation Council of ISQua, and has valid accreditations as an external evaluation organization, for its surveyor training programme, and for several sets of accreditation standards. In 2016 a mandatory accreditation scheme was initiated in Denmark, and during a 3-year period all practices, as default, should undergo accreditation according to the Danish Healthcare Quality Program.⁹¹

Council for Health Service Accreditation of Southern Africa (COHSASA):⁹²

The Council for Health Service Accreditation of Southern Africa (COHSASA) is the only internationally accredited quality improvement and accreditation body for healthcare facilities in sub-Saharan Africa. In the past 24 years over 600 facilities throughout the continent have entered the COHSASA programme to improve the quality and safety of healthcare provided to patients.

The Council for Health Service Accreditation of Southern Africa (COHSASA), a not-for-profit organisation in Cape Town, South Africa, assists a wide range of healthcare facilities to meet and maintain quality standards. This process enables the facilities to provide safe, quality services to their patients and families. In the past 21 years of operation, COHSASA has worked in over 600 facilities in both the public and private sectors in South Africa, Botswana, Swaziland, Lesotho, Namibia, Rwanda, Nigeria, Uganda, Zambia, Tanzania, Ghana, Egypt and Kenya. COHSASA runs programmes in hospitals, clinics, hospices, emergency medical services, environmental health offices and rehabilitation/sub-acute establishments. There is a strong focus on building capacity. The COHSASA programme helps healthcare professionals to measure themselves against standards. This approach teaches healthcare workers how to monitor improvements using quality improvement methods, internationally accredited standards and a web-based information system. COHSASA has achieved global recognition and is the only African health facility accrediting body that is accredited by the International Society for Quality in Health Care (ISQua). Since it achieved its first accreditation award from ISQua in 2002, the Council has maintained its accredited status with three further accreditations. Its current ISQua accreditation status is valid until December 2018. Two sets of its standards – for hospitals and palliative care – are currently accredited by ISQua and COHSASA's Surveyor Training Programme is accredited by ISQua until 2018. The programme developed by COHSASA builds capacity in local organisations so that they can take ownership of the programme from the outset. Initial training is followed by a baseline assessment, where all departments in a facility are assessed against the standards. In an average hospital (+/- 100 beds) about 3,500 measurable elements are evaluated. Quality Advisors (QAs) then train and support staff in quality assurance concepts, quality improvement methods and self-evaluation so that ownership of the data and the overall programme is quickly established. The Council has introduced a graded recognition process where incremental levels of progress in achieving compliance with standards are recognised through certification. COHSASA certifies departments within facilities and also facilities that do not achieve full accreditation but have achieved acceptable and safe levels of standards compliance and service delivery. This has the effect of encouraging efforts towards full compliance with standards and institutionalising quality improvement. The web-based electronic COHSASA Quality Information System (CoQIS) allows facility staff to have access to a continuous, easy-to-use management tool that assists them to run their establishments efficiently. CoQIS captures all the evaluation data compiled by surveyors and quality advisors during a baseline survey. This enables users to

understand the baseline situation in healthcare facilities, identify deficiencies, prioritise interventions and monitor improving compliance with standards at individual facilities and across groups of them. The information system enables personnel in healthcare facilities to have direct access to quality improvement data so that they can monitor their performance against standards. CoQIS supports on-going quality improvement programmes in all areas of healthcare facilities and enables management at all levels to make informed decisions when responding to deficiencies. CoQIS guides hospital management and clinical staff to make targeted, realistic and sustained interventions that will improve quality in a facility. In addition to its own programmes, the Council also uses the extensive knowledge and experience of its quality advisors to support and train clients using other quality programmes such as the SafeCare Programme and the National Core Standards. The capacity building approach is used to develop skills in quality improvement and quality assurance methods, including self-evaluation against standards and developing quality improvement plans and programmes to address identified deficiencies. The level of assistance provided to clients is determined by client need. Patient Safety is an integral part of quality health care. In 2006, the Council became the distributor for the Australian Advanced Incident Management System (AIMS) and successfully supported the implementation of a major patient safety programme in the Free State Province. A similar electronic system, PatSIS, has now been developed by the Council. The patient safety programme currently uses a call centre, located at the Council, where all reported incidents are captured into the system. As soon as the incident is captured, the information is available to the users. When the most serious incidents occur, the hospital CEO and relevant officials are immediately notified by a text message. The users are required to manage each incident according to agreed protocols, which vary according to the severity of each incident. The process is monitored by the call centre team and by the relevant officer in the facility. The local Department of Health oversees the whole process. The setup of PatSIS can be configured to meet client needs – either with a remote or local call centre or with centralised or remote technical assistance. The quality improvement and patient safety programmes together offer a highly efficient and effective mechanism for improving patient and staff safety. They enable staff to take responsibility for the quality of patient care and provide invaluable data for research to identify trends that can further improve the care of patients. With staff doing the right thing first time and avoiding errors, the cost effectiveness of care is also improved. COHSASA offers its services to meet individual client needs so that healthcare facilities are equipped for the long-term to meet the safety and quality health needs of the population they serve in the most efficient and cost-effective manner possible.⁹³

By making health systems more resilient, COHSASA assists a range of healthcare facilities in Southern Africa to meet and maintain quality standards. This range includes hospitals, clinics, general and family practitioners, rehabilitation centres, hospices, emergency centres, ambulances and laundries. Standards are also being developed for individual services such as sedation units and home-based care.

There is a strong focus on building capacity to help healthcare professionals measure themselves against the standards. The COHSASA approach teaches healthcare workers how to monitor improvements using quality improvement methods, internationally accredited standards and a web-based information system. Strictly applied quality improvement methods can improve patient safety and the quality of care by identifying deficiencies, guiding interventions and monitoring progress. COHSASA's web-based information system – CoQIS – identifies deficiencies and weaknesses in healthcare facilities and creates prioritised quality improvement plans to overcome them. The data generated helps authorities to provide cost-effective interventions.

COHSASA holds a fourth consecutive accreditation by the International Society for Quality in Health Care (ISQua). ISQua is the global authority responsible for ensuring that health accreditors themselves meet standards. COHSASA's hospital standards (Edition 6.7) and its surveyor training programme are currently accredited by ISQua.

“There is consistent evidence that shows that accreditation programs improve the process of care provided by healthcare services. There is considerable evidence to show that accreditation programs improve clinical outcomes of a wide spectrum of clinical conditions. Accreditation programs should be supported as a tool to improve the quality of healthcare services.”⁹⁴

Healthcare System, Quality Improvement and Patient Safety in India:

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines “**Health**” as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity, and “**Healthcare**” is the prevention, treatment, and management of illness and the preservation of mental and physical well-being through the services offered by the medical and allied health professions.

Health care is the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of disease, illness, injury, and other physical and mental impairments in humans. Health care is delivered by practitioners in medicine, chiropractic, dentistry, nursing, pharmacy, allied health, and other care providers. It refers to the work done in providing primary care, secondary care and tertiary care, as well as in public health.

Access to health care varies across countries, groups and individuals, largely influenced by social and economic conditions as well as the health policies in place. Countries and jurisdictions have different policies and plans in relation to the personal and population-based health care goals within their societies. Health care systems are organizations established to meet the health needs of target populations. Their exact configuration varies from country to country. In some countries and jurisdictions, health care planning is distributed among market participants, whereas in others

planning is made more centrally among governments or other coordinating bodies. In all cases, according to the World Health Organization (WHO), a well-functioning health care system requires a robust financing mechanism; a well-trained and adequately-paid workforce; reliable information on which to base decisions and policies; and well maintained facilities and logistics to deliver quality medicines and technologies.

Patient safety and affordable healthcare have emerged as major concerns all over the world and more so among the developing nations. Around 190 young women die out of 100,000 live births⁹⁵ and about 40 children die on the day they are borne out of every 1,000 live births in India, mainly for want of adequate patient safety measures. India has about 9.5 million deaths a year⁹⁶. Cardiovascular diseases account for nearly 27 per cent of the deaths⁹⁷. Infectious and parasitic diseases account for nearly 20 per cent. Respiratory infection (pneumonia) with 11 per cent, respiratory diseases (COPD, Asthma) with nine per cent, and cancer with eight per cent, is some of the other causes of deaths. India has more than 60 million people with diabetes⁹⁸ and nearly 15 per cent population⁹⁹ has raised fasting blood sugar. Considering that about 50 per cent of our population is in the productive age group (16-45 years)¹⁰⁰, this is going to be a major concern.

As per WHO report, road fatalities will become world's fifth biggest killer by 2030¹⁰¹. Ninety per cent of deaths on world's roads occur in low and middle income countries, though they have less than 50 per cent of all registered vehicles. India has very poor record, as it registers about 12 deaths per 100,000 population every year¹⁰². We urgently need to up-grade trauma care on our highways and evolve policies on emergency care through creation of National Road Accident Fund.

In order to encounter this voluminous disease burden, we need matching healthcare infrastructure. We have not been able to raise healthcare spending (public + private) more than five per cent of GDP¹⁰³. As compared to global average of 10.1 per cent¹⁰⁴. We have nearly five beds per 10,000 of population as compared to 30 in the USA¹⁰⁵. We have close to 400 medical colleges which annually produce over 50,000 doctors¹⁰⁶ and about 20,000 specialists¹⁰⁷.

Besides this about 21,500 dentists from 290 dental colleges¹⁰⁸, 1.2 lakh nurses from 2,400 nursing schools and 1,500 colleges¹⁰⁹, 30,000 Auxiliary Nursing and Midwifery (ANMs) from 1,300 schools and 70,542 pharmacists pass out from 1,211 schools/colleges. We are still grappling with severe shortage of doctors, nurses and midwives, which is presently half of the norm of 24.5 healthcare professionals per 10,000 populations¹¹⁰.

Complying with patient safety across the nation is going to be daunting task, more so when we do not have any uniform regulatory framework in the country. Introduction of NABH in year 2006 was truly a land mark event, which provided us with patient safety framework of global standards. During past nine years, only 300 hospitals have been able to get NABH accreditation¹¹¹. Considering that we have more than 50,000 hospitals/nursing

homes, we have long way to go. Presently there are no incentives for accrediting hospitals, in-spite of fact that they are required to put in huge efforts. Government need to urgently initiate measures by which all empanelment in the government insurance schemes and equally by private insurance companies are linked with NABH accreditation.

Next to patient safety, we have accessibility and affordability as major concerns. Large percentage of populations pays out of pocket for healthcare. With more and more state governments coming out with their insurance schemes, it is projected that more than 50 per cent population¹¹² will get covered by current financial year under some or other government scheme. These also include Central Government Health Scheme (CGHS), Ex-Servicemen Contributory Health Scheme (ECHS), Employee's State Insurance (ESI), Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojna (RSBY) and private insurance schemes. As we do not have effective template to fix rates for various medical procedures, it is going to be tough task to fix reimbursement rates under these schemes. In order to bring down the cost of healthcare, we need to enable our hospitals/nursing homes to apply modern management tools to improve the efficiency. Healthcare can pick up some of the tried and tested tools from manufacturing sector i.e. 5S, KAIZEN, LEAN, six-sigma, balance score card, total productive maintenance, etc. and apply in their operations. Green concepts can also help in improving efficiency through optimal use of resources and in cutting down of waste processes.

Since independence, healthcare in India has been challenged by the issues of affordability and accessibility to quality healthcare. With around a quarter of the population living below poverty line and around 70 per cent dwelling in rural areas¹¹³, providing healthcare to these section of society should be central to policies being drafted by the government. In this scenario, the concept of universal health coverage becomes imperative and core to the health development and needs of the people. Singapore model of social health insurance has created an environment that not only helps ensures quality but also an affordable healthcare, and this has won applauses across the globe. This model can inspire Indian policymakers to adopt a social health security model that aspires to deliver healthcare across four pillars -availability, affordability, accessibility and acceptability.

Today, Indian healthcare system stands at a cross-road. In the last one decade, even though Indian healthcare has taken leaps in terms of becoming a medical tourism destination, the delivery system both public and private, continues to remain elusive to the section of society with high healthcare needs. With efforts to meet health targets envisioned under Millennium Development Goals getting either off-track or dawdling, it becomes imperative for Indian healthcare stakeholders to revisit the policy and identify any gaps in the actions taken.

Deliberation of the current state of Indian healthcare is an integral step to begin with. This will help in identifying gaps and a structured approach under the policies being penned down. A thoughtful critique of the National Health Policy 2015 (NHP 2015) draft will enable the stakeholders to identify any challenges that remains to be answered.

Healthcare sector is emerging at a healthy growth rate of around 15 per cent¹¹⁴. It has huge potential in providing employment more so to the women. The private sector is investing in a big way. Government need to incentivise and streamline the clearance process.

In time to come, we hope to see happy and healthy India under National Health Assurance mission, launched by Government of India. The mission should be able to integrate promotive, preventive and curative segments and include associated subjects like safe drinking water, sanitation and sustainable environment. Government must accord priority to collect demography and disease related data to support policy and plans.

The healthcare sector in India is poised at a crossroads where the right policy action is extremely critical in determining the future course of the sector. The industry faces major challenges owing to the changing demographics of the country, the poor state of the public infrastructure, lack of financial resources, paucity of human capital and poor governance. The staggeringly low contribution of the public sector in the healthcare industry sits at the centre of all these problems. While the National Health Policy tries to address the majority of these challenges, it lacks significantly in terms of the feasibility of implementation and also inadequate finances.¹¹⁵

Health and health care need to be distinguished from each other for no better reason than that the former is often incorrectly seen as a direct function of the latter. Health is clearly not the mere absence of disease. Good Health confers on a person or groups freedom from illness - and the ability to realize one's potential. Health is therefore best understood as the indispensable basis for defining a person's sense of well being. The health of populations is a distinct key issue in public policy discourse in every mature society often determining the deployment of huge society. They include its cultural understanding of ill health and well-being, extent of socio-economic disparities, reach of health services and quality and costs of care and current bio-medical understanding about health and illness.¹¹⁶

Health care covers not merely medical care but also all aspects pro preventive care too. Nor can it be limited to care rendered by or financed out of public expenditure within the government sector alone but must include incentives and disincentives for self care and care paid for by private citizens to get over ill health. Where, as in India, private out-of-pocket expenditure dominates the cost financing health care, the effects are bound to be regressive. Health care at its essential core is widely recognized to be a public good. Its demand and supply cannot therefore, be left to be regulated solely by the invisible hand of the market. Nor can it be established on considerations of utility maximizing conduct alone.

What makes for a just health care system even as an ideal? Four criteria could be suggested- First universal access, and access to an adequate level, and access without excessive burden. Second fair distribution of financial costs for access and fair distribution of burden in rationing care and capacity and a constant search for

improvement to a more just system. Third training providers for competence empathy and accountability, pursuit of quality care of cost effective use of the results of relevant research. Last special attention to vulnerable groups such a children, women, disabled and the aged.

Patient Safety in India

Patient Safety is becoming an issue of concern worldwide. Pressed with this consideration, in October 2004, WHO launched the World Alliance for Patient Safety in response to a World Health Assembly Resolution in the year 2002, urging WHO and Member States to pay closest possible attention to the problem of patient safety. A vast body of work has been done in western countries for issues relating to patient safety. ¹⁶ Hospitals and health care delivery systems have systemized quality and patient safety initiatives within their culture, thus building in more accountability and tangibility to safer care. However, the culture of patient safety in India is in an extremely nascent stage in the current milieu. Even though globalization, medical tourism and the socioeconomic changes may be ringing in winds of change in the context of patient safety, however, considering the complexity and diversity of our country, this is in a highly premature state.

Patient safety is a new field in India. There is no national level body looking after this aspect at present, neither are there any rules or regulations. Healthcare sector continues with a fragmented approach and a systems approach to handle the issue is lacking. National Accreditation Board for Hospitals and Healthcare Providers (NABH) has incorporated patient safety performance in its standards (NABH, Chapter 1, 5 and 6). Corporate hospitals, which are accredited by any agency and few apex institutes have started with patient safety activities like incident reporting, analysis of sentinel events, training and education programme for the employees. However, in the majority of the hospitals the approach is still far from satisfactory.

One out of 10 patients in developed countries are a victim of medical error while receiving treatment, studies revealed. Today, these countries recognize the importance of improving patient safety and have taken steps to be extra careful in their treatment.

In India, too, the importance of quality in healthcare has grown over the last two decades; Academy of Hospital Administration (AHA) has been playing an active role in evolving standards for hospitals and healthcare establishments through Quality Council of India and National Board for Hospital (NABH) accreditation.

The NABH has incorporated patient safety performance in its standards. Patient safety is the central theme of quality in health care, adding that well-designed work flows, processes, and checklists for delivering quality healthcare will ensure patient safety. Healthcare needs to build up a culture of quality for patient safety through measuring and improving performance through leadership and teamwork.

Communication, teamwork, and leadership skills are the key drivers of patient safety and quality in health care.¹¹⁷

The Indian Confederation for Healthcare Accreditation (ICHA) began collaboration with the World Health Organization's "World Alliance for Patient Safety," according to the *"The Times of India"*. Doctors, nurses, hospital administrators, patients' groups, and non-governmental organizations met at King Edward Memorial (KEM) Hospital to begin implementing the new patient safety initiatives.

Till now, patient- doctor relations have hinged on a confrontational, we-versus-them approach. According to *The Times of India*, the ICHA will now begin to identify clear-cut health care standards, train employees of hospitals, nursing homes, and clinics to spot medical errors and adverse reactions as well as encouraging the reporting of such events to help create a "*Desi*" database.

Many view quality health care as the overarching umbrella under which patient safety resides. For example, the Institute of Medicine (IOM) considers patient safety "indistinguishable from the delivery of quality health care."¹¹⁸ Ancient philosophers such as Aristotle and Plato contemplated quality and its attributes. In fact, quality was one of the great ideas of the Western world. Harteloh reviewed multiple conceptualizations of quality and concluded with a very abstract definition: "***Quality is an optimal balance between possibilities realized and a framework of norms and values.***" This conceptual definition reflects the fact that quality is an abstraction and does not exist as a discrete entity. Rather, it is constructed based on an interaction among relevant actors who agree about standards (the norms and values) and components (the possibilities).

Work groups such as those in the IOM have attempted to define quality of health care in terms of standards. Initially, the IOM defined quality as the "the degree to which health services for individuals and populations increase the likelihood of desired health outcomes and are consistent with current professional knowledge."¹¹⁹ This led to a definition of quality that appeared to be listings of quality indicators, which are expressions of the standards. These standards are not necessarily in terms of the possibilities or conceptual clusters for these indicators. Further, most clusters of quality indicators were and often continue to be comprised of the 5Ds— Death, Disease, Disability, Discomfort, and Dissatisfaction¹²⁰—rather than more positive components of quality.

The most recent IOM work to identify the components of quality care for the 21st century is centered on the conceptual components of quality rather than the measured indicators: quality care is safe, effective, patient centered, timely, efficient, and equitable. This safety is the foundation upon which all other aspects of quality care are built.¹²¹

Forecasting in Health Sector:

In general predictions about future health - of individuals and populations - can be notoriously uncertain. However all projections of health care in India must in the end rest on the overall changes in its political economy - on progress made in poverty mitigation (health care to the poor) in reduction of inequalities (health inequalities affecting access/quality'), in generation of employment /income streams (to facilitate capacity to pay and to accept individual responsibility for one's health). In public information and development communication (to promote preventive self care and risk reduction by conducive life styles) and in personal life style changes (often directly resulting from social changes and global influences). Of course it will also depend on progress in reducing mortality and the likely disease load, efficient and fair delivery and financing systems in private and public sectors and attention to vulnerable sections- family planning and nutritional services and women's empowerment and the confirmed interest of me siat-e 10 ensure just health care to the Largest extent possible. To list them is to recall that Indian planning had at its best attempted to capture this synergistic approach within a democratic structure. It is another matter that it is now remembered only for its mixed success.

Available health forecasts:

There is a forecast on the new health challenges likely to emerge in India over the next few decades. Murry and Lopez (World Bank B 2000) have provided a possible scenario of the burden of disease (BOD) for India in the year 2020, based on a statistical model calculating the change in DALYS are applied to the population projections for 2020 and conversely. The key conclusions must be understood keeping in the mind the fact that the concept of DALYs incorporates not only mortality but disability viewed in terms of healthy years of life lost. In this forecast, DALYs are expected to dramatically decrease in respect of diarrheal diseases and respiratory infections and less dramatically for maternal conditions. TB is expected to plateau by 2000, and HIV infections are expected to rise significantly up to 2010. Injuries may increase less significantly, the proportion of people above 65 will increase and as a result the burden of non communicable disease will rise. Finally cardiovascular diseases resulting any from the risk associated with smoking urban stress and improper diet are expected to increase dramatically. Under the same BOD methodology another view is available from a four – state analysis done in 1996 <World Bank B 2000> these four states - AP, Karnataka, W. Bengal and Punjab - represent different stages in the Indian health transition. The analysis reveals that the poorer and more populated states. West Bengal, will still face a large incidence of communicable diseases. More prosperous states, such as Punjab further along the health transiting will witness sharply increasing incidence of non communicable diseases especially, in urban areas. The projections highlight that we still operating on unreliable or incomplete base data on mortality and causes of death in the absence of vital registration statistics and know as yet little about how they differ between social classes and regions or about the dynamic patterns of change at work. It also highlights the policy dilemma of how to balance between the articulate middle upper class

demand for more access to technologically advanced and subsidized clinical services and the more pressing needs of the poor for coverage of basic disease control interventions. This conflict over deployment of public resources will only get exacerbated in future. What matters most in such estimates are not societal averages with respect to health but sound data illuminating specifically the health conditions of the disadvantaged in local areas that long tradition of health sector analysis looking at unequal access, income poverty and unjustly distributed resources as the trigger to meet health needs of the poor. That tradition has been totally replaced by the currently dominant school of international thought about health which is concerned primarily with efficiency of systems measured by cost effectiveness criteria.

Future of State Provided Health Care:

Historically the Indian commitment to health development has been guided by two principles-with three consequences. The first principle was State responsibility for health care and the second (after independence) was free medical care for all (and not merely to those unable to pay), The first set of consequences was inadequate priority to public health, poor investment in safe water and to the neglect of the key role of personal hygiene in good health, culminating in the persistence of diseases like Cholera. The second set of consequences pertains to substantially unrealized goals of NHP 1983 due to funding difficulties from compression of public expenditures and from organizational inadequacies. The ambitious and far reaching NPP - 2000 goals and strategies have however been formulated on that edifice in the hope that the gaps and the inadequate would be removed by purposeful action. Without being too defensive or critical about its past failures, the rural health structure should be strengthened and funded and managed efficiently in all States by 2005. This can trigger many dramatically changes over the next twenty years in neglected aspects or rural health and of vulnerable segments. The third set of consequences appears to be the inability to develop and integrate plural systems of medicine and the failure to assign practical roles to the private sector and to assign public duties for private professionals. To set right these gaps demanded patient redefinition of the state's role keeping the focus on equity. But during the last decade there has been an abrupt switch to market based governance styles and much influential advocacy to reduce the state role in health in order to enforce overall compression of public expenditure and reduce fiscal deficits. People have therefore been forced to switch between weak and efficient public services and expensive private provision or at the limit forego care entirely except in life threatening situations, in such cases sliding into indebtedness. Health status of any population is not only the record of mortality and its morbidity profile but also a record of its resilience based on mutual solidarity and indigenous traditions of self-care – assets normally invisible to the planner and the professional. Such resilience can be enriched with the State retaining a strategic directional role for the good health of all its citizens in accordance with the constitutional mandate. Within such a framework alone can the private sector be engaged as an additional instrument or a partner for achieving shared public health outcomes. Similarly, in indigenous health systems must be promoted to the extent possible to become another

credible delivery mechanism in which people have faith and away fond for the vat number of less than folly qualified doctor in rural areas to get skills upgraded. Public programs in rural and poor urban areas engaging indigenous practitioners and community volunteers can prevent much seasonal and communicable disease using low cost traditional knowledge and based on the balance between food, exercise medicine and moderate living. Such an overall vision of the public role of the heterogenous private sector must inform the course of future of state led health care in the country.

Quality of Healthcare Services in Rural India:¹²²

The role of government in ensuring that its country's healthcare system provides optimal services for its population has been greatly emphasized upon (The World Health Report, 2000). Improvement in the quality of primary healthcare services apart from increasing accessibility and affordability has become a matter of grave concern for the developing nations in the recent years. However, the meaning of quality in healthcare system has been interpreted differently by different researchers. Ovretveit (1992) identified three "stakeholder" components of quality: client, professional, and managerial. From the client's viewpoint, it is the meeting of the patient's unique need and want (Atkins, Marshall and Javalgi, 1996)¹²³ at the lowest cost (Ovretveit, 1992)¹²⁴, provided with courtesy and on time (Brown et al., 1998) while professional quality involves carrying out of techniques and procedures essential to meet the client's requirement and managerial quality entails optimum and efficient utilization of resources to achieve the objectives defined by higher authorities. According to the Institute of Medicine (2001), quality in healthcare is, "the degree to which health services for individuals and populations increase the likelihood of desired health outcomes and are consistent with current professional knowledge." Meeting the objectives of both physicians and patients has been equated with the concept of quality in healthcare by some researchers (Morgan and Murgatroyd, 1994)¹²⁵ while others have focused on user perception, technical standards, and provision of care (Boller et al., 2003; Hulton, Mathews and Stones, 2000)¹²⁶. Quality of care comprises structure, process, and health outcomes (Peabody et al., 1999)¹²⁷; and there are eight dimensions of healthcare service delivery: effectiveness, efficiency, technical competence, interpersonal relations, access to service, safety, continuity, and physical aspects of healthcare (Brown et al, 1998)¹²⁸. The concept of quality is multifaceted connoting different meanings to different stakeholders such as government, service provider, hospital administration, and patients.

Indian Healthcare Sector

With the Indian population adding over 450 million people over the last 25 years, with hanging demographics and socio-economic mix, and with the economy growing at above 7%, there have been significant changes in the healthcare requirements of the country. The Indian healthcare sector has grown at a nearly 16.5 percent CAGR since 2008 to become a \$110 billion industry in 2016 and is expected

to touch \$280 billion by 2020. Over the years, Indian Healthcare scenario has shown great progress on several health indicators like life expectancy and maternal and child mortality. The year 2014 marked a remarkable moment in the Indian Public Healthcare system with the World Health Organization (WHO) declaring India a polio-free nation. India was only the fourth such region in the world after the Americas (1994), the Western Pacific Region (2000) and the European Region (2002). The Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) has significantly come down from 57 deaths per thousand live births in 2004 to 34 deaths in 2016. Life expectancy at birth during the same period increased from 63.80 years to 68.35 years. The significant progress made by the healthcare system in India is attributed to the combined efforts of the public and the private sector.

Despite the rosy picture painted by these numbers, the current healthcare system in India faces major challenges owing to several social, economic and political factors. Broadly speaking, the healthcare system faces the triple challenge of raising service quality and providing equitable access while addressing and tackling the changing disease incidence profiles.

Health Infrastructure

Infrastructure is another pain point in the Indian healthcare sector. The country faces severe resource shortage on both capital invested and manpower. India faces an acute shortage of hospital beds with a ratio 0.5 per 1000 population for India as compared to 2.3 for China, 2.6 for Brazil and 3.2 for the US (Sinha, 2011)¹²⁹. Huge regional variations exist with some of the more prosperous states with excess capacity while others with a huge shortage. This ratio is much lower than the requirement of 1 bed per 1000 population as defined for the low-income countries by WHO. Providing for quality healthcare services is highly capital intensive where the cost of building a secondary care and a tertiary care hospital could be as high as 25 lakhs and 40 lakhs per installed bed, respectively. This means that in order to meet the WHO standards of 1 bed per 1000 population would require an investment of INR 1,62,500 crores.

Remedying Indian Healthcare:

Healthcare should not be restricted merely to medical care but cover aspects of pro-preventive care as well. Primary health care needs to be recognized as a public good which is non-excludable and non-rival consumption. Hence, its supply and demand cannot be left to be regulated by the invisible hand of the market. Elements of health like sanitation, vaccination, health education and primary healthcare have large positive and negative externalities and hence need public funding to be provided at socially optimal levels. Lately, a lot of public funding has been directed to improve our secondary and tertiary care systems that mostly provide private benefits. While there is a need to work at all the three levels of primary, secondary and tertiary healthcare, the main focus of the government today should be on improving the primary healthcare as a public good.

Information Management Systems:

Another major problem plaguing the Indian healthcare system is the lack of information that is available about the patient's history. Take for instance a migrant worker who moves from Bihar to Delhi for work. He falls ill and consults a doctor in Delhi, gets the required treatment and moves to Mumbai in search for better work. There he falls ill again and consults another doctor but unfortunately, the doctor knows no medical history of the patient as there are no medical records other than what the patient can himself explain to the doctor of his past treatments based on his limited medical knowledge. Such is the case with more than 80 percent of our population.

Another important issue in the healthcare system is the information asymmetry between the patients and the doctors. While doctors know a lot about the condition of the patient, the patients have very little knowledge about their own medical condition or the quality of healthcare that they get from a doctor.

This kind of information management problem can be tackled through a two-pronged approach- one, maintenance of electronic medical records and two, information sharing through internet and other media about the quality of healthcare that one can get from a doctor. With the ever-growing use of smartphones and increasing internet penetration in the country, this could be a very effective solution going forward. The medical records of a person can be linked to his Aadhaar number and can be accessed by any doctor through this. The government needs to maintain single standard for Electronic Medical Records which can be accessed from any part of the country. The government should also support consumer's search for good healthcare by providing access to information about the various healthcare centers and the available services. They can also share the reviews of previous consumers in order to give an idea about the quality of healthcare services that can be availed from any center. It can supplement the efforts of the already existing websites, like Practo, that help the consumers locate doctors round them, through its regulatory framework. The internet can be used as a very powerful tool to remove the problem of information asymmetry between the patients and doctors in India.¹³⁰

Primary Health Care in India: Coverage and Quality Issues:

Health is an important dimension of well-being. While a country's per capita income is one indicator of how well it is doing, health and educational outcomes are equally, if not more important indicators of a country's level of development. In the last two decades, India has grown at an average rate of five percent. Literacy rates have also been steadily climbing. Overall literacy rate was 65.3 percent in 2001, and the absolute number of illiterates actually fell for the first time historically by 32 million (Census of India, 2001). Health wise, however, the picture for India is bleak. Even though life expectancy has risen for both males and females and overall life expectancy at birth in India is now 63.3 years, in general, health outcomes are far from satisfactory. There are very high levels of premature mortality and widespread

morbidity in the population, especially in the younger age-groups, among women and among the aged. Millions of children die due to infectious diseases and childhood illnesses and pregnancy and child birth related complications take a toll on many women. In 2000, the infant mortality rate was 68 per 1000 live births and under-five mortality was 96 per 1000 live births. The Indian maternal mortality rate of 407 per 100,000 live births was one of the highest in the world, higher even than many sub-Saharan African countries. Another bitter statistic is the lopsided sex-ratio of 927 females per 1000 males, largely due to discrimination against girls and women in nutrition and medical care. Malaria and Tuberculosis claim more than 500,000 lives every year. Added to this is the specter of AIDS: there are an estimated 4 million HIV positive cases in India and their numbers are expected to grow rapidly.

Primary Health Care: Coverage and Quality:

On the 12th of September, 1978, the International Conference on Primary Health Care being held in Alma-Ata, in the erstwhile USSR, adopted the 'Declaration of Alma-Ata' which proclaimed a positive view of health as complete physical, mental and social wellbeing and a fundamental human right. The declaration envisaged primary health care as the first level of contact between individuals and families with their country's health system. According to this declaration, primary health care was to have its basis in the community it served; the notion of primary health care included maternal and child care including family planning, immunization against major infectious diseases, prevention and control of locally endemic diseases, appropriate treatment of common diseases and injuries, provision of essential drugs, education concerning prevailing health problems and ways to deal with them, provision of adequate food and nutrition and adequate supply of clean water. The Declaration of Alma-Ata set a goal for the year 2000 for all the people of the world to achieve a level of health such as to enable them to lead socially and economically productive lives. India, along with other countries, ratified the declaration.

Quality of health care services provided can be assessed along the following dimensions (which are by no means exhaustive): (1) an adequately equipped and easily accessible public health facility, (2) appropriate and timely clinical care and (3) patient satisfaction with health care received and the outcome of treatment. Ultimately, the real test of the quality of health care services is how they affect health outcomes, especially of the poor. Below we describe some aspects of the quality of publicly provided primary health care services in India.

Health care provision requires specialized skill and training on the part of medical personnel. This leads to asymmetry of information between the provider and patient and therefore, a medical transaction is fraught with moral hazard. Medical practitioners need to keep up with the latest developments in medicine and also need to respect the right of the patient to informed consent in the treatment prescribed. One of the major lacunae in India's health system is lack of quality control. There is little public enforcement to ensure appropriate standards of care in clinical practices. This

is as true of the public sector as of the private sector which is largely unregulated. The Medical Council of India, the main body overseeing standards of care, has no process in place whereby doctors are assessed as to their competence with respect to current standards of care when they renew their registration. Given the lack of effective monitoring, there is little information to go by in terms of competence of medical personnel and actual practice in clinical settings, though there is some evidence of overuse of antibiotics and tranquilizers in public health care centers.¹³¹

One of the striking features of India's health care sector is the range of quality in available services. India is home to global leaders in innovation in and quality of health care such as the Narayana Hospitals, known for providing high-quality cardiovascular surgery at low cost, and the Aravind Eye Care System, whose hospitals provide a high volume of cataract surgery, as well as globally renowned medical teaching institutions such as the All India Institute of Medical Sciences, in New Delhi. Simultaneously, many Indians—especially the poor—receive unacceptably low-quality primary and hospital care. The rapidly growing burden of chronic diseases in India makes the low quality of care highly salient for health policy. The challenge of low quality in health care is not unique to India. Studies from a range of developed and developing countries have demonstrated widespread problems with providers who make little effort to ensure that patients receive high-quality care, geographic variations in the quality of health care services, and high levels of medical errors.

Measurement of Quality:¹³²

Efforts to improve the quality of health care in India and attempts to evaluate the impact of these efforts invariably face challenges because of the lack of reliable administrative data. Of the three categories of Avedis Donabedian's measures of the quality of health care (structure, process, and outcomes), structural measures have traditionally received the most attention in the form of government surveys of health facilities and record keeping to track the availability of resources such as numbers of hospital beds and personnel and quantities of supplies. Whether these resources can be used productively in delivering high-quality care to patients depends on the process aspects of care, including the capacity of health-sector workers. Measuring the quality of the process of delivering health care and the resulting health outcomes is especially challenging, requiring methods and approaches that go beyond standard service statistics and facility surveys.

Strategies to Improve Quality:

A unique aspect of India's health care sector is the limited availability of formally trained health care providers—those with at least a bachelor of medicine and bachelor of surgery (MBBS) degree, the equivalent of an MD in the United States—in rural areas, which is partly due to the challenges of recruiting and retaining qualified staff in the public sector in such areas. As a result, most health care in rural areas of India, where 75 percent of the country's population lives, is delivered by providers who do not have formal medical training. Perhaps even more concerning is the fact

that empirical studies have found that providers in such rural areas in India with formal medical training do not provide significantly higher-quality care compared to informal providers—which suggests that increasing the supply of formally trained providers alone might not solve the problem.

Moving Forward On Improving Health Care Quality:

This cluster of Health Affairs articles examines issues central to the quality of health care in India against a background of significant ongoing reforms that create new opportunities for states to change their allocations of resources to the health sector. Given the measurement and data challenges that these articles address, it is important to note that even with improved data to clarify the problems and challenges in providing high-quality health care, the ability of national and state governments to take appropriate action to improve the quality of care is related to overall governance and accountability. In India's federalist structure, health is a matter of state jurisdiction. Although the central government has traditionally tried to influence health sector priorities through policies and vertical programs, states are ultimately responsible for how their respective health systems function. A significant recent financial development in India was the fiscal federalism reform in 2015 that was part of the Fourteenth Finance Commission's effort to give states more control of spending. India's central government decided to increase the share of total tax revenue to be returned to individual states from 32 percent to 42 percent—an annual increase of approximately \$16 billion that states will have full autonomy in deciding how to allocate.¹³³

Healthcare System, Quality Improvement and Patient Safety in Australia:

Healthcare accreditation involves performance assessment against an industry agreed set of standards. it is “an internationally recognised evaluation process used to assess and improve the quality, efficiency, and effectiveness of healthcare organisations; it is also a way to publicly recognise that a healthcare organization has met national quality standards¹³⁴. The Australian Council on Healthcare standards (ACHs) is an independent, not-for-profit organisation that has been at the forefront of healthcare accreditation in Australia since 1974. Its member organisations reflect the changing structure and diversity of the Australian healthcare system, and include acute services in both the public and private sectors, day procedure services, community health organisations, non-government drug and alcohol services and peak bodies. One of the major and continuing aims of ACHs is to adapt to a changing healthcare environment, in order to continue to offer the most relevant accreditation products and services to its member organisations. To 31 December 2012, ACHs' accreditation services were centred predominantly upon the company's evaluation and Quality improvement Program (eQuiP). on 1 January 2013, ACHs implemented eQuiP national, an accreditation program that encompasses the Australian Commission on safety and Quality in Health Care's (ACsQHC's) mandatory National Safety and Quality Health Service (NSQHS) Standards, while maintaining the organisation-wide accreditation perspective that was the basis of eQuiP. Every two

years, ACHs publishes the National Report on Health Services Accreditation Performance (National Accreditation Report). This 5th edition describes the combined accreditation performance of ACHs member organisations under eQuiP 4, and following the implementation of the revised eQuiP5 program on 1 July 2011. Viewing the ACHs data in this way provides an overview of Australian healthcare organisations, together with their collective strengths and opportunities for improvement.

Overview of ACHS accreditation programs and activities:

The ACHs offers a variety of programs to meet the specific needs of its member organisations. National Safety and Quality Health Service (NSQHS) Standards ACHs is an approved accrediting agency for the NSQHS Standards, mandatory for hospitals, day procedure services and public dental services from 1 January 2013, and for the interim accreditation of new organisations which will ultimately require full accreditation against the NSQHS Standards.

EQuIPNational

The ACHs eQuiP national accreditation program adds to the ten NSQHS Standards a further five standards derived from the eQuiP program, which focus on the performance of non-clinical systems as part of a comprehensive, organisation-wide assessment for hospitals and public dental services.

EQuIPNational Day Procedure Centres

in addition to the ten NSQHS Standards, this program provides a further five eQuiP-derived standards which have been tailored to the needs of day procedure centres while offering an organisation-wide perspective.

Medicare Locals Accreditation

ACHs is an approved accrediting agency for the Medicare Locals Accreditation Standards, implemented from 1 June 2013 for all Medicare Locals.

EQuIPNational Corporate Health Services

An accreditation program intended to align corporate offices with health services accredited under EQuIPNational. the program retains the relevant actions from the ten NSQHS Standards and the five eQuiPderived standards of EQuIPNational, and provides guidelines to assist with the interpretation of those actions by the corporate office.

ACHS accreditation programs:

The ACHs eQuiP accreditation programs are designed to guide healthcare organisations to identify and prioritise their opportunities for improvement. Accreditation is also a form of external recognition for high-performing healthcare organisations and the people who work within them, and provides an opportunity for organisations and their staff to demonstrate what they do well.

EQuIP5 accreditation outcomes

In the five-tier eQuIP accreditation system, a Little Achievement (LA) rating indicates that organisations are aware of the requirements (jurisdictional, legislative and otherwise) for a particular area of operations, while a some Achievement (sA) rating indicates that appropriate systems and processes have been implemented. To achieve a Marked Achievement (MA) rating, organisations must be able to demonstrate that they evaluate the effectiveness of their systems and processes and that, based upon this evaluation, they make improvements as required. organisations demonstrating that they have progressed beyond the internal evaluation of their systems into research, external benchmarking, advanced management strategies or leadership may be awarded an extensive (eA) or outstanding (oA) Achievement rating. On survey under eQuIP5, organisations are assessed against 47 different criteria that consider aspects of both their clinical and non-clinical operation. There are 15 mandatory criteria under eQuIP5. To be accredited, organisations are required to receive an MA rating at survey in all mandatory criteria. Performance against the mandatory criteria is assessed at both organisation-wide survey (ows) and Periodic review (Pr), while non-mandatory criteria are assessed at ows only. the survey data analysed for this report are from 341 surveys conducted between 1 July 2011 – 31 december 2012, with accreditation status finalised by 24 May 2013. of the organisations surveyed, 178 (52%) were in the public sector, and 163 (48%) were in the private sector. The type of survey conducted was determined by each member organisation's stage in the four-year eQuIP cycle: 148 surveys (43%) were owss and 193 (57%) were Prs.

ACHs is involved in collaborative research examining the impact of healthcare accreditation. it is one of the partners in the Accreditation Collaborative for the Conduct of research, evaluation and designated investigations through teamwork (ACCredit) Project, along with the Centre for Clinical governance research and the Centre for Health systems and safety research, in the Australian institute of Health innovation at the University of new south wales. other project partners are the Australian general Practice Accreditation Limited; the Aged Care and standards Accreditation Agency; the Australian Commission on safety and Quality in Health Care; and the new south wales Clinical excellence Commission. The collaboration is implementing a study comprising four aims, summarised as: (i) evaluate current accreditation processes; (ii) analyse the costs and benefits of accreditation; (iii) improve future accreditation via evidence; and (iv) develop and apply new standards of consumer involvement in accreditation. the four aims are being addressed in 12 interrelated studies funded by a Linkage grant (LP100200586) from the Australian research Council.¹³⁵

The Australian healthcare system is recognised as one of the best in the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD); however, it has come under intense pressure due to changes in healthcare needs, such as the increase in demand and healthcare costs, inequities, complex health conditions and a push to

improve the outcomes. The Australian healthcare system not only faces inefficiencies and workforce shortages, there is an expectation of greater public reporting of the availability of needed services, as well as clinical indicators and patient-reported outcomes, to ensure informed decision-making by patients and their carers¹³⁶. In addition, the healthcare sector in Australia should be prepared to deal with the changing needs of patients and technological advancements. Policymakers are advised to address care coordination, patients' needs, patients' engagement in healthcare delivery and the redesign of funding mechanisms¹³⁷.

Organisation of public healthcare in Australia:

There are three healthcare system models in the world, namely, the welfare state model, the market model and a mix of the welfare state and market models – the hybrid model. In a welfare state model, healthcare is funded by tax dollars, and the government assumes full responsibility for the provision of healthcare services. In a market model, the choice and payment of healthcare services are left to the individual citizens and private institutions. In a hybrid model, the government provides public insurance for basic coverage, and individuals can buy private insurance for healthcare coverage on the top of any public insurance they have. The Australian healthcare system is a hybrid model under which citizens, permanent residents and refugees can buy private insurance coverage in addition to the public insurance they already have and gain access to both private and public hospitals¹³⁸. The provision of healthcare services by the government requires some gate-keeping – the administration and approval of healthcare services – in some cases. Australia, Belgium, Canada and France have similar healthcare systems because they provide public insurance for the basic coverage, and private insurance can be purchased by individuals on top of the public insurance¹³⁹. Australia had the lowest public health expenditure, as a percentage of the total health expenditure, during the period 2010–2014 of these four countries with similar health systems.

Australian healthcare system – key issues and problems

In this section, the key issues and problems of the Australian public hospitals are discussed. Australia is a member of the OECD, and it follows the international standards for quality and performance measurement¹⁴⁰. In its peer group – with other two countries Canada and France – Australia spends the lowest amount of money on healthcare as a percentage (9.4%) of its gross domestic product (GDP) while its annual growth rate of healthcare spending (2.42%) was the highest during the period 2009–2013. Australia has the highest number of practicing physicians (3.39) per 1000 people; however, the average annual number of physician visits (7.1) is lower than Canada (7.7). In terms of hospital spending, utilization and capacity, Australia tops the list in its peer group. Australia has the highest number of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) machines (13.4) per million people but has the lowest MRI exams (27.6) per 1000 people. MRI exams per 1000 people of the OECD28 countries were 51.7.15 The data for the OECD countries (Japan, Korea, Norway, Italy, Switzerland, the Netherlands, Sweden, Austria, Belgium, Denmark, France, Portugal, Israel,

Poland, Spain, Estonia, Czech Republic, Iceland, Luxembourg, Germany, Finland, the United Kingdom, Chile, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, Mexico and the United States) indicated that 14.5% of their populations, aged 15 years or older, were obese in 2000, and this increased to 18.4% in 2013. The obesity rate in Australia for the same group of the population increased from 19.8% in 1995 to 28.3% in 2011.¹⁵ Hip replacement surgeries per 100,000 people were 170.6, 161.2, 135.6 and 235.5 for Australia, the average of the OECD33 (Switzerland, Germany, Austria, Belgium, Norway, Finland, Sweden, France, Denmark, the Netherlands, Luxembourg, the United States, Iceland, the United Kingdom, Australia, Czech Republic, Italy, Slovenia, Greece, New Zealand, Hungary, Canada, Ireland, Estonia, Spain, Slovak Republic, Portugal, Poland, Israel, Turkey, Chile, Korea and Mexico), Canada and France, respectively. Knee replacement surgeries per 100,000 people were 180.4, 120.6, 165.8 and 145.4 for Australia, the average of the OECD30 (the United States, Austria, Finland, Germany, Belgium, Australia, Switzerland, Luxembourg, Denmark, Canada, France, the United Kingdom, Sweden, Iceland, the Netherlands, Czech Republic, Korea, Spain, Slovenia, Italy, New Zealand, Norway, Turkey, Portugal, Hungary, Israel, Ireland, Poland, Chile and Mexico), Canada and France, respectively¹⁴¹.

Appropriateness of healthcare delivery

A widely disseminated study, called the CareTrack study, was conducted in Australia by Runciman et al., to determine the appropriateness of healthcare delivery as a result of patients' encounters with healthcare professionals, including GPs, specialists and physiotherapists. Some of the health conditions chosen for the CareTrack study were taken from a seminal study in the United States by McGlynn et al.¹⁴². The CareTrack study revealed that significant improvements were needed to deliver appropriate healthcare in Australia.¹⁴³

Australia has an institutionally set publicly funded health system (i.e. Medicare) that is underpinned by a 'universal access' principle. This entitles Australian residents to subsidized treatment from health care professionals (i.e. doctors, medical specialists, etc.) and access to free treatment in publicly funded hospitals. Interestingly, Australians have a choice to access private health insurance (which covers private hospitals, dental, specialists, etc.); however, the cost of this is predominantly borne by the insured making payment to a few private health providers. Australia's health system is complex in structure; in particular, its funding and responsibilities is shared between federal, state and territory governments. This fragmented funding model and informational asymmetry between patients and health service providers has made coordinating patient care difficult. Australia's publicly funded Medicare system ranks well internationally (e.g. high life expectancy, low infant mortality rates, etc.)¹⁴⁴. However, Australia, like many industrialised countries, will confront major issues and challenges over the next decade in maintaining and importantly, improving patient health care.¹⁴⁵

The role of government in Australia

Three levels of government are collectively responsible for providing universal health care: federal; state and territory; and local. The federal government mainly provides funding and indirect support to the states and health professions, subsidizing primary care providers through the Medicare Benefits Scheme (MBS) and the Pharmaceutical Benefits Scheme (PBS) and providing funds for state services. It has only a limited role in direct service delivery.

States have the majority of responsibility for public hospitals, ambulance services, public dental care, community health services, and mental health care. They contribute their own funding in addition to that provided by federal government. Local governments play a role in the delivery of community health and preventive health programs, such as immunization and the regulation of food standards¹⁴⁶.

Hospitals in Australia:

In 2014–2015, there were 698 public hospitals (678 acute, 20 psychiatric), with a total of nearly 60,300 beds, an increase of 1,700 beds over the previous year, despite there being 20 fewer hospitals. In the same period, there were 624 private hospitals (342 day hospitals and 282 others) with 32,000 beds¹⁴⁷. Private hospitals are a mix of for-profit and nonprofit.

Public hospitals receive a majority of funding (91%) from the federal government and state governments, with the remainder coming from private patients and their insurers. Most of the funding (62% of the total recurrent expenditure) is for public-physician salaries. Private physicians providing public services are paid on a per-session or fee-for-service basis. Private hospitals receive most of their funding from insurers (47%), federal government's rebate on health insurance premiums (21%), and private patients (12%)¹⁴⁸.

Public hospitals are organized into Local Hospital Networks (LHNs), of which there were 147 in 2016. These vary in size, depending on the population they serve and the extent to which linking services and specialties on a regional basis is beneficial. In major urban areas, a number of LHNs comprise just one hospital.

State governments fund their public hospitals largely on an activity basis, using diagnosis-related groups. Federal funding for public hospitals includes a base level of funding, with funding for growth set at 45 percent of the "efficient price of services," determined by the Independent Hospital Pricing Authority. From July 2017, the Commonwealth will fund 45 percent of the efficient growth in these services, capped at 6.5 percent of total growth¹⁴⁹. States are required to cover the remaining cost of services, providing an incentive to keep costs at the efficient price or lower. Small rural hospitals are funded through block grants¹⁵⁰.

Mental health care in Australia:

Mental health services are provided in many ways, including by GPs and specialists, in community-based care, in hospitals (both in- and outpatient, public and private), and in residential care. GPs provide general care and may devise treatment plans of their own or refer patients to specialists. Specialist care and pharmaceuticals are subsidized through the MBS and PBS.

State governments fund and deliver acute mental health and psychiatric care in hospitals, community-based services, and specialized residential care. Public hospital-based care is free to public patients¹⁵¹.

As part of the federal government's response to a recent review by the National Mental Health Commission, funding through Primary Health Networks will be redirected to commission mental health services that meet local needs. The focus will be on suicide prevention and coordinated care¹⁵².

Long-term care and social supports in Australia:

The majority of people living in their own homes with severe or profound limitations in core activities receive informal care (92%). Thirty-eight percent receive only informal assistance, and 54 percent receive a combination of informal and formal assistance. In 2009, 12 percent of Australians were informal caregivers, and around 30 percent of those were the primary caregiver (carer). In 2011–2012, federal government provided AUD3.18 billion (USD2.07 billion) under the income-tested Carer Payment program, and AUD1.75 billion (USD1.14 billion) through the Carer Allowance (not income-tested and offered as a supplement for daily care). Federal government also provides an annual Carer Supplement of AUD480 million (USD312 million) to help with the cost of caring. Recipients of the Carer Allowance who care for a child under the age of 16 receive an annual Child Disability Assistance Payment of AUD1,000 (USD649). There are also a number of respite programs providing further support for caregivers¹⁵³. Regulatory oversight is provided by a number of agencies, such as the Therapeutic Goods Administration, which oversees supply, imports, exports, manufacturing, and advertisement; the Australian Health Practitioner Regulation Agency, which ensures registration and accreditation of the workforce in partnership with National Boards; and the Australian Prudential Regulation Authority, for private health insurance. The Australian Competition and Consumer Commission promotes competition among private health insurers. Beginning in July 2016, the Australian eHealth Commission will take over responsibility from the National eHealth Transition Authority for matters relating to electronic health data.¹⁵⁴

Healthcare System, Quality Improvement and Patient Safety in Denmark:

In 2016, Denmark abolished mandatory hospital accreditation and replaced it with a National Quality Programme. The overall aim of the program is to build a nationwide improvement culture and to focus the improvement work on the results

and experience of health Care for the patients. Denmark is facing the same challenges as the rest of Europe: An aging population, a dramatic increase in chronic diseases, and a rise in health expenditure. The Quality Programme is there for only a part of a wider vision and work to-wards a systems change in Danish Health Care: Population health management, value based health care, Big Data, Personalized Medicine and a political obligation to not only deliver health care services but Health to all citizens. The Hope Study Tour will provide the participant with an understanding of the current work and visions for changes in Denmark, and the possibility to discuss the developments with peers. We will focus on experts exchanging knowledge and experiences in this particular field. Through the introduction to national programs, challenges and field studies, we expect the participants to share their own experiences in order to make it a lively and fruitful study tour.¹⁵⁵

The Danish health system can be characterized as fairly decentralized, because responsibility for primary and secondary health care lies with the regions and municipalities. The Danish health system moved to its decentralized form in the 1970s and 1980s. However, recent reforms have recentralized the system in some respects as the state now has a higher regulatory and governing role than earlier. At the state level, the Ministry of Health has a governing role over regional and municipal organization and management of health care, as well as the supervision and partial financing of the municipalities and regions. In the field of health care, the Ministry is in charge of the administrative functions that are related to the organization of hospitals, community psychiatry and self-employed health professionals with agreements with the region, as well as the market authorization of pharmaceuticals and supervision of the pharmacy sector. Prevention and health promotion are also part of the Ministry's remit. The regions own and run hospitals and partly or fully finance private practitioners such as GPs, specialists, chiropractors and physiotherapists, based on transfers from the state and municipalities. They also provide reimbursement for pharmaceutical care. At the local level, the municipalities are responsible for disease prevention, health promotion and rehabilitation outside hospitals, as well as other areas of health care such as health visitors, school health services, home care and nursing homes.

A number of public registers exist within the health care field concerning the population's use of health care benefits, disease incidence and prevalence, causes of death, and so on (Thygesen & Ersbøll, 2011)¹⁵⁶. The registers are mainly compiled for administrative purposes and the information regarding individuals is used for treatment and statistical research purposes. More specifically, the data can be used for the management of health expenses or the planning of activities within the health system. The registers and their data are furthermore very important for both epidemiological studies and health services research in Denmark.

In the most commonly used registers, individuals are labelled according to a personal identification number (in the Central National Register (Centrale Person

Register), the Danish Civil Registration System) and the Register contains information on the individuals, including their family relations, education and income status (Vallgård & Krasnik, 2008)¹⁵⁷. This provides researchers with the opportunity to collect and combine information at an individual level from different registers for the analysis of statistical associations (Knudsen & Hansen, 2008). Such coupling of registers is under strict regulation, because of data sensitivity.

Danish health legislation (the Health Act of 2005) formally provides the right to easy and equal access to health care for all citizens in Denmark; the right to choice of health provider; and the patient's right to information and self-determination. Stated objectives also include general ones regarding high quality of care, continuity of care (coherent and linked services) and transparency of the health system.

Legislation regarding access and free choice ensures that patients are entitled to choose to be treated at any hospital in the country. This has been a right since 1993, as an effect of changes in the health legislation, but the effect has been moderate and slow as most patients still seem to be in favour of treatment in a place close to their residence. The process regarding choice of other hospitals, however, has been accelerated by the policies regarding waiting time guarantees, which provide the right to treatment within one month after referral, the region having to pay the costs at a private hospital or clinic if their public hospitals are not able to meet this time limit. In 2006, 87% of patients admitted to hospital for planned procedures were actually aware of their right to choose, and in 2009, around 10% of planned operations took place according to the waiting time guarantee (Ministry of Interior and Health, 2010b)¹⁵⁸.

The issue of easy access is also related to user fees, geographical availability and communication. Implementing new user fees is publicly debated but is still not officially seen as an option regarding access to GP and specialist care for the general population. In spite of the stated objectives of easy access for everyone, the former government implemented a new fee for using interpreters for immigrant patients with more than seven years of stay in Denmark.

Ensuring availability of health care in all parts of Denmark is increasingly seen as an issue. In primary health care, GP shortage in some areas, and the latest contract between the Regions Board for Wages and Tariffs and the GPs, has created an opportunity for regions to set up their own clinics with publicly employed GPs in outlying areas, but also allows GPs to establish branch facilities staffed with employed physicians. Quality of care is a continuous issue, and a series of initiatives has taken place, including the monitoring of quality in the DDKM, the introduction of the national accreditation system of hospitals and the launching of the Danish National Indicator Project (*Nationale Indikator Projekt*). This will be integrated as an element of the DDKM alongside annual surveys on patient-experienced quality, thus creating a better basis for assessment and quality improvement.

Quality of care in Denmark

The quality of preventive care can be indicated by looking at the rates of vaccination among children and older people. Denmark has a national children's vaccination programme (see section 1.4.3) that covers vaccinations against diphtheria, tetanus, pertussis, polio, Hib infection, pneumococcal disease, MMR and diseases caused by the human papilloma virus. In 2008, 89% of Danish children were vaccinated against measles; this is a smaller figure than the OECD average or the EU15 average. The rate of influenza vaccinations among older people (above the age of 65) is also below OECD and EU15 averages, at 53.7% in 2006 (National Board of Health, 2010a)¹⁵⁹. The vaccination for diphtheria, tetanus and pertussis is given as part of a vaccination package that also includes vaccination against polio and Hib. The vaccination rate for this particular vaccination is around 90% (National Serum Institute, 2010)¹⁶⁰ and has not changed substantially during recent decades.

The quality of care for chronic conditions can be examined by looking at avoidable hospital admission rates for asthma, COPD, congestive heart failure, hypertension and diabetes-related complications, as these admissions potentially could have been avoided by timely access to primary or ambulatory care. These rates have been gathered as part of the OECD HCQI project, with all data referring to people aged 15 years and older. According to data from this project, the admission rate for asthma was 43 per 100 000 in 2007. This is lower than the OECD average of 54.6 but is still significantly higher than the rate in Sweden of only 24.6. The hospital admission rate for COPD was 319.5 per 100 000 in 2007. This is markedly higher than most of the countries included in the OECD HCQI project. The average is 201.4 and in France, for example, it was just 79.1. These gaps might not be caused just by health care differences but can also reflect differences in the incidence of COPD. The other Nordic countries also have admission rates below the level of Denmark. For congestive heart failure, however, Denmark has an admission rate well below the average: in Denmark, it is 165.3 per 100 000, compared with an average rate of 229.7 in the OECD HCQI. The admission rate is also smaller than those in the other Nordic countries. For hypertension, the admission rates documented in the OECD HCQI project vary widely, from 11.2 to 412.7 per 100 000. The admission rate for Denmark is 85, which is higher than both Sweden (61.4) and Norway (69.9). The admission rate for diabetes-related complications can be divided into rates for lower extremities amputation and for diabetes acute complications. The diabetes lower extremities amputation rate for Denmark was 20.9 per 100 000 in 2007. This is amongst the highest rates in Europe. The rate for admissions for acute complications from diabetes was 20.11 in 2007, which is slightly higher than the average in the OECD HCQI project. All in all, Denmark's avoidable admission rates are for the most part lagging behind when compared with the other Nordic countries and in some instances also when compared with OECD HCQI averages (OECD, 2009).

Quality of care for acute exacerbations of chronic conditions, as expressed in in-hospital mortality rates (deaths within 30 days of admission) following acute

myocardial infarction, haemorrhagic stroke and ischaemic stroke, are outcome measures for the quality of acute care. The in-hospital mortality rate for acute myocardial infarction was 2.9% in 2007. This was similar to Sweden and lower than the EU15 average, as well as lower than all the other OECD countries apart from Iceland. The in-hospital mortality rate for haemorrhagic stroke was 16.7% in Denmark in 2007. This rate lies below the EU15 and OECD averages but is higher than the rates in the other Nordic countries. The in-hospital mortality rate for ischaemic stroke was 3.1% in Denmark in 2007. This is lower than in all the other Nordic countries and the EU15 and OECD averages, which are both 5%. The in-hospital mortality rates for the diseases in question are, therefore, generally relatively good compared with EU and OECD averages (National Board of Health, 2010a).

Quality is monitored by national measures of patient satisfaction and various national and regional initiatives to develop standards, clinical guidelines and clinical databases. All hospitals have been included in the general Danish model for quality assurance since 2007, and external accreditation takes place at regular intervals. A national system for reporting inadvertent events has also been established. HTA has become an integrated part of the system, along with other types of evaluation at local or regional level. Evaluations may be performed by local or regional initiatives in addition to the nationally mandated quality assurance programme. Patient rights have been extended and formalized during recent years. These rights are generally respected and there are mechanisms in place for sanctioning professional misconduct and abuse.¹⁶¹

A comprehensive standards-based programme for assessing quality is currently being implemented. The programme is systemic in scope, aiming to incorporate all health care delivery organisations and including both organisational and clinical standards. Organisations are assessed on their ability to improve performance measured against standards for standards processes and outcomes. The core of the assessment programme is a system of regular accreditation based on annual self assessment and external evaluation (every third year) by a professional accreditation body. The self assessment involves reporting of performance against national input, process and outcome standards, which allows comparison over time and between organisations. The external evaluation begins with self assessment and goes on to assess status for quality development.¹⁶²

Quality improvement and patient safety have been important topics on the agenda in the Danish health care system for >20 years. Over the years, Denmark has developed an array of national quality and patient safety initiatives. The Danish health care system is mainly publicly owned, and it is run and organized across three administrative levels: the state, the regions and municipalities¹⁶³. The Danish state is responsible for establishment of political values and goals for public healthcare services nationwide and overall regulatory functions in terms of legislation, the distribution of medical specialties at hospital level, quality monitoring, etc¹⁶⁴. The five

Danish regions are responsible for hospitals and self-employed healthcare professionals in terms of general practitioners (GPs), specialists, dentists, etc. The 98 Danish municipalities are mainly responsible for home nursing, disease prevention and health promotion.

Values in the Danish health care system

The Danish health care system rests upon three basic values. Firstly, it is the responsibility of the society to help the residents with their health problems. It is a fundamental principle in the Danish health care system that all citizens should have free and equal access to healthcare services. Access to health services is therefore largely free of charge for all Danish residents; 86% of health spending was funded by public sources in 2012. Secondly, providing health care should be solved within the public healthcare system. The third value is self-determination for the majority of healthcare services and freedom of choice. By legislation, the Danish residents have the right to treatment at GPs and to choose [after referral] treatment at any hospital in the country, and the Danish residents have improved options to choose GPs.

The basis of quality improvement and patient safety initiatives in Denmark

Denmark has unique opportunities for quality measurement and benchmarking since Denmark has well-developed health registries and unique patient identifier that allow all registries to include patient-level data using the patients' unique patient identifier. Each patient contact with the healthcare system is recorded in administrative and medical registers using the patient's unique, 10-digit civil registration number to ensure monitoring and regulation of the healthcare system (M. Joergensen et al., Unpublished results). In general, digitally stored data open great potential for research, system level and everyday improvement in quality and safety. When shared, communicated and lived out extensively, the processes data are the basis for accountability.

Perspectives on quality improvement in health care in Denmark

OECD has recently evaluated quality improvement in the Danish health care system¹⁶⁵. As part of the conclusion it is stated: 'Denmark is rightly seen as a pioneer in health care quality initiatives among OECD countries. Over many years, it has developed a sophisticated array of quality assurance mechanisms. Denmark has impressive quality monitoring and improvement initiatives. It has extensive databases on processes and outcomes of care and a strong agenda to strengthen its information infrastructure; it can also boast many local clinical guidelines, national guidelines and standards developed as part of disease management programmes and pathways.' This can be regarded as a positive evaluation. Over 20 years, Denmark has been shifting its focus from a governance model that has been based on cost control toward a governance model that is focused on the quality of care and quality management alongside cost control.

Currently, however, quality improvement and quality management are focused on hospital care, which are also emphasized in the OECD review of the Danish health care system¹⁶⁶. To further develop the Danish governance model focusing on quality of care and quality management, it is important to expand the model to the primary care sector by ensuring a transparent all-round quality improvement culture like the one present in the hospital sector with guidelines, disease management programmes and pathway initiatives, implementation of the Danish Health Quality Programme and participation in the clinical registries. To meet the requirements in the 2015–18 National Quality Programme¹⁶⁷, cross-sector patient-reported outcome measures should be utilized along with quality improvement in partnership with patients using real-time data. This later challenges the current model and it will be essential to ensure valid, reliable data to guide development, decision-making, sound evaluation and research.¹⁶⁸

The Danish Health care sector is mainly public and predominantly financed through taxes, with only a few private hospitals. General Practitioners (GPs) and private medical specialists are independent, but nearly all have contracts with their regional administrations to deliver health care services, for fixed fees. Admission to hospital generally is by referral through GPs, who act as gatekeepers, or through emergency departments and acute admission units. Planning for the health care system is strongly regulated by laws and statutes, as for instance, which medical specialties are allowed in which hospitals. In recent years a patient's general right was introduced, which gave a four week maximum waiting time for first appointment at an outpatient clinic, and another maximum of 4 weeks before starting treatment, for all diseases irrespectively of severity. Hospitals and primary health care are managed by 5 regions, and before 2007, by 17 counties. The social care sector is managed by the 98 municipalities. All primary health care and hospital services are free for citizens.

Current situation for Quality Improvement in Denmark

The current situation can be described as a process of maturation of methods and implementation of the above initiatives on a national scale, together with increasing involvement from the national and regional administrations. It is now increasingly recognized that QI has to be an integral part of everyday management in the health care sector. QI has been institutionalised, but is still characterized by a lack of integration between the different initiatives, and by limitations in the fragmented health information technology systems.

Challenges for Quality improvement in the coming years in Denmark

Looking at QI today in Denmark, it still appears somewhat fragmented. Each initiative is governed by its own logic and organisation, and there is little mutual coordination. Patients making transitions between sectors, departments, specialties etc. are currently the main focus, since transitions carry high risks and threats to good quality and patient-safety. To improve the situation the challenge is to find new ways of organising, even within hospitals, to support well defined patient pathways, while

not sacrificing quality for patients who do not fit into these pathways. Growing attention is being given to patient involvement in their own treatment, by building partnerships and mutual expectations. For the increasing number of indicators that are required to be documented, the challenge is to build automatic data-collection from existing health care systems. Standardisation as the primary tool to increase quality and patient safety in all areas is beginning to be challenged. Standardisation has its own risks and limitations, and not all situations can be put in formulas. The challenge emerges in building new ways of working with QI, where standardisation is combined with appropriate flexibility to respond to unforeseen critical situations and raising awareness of these. Finally, one of the biggest challenges under the severest budgetary constraints we have seen for some years, is to ensure QI is an integral part of everyday management, as important as everything else. QI has too much potential and is too important to be left solely to health professionals; it should be a common focus point between them and the management.¹⁶⁹

Healthcare System, Quality Improvement and Patient Safety in South Africa:

The inaugural South African Health Review, published in 1995, noted the appointment of a National Health Legislation Review Committee, tasked with developing a “comprehensive, development-oriented Public Health Act” for South Africa¹⁷⁰. The Department of Health was described as “reluctant to amend legislation on a piecemeal basis”. The chapter also noted the risks attendant on a process of wholesale reform of health legislation: “unless this process is carefully managed and properly co-ordinated, administrative chaos and increased fragmentation of the health system may ensue”. In the spirit of the times, the chapter also emphasised the need for “active community participation in the formulation of legislation”, noting that “not only are undemocratic legislative processes ideologically unacceptable, but they also give rise to legislation that is poorly implemented”. This chapter, taking advantage of the 20th edition of the Review, provides a concise summary of health-related legislative instruments at the national level that have been the subject of change since the last edition was published in 2016. These include primary legislation (in the forms of Bills or Acts of Parliament), secondary legislation (Regulations published by the Minister of Health) and tertiary legislation (Board Notices issued by statutory health councils). However, changes to provincial health legislation or health-related municipal by-laws are beyond the scope of this chapter. Important health-related jurisprudence is also described, as are selected national policies and the processes for their development and implementation. National legislation related to health unlike in 2015, when just one health-related Act was passed (the Medicines and Related Substances Amendment Act 14 of 2015), Parliament did not pass a single health-related law in 2016. Two draft Bills which had previously been published for comment have yet to be tabled (National Health Laboratory Service Amendment Bill4 and National Public Health Institute of South Africa Bill5). A draft Dental Technology Professions Bill has been gazetted for comment by the Dental Technicians Council, but has also not yet been tabled in Parliament¹⁷¹. This is a comprehensive Bill which seeks to repeal the existing South African Dental

Technicians Act (19 of 1979). The Medical Innovation Bill (Private Member's Bill 1 of 20147) remains before Parliament, but appears to be in abeyance while the Medicines Control Council considers how to apply existing provisions to enable access to cannabis for medical purposes¹⁷².

The year 2016 marked critical steps being taken in the implementation of the Office of Health Standards Compliance (OHSC). Final regulations outlining procedures for the functioning of the OHSC and the Health Ombud were issued in November 2016¹⁷³. The first report from the Ombud, relating to the transfer of psychiatric patients from the Life Esidimeni facility in Gauteng (the so-called 'Gauteng Marathon Project'), was issued on 1 February 2017¹⁷⁴. The Ombud found "prima facie evidence, that certain officials and certain NGOs and some activities within the Gauteng Marathon Project violated the Constitution and contravened the National Health Act and the Mental Health Care Act (2002)". He further found that "some executions and implementation of the project have shown a total disregard of the rights of the patients and their families". The responses to the report are ongoing, but have included the resignation of the provincial MEC responsible for Health, the suspension of the Head of Department and other senior officials, and remedial action to ensure the safety of patients who were transferred to inappropriate facilities. An ad hoc tribunal chaired by a retired Judge President has been appointed by the Minister of Health to process appeals lodged against the Health Ombud's report¹⁷⁵. Health Professions Council of South Africa As was noted in the 2016 edition of the Review, the 10-year period allowed for the registration of dental assistants expired in 2015¹⁷⁶.

Despite a court challenge, the need for registration was upheld. In July 2016, the Minister of Health, on the recommendation of the Health Professions Council of South Africa (HPCSA), issued a draft regulation for comment which would provide some flexibility¹⁷⁷. Once issued in final form, dental assistants already in practice will be given four months to apply for registration, and a further two years in which to pass the board examination. A similarly contested scope of practice for psychologists, initially published in 2011¹⁷⁸, was declared invalid by the Cape High Court in November 2016¹⁷⁹. Although the order of invalidity was postponed for 24 months, the professional board concerned and the Council were instructed to consider postponing any disciplinary action for acting outside the prescribed scope until new regulations were promulgated.¹⁸⁰

We live in a world of finite resources. Budgets are constrained within the health system, yet the demand for quality health care is seemingly infinite. In South Africa, healthcare policymakers face difficult choices on a daily basis as they balance optimal patient care against the best value for healthcare spending. Explicit, transparent and evidence-informed approaches to healthcare prioritization can greatly enhance the quality and integrity of our policymakers' decisions¹⁸¹. South Africa has adopted a universal health coverage (UHC) approach to health care in its constitution and recognises the health inequalities present in the country.

This approach was implicit in the 1994 provision of free primary health care nationally and in the 1996 extended healthcare plan for pregnant women and children, but was made explicit in the National Health Insurance (NHI) White Paper in 2015¹⁸². The NHI mechanism aims to achieve UHC by 2025 with the delivery of a platform of comprehensive quality healthcare services to all South Africans (sometimes referred to as the benefits package). However, as noted in the 2016 South African Health Review, the 2015 NHI White Paper does not yet provide details of the package or the methods required to determine the contents of such a package¹⁸³, but proposes the establishment of an NHI Benefits Advisory Committee to do so. Clearly, a fair, evidence-based and trusted approach to determining the criteria for inclusion of services and new technologies within the NHI healthcare platform will be required prior to implementation. International experience has shown that a health technology assessment (HTA) system can aid identification and inform decision making about funding of health services and technologies. This might take into account clinical excellence and cost-effectiveness, practical issues such as affordability and human-resource constraints, and social values such as equity, fairness, and access to health services. As a country moves towards UHC, one of the issues for consideration is governmental recognition of the need to drive, sustain and actively support the HTA process¹⁸⁴.

How is healthcare policy and legislation made in South Africa?

The National Department of Health (NDoH) is responsible for formulation of national health policy. Legislation and regulations that determine policy should be approved by parliament following a period of public participation and comment¹⁸⁵. At provincial level, legislation can be passed that is specific to the provision and functioning of district health councils, and to establish and describe the functions of clinic and community health centre committees¹⁸⁶. Responsibility for development of legislation and policy related to HTA lies with the NDoH. 2011 Human Resources for Health South Africa HRH Strategy for the Health Sector 2012/13–2016/17 The HRH Strategy published in 2011 recommends that a National Coordinating Centre for Clinical Excellence in Health and Health Care be established with functions reflective of HTA. However, the recommendation is not explicit.

Oral health professionals in South Africa

By mid-2017, there were 6 333 dentists, 3 550 dental assistants, 1 226 oral hygienists and 708 dental therapists registered with the HPCSA.

Health facilities in South Africa

There are 4 200 public health facilities in South Africa. The number of people per clinic is 13 718, exceeding WHO guidelines of 10 000 per clinic¹⁸⁷.

In 2007, the South African Human Rights Commission (SAHRC) held public hearings about the nation's healthcare system, noting that 'the right of access to healthcare services is one of the indivisible and interdependent rights entrenched in

Constitution of the Republic of South Africa Act' of 1996¹⁸⁸. In addition to discussing the ways that poverty creates barriers to accessing health services, the report emphasized that health disparities were exacerbated by the divide between the public and private (for-profit) health sectors. Primary healthcare at public clinics in South Africa is tax-funded and free to the user; payment for services at public hospitals is income-based, with the very poor receiving free care¹⁸⁹. However, patients and their families are responsible for transportation to the healthcare facility, including emergency transport, and may also lose income when they have to wait long hours to receive care. Thus, while the user may not have to pay for the direct costs of medical or nursing care, high indirect costs may make accessing health services a financial strain for low income households.

Concerns about health system resources, costs and quality are not unique to South Africa, but South Africa has a special commitment to addressing the racial and ethnic inequalities in access to health that originated under the apartheid system. Apartheid policies (1948–94) limited access to many healthcare facilities based on racial and ethnic classifications as well as income¹⁹⁰. Although free primary healthcare for all (with additional free services for pregnant women and young children) was initiated in 1996, health disparities remain¹⁹¹. Health metrics in the white population are significantly more favourable than statistics from the black African population.¹⁹²

A quality assurance policy for the whole health system - public and private in South Africa

Each year 8% or more of the gross national product (GNP is an indicator of the wealth produced by the country) is spent on the national health system, including both the public and private health sectors. On average 60% of this is spent in the private sector, which provides care to 20% of the population. 80% of the population relies on the public health system for health care. This sector receives 40% of total expenditure on health. Any national policy must therefore include both private and public sector issues, and by so doing contribute towards strengthening the partnership between the public and private sector.

To achieve necessary improvements, a national policy on quality in health care is needed, together with commitment from all stakeholders, beginning with leadership from the highest levels of government, the national health system, labour, and the health care professions.

Health care capacity should be matched to the health needs of the population in South Africa

There is a need to reduce excess capacity, avoid waste and reduce costs, as well as increase capacity in other areas to ensure access for under-served populations, and ensure that the care provided across the health care system is appropriate.

Improved co-ordination of capacity in South Africa

Access to knowledgeable and experienced health professionals is essential to improve access to quality health care. Also, research shows that facilities and practitioners that perform a higher volume of specific procedures can achieve better results than those that perform relatively few of the same procedures. Improved planning for which services are to be provided at which levels can help to maximize the benefits of volume and expertise.

An increase in health care capacity increases health care use in South Africa

With more services and resources available, more people will want to use these services. This can help to extend the delivery of health care services to previously under-served populations.

Focusing on equity of health care and vulnerable populations in South Africa

Equity means ensuring that the whole population has access to quality health care. This means addressing the uneven distribution of health care resources across the country, as well as the wide variation in the quality of care throughout the health care system. In particular, there is a need to focus on the needs of historically disadvantaged individuals and communities and the most vulnerable sectors of society, i.e. women, children, older people and people with disabilities. Primary health care is the vehicle for achieving the long-term ambition of bringing the quality of health care for all people up to an acceptable standard. Norms and standards for primary health care spell out the standards of quality that are expected of the primary health care services in the public health sector.

Packages of care and associated norms and standards need also to be developed for other levels of care. These packages of care and associated norms and standards for the public sector will also be useful in the private sector to help address the problems of oversupply and overuse of services.

Ensuring accountability for quality improvement in both the public and private sectors in South Africa

To ensure that the public and private health sectors are collectively accountable for improving quality of health care throughout the country, strong public/private partnerships need to be developed through structures such as the National Consultative Health Forum, the Provincial Health Councils, Provincial Consultative Bodies and District Health Councils. These structures are ideally placed to ensure all stakeholders are incorporated or involved, the required technical expertise is accessed, and a nationwide agenda to improve health care quality is promoted and followed.

Delivering quality care - in the public sector in South Africa

While it is sensible to have a national policy and develop national standards for both public and private health care, it is the task of staff in each sector to deliver

the quality improvements. This requires a Quality Assurance culture and approach to the delivery of health care. For the public sector this requires action at all levels. This part of the policy document describes proposed methods to be used that follow the approaches outlined above. Consistent local action is needed to ensure that national standards and guidelines are reflected in the delivery of services. The District Health System is ideally positioned to facilitate this local action, because it is close enough to the community to be responsive to their needs, and is a powerful vehicle for improving the quality of care.

Quality monitoring by professional bodies in South Africa

Professional bodies will continue to monitor standards of professional conduct in accordance with relevant legislation.¹⁹³

Access to health services

Access relates to the opportunity to obtain and appropriately use quality health services. It is concerned with the “degree of fit” or compatibility between the health system on the one hand and individuals who need to use these services on the other hand. Access is generally seen as being multidimensional or having different elements. In this paper, access dimensions are summarised as: the availability (or physical access), affordability (or financial access) and acceptability (or cultural access) of health services¹⁹⁴. The availability dimension of access deals with whether the appropriate health services are available in the right place and at the right time to meet the needs of the population. Affordability concerns the ‘degree of fit’ between the full costs of using health care services and individuals’ ability-to-pay in the context of the household budget and other demands on that budget. Acceptability is concerned with the fit between provider and patient attitudes towards and expectations of each other. Beliefs and perceptions also influence acceptability.

The most widely used definition of health care quality is that developed by the Institute of Medicine (IOM)¹⁹⁵: “the degree to which health care services for individuals and populations increase the likelihood of desired health outcomes and are consistent with current professional knowledge.” The IOM further indicates that quality health services should be: effective; efficient; equitable; patient centred; safe; and timely. The UK National Health Service (NHS) has also provided a helpful definition of quality of care, which they see as relating to three areas: clinical effectiveness, patient safety and patient experience¹⁹⁶. This could be further summarised as technical and interpersonal excellence.

The government elected in the first democratic elections in 1994 inherited a highly fragmented health system, with separate public and private health sectors and a multiplicity of health departments in the public sector, including one for each of the 4 former provinces and 10 former ‘homelands’. While public sector health services had been officially desegregated in 1988, historically ‘black’ health care facilities and the ‘homelands’ health departments had been systematically underfunded during the

apartheid era. For example, average per capita public sector health care expenditure was R55 in the 'homelands' compared to an average of R172 in the rest of South Africa in the 1986/87 financial year¹⁹⁷. Thus, the health system was not only fragmented, but had large disparities in resource distribution between geographic areas and between individual facilities within the public sector. Although South Africa was already devoting a relatively large amount of resources to the health sector (8.5% of GDP in 1992/93), it had very poor health status indicators relative to comparable middle-income countries, indicating poor use and distribution of available health care resources¹⁹⁸.

After the first democratic elections, South Africa saw a rapid increase in annual registered deaths, rising from 317,727 in 1997 to a high of 614,014 in 2006. This then declined to 453,360 in 2014. The AIDS epidemic, and the initial refusal to introduce anti-retroviral (ARV) treatment and subsequent introduction of the largest ARV program globally, has been critical in this trend.

Access to health services in South Africa

As indicated earlier, it is difficult to measure access in an integrated and comprehensive way. Nevertheless, using the access framework outlined in the earlier section, information on various aspects of the different dimensions of access can be provided. There is extremely limited data on private sector providers, and any estimates that have been produced have been hotly contested. For this reason, and because the public health sector is the largest and most widely used health service provider, the focus is on indicators of access to public sector health services.

Information on the availability of health services in South Africa

The distance people need to travel to a health facility is a key element of the availability dimension of access. There are considerable differences in households' proximity to a health facility between rural and urban areas, across provinces and between socio-economic groups in South Africa. For example, one analysis of General Household Survey (GHS) data for the period 2002-2008 indicated that about 20% of households in the lowest income quintile lived an hour or more from the nearest public clinic and 36% lived an hour or more from the nearest hospital, compared with less than 5% of households in the highest income quintile¹⁹⁹. There was a similar finding from an analysis of the 2008 National Income Dynamics Survey (NIDS); 20% of the lowest income quintile²⁰⁰ lived more than 5 km from the nearest clinic compared with only 5% of the richest quintile. The likelihood of using a health service is far lower for those living furthest from health facilities. A very detailed household survey combined with a geographic information system analysis in the Hlabisa sub-district of KwaZulu-Natal found that households within 30 minutes of a clinic were 10 times more likely to make use of a clinic than households having to travel for 90-120 minutes to a clinic²⁰¹. These disparities persist even in relation to critical health services where lack of access can have serious consequences for premature death, such as attended deliveries. An analysis of the NIDS data found that

children in households that lived more than 2km from the nearest clinic were 8 percentage points less likely to have had a doctor or nurse present at birth than those within 2km of a clinic²⁰². The number and distribution of health facilities clearly influences various communities' proximity to a health facility. The availability of health personnel is also a key element of access to quality health care. Relative to WHO recommended availability indicators of 2.5 hospital beds per 1,000 population and 230 core health workers (doctors and nurses) per 100,000 people²⁰³, South Africa has a relatively low level of public hospital beds of 1.9 per 1,000 people dependent on public hospital inpatient services (non-medical scheme members) but has public sector core health worker levels that exceed the WHO recommendation at 339 nurses and doctors per 100,000 population, although staffing levels are lower than the average in upper-middle income countries of 503 per 100,000 population²⁰⁴.

Information on the affordability of health services in South Africa

The affordability of health services is influenced by the costs of health care on the one hand and household resources to cover these costs on the other hand. The way in which health services are financed is critical to affordability, particularly whether this takes the form of out-of-pocket payments (i.e. direct payments by a patient to a health care provider, usually at the time of using a health service) or on a pre-payment basis (i.e. either through tax payments, some of which are then allocated to funding health care, or contributions to a voluntary or mandatory health insurance scheme). Out-of-pocket (OOP) payments are the most concerning from an affordability perspective given that there is considerable uncertainty about when a person may fall ill and what financial resources they may have available at that particular point in time. Internationally, millions of people are impoverished, i.e. pulled below the poverty line, by paying for health services on an OOP basis²⁰⁵.

Information on the acceptability of health services in South Africa

Most household surveys collect 'general satisfaction' information. Although general satisfaction with private sector services tends to be higher than for public sector services, there are relatively high levels of respondents reporting being very or somewhat satisfied with health services at public health facilities (around 80%). There has been an increase over time in the percentage of recent users of public sector health services indicating that they were very satisfied with the service, increasing from 58% in 2002 to 62% in 2012²⁰⁶. There are differences across socio-economic groups, with higher-income groups expressing more dissatisfaction than lower-income groups. The major source of dissatisfaction relates to the length of waiting time before receiving care (38% in the case of public sector outpatient services and 18% in the private sector). The next most important sources of dissatisfaction were: not being treated with respect and dignity (20% in public and 10% in private sectors respectively); perceptions of lack of effectiveness of drugs received (18% in public and 9% in private sector); lack of privacy in consultations (14% and 8%); and lack of confidentiality (10% and 7%). Lack of respectful treatment, privacy in consultations and confidentiality were seen as more problematic in inpatient than outpatient

services in public sector facilities²⁰⁷. Stigma and judgemental behaviour of health care providers, which pose acceptability barriers to health service access, are particularly a problem in relation to certain services such as HIV, tuberculosis, pregnancy related services for teenagers and termination of pregnancy²⁰⁸.

Quality of health services in South Africa

As indicated in the conceptual overview in Annex 2, there is a strong link between quality and access, particularly the availability and acceptability dimensions. A key problem in the South African context is that there are almost no data to assess quality in a comprehensive way; instead, there is only anecdotal evidence and media coverage of the worst consequences of poor quality care. The extent of litigation is also seen as an indicator of poor quality of care. There has been a dramatic increase in medical malpractice litigation against health care providers in both the public and private health sectors. Medical litigation costs in the public health sector increased from around R191 million in 2011/12 to R389 million in 2014/15²⁰⁹. Settlement of claims by malpractice insurers on behalf of health care professionals run into billions of Rands, with claims against gynaecologists and obstetricians alone being over R4 billion. However, it should be noted that the increase of malpractice litigation does not necessarily represent declining quality of care, but is also driven by increased advertising around legal services for medical malpractice and patient knowledge of legal options, and the faultless liability regime created by section 61 of the Consumer Protection Act 68 of 2008²¹⁰. There are growing calls for moving to a system of mediation around medical malpractice to compensate those affected by poor quality of care while avoiding the large and rapidly growing litigation costs which are contributing to overall cost increases in the health sector²¹¹.

Even though some surveys present information on patient satisfaction with health care, as presented in the acceptability section above, such data is generally not regarded as a good indicator of technical quality of care, or sometimes even interpersonal quality of care. Very high levels of patient satisfaction are often reported, which could be due to gratitude, limited previous alternative experiences against which to assess care received and low expectations of the health service, i.e. patients could express satisfaction with what is technically low quality care²¹². Conversely, perceptions are influenced by factors such as negative media reports, with those who have never been admitted to a public hospital reporting higher levels of negative perceptions about quality of care in public hospitals than those who had been admitted to a public hospital in the previous year, and those without first-hand experience of public facilities listing media reports as the primary source of information on public facility quality of care²¹³.

Reform options and their potential to address inequitable access to quality health services in South Africa.

Various reform options have been put forward since 1994, with the National Health Insurance (NHI) proposals having dominated policy discussions for the last

decade. This section provides a brief overview of reform proposals since 1994. This is followed by detailed consideration of the current government proposals for reform, namely the National Health Insurance (NHI) proposals. The reason for this focus is that the Terms of Reference for this report require consideration of legislation and policies related to the health system; the NHI is currently the official government policy on future health system reform with both a Green and White Paper having been published. It is, therefore, critical to gain a clear understanding of the proposed reforms and critically assess their potential to address inequitable access to quality health care. Thereafter, alternatives that have been put forward are considered from the same 'equitable access to quality health care' perspective.²¹⁴

South Africa's health system consists of a large public sector, a smaller but fast growing private sector and an NGO sector. The public health sector is funded by the state. 40% of all expenditure on health comes from the National Treasury. Public health consumes around 11% of the government's total budget and is allocated mostly to nine provincial departments. This is higher than the 5% of GDP recommended by the World Health Organisation (WHO) and reflects the major burden of disease management and treatment carried by the public sector in South Africa. This includes the treatment of HIV and tuberculosis (TB) as a large component of the disease burden in South Africa. The high levels of poverty and unemployment in the country mean that healthcare remains largely the burden of the state with the National Department of Health holding overall responsibility for health care, with a specific responsibility for the public sector. Despite this high expenditure, health outcomes are poor in comparison with other similar middle-income countries, reflecting an inequity in healthcare in the country. The public sector is further hampered by a shortage of key medical personnel.

The Public Healthcare System in South Africa

The foundation of the public health system is the primary healthcare clinics that are the first line of access for people needing healthcare services. These clinics provide their services free. Access to clinics has improved significantly since 1994 (the country's transition to democracy) but in many instances, the quality of health care provided at this level has fallen. The next tier of the public healthcare system in South Africa are the district hospitals to which patients are referred from primary healthcare clinics when they need more sophisticated treatment. At the tertiary level are the academic hospitals where advanced diagnostic procedures and treatments are provided. These also serve as training institutions for healthcare providers.

The annual expenditure of the public healthcare sector is around R122.4-billion to serve 84% of the population, or 42-million people, who are dependent on the public health care sector for services.

The Private Healthcare System in South Africa

The private healthcare system is made up of healthcare professionals who provide their services on a private basis, usually funded by the subscriptions of individuals to medical aid schemes. Private healthcare practitioners also provide services through private hospitals. The private healthcare sector spends around R120.8-billion annually to cover 16.2% of the population or 8.2-million people, many of whom have medical cover. South Africa has more than 110 registered medical schemes, with around 3,4-million principal members (and 7,8- million beneficiaries). There are 238 private hospitals in the country, 188 in urban areas and 50 in rural areas.

NGO Healthcare Provision in South Africa

Multiple NGOs contribute to the health sector with a focus on HIV/Aids and TB, accounts for a spend of donor money of around R5.3 billion.²¹⁵

Patient safety is at the forefront of service delivery in South Africa (SA), as the health system is struggling to cope with the collision of four excessive health burdens, namely communicable diseases (especially HIV/AIDS); non-communicable diseases; maternal, neonatal and child deaths; and deaths from injury and violence (Coovadia *et al.* 2009:817–843). At the same time, SA experiences acute shortages of health professionals in the publicly funded sector. This combination of increasing numbers of patients and a shortage of professionals is a real concern for nurse managers, as nurse practitioners are responsible for all acts and omissions in the delivery of quality patient care (Eygelaar & Stellenberg 2012:1) and patients have little guarantee that they are receiving safe health care.

Many healthcare quality problems have been identified in both the private and public sectors in SA. The most notable are: under- and over-use of services; avoidable errors; lack of resources; inadequate diagnosis and treatment; inefficient use of resources; and drug shortages and poor delivery systems (National Department of Health 2007:3). In July 2009 the SA Ministry of Health released a programme of action which comprised ten priority actions to address the service delivery challenges. One of the key priorities of this plan is the improvement in the quality of healthcare services (National Department of Health 2010:6). The most common problems experienced by healthcare users in public institutions include: lack of cleanliness; poor safety and security; long waiting times; poor staff attitude; and poor infection control measures and the non-availability of drugs (National Department of Health 2011a:4). In summary all these issues indicate possible poor quality of care.

Quality care can be defined in the light of the provider's technical standards but also patients' expectations. Quality is a comprehensive and multifaceted concept, and dimensions of quality include technical competence; access to service; effectiveness; interpersonal relations; efficiency; continuity of care; safety and

amenities (Brown *et al.* 1993:8–10). Nurse managers need to be able to meet these provider- and patient expectations within policy and fiscal constraints.

Patient safety is a dimension of quality assurance. 'Patient safety practices' refers to those processes or structures which, when applied, reduce the probability of adverse events resulting from exposure to the healthcare system across a range of diseases and procedures (World Health Organization 2008:1). Furthermore, patient safety includes initiatives to identify, report, analyse and prevent any unintended or unexpected incidents that could harm healthcare users (National Department of Health 2011b:22). Patient safety is a serious global public health issue and patient safety is a top priority for action by the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality in the United States of America (Kronick 2014:196). Unsafe patient care is associated with significant morbidity and mortality rates throughout the world, and much of it might be amenable to timely intervention (World Health Organization, World Alliance for Patient Safety 2008:3). In developing countries the probability of a patient being harmed in hospitals is high, with the risk of healthcare-associated infection as much as 20 times higher than in developed countries (World Health Organization n.d., fact 3). Wilson *et al.* (2012:1–14) conducted a study in eight developing countries, including SA. The aim of the study was to assess both the frequency and the nature of adverse events experienced by patients. The results indicated that of the 15 548 records reviewed 8.2% showed at least one adverse event, with a range of 2.5% to 18.4% per country. 83% of those adverse events were preventable and 30% were associated with the death of the patients (Wilson *et al.* 2012:4.). Key to ensuring patient safety is ensuring a patient safety culture (PSC) in the organisation.

The Manchester Patient Safety Framework

The MaPSaF is a tool that was developed by Parker *et al.* in 2006 and was developed through extensive healthcare literature reviews and consultations with healthcare professionals (Law *et al.* 2010:110). The MaPSaF makes the concept of a 'safety culture' more accessible to healthcare teams and organisations. Originally designed for use by general practices and primary care setting, the MaPSaF has now been adapted for use in other healthcare settings. The tool describes nine quality dimensions and was tested and validated in acute care settings in Canada and the United Kingdom (Law *et al.* 2010:111). The MaPSaF outlined was developed to help make the concept of safety culture more accessible to healthcare teams and to assist organisations to understand their level of development with respect to the value that they place on patient safety (National Health Service 2006:1). Since the completion of this study, these quality dimensions were refined resulting in a list with 10 dimensions. The tool helps healthcare teams and organisations reflect on their progress in developing a mature safety culture (National Health Service 2006:1). The MaPSaF was chosen to assess the PSC at the National District Hospital (NDH) as an opportunity to foreground quality concerns within the hospital. The MaPSaF is not designed to be used for performance management or assessment purposes, or to assign blame when the results show that an organisation's safety culture is not yet

satisfactorily mature. This characteristic of not assigning blame was important in the methodology.

The challenge of healthcare reform in South Africa

Healthcare reform is an urgent and at the same time extremely difficult challenge for South Africa's policy makers, one which presents opportunities and risks across both public and private healthcare sectors. In its August 2011 Green Paper on NHI, the government set the ambitious goal of achieving universal access to quality healthcare over the next 14 years. The ideal that inspires NHI is a scheme that is universal, compulsory and 'free at the point of use'. No matter how much the system will cost to run, no matter how much or how little an individual will contribute to the cost, users of its comprehensive services will not be billed for them. This is an enormous challenge in one of the most unequal countries in the world. Only 41 per cent of South Africa's working-age population participate in the economy and there are only 5.9 million registered individual taxpayers. This is the very narrow base of 'solidarity' funding which the government is banking on to achieve its healthcare goals for over 50 million people.

Health outcomes in South Africa

Health outcomes are customarily calculated in terms of rates of mortality (death) and morbidity (disease). Sometimes these indicators are combined to give an overview measure – 'disease burden' – while an increasingly common indicator, which has been devised by the World Health Organisation (WHO), is 'disability-adjusted-life-years', a measure of the number of healthy years of life lost to premature death and disability. These outcomes are not a simple measure of a country's healthcare system. Socioeconomic determinants of health that affect many South Africans are important. These include inadequate access to sanitation, poor nutrition and alcohol abuse which, apart from direct effects on health, leads to high levels of motor vehicle accidents and interpersonal violence. However indicators such as life expectancy, especially when combined with information about expenditure and resources do give a general idea of the comparative effectiveness of healthcare systems.

South African healthcare - high expenditure, poor outcomes

The most recent authoritative assessment of South Africa's health outcomes was published in a series of six papers in *The Lancet* medical journal (2009). Although *The Lancet* is an international journal based in London, the work was carried out by a team of distinguished medical researchers, clinicians and public health experts most of whom live in South Africa or are South African. The recurring theme across the six papers is: 'the paradox of persistently poor health outputs and outcomes despite high health expenditure and many supportive policies'²¹⁶

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CHAPTER- 3

DATA ANALYSIS

Introduction:

In order to analyse the objectives of this research, the researcher has purchased the national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals of India (NABH) and South Africa (COHSASA) as the standards of Denmark (DDKM) and Australia (NSQHS) are freely available and accessible on their websites. After reading all these standards in details, the researcher noticed that the chapters, standards and measurable elements are duplicated or phrased in some other way around by keeping the same meaning. Hence, all such duplicated chapters, standards and measurable elements were eliminated by mapping, filtration and merging of Chapters, Standards and Measurable Elements and a new list of chapters, standards and measurable elements

Hence, all such duplicated chapters, standards and measurable elements were eliminated by mapping, filtration and merging of standards and measurable elements in the relevant chapters and a new list of chapters, standards and measurable elements was developed in order to measure the measurable elements against this developed standards.

Standard scoring methodology is used to score each measurable element as per the national and international healthcare organizations. The scoring methodology used is- Fully Met=FM, Partially Met=PM, Not Met= NM. Also, the researcher has used a zero number “0” in the tables of NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA for showing the non-compliance. Each Measurable Element can only have one score as – Fully Met (FM), Partially Met (PM) or Not Met (NM).

The researcher has tested all the hypotheses as per the objectives of the research in this chapter.

Table Number-1: National Accreditation Board for Hospitals and Healthcare Providers (NABH) Standards, India

Sr. No.	Chapters in NABH Standards (India)	Number of Standards	Number of Measurable Elements (ME's)
1	Access, Assessment and Continuity of Care (AAC)	14	96
2	Care of Patients (COP)	22	151
3	Management of Medication (MOM)	13	76
4	Patient Rights and Education (PRE)	8	54
5	Hospital Infection Control (HIC)	9	54
6	Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI)	9	59

Sr. No.	Chapters in NABH Standards (India)	Number of Standards	Number of Measurable Elements (ME's)
7	Responsibilities of Management (ROM)	6	98
8	Facility Management and Safety (FMS)	7	56
9	Human Resource Management (HRM)	10	53
10	Information Management System (IMS)	7	98
	Total	105	795

Table Number-1 depicts that, there are total 10 Chapters, 105 Standards and 795 Measurable Elements in the National Accreditation Board for Hospitals and Healthcare Providers (NABH), India.

Table Number- 2: National Safety and Quality Health Service (NSQHS), Australia

Sr. No.	Chapters in NSQHS Standards (Australia)	Number of Standards	Number of Measurable Elements (ME's)
1	Clinical Governance Standard (CGS)	4	33
2	Partnering with Consumers Standard (PCS)	4	14
3	Preventing and Controlling Healthcare-Associated Infection Standard (PCHAIS)	4	16
4	Medication Safety Standard (MSS)	4	15
5	Comprehensive Care Standard (CCS)	4	36
6	Communicating for Safety Standard (CSS)	5	11
7	Blood Management Standard (BMS)	3	10
8	Recognizing and Responding to Acute Deterioration Standard (RRADS)	2	13
	Total	30	148

Table Number- 2 depicts that, there are total 8 Chapters, 30 Standards and 148 Measurable Elements in the National Safety and Quality Health Service (NSQHS), Australia.

Table Number- 3: Danish Healthcare Quality Programme (DDKM), Denmark:

Sr. No.	Chapters in DDKM Standards (Denmark)	Number of Standards	Number of Measurable Elements (ME's)
1	Management	5	23
2	Quality and risk management	7	43
3	Documentation and data management	4	23
5	Employment, work planning and competence development	6	28
6	Hygiene	5	30
7	Preparedness	2	15
8	Equipment and technology	4	19
9	Buildings and supplies	5	31
10	Patient involvement	3	17
11	Patient information and communication	2	14
12	Coordination and continuity	1	6
13	Referrals	1	4
14	Reception, assessment and planning	5	35
15	Diagnosis	3	20
16	Medication	6	32
17	Observation	2	8
18	Invasive treatment	4	23
19	Intensive care	1	8
20	Resuscitation	1	4
21	Nutrition	1	7
22	Recovery	2	10
23	Prevention and health promotion	1	7
24	Transfer	3	15
25	Patient transport	1	6
26	At the end of life	2	8
27	Disease-specific standards	3	25
	Total	80	461

Table Number- 3 depicts that, there are total 27 Chapters, 80 Standards and 461 Measurable Elements in the Danish Healthcare Quality Programme (DDKM), Denmark.

Table Number- 4: The Council for Health Service Accreditation of Southern Africa (COHSASA), South Africa:

Sr. No.	Chapters in COHSASA Standards (South Africa)	Number of Standards	Number of Measurable Elements (ME's)
1	Management and Leadership	11	78
2	Human Resource Management	12	62
3	Administrative Support	7	59
4	Access to Care and Patient Rights	12	57
5	Risk Management	12	65
6	Resuscitation System	4	78
7	Information Management and Quality Improvement	12	53
8	Prevention and Control of Infection	6	33
9	General Medical/Surgical/Paediatric and Obstetric Care	28	161
10	Medical Care	25	137
11	Surgical Care	25	138
12	Paediatric Care	27	154
13	Obstetric and Maternity Care	27	156
14	Operating Theatre and Anaesthetic Services	15	89
15	Critical Care	28	152
16	Mental Health Service	28	156
17	Medical Oncology	27	143
18	Emergency Care	33	182
19	Outpatient Care	24	135
20	Combined Outpatient and Emergency Care	33	187
21	Occupational Health Service	17	111
22	Therapeutic Support Services	12	60
23	Laboratory Service	13	77
24	Radiology and Diagnostic Imaging Service	13	152
25	Nuclear Medicine Service	13	103
26	Pharmaceutical Service	9	51
27	Central Sterile Supplies Department	7	82
28	Food and Therapeutic Nutritional Services	17	84
29	Linen Management	9	53
30	Housekeeping Service	7	36
31	Maintenance Service	12	55
32	Medical Equipment Management Service	7	49
33	Medical Physics Service	15	89
34	Radiation Oncology	14	97
	Total	561	3374

Table Number- 4 depicts that, there are total 34 Chapters, 561 Standards and 3374 Measurable Elements in the Council for Health Service Accreditation of Southern Africa (COHSASA), South Africa.

Table Number-5: Comparison NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA based on number of Chapters, Standards and Measurable Elements (ME's).

Sr. No.	Names of the Standards	Number of Chapters	Number of Standards	Number of ME's
1	NABH (India)	10	105	795
2	NSQHS (Australia)	8	30	148
3	DDKM (Denmark)	27	80	461
4	COHSASA (South Africa)	34	561	3374
	Total	79	776	4778

Table number 5 depicts that the NABH has 10 chapters, 105 standards and 795 ME's. NSQHS has 8 Chapters, 30 standards and 148 ME's. DDKM has 27 Chapters, 80 Standards and 461 ME's and COHSASA has 34 chapters, 561 Standards and 3374 ME's.

Figure-1: Comparison of four selected accreditation standards for hospitals, Chapters and Measurable Elements (ME's).

Figure number-1 depicts that the NABH has 10 chapters, 105 standards and 795 ME's. NSQHS has 8 Chapters, 30 standards and 148 ME's. DDKM has 27 Chapters, 80 Standards and 461 ME's and COHSASA has 34 chapters, 561 Standards and 3374 ME's.

Table Number-6: Chapters, Standards and Measurable Elements after mapping, filtration and merging of Standards and Measurable Elements in NABH, DDKM, NSQHS and COHSASA standards for hospitals

Sr. No.	Names of the Chapters	Number of Standards	Number of Measurable Elements (ME's)
1	Facility Management and Safety (FMS)	48	325
2	Access to Care and Continuity of Care (ACC)	22	113
3	Emergency Department (ED)	10	55
4	Management of Information (MOI)	15	103
5	Patient and Family Rights (PFR)	27	123
6	Patient and Family Education (PFE)	9	38
7	Laboratory (LAB)	29	132
8	Radiology (RAD)	17	105
9	Human Resource (HR)	22	128
10	Pharmacy (PHARM)	38	167
11	Prevention and Control of Infection (PCI)	32	142
12	Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI)	36	192
13	Governance Leadership and Direction (GLD)	22	162
14	Care of Patients (COP)	45	244
15	Anesthesia and Surgical Care (ASC)	15	102
16	Assessment of Patient (AOP)	15	110
17	Nuclear Medicine	9	86
18	Central Sterile Supply Department (CSSD)	5	23
19	Dietary Services	15	83
20	Linen Services	4	29
21	Housekeeping Services	3	19
22	Medical Physics	10	67
23	Radiation Oncology	9	75
24	Occupation Health	9	55

Sr. No.	Names of the Chapters	Number of Standards	Number of Measurable Elements (ME's)
	Total	466	2678

Table Number 6 depicts that after mapping, filtration and merging of duplication and common chapters, standards and measurable elements in NABH, DDKM, NSQHS and COHSASA standards; finally there are 24 chapters, 466 standards and 2678 measurable elements which are unique.

Table Number-7: Facility Management and Safety (FMS):

The Facility Management and Safety Chapter have 48 Standards and 325 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
1	The Facility Maintenance Service is managed to ensure the provision of a safe and effective service.	1	A designated individual is responsible for supervising the maintenance of buildings, plant and installations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.1.1-1;		
2		2	The responsibilities of the manager are documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.1.1-2;		
3		3	The maintenance manager identifies the requirements of the hospital's maintenance programme, which informs the budgeting process.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.1.1-3;		
4		4	Laws, regulations and other requirements applicable to the hospital's facilities are available to personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.1.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
5		5	Policies and procedures guide personnel in the implementation of country-specific legislation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.1.1-5;		
6		6	The manager works with the multidisciplinary team to develop and implement risk management systems according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.1.1-6;		
7	Service facilities and equipment	7	There is a dedicated work area for maintenance activities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.1.2-1;		
8		8	Basic maintenance equipment, tools and spare parts are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.1.2-2;		
9		9	There is a separate area for personnel with adequate, secure storage facilities for outdoor clothing and personal possessions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.1.2-3;		
10		10	There are adequate, suitable and conveniently placed change rooms, toilets and ablution facilities for personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.1.2-4;		
11	There is an adequate number of suitably qualified and/ or experienced personnel to provide a safe and effective service.	11	There are sufficient suitably trained and/or experienced personnel to manage the hospital's buildings, plant and machinery.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.1.3-1;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
12		12	Where there are no in-house personnel to perform these functions, the services of consultants/service providers are utilised.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.1.3-2;		
13		13	Contact details for specialist service contractors for buildings, plant and machinery are available, which include the name of the organisation, their location, telephone numbers, responsible persons and specified nominated contact person(s).	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.1.3-3;		
14		14	There is a system for the provision of emergency technical backup.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.1.3-4;		
15	The organisation has a system in place to provide a safe and secure environment.	15	Safety committee coordinates development, implementation and monitoring of the safety plan and policies.	FMS-1, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16		16	Patient-safety devices & infrastructure are installed across the organisation and inspected periodically.	FMS-1, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17		17	The organisation is a non-smoking area.	FMS-1, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
18		18	There is a procedure which addresses the identification and disposal of material(s) not in use in the organisation.	FMS-1, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19		19	Facility inspection rounds to ensure safety are conducted at least twice in a year in patient-care areas and at least once in a year in non-patient-care areas.	FMS-1, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
20		20	Inspection reports are documented and corrective and preventive measures are undertaken.	FMS-1, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
21		21	There is a safety education programme for staff.	FMS-1, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
22	The organisation's environment and facilities operate in a planned manner to ensure safety of patients, their families, staff and visitors and promotes environment friendly measures.	22	Facilities are appropriate to the scope of services of the organisation.	FMS-2, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
23		23	Up-to-date drawings are maintained which detail the site layout, floor plans and fire-escape routes.	FMS-2, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
24		24	There is internal and external sign postings in the organisation in a language understood by the patient, families and community.	FMS-2, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25		25	The provision of space shall be in accordance with the available literature on good practices (National or international standards) and directives from government agencies.	FMS-2, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
26		26	Operational planning describes access to different areas in the hospital by staff, patients, visitors and vendors.	FMS-2, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
27		27	Potable water and electricity are available round the clock.	FMS-2, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28		28	Alternate sources for electricity and water are provided as backup for any failure/shortage.	FMS-2, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29		29	The organisation regularly tests these alternate sources.	FMS-2, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30		30	There are designated individuals (with appropriate equipment) responsible for the maintenance of all the facilities.	FMS-2, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31		31	Maintenance staff is contactable round the clock for emergency	FMS-2, j			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			repairs.												
32		32	There is a maintenance plan for facility and furniture.	FMS-2, k			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
33		33	Response times are monitored from reporting to inspection and implementation of corrective actions.	FMS-2, l			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
34		34	The organisation takes initiatives towards an energy efficient and environmental friendly hospital.	FMS-2, m			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
35	The hospital's buildings and surrounding areas are accessible and safe to walk in.	35	There are on-going plans for ensuring buildings' and surrounding areas' safety and accessibility.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.1-1; 1.8.1-2;			0	0	0
36		36	The hospital has planned measures to ensure the accessibility in all weather conditions. The effort is based on a risk assessment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.1-3;			0	0	0
37		37	According to current legislation, the hospital is accessible for persons with impairments.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.1-4;			0	0	0
38		38	The hospital has implemented measures to ensure against unauthorised access (theft and assault). The effort is based on a	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.1-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			risk assessment.												
39		39	The hospital's buildings and surrounding areas are maintained so the buildings and access roads do not pose a danger to people. The effort is based on a risk assessment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.1-6;			0	0	0
40		40	The hospital has implemented measures to prevent fire. The measures include safe storage of inflammable materials. The effort is based on a risk assessment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.1-7;			0	0	0
41		41	The hospital has planned measures for fire fighting and protection of patients and staff from the consequences of a fire, including safety precaution of escape routes and presence of fire-fighting equipment. The effort is based on a risk assessment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.1-8;			0	0	0
42	The hospital's buildings and facilities support the assignment of tasks, operations and safety for people.	42	The hospital has a process to assess whether the buildings and facilities for treatment of patients are suitable for the intended purpose.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.2-1;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
43		43	Prior to large reconstructions and new buildings and in connection with significant changes for using the facilities for patient treatment, the suitability of the buildings and facilities is assessed in relation to the intended purpose.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.1-9; 1.8.2-1;			0	0	0
44		44	Prior to large reconstructions and new buildings, a risk assessment of the construction phase, including evaluation of hygiene and fire safety, is made. Based upon this, relevant precautionary measures are initiated.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.1-9; 1.8.2-2;			0	0	0
45		45	There is documentation for assessment of the suitability of the buildings and facilities when used for new purposes. This only applies to facilities for patient treatment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.2-3;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
46		46	If there are lacks in relation to the assessment of the suitability of buildings and facilities when used for new purposes, initiatives have been made to improve the quality. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.2-4;			0	0	0
47	Functional facilities are available to provide safety and comfort for patients and personnel.	47	Sufficient office/administrative space is available for personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.4-1;		
48		48	Where required, air-conditioning is installed in laboratories, pharmacies, operating theatres and sterilising departments and is tested and maintained according to hospital policy or manufacturer's guidelines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.4-2;		
49		49	Temperature and ventilation control mechanisms are installed in the kitchen, laundries and other relevant areas and tested and maintained according to hospital policy or manufacturer's	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.4-3;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			guidelines.												
50	A security system is maintained for the routine monitoring and safeguarding of the premises, patients, personnel, volunteers and visitors.	50	Internal security is provided 24 hours per day, seven days per week.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.4.1-1;		
51		51	External security is provided 24 hours per day, seven days per week.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.4.1-2;		
52		52	Policies on the management of weapons are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.4.1-3;		
53		53	Policies on the management of violence and aggression are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.4.1-4;		
54		54	Where vulnerable patients are cared for, special safety and security measures are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.4.1-5;		
55		55	There is a mechanism known to personnel for summoning the assistance of the local security/police/protection service in case of an emergency.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.4.1-6;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
56	The organisation has a programme for engineering support services and utility system.	56	The organisation plans for equipment in accordance with its services and strategic plan.	FMS-3, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
57		57	Equipment are selected, rented, updated or upgraded by a collaborative process.	FMS-3, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
58		58	Equipment are inventoried and proper logs are maintained as required.	FMS-3, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
59		59	Qualified and trained personnel operate, inspect, test and maintain equipment and utility systems.	FMS-3, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
60		60	Utility equipment are periodically inspected and calibrated (wherever applicable) for their proper functioning.	FMS-3, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
61		61	There is a documented operational and maintenance (preventive and breakdown) plan.	FMS-3, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
62		62	There is a maintenance plan for water management.	FMS-3, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
63		63	There is a maintenance plan for electrical systems.	FMS-3, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
64		64	There is a maintenance plan for heating, ventilation and air-conditioning.	FMS-3, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
65		65	There is a maintenance plan for Information technology & communication network	FMS-3, j			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
66		66	There is a documented procedure for equipment replacement and disposal.	FMS-3, k			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
67	The hospital has a process to protect hospital occupants in the event of electrical system disruption or failure, which is tested on a regular basis.	67	Electrical power is available continuously from regular and emergency sources.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.3.1-1;
68		68	Emergency electricity supply is available in the areas and services that present the greatest patient safety risk during a power failure.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.3.1-2;
69		69	Sufficient fuel, e.g. diesel, is available to provide power for 24 hours.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.3.1-3;
70		70	The hospital ensures that relevant personnel are trained to use/operate emergency electrical supply systems.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.3.1-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
71	Water supplies are regularly inspected, tested, maintained and, when appropriate, improved.	71	Regular and emergency water supplies, including drinkable water, are available continually.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
72		72	All water supplies are tested and the results are documented on a regular basis.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
73		73	Should the water supply be contaminated or interrupted, the areas and services at risk have been identified and provision has been made for an alternative water supply.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
74		74	There is documented evidence that relevant personnel are regularly trained to ensure that all operations to secure safe water are properly performed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75	The hospital receives utensils of an appropriate amount and quality in relation to the handling of tasks.	75	There are guidelines for ordering, reception and storage of utensils.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.4-1;			0	0	0
76		76	There are guidelines for follow-up on quality flaws when receiving utensils.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.4-2;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
77		77	The hospital describes precautionary measures for situations where the supply of utensils fails.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.4-3;			0	0	0
78		78	Utensils are ordered and requested in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.4-4;			0	0	0
79		79	Follow-up is made for quality flaws on reception of utensils in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.4-5;			0	0	0
80		80	Relevant managers and staff are familiar with the precautionary measures for situations where the supply of utensils fails.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.4-6;			0	0	0
81	The hospital's technical supplies are in accordance with the need.	81	There are guidelines for operations, maintenance, control and prevention of breakdown of technical supplies. The guidelines are based on a risk assessment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.4-1;			0	0	0
82		82	Managers and staff are familiar with relevant parts of the guidelines and work accordingly.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.4-2; 1.7.1-2;			0	0	0
83		83	There are guidelines for documentation of microbiological and toxicological control of tap water.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.4-3;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
84		84	There is documentation for control of compressed-air plant, oxygen, medical gases and vacuum.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.4-4;			0	0	0
85		85	There is documentation for control of ventilation system.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.4-5;			0	0	0
86		86	There is documentation for control of emergency supplies of tap water.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.4-6;			0	0	0
87		87	There is documentation for test runs of emergency supplies.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.4-7;			0	0	0
88		88	If there are lacks in relation to technical supplies, initiatives have been made to improve the quality. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.4-8;			0	0	0
89	The hospital implements a documented planned preventative maintenance programme (PPM) for buildings, installations and machinery.	89	Policies and procedures relating to the maintenance of plant, equipment and installations are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.1-1;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
90		90	The service implements planned preventative maintenance according to a schedule.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.1-2;		
91		91	The department holds regular, documented, current and accurate inspections of the hospital's physical facility, plant and machinery.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.1-3;		
92		92	Records/log books indicate that emergency generators are regularly tested on full load according to manufacturer's specifications.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.1-4;		
93		93	Servicing and testing of the uninterruptible power supplies (UPS) and/or battery backup systems is documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.1-5;		
94		94	There is documented evidence that the recommendations of the inspections have been addressed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.1-6;		
95		95	A documented procedure for reporting defects in maintenance installations during and after normal working hours is known to departmental and hospital personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.1-7;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
96		96	Records indicate that upgrading, replacement, de-commissioning and/or disposal of operational plant are undertaken according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.1-8;		
97		97	There are site and floor plans that depict the locations and layout of the main services (i.e. water, sanitation, electricity supply).	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.1-9;		
98		98	Records indicate that the sewerage management system is maintained according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.1-10;		
99	The organisation has plans for fire and non-fire emergencies within the facilities.	99	The organisation has plans and provisions for early detection, abatement and containment of fire, and non-fire emergencies.	FMS-6, a			0	0	0	1.6.1-1; 1.6.1-3;			0	0	0
100		100	The organisation has a documented safe-exit plan in case of fire and non-fire emergencies.	FMS-6, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
101		101	Staff is trained for its role in case of such emergencies.	FMS-6, c			0	0	0	1.6.1-2;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
102		102	Mock drills are held at least twice a year.	FMS-6, d			0	0	0	1.6.1-4; 1.6.1-5; 1.6.1-6; 1.6.1-7; 1.6.1-8; 1.6.3-3; 1.6.3-4; 1.6.3-5; 1.6.3-6; 1.6.3-7;			0	0	0
103	Structured systems to ensure fire safety are implemented.	103	Structured systems and processes to ensure that all occupants of the hospital facilities are safe from fire or smoke are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.6.1-1;			5.4.2-1;		
104		104	Documented evidence is available from the relevant authority to confirm that the hospital complies with applicable laws and regulations in relation to fire safety.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.6.3-1;			5.4.2-2;		
105		105	Fire-fighting equipment is inspected and serviced at least annually with the date of service recorded on the apparatus.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.4.2-3;		
106		106	Flammable materials are clearly labelled and safely stored.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.4.2-4;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
107		107	Easily recognised and understood signs prohibiting smoking are displayed in areas where flammable materials and combustible gases are stored.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.4.2-5;		
108		108	A floor plan is displayed, which shows the location of fire fighting equipment, evacuation routes and emergency exits.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.4.2-6;		
109		109	Annual personnel training in fire prevention and evacuation procedures is documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.6.1-2; 1.6.3-2;			5.4.2-7;		
110		110	The hospital has implemented a policy regarding smoking, which applies to patients, families, visitors, personnel and volunteers.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.4.2-8;		
111		111	There is a maintenance plan for fire-related equipment & infrastructure	FMS-6, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
112	The organisation has a programme for bio-medical equipment management.	112	The organisation plans for equipment in accordance with its services and strategic plan.	FMS-4, a			0	0	0	1.7.1-1;			0	0	0
113		113	Equipment are selected, rented, updated or upgraded by a collaborative process.	FMS-4, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
114		114	Equipment are inventoried and proper logs are maintained as required.	FMS-4, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
115		115	Qualified and trained personnel operate and maintain the medical equipment.	FMS-4, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
116		116	Equipment are periodically inspected and calibrated for their proper functioning.	FMS-4, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
117		117	There is a documented operational and maintenance (preventive and breakdown) plan for equipment.	FMS-4, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
118		118	There is a documented procedure for equipment replacement and disposal.	FMS-4, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
119		119	The procedure addresses medical equipment recalls.	FMS-4, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
120		120	Response times are monitored from reporting to inspection and implementation of corrective actions.	FMS-4, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
121	Adequate human resources are available for the Medical Equipment Management Service (MEMS) to ensure safety and the correct management, usage and operation of medical equipment.	121	A medical equipment maintenance manager is designated by the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.1.1-1;
122		122	The responsibilities of the medical equipment maintenance manager are defined in writing.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.1-2;						32.1.1-2;
123		123	Policies and procedures developed in accordance with country-specific legislation guide personnel in the acquisition, allocation and utilisation of equipment and technical support for MEMS.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.1.1-3;
124		124	A multidisciplinary advisory committee is appointed to represent managers, clinical and technical personnel involved in the management and use of medical equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.1.1-4;
125		125	Members of the committee are appointed in writing, based on their competence in the area of	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.1.1-5;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			healthcare technology management.												
126		126	The responsibilities of the committee are documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
127		127	The committee meets regularly to discuss and advise on issues relating to healthcare technology management and these meetings are minuted.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
128		128	The committee has ready access to a reliable source of expertise relating to healthcare technology.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
129	Medical equipment is managed and maintained throughout the hospital.	129	An audit of medical equipment is conducted.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
130		130	There is a comprehensive inventory of all medical equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
131		131	Operator and/or service manuals are available to operators and technicians at all times.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
132		132	Operator and/or service manuals for donated equipment are available in local languages.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
133		133	Initial commissioning records are available for all high risk medical equipment, which include details	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			of tests performed and training given.												
134		134	The hospital develops and implements a planned preventative inspection and maintenance system according to the service requirements specified by the manufacturers.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.2.1-6;
135		135	The manager identifies the requirements of the hospital's medical equipment maintenance programme, which informs the budgeting process.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.2.1-7;
136		136	There is a service history for each piece of equipment, which includes signed and dated job-cards detailing all time and expenses associated with maintaining the device, e.g. procedures carried out, time taken to complete the procedure, parts fitted, etc.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.2.1-8;
137		137	Patient care unit managers have access to information on service and repairs of equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.2.1-9;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
138		138	A documented system which addresses the provision of basic technical support in first line emergency situations is in place and known to all relevant persons.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.2.1-10;
139		139	Advanced technical support is provided in emergency situations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.2.1-11;
140		140	Names of specialist service contractors are available with their locations, telephone numbers and the responsible persons specified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.2.1-12;
141		141	Where there are in-house clinical engineering personnel the department has access to all specialised test equipment and consumables (as specified by the manufacturer of the medical equipment) for the equipment they are expected to maintain.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.2.1-13;
142		142	Where there are in-house clinical engineering personnel, the tools and test equipment required to offer the service are appropriately maintained.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.2.1-14;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
143		143	Where there are in-house clinical engineering personnel, they are provided with access to appropriate support documentation, such as equipment standards and other regulatory documentation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.2.1-15;
144		144	Checklists are available for the inspection and maintenance of each type of device in use in the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.2.1-16;
145		145	Where there are in-house clinical engineering personnel, the service develops and implements a system to obtain information on medical device hazard alerts or safety bulletins and responds to the information appropriately.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.2.1-17;
146	There are systems in place to ensure that all users of medical equipment and devices are competent in the use thereof.	146	Training is provided for all users of basic medical equipment, with a record of all such training given and successfully completed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.2-1;						32.3.1-1;
147		147	Training is provided for all users of complex and/or critical life-support equipment, with a record of all such training given and	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.3.1-2;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			successfully completed.												
148		148	Training in basic electrical safety is provided to all personnel involved in the use of electrically operated equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.3.1-3;		
149		149	Where clinical engineering personnel are employed, they are provided with appropriate training in respect of all medical equipment, devices and instruments, which they are expected to maintain and/or repair.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.3.1-4;		
150		150	Where clinical engineering personnel are employed, they are encouraged and assisted by management to attend seminars, congresses, conferences and training sessions, to improve their knowledge of and proficiency in medical technology matters.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.3.1-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
151	Where clinical engineering personnel are employed, systems are in place to ensure safe working conditions and the safety of equipment in clinical engineering workshops.	151	Clinical engineering personnel implement risk management processes in accordance with the hospital risk management systems.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.4.1-1;
152		152	There is an adequate scavenging system for the removal of nitrous oxide and volatile anaesthetic agents in the medical equipment workshop.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.4.1-2;
153		153	Where anaesthetic vaporisers are tested and serviced in the workshop, a suitable fume extraction chamber is provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.4.1-3;
154		154	Where extensive soldering work is undertaken, soldering stations are provided with a suitable fume extraction system.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.4.1-4;
155		155	Where volatile cleaning agents are used, an appropriate fume extraction chamber is provided for the safe dispersal of hazardous vapours, e.g. ether.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.4.1-5;
156		156	The medical equipment workshop has adequate 15 amp	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.4.1-6;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			surge-protected electrical power outlets.												
157		157	The medical equipment workshop is fitted with air-conditioning capable of maintaining a year-round constant temperature of 21 degrees Celsius.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.4.1-7;
158	Any acquisition, testing and implementation of equipment for clinical use are made in accordance with current rules.	158	There are guidelines for acquisition, testing and implementation of equipment for clinical use taking the administrative, clinical and medico-technical conditions into consideration.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.1 -1			0	0	0
159	The staff is trained to handle equipment for clinical use.	159	There are guidelines for systematic training in handling of equipment for clinical use.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
160		160	There are easily accessible instructions and manuals for relevant equipment for clinical use in the departments.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.2-2;			0	0	0
161		161	Relevant staff is trained in handling equipment for clinical use.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.2-3;			0	0	0
162		162	It is documented that relevant staff has completed training in	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.2-4;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			handling high-risk equipment.												
163		163	If there are any lacks in completing the training of handling high-risk equipment, the hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the participation. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.2-5;			0	0	0
164	Equipment for clinical use is controlled, maintained, repaired and phased-out in accordance with stipulated plans.	164	There are guidelines for preventive maintenance and control of equipment for clinical use.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.3-1;			0	0	0
165		165	There are guidelines for handling of faulty equipment for clinical use.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.3-2;			0	0	0
166		166	Training of relevant clinical and technical staff in preventive maintenance, repair and control of equipment has been completed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.3-3;			0	0	0
167		167	Equipment for clinical use is controlled and maintained in accordance with the hospital's	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.3-4;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			guidelines.												
168		168	There is an updated registration of all equipment for clinical use and documentation of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> preventive maintenance and control within determined time frames repairs carried out expected service life of equipment any software changes 	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.3-5;			0	0	0
169		169	If any lacks are shown in relation to preventive maintenance and control, initiatives have been made to improve the quality. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7.3-6;			0	0	0
170	The organisation has a programme for medical gases, vacuum and compressed air.	170	Documented procedures govern procurement, handling, storage, distribution, usage and replenishment of medical gases.	FMS-5, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
171		171	Medical gases are handled, stored, distributed and used in a safe manner.	FMS-5, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
172		172	The procedures for medical gases address the safety issues at all levels.	FMS-5, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
173		173	Alternate sources for medical gases, vacuum and compressed air are provided for, in case of failure.	FMS-5, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
174		174	The organisation regularly tests these alternate sources.	FMS-5, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
175		175	There is an operational, inspection, testing and maintenance plan for, piped medical gas, compressed air and vacuum installation.	FMS-5, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
176	Medical gas systems are regularly inspected, maintained and when necessary improved.	176	Medical gas (oxygen, nitrous oxide and medical air) supplies are available according to the operational requirements of the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.2-1;
177		177	Medical gas supply systems comply with safety standards.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.2-2;
178		178	Where there is piped gas, the enclosure, gas bank, pressure regulators, related control/alarm systems and all outlet points are clean and in good operating condition.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.2-3;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
179		179	Where there is piped gas, the main oxygen supply system is fitted with an alarm, which operates automatically in the event of low pressure in the gas supply system and is regularly tested and documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.2-4;		
180		180	Documented testing of medical gas alarm systems is undertaken regularly according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.2-5;		
181		181	Backup supplies of medical gases are available and strategically positioned to ensure timely deployment in emergencies.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.2-6;		
182	Medical vacuum systems are regularly inspected and maintained.	182	Where there is a piped vacuum system, it is externally ventilated and able to provide sufficient suction to all piped vacuum points in the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.3-1;		
183		183	In the event of failure of the piped vacuum/suction facilities, backup facilities are provided in relevant services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31.2.3-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
184		184	Where there are no piped vacuum facilities installed, portable/ mobile vacuum/suction units are available and strategically positioned to ensure timely deployment in emergencies.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
185	The organisation has a plan for management of hazardous materials.	185	Hazardous materials are identified within the organisation.	FMS-7, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
186		186	The organisation implements processes for sorting, labelling, handling, storage, transporting and disposal of hazardous material.	FMS-7, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
187		187	Requisite regulatory requirements are met in respect of radioactive materials.	FMS-7, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
188		188	There is a plan for managing spills of hazardous materials.	FMS-7, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
189		189	Staff are educated and trained for handling such materials.	FMS-7, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
190	The hospital handles and disposes of waste, chemicals and isotopes in a healthrelated and safe manner.	190	There are guidelines for handling, storing and disposing waste material, including clinical hazardous waste.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.3.-1;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
191		191	There are guidelines for handling, storing and disposing chemicals and isotopes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.3.-2;			0	0	0
192		192	Clinical hazardous waste is handled in accordance with the the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.3.-3;			0	0	0
193		193	Chemicals and isotopes are handled in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.3.-4;			0	0	0
194	The hospital has documented control systems for the handling, storage and disposal of healthcare waste.	194	Waste is managed according to documented systems consistent with legislation, local by-laws and regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.5.1-1;		
195		195	Control systems include safe handling of different types of waste.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.5.1-2;		
196		196	Control systems include safe storage of different types of waste.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.5.1-3;		
197		197	Control systems include safe disposal of different types of waste.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.5.1-4;		
198		198	Control systems include the procedures to be adopted if spills occur.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.5.1-5;		
199		199	Control systems include the use of personal protective equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.5.1-6;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			when handling waste.												
200		200	There is a colour-coding system for bags to be used for the segregation of different types of waste.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.5.1-7;		
201	A documented plan to respond to emergencies is developed and rehearsed.	201	There is a documented plan to deal with internal and external emergencies.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.4.3-1;		
202		202	Documented evidence is available that personnel participate in a rehearsal of the plan at least annually.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.4.3-1;		
203	Adequate resources are available for the provision of safe care to patients in the ward and units.	203	Patient and personnel accommodation and equipment in the service are adequate to meet patient care needs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.1-1; 10.1.1-1; 11.1.1-1; 12.1.1-1; 13.1.1-1; 15.1.1-1; 16.1.1-1; 17.1.1-1; 18.1.1-1; 19.1.1-1; 20.1.1-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
204		204	Oxygen and vacuum supplies meet patient care requirements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.1-2; 10.1.1-2; 11.1.1-2; 12.1.1-2; 13.1.1-2; 15.1.1-2; 16.1.1-2; 17.1.1-2; 18.1.2-4;		
205		205	When patients receive oxygen from a cylinder, the cylinder pressures are monitored according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.1-3; 10.1.1-3; 11.1.1-3; 12.1.1-3; 13.1.1-3; 15.1.1-3; 16.1.1-3; 17.1.1-3; 18.1.2-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
206		206	There is evidence that equipment is maintained in accordance with hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.1-4; 10.1.1-4; 11.1.1-4; 12.1.1-4; 13.1.1-4; 15.1.1-4; 16.1.1-4; 17.1.1-4; 18.1.2-7;
207		207	Resuscitation equipment is available in accordance with hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.1-5; 10.1.1-5; 11.1.1-5; 12.1.1-5; 13.1.1-5; 15.1.1-5; 16.1.1-5; 17.1.1-5;
208		208	Each patient has access to a nurse call system at all times.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.1-6; 10.1.1-6; 11.1.1-6; 12.1.1-6; 13.1.1-6; 15.1.1-6; 16.1.1-6; 17.1.1-6; 18.1.2-8;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
209		209	There are isolation rooms available which comply with the minimum requirements for isolation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.1-7; 10.1.1-7; 11.1.1-7; 13.1.1-7; 15.1.1-7; 16.1.1-7; 17.1.1-7; 9.1.3-3; 12.1.2-3;		
210		210	Electricity and water are available in accordance with the hospital's arrangements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.1-8; 10.1.1-8; 11.1.1-8; 12.1.1-7; 13.1.1-8; 15.1.1-8; 17.1.1-8;		
211	Clinical areas within the emergency unit are adequate to meet the needs of patients.	211	Facilities allow privacy when providing personal information or undergoing examination or procedures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.1-2; 19.1.1-2; 20.1.1-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
212		212	Electricity and water are available in accordance with the hospital's arrangements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.1-3; 19.1.1-3; 20.1.1-3;
213		213	There is a waiting area for patients and families.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.1-4; 19.1.1-4; 20.1.1-4;
214		214	There is adequate seating in the waiting area.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.1-5; 19.1.1-5; 20.1.1-5;
215		215	Wheelchair-accessible toilets are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.1-6; 19.1.1-6; 20.1.1-6;
216		216	Quiet and private areas are available for waiting relatives and grieving or otherwise distressed relatives or carers.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.1-7; 20.1.1-7;
217		217	There is access to a functioning telephone facility for use by the public.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.1-8; 19.1.1-8; 20.1.1-8;
218		218	There is a designated triage area.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.2-1;
219		219	There is a designated resuscitation area.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.2-2;
220		220	There is a mechanism for summoning medical help in an emergency.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.2-3;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
221		221	There is adequate storage space to enable rapid retrieval and removal of equipment when needed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.2-6;		
222		222	There is a low pressure, hand-held shower suitable for the management of patients contaminated with hazardous materials.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.2-9;		
223		223	There is access to inpatient facilities consistent with the level of emergency care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.2-10;		
224		224	There is easy access to the operating theatre.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.2-11;		
225	Resuscitation equipment is available in accordance with the policies of the hospital in Emergency Unit.	225	Resuscitation equipment is available in accordance with hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.3-1;		
226		226	Recommended appliances are available for specialised resuscitations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.3-2;		
227		227	Diagnostic and vital sign monitoring equipment is available as per hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.3-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
228	There is a rest area for personnel in close proximity to the clinical areas in Emergency Unit, all other wards, units and OPD.	228	There is an adequately equipped kitchen, with at least a kettle, toaster and microwave.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.4-1; 20.1.4-1;
229		229	There are rest room facilities for personnel including a changing area, toilet and hand washing facilities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.4-2; 20.1.4-2;
230		230	Where personnel undertake 24 hour shifts, there are sleeping and shower facilities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.4-3; 20.1.4-3;
231		231	The rest area is equipped with a telephone or intercom system.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.1.4-4; 20.1.4-4;
232	Specific resources are available for the provision of safe care to patients in the Obstetric and Maternity unit/ Ward.	232	Available medical equipment complies with accepted norms for obstetric/maternity care services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.2-3;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
233		233	Where resuscitation, intensive care, life support or obstetric/maternity monitoring equipment is used that does not have built-in battery backup units, there is an uninterruptible power supply (UPS) that complies with relevant requirements and is regularly serviced and tested.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.2-4;		
234		234	Security measures are adequate to safeguard newborns, including identification of newborns and restricted access and exit monitoring in wards.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.2-5;		
235	Specific resources are available for the provision of safe care to patients in the Paediatric Ward.	235	Security measures are adequate to safeguard paediatric patients, including identification of children and restricted access and exit monitoring in wards.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.3-1;		
236		236	Single rooms are available that are large enough to accommodate parents/guardians who choose to stay with their children.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.3-2;		
237		237	There are isolation rooms available which comply with the minimum requirements for	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.3-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			isolation.												
238		238	A treatment room for patient assessment and procedures is provided separate from the other patients.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.3-4;		
239		239	Window guards are fitted and/or opening potential is limited on all windows.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.3-5;		
240		240	Electrical sockets are placed above child height and/or covered.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.3-6;		
241		241	Door latches and locks are located above child height.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.3-7;		
242		242	Floor surfaces are non-slippery and clear of clutter.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.3-8;		
243		243	Safety gates have small openings to prevent children getting through or being trapped.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.3-9;		
244		244	Restraining measures such as secure cot sides on cots and beds are used.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.3-10;		
245		245	Appropriate padding is available for sharp edges on furniture and equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.3-11;		
246		246	Where play/education area/s are available, age appropriate furniture and equipment are	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.3-12;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			provided.												
247	There is a dedicated area for the preparation of Infant Feeds.	247	Personnel working in the feed preparation area wear protective clothing such as gloves, masks and aprons.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.4-1;		
248		248	Appropriate hand washing facilities are available in the feed preparation area with appropriate disinfectant solutions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.4-2;		
249		249	Appropriate facilities and equipment to clean and disinfect utensils in the feed preparation area are available and functional.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.4-3;		
250		250	Information about disinfectant solutions and frequency of replacement in the feed preparation area is displayed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.4-4;		
251		251	There is clear signage of unauthorised entry on the door to limit people traffic.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.4-5;		
252		252	The storage cupboard for baby formula is clearly marked and locked.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.4-6;		
253	Facilities for safe surgical and anaesthetic care are provided and maintained.	253	The design of the theatre suite provides space for the reception, induction of anaesthesia, surgery, recovery and observation of patients.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.1-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
254		254	The theatre suite is equipped in accordance with approved requirement lists.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.1-2;		
255		255	There is direct access to the operating theatres from the receiving, scrubbing-up and recovery areas.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.1-3;		
256		256	There is safe and adequate storage space for pharmaceutical and surgical supplies.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.1-4;		
257		257	Access to the theatre suite is controlled.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.1-5;		
258		258	There is access to sterilisation and disinfection facilities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.1-6;		
259		259	There is a system for controlling the environmental temperature and humidity that ensures safe limits for anaesthetised patients in accordance with professional society guidelines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.1-7;		
260		260	Where resuscitation, intensive care, life support or critical monitoring equipment without built-in battery backup units is used, there is an uninterruptible power supply (UPS), which is regularly serviced and tested	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.1-8;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
261		261	There is either an UPS or a battery backup system for the theatre lamp, which is regularly tested, with such tests being fully documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.1-9;
262		262	The theatre has a refrigerator for medication, the temperature of which is measured and recorded daily.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.1-10;
263		263	Appropriate action is taken and recorded when the temperature of the refrigerator is outside the recommended range.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.1-11;
264	Recovery Room facilities and equipment are available to provide safe and effective care.	264	The recovery area forms part of the theatre suite.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.5-1;
265		265	There are an adequate number of recovery beds for the patients from the operating theatre.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.5-2;
266		266	There is adequate lighting.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.5-3;
267		267	The provision, use and maintenance of recovery room equipment comply with the guidelines for practice of the relevant professional society.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.5-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
268	Clinical areas within the outpatient department are adequate to meet the needs of patients.	268	There is a mechanism for the summoning of medical help in an emergency.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19.1.2-1; 23.2.2-1;		
269		269	Diagnostic and vital sign monitoring equipment is available as per hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19.1.2-5; 18.1.3-3; 20.1.3-3;		
270		270	There is adequate storage space to enable rapid retrieval and removal of equipment when needed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20.1.2-6; 19.1.2-6; 18.1.2-6;		
271		271	There is access to inpatient facilities consistent with the level of care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19.1.2-8;		
272	Required furniture and equipment are available and functional in Occupational Therapy Department	272	Occupational health offices are clearly sign-posted.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.2.1-1;		
273		273	There is a mechanism to prevent unauthorised individuals from entering the offices.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.2.1-2;		
274		274	There is a reception area for employees.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.2.1-3;		
275		275	There is adequate office space for administrative activities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.2.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
276		276	There is privacy for interviewing employees.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.2.1-5;		
277		277	Lockable facilities for storing personal clothing and property are provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.2.1-6;		
278		278	Ablution facilities are provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.2.1-7;		
279		279	Transport is available for occupational health personnel to perform their functions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.2.1-8;		
280		280	Facilities and equipment are maintained to provide clean and safe working conditions, which comply with relevant legislation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.2.1-9;		
281		281	Records of equipment maintenance are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.2.1-10;		
282	Resources are available to meet the treatment needs of the population served.	282	Each service has adequate space to treat patients effectively.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.3.1-1;		
283		283	There is adequate space for the storage of equipment and materials.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.3.1-2;		
284		284	Privacy is ensured through private cubicles, curtains or screens.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.3.1-3;		
285		285	There is an emergency call system for summoning of medical assistance.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.3.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
286		286	The audiology service has relevant equipment and materials to provide an effective service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.3.1-5;		
287		287	The clinical psychology service has relevant equipment and materials to provide an effective service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.3.1-6;		
288		288	The occupational therapy service has relevant equipment and materials to provide an effective service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.3.1-7;		
289		289	The physiotherapy service has relevant equipment and materials to provide an effective service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.3.1-8;		
290		290	The social work service has relevant equipment and materials to provide an effective service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.3.1-9;		
291		291	The speech therapy service has relevant equipment and materials to provide an effective service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.3.1-10;		
292		292	The prosthetics and orthotics service has relevant equipment and materials to provide an effective service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.3.1-11;		
293		293	The manager of each department ensures that equipment is included in the hospital's maintenance programme.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.3.1-12;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
294	Safe environment	294	The health service organisation maximises safety and quality of care: a. Through the design of the environment b. By maintaining buildings, plant, equipment, utilities, devices and other infrastructure that are fit for purpose	0	0	0	CGS-1.29,a, b			0	0	0	0	0	0
295		295	The health service organisation: a. Identifies service areas that have a high risk of unpredictable behaviours and develops strategies to minimise the risks of harm for patients, carers, families, consumers and the workforce b. Provides access to a calm and quiet environment when it is clinically required	0	0	0	CGS-1.30,a, b			0	0	0	0	0	0
296		296	The health service organisation facilitates access to services and facilities by using signage and directions that are clear and fit for purpose	0	0	0	CGS-1.31			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
297		297	The health service organisation admitting patients overnight has processes that allow flexible visiting arrangements to meet patients' needs, when it is safe to do so	0	0	0	CGS-1.32			0	0	0	0	0	0
298		298	The health service organisation demonstrates a welcoming environment that recognises the importance of the cultural beliefs and practices of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people	0	0	0	CGS-1.33			0	0	0	0	0	0
299	Where Information Technology equipment is available, it is properly maintained to meet the needs of the services.	299	A designated individual supervises the management of IT equipment in the organisation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.4.1-1;		
300		300	Technical IT support is provided in the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.4.1-2;		
301		301	Clinical and managerial personnel participate in IT decisions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.4.1-3;		
302		302	Policies and procedures that guide the management of IT equipment are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.4.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
303		303	All server computers are attached to an uninterrupted power supply (UPS) with surge protection.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.4.1-5;		
304		304	Records are kept of the maintenance of IT equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.4.1-6;		
305		305	There is a documented procedure known to personnel for reporting defects in IT equipment during and after normal working hours.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.4.1-7;		
306		306	Quality management processes are designed and implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.4.1-8;		
307	The use of organisational motor vehicles by personnel is planned and monitored to ensure safety and legality.	307	A specific manager is identified for the control, use and maintenance of vehicles.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.5.1-1;		
308		308	The ability of the transport service to meet the transport needs of the departments/services is evaluated on an annual basis and appropriate action taken when necessary.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.5.1-2;		
309		309	There is a system for monitoring the use of vehicles.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.5.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
310		310	There is a system for booking vehicles in advance.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.5.1-4;		
311		311	There is a control system for mileage travelled.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.5.1-5;		
312		312	There is a vehicle maintenance plan.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.5.1-6;		
313		313	There is proof of vehicle maintenance.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.5.1-7;		
314		314	There is proof of current licensing of vehicles.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.5.1-8;		
315		315	Drivers of vehicles are suitably licensed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.5.1-9;		
316		316	Drivers of vehicles are suitably insured.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.5.1-10;		
317		317	Quality management processes are designed and implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.5.1-11;		
318	Structural barriers to access to the hospital are identified and overcome or lessened.	318	Directional signage to the hospital is clearly visible from all main access roads.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.2-1;		
319		319	The name of the hospital and the services provided is clearly indicated on the site.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.2-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
320		320	Adequate parking is available for patients and visitors, including designated parking provision for disabled patients.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.2-3;		
321		321	Ramps and stairs include safety features such as rails where appropriate.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.2-4;		
322		322	Directional signage within the hospital includes local languages and relevant symbols.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.2-5;		
323		323	The hospital makes assistive mobility devices, e.g. wheelchairs, available for patients who require such assistance during their visit.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.2-6;		
324		324	There is access to and within the building for patients using assistive devices, e.g. wheelchairs, walking frames, etc.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.2-7;		
325		325	Lifts or ramps are available in multi-storey buildings for patients unable to use the stairs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.2-8;		

Table Number-8: Access to Care and Continuity of Care (ACC):

The Access to Care and Continuity of Care Chapter have 22 Standards and 113 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	The organisation defines and displays the healthcare services that it provides.	1	The healthcare services being provided are clearly defined and are in consonance with the needs of the community.	ACC-1, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2		2	Each defined service should have appropriate diagnostics and treatment facilities with suitably qualified personnel who provide out-patient, in-patient and emergency cover	ACC-1, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3		3	The defined healthcare services are prominently displayed	ACC-1, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4		4	The staff are oriented to these services.	ACC-1, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
5	The organisation has a well-defined registration and admission process.	5	Documented policies and procedures are used for registering and admitting patients.	ACC-2, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6		6	The documented procedures address out-patients, in-patients and emergency patients	ACC-2, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7		7	A unique identification number is generated at the end of registration	ACC-2, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8		8	Patients are accepted only if the organisation can provide the required service	ACC-2, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9		9	The documented policies and procedures also address managing patients during non-availability of beds	ACC-2, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10		10	Access to the healthcare services in the organisation is prioritised according to the clinical needs of the patient.	ACC-2, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11		11	The staff are aware of these processes.	ACC-2, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	There is a process for admitting patients to inpatient facilities.	12	There is a process known to personnel for admitting patients to the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.10.3-1; 19.8.2-1; 20.10.3-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
13		13	The unit which accepts the patient for admission is noted in the patient record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.10.3-2; 19.8.2-2; 20.10.3-2;		
14		14	The time that the patient is accepted to the inpatient unit and the time the patient is transferred are documented in the patient record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.10.3-3; 19.8.2-3; 20.10.3-3;		
15		15	Holding times in the unit while awaiting transfer are monitored.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.10.3-4; 19.8.2-4; 20.10.3-4;		
16		16	Policies and procedures that address the management of patients when bed space is not available in the desired service or unit or elsewhere in the hospital are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.10.3-5; 19.8.2-5; 20.10.3-5;		
17	Admission or transfer to units providing intensive or specialised services is determined by established criteria.	17	The hospital has established entry and/or transfer criteria for its oncology units, to meet specialised patient needs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.5-1;		
18		18	There are guidelines for the medical responsibility on admission and treatment in intensive therapy unit.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.5-2;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
19		19	The criteria are physiological where possible and appropriate.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.5-3;		
20		20	Appropriate individuals are involved in developing the criteria.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.5-4;		
21		21	Personnel are trained to apply the criteria.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.5-5;		
22		22	Patients transferred or admitted to intensive and specialised units/services meet the criteria, as documented in the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.5-6;		
23	There is a system to ensure that patients are seen within the shortest possible time in out-patients, units and wards.	23	There is a screening process to separate those patients requiring emergency care from those requiring only outpatient services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19.3.1-1; 20.5.3-1;		
24		24	There is a process of registration for outpatient care and treatment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19.3.1-2; 20.5.3-2;		
25		25	The outpatient register contains at least the patient's name, patient specific identification number, age, gender, date and time of attendance, treatment, procedures, referral or death.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19.3.1-3; 20.5.3-3;		
26		26	There is an appointment system for outpatient patients.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19.3.1-4; 20.5.3-4;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
27		27	Patients who are waiting are advised of any delays that may be experienced in receiving attention.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19.3.1-5; 20.5.3-5;		
28		28	Waiting times are monitored as part of the hospital's quality management and improvement programme.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19.3.1-6; 20.5.3-6;		
29		29	The hospital implements policies and procedures for assessing patients referred to therapeutic support services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.4.1-1;		
30	There is an appropriate mechanism for transfer (in and out) or referral of patients.	30	Documented policies and procedures guide the transfer-in of patients to the organisation.	ACC-3, a			0	0	0	2.17.4-1;			0	0	0
31		31	Documented policies and procedures guide the transfer-out/referral of unstable patients to another facility in an appropriate manner.	ACC-3, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
32		32	Documented policies and procedures guide the transfer- out/referral of stable patients to another facility in an appropriate manner.	ACC-3, c			0	0	0	2.17.4-2;			0	0	0
33		33	The documented procedures identify staff responsible during transfer/ referral.	ACC-3, d			0	0	0	2.3.2-2;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
34		34	The organisation gives a summary of patient's condition and the treatment given.	ACC-3, e			0	0	0	2.3.2-3;			0	0	0
35		35	The hospital has targets for the quality of the transfer between departments and hospitals, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.				0	0	0	2.17.4-3;			0	0	0
36		36	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the information on transfer between departments and hospitals. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.				0	0	0	2.17.4-4;			0	0	0
37	The hospital sets up and reports requirements to referrals from the primary sector.	37	There are guidelines for the content of referrals of acute as well as electively referred patients to the hospital's services.				0	0	0	2.4.1-1;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
38		38	Requirements to referrals are easily accessible for referring doctors, e.g. on hospital's websites or in relevant information systems for practises.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.3.2-4; 2.4.1-2;			0	0	0
39		39	The hospital has targets for the quality of the referrals and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.3.2-5; 2.4.1-3;			0	0	0
40		40	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the referrals. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.3.2-6; 2.4.1-4;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
41	There is a process known to personnel to refer patients for specialised consultation, investigations and/or treatment at other healthcare organisations.	41	Policies and procedures that guide the movement of patients for referral to another organisation are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.2-1; 10.7.2-1; 11.7.2-1; 12.7.2-1; 13.7.2-1; 15.7.2-1; 16.7.2-1; 17.7.2-1; 18.10.4-1; 19.8.3-1; 20.10.4-1;
42		42	A copy of the referral note is available in the patient record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.2-2; 10.7.2-2; 11.7.2-2; 12.7.2-2; 13.7.2-2; 15.7.2-2; 16.7.2-2; 17.7.2-2; 18.10.4-2; 19.8.3-2; 20.10.4-2;

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
43		43	Follow-up care based on the findings of investigations and/or consultations performed outside the referring hospital is documented in the patient record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.2-3; 10.7.2-3; 11.7.2-3; 12.7.2-3; 13.7.2-3; 15.7.2-3; 16.7.2-3; 17.7.2-3; 18.10.4-3; 19.8.3-3; 20.10.4-3;
44	The treatment of the electively referred patient is managed by a treatment plan systematically adjusted on the basis on an on-going assessment of the patient.	44	There is a description of which types of electively referred patients the hospital can receive.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.7-1;			0	0	0	
45		45	There are guidelines for reception and medical assessment of a referral.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.7-2;			0	0	0	

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
46		46	There are guidelines for letter of appointment of electively referred patients for treatment. The guidelines ensure that the content of the letters of appointment and the like meet the requirements in the legislation and the agreements. The guidelines ensure that time limits in the legislation and the agreements are met.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.7-3;			0	0	0
47		47	There are guidelines for preparation and content of a treatment plan for the individual electively referred patient. The treatment plan could be a standardised programme which to a relevant extent is adjusted in collaboration with the patient and relatives, if any.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.7-4;			0	0	0
48		48	There are guidelines for when to re-assess a treatment plan.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.7-5;			0	0	0
49		49	The hospital's description of the types of electively referred patient which can be received is public.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.7-6;			0	0	0
50		50	Medical assessment of received referrals takes place according to the hospital's guidelines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.7-7;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
51		51	Electively referred patients receive a letter of appointment for treatment in accordance with the hospital's guidelines and requirements in the legislation and agreements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.7-8;			0	0	0
52		52	There is a treatment plan for the individual patient. The treatment plan is prepared within the determined time frame stipulated by the hospital and meets the time limits in the legislation and agreements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.7-9;			0	0	0
53		53	The individual treatment plan is re-assessed according to the hospital's guidelines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.7-10;			0	0	0
54		54	The hospital has targets for the quality of the treatment of electively referred patients and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.7-11;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
55		55	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the treatment of electively referred patients. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.7-12;			0	0	0
56	There is a process to transfer patients to another healthcare organisation to meet their continuing needs.	56	There is a documented process for transferring patients to other healthcare organisations (for specialised and support services).	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.18.1-1; 2.18.1-4;			9.7.3-1; 10.7.3-1; 11.7.3-1; 12.7.3-1; 13.7.3-1; 15.7.3-1; 16.7.3-1; 17.7.3-1; 18.10.5-1; 19.8.4-1; 20.10.5-1;		
57		57	Patients are stabilised according to appropriate clinical guidelines prior to transfer.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.10.5-2; 20.10.5-2;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
58		58	The transferring hospital determines that the receiving healthcare organisation can meet the patient's continuing care needs and establishes arrangements to ensure continuity.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.18.1-3;			18.10.5-3; 19.8.4-2; 20.10.5-3;		
59		59	The process for transferring the patient considers transportation needs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.10.5-4; 19.8.4-3; 20.10.5-4;		
60		60	A policy that requires the responsible clinician to communicate the level of care required to Emergency Medical (ambulance) services is implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.18.1-2;			18.10.5-5; 20.10.5-5;		
61		61	The process determines that patients are accompanied and monitored by an appropriately qualified person during transfer.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.18.1-2; 2.18.1-6;			18.10.5-6; 19.8.4-4; 20.10.5-6;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
62		62	When a patient is transferred to another healthcare organisation, the receiving organisation is given a written summary of the patient's clinical condition and the interventions provided by the referring hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.3-2; 10.7.3-2; 11.7.3-2; 12.7.3-2; 13.7.3-2; 15.7.3-2; 16.7.3-2; 17.7.3-2; 18.10.5-7; 19.8.4-5; 20.10.5-7;
63		63	A copy of the transfer summary is available in the patient record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.3-3; 10.7.3-3; 11.7.3-3; 12.7.3-3; 13.7.3-3; 15.7.3-3; 16.7.3-3; 17.7.3-3; 18.10.5-8; 19.8.4-6; 20.10.5-8;

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
64		64	The hospital agreeing to receive the patient is noted in the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.3-4; 10.7.3-4; 11.7.3-4; 12.7.3-4; 13.7.3-4; 15.7.3-4; 16.7.3-4; 17.7.3-4; 18.10.5-9; 19.8.4-7; 20.10.5-9;
65	Patient care is continuous multidisciplinary and in nature.	65	During all phases of care, there is a qualified individual identified as responsible for the patient's care.	ACC-12, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
66		66	Information about the patient's care and response to treatment is shared among medical, nursing and other care-providers.	ACC-12, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
67		67	Information is exchanged and documented during each staffing shift, between shifts, and during transfers between units/departments.	ACC-12, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
68		68	Transfers between departments/ units are done in a safe manner.	ACC-12, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
69		69	The patient's record(s) is available to the authorised care-providers to facilitate the exchange of information.	ACC-12, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
70		70	The organisation has a mechanism in place to monitor whether adequate clinical intervention has taken place in response to a critical value alert.	ACC-12, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
71	Collaboration and teamwork	71	The health service organisation has processes to: a. Support multidisciplinary collaboration and teamwork b. Define the roles and responsibilities of each clinician working in a team	0	0	0	CCS-5.5, a,b			0	0	0	0	0	0
72		72	Clinicians work collaboratively to plan and deliver comprehensive care	0	0	0	CCS-5.6			0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
73	Designing systems to deliver comprehensive care	73	The health service organisation has systems for comprehensive care that: a. Support clinicians to develop, document and communicate comprehensive plans for patients' care and treatment b. Provide care to patients in the setting that best meets their clinical needs c. Ensure timely referral of patients with specialist healthcare needs to relevant services d. Identify, at all times, the clinician with overall accountability for a patient's care	0	0	0	CCS-5.4, a,b,c,d				0	0	0	0	0	0
74	The service is organised to provide a safe and effective service and is coordinated with other relevant services.	74	An on-call roster is available for after-hours, weekend and holiday emergency cover (e.g. for infectious diseases).	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.1.1-3;

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
75	The hospital designs and implements processes to provide continuity of patient care services within the hospital and coordination among health professionals.	75	Policies and procedures that guide the movement of patients within the hospital are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.1-1; 10.7.1-1; 11.7.1-1; 12.7.1-1; 13.7.1-1; 15.7.1-1; 16.7.1-1; 17.7.1-1;		
76		76	Documentation regarding the transfer of a patient from the forensic service to another service within the hospital meets legal requirements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.7.1-1;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
77	Developing the comprehensive care plan	77	Clinicians use processes for shared decision making to develop and document a comprehensive and individualised plan that: a. Addresses the significance and complexity of the patient's health issues and risks of harm b. Identifies agreed goals and actions for the patient's treatment and care c. Identifies the support people a patient wants involved in communications and decision-making about their care d. Commences discharge planning at the beginning of the episode of care e. Includes a plan for referral to follow-up services, if appropriate and available f. Is consistent with best practice and evidence	0	0	0	CCS-5.13, a,b,c,d,e, f			0	0	0	0	0	0
78	The organisation has a documented discharge process.	78	The patient's discharge process is planned in consultation with the patient and/or family.	ACC-13, a			0	0	0	2.17.2-1; 2.17.5-1; 2.17.5-3;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
79		79	Documented procedures exist for coordination of various departments and agencies involved in the discharge process (including medico-legal and absconded cases).	ACC-13, b			0	0	0	2.17.5-2;			0	0	0
80		80	Documented policies and procedures are in place for patients leaving against medical advice and patients being discharged on request.	ACC-13, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
81		81	A discharge summary is given to all the patients leaving the organisation (including patients leaving against medical advice and on request).	ACC-13, d			0	0	0	2.17.2-2;			0	0	0
82		82	The organisation defines the time taken for discharge and monitors the same.	ACC-13, e			0	0	0	2.17.2-3; 2.17.2-4;			0	0	0
83		83	The hospital has targets for the quality of discharge planning in collaboration with the patient and the hospital assesses whether the goal/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.				0	0	0	2.17.5-4;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
84		84	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of discharge by planning in collaboration with the patient. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.17.5-5;			0	0	0
85	Organisation defines the content of the discharge summary.	85	Discharge summary is provided to the patients at the time of discharge.	ACC-14, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
86		86	Discharge summary contains the patient's name, unique identification number, date of admission and date of discharge.	ACC-14, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
87		87	Discharge summary contains the reasons for admission, significant findings and diagnosis and the patient's condition at the time of discharge.	ACC-14, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
88		88	Discharge summary contains information regarding investigation results, any procedure performed, medication administered and other treatment given.	ACC-14, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
89		89	Discharge summary contains follow-up advice, medication and other instructions in an understandable manner.	ACC-14, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
90		90	Discharge summary incorporates instructions about when and how to obtain urgent care.	ACC-14, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
91		91	In case of death, the summary of the case also includes the cause of death.	ACC-14, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
92		92	The hospital has targets for the deadlines for forwarding of discharge letters in accordance with national and regionally determined targets. The hospital observes the deadlines for forwarding discharge letters on an on-going basis.				0	0	0	2.17.2-4;			0	0	0
93		93	The hospital has targets for the quality of the content of discharge letters and the hospital assesses whether the targets/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.				0	0	0	2.17.2-5;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
94		94	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the discharge letters. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.17.2-6;			0	0	0
95	There is an organised process to discharge patients from wards and Emergency Department	95	There is a documented process to discharge patients.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.4-1; 10.7.4-1; 11.7.4-1; 12.7.4-1; 13.7.4-1; 15.7.4-1; 16.7.4-1; 17.7.4-1; 18.10.6-1; 19.8.5-1; 20.10.6-1;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
96		96	Where the initial assessment indicates that discharge planning will be required, planning requirements are included in the patient's care plan and completed as scheduled.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.4-2; 10.7.4-2; 11.7.4-2; 12.7.4-2; 13.7.4-2; 15.7.4-2; 16.7.4-2; 17.7.4-2;		
97		97	The hospital works with the family, caregivers, healthcare practitioners and agencies outside the hospital to ensure timely and appropriate discharge.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.4-3; 10.7.4-3; 11.7.4-3; 12.7.4-3; 13.7.4-3; 15.7.4-3; 16.7.4-3; 17.7.4-3; 18.10.6-2; 19.8.5-2; 20.10.6-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
98		98	Patients and where appropriate their families or caregivers are given understandable follow-up instructions which are documented in the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.4-4; 10.7.4-4; 11.7.4-4; 12.7.4-4; 13.7.4-4; 15.7.4-4; 16.7.4-4; 17.7.4-4; 18.10.6-3; 19.8.5-3; 20.10.6-3;
99		99	A discharge summary is written by the medical practitioner when each patient is discharged.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.4-5; 10.7.4-5; 11.7.4-5; 12.7.4-5; 13.7.4-5; 15.7.4-5; 16.7.4-5; 17.7.4-5; 18.10.6-4; 19.8.5-4; 20.10.6-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
100		100	Each record contains a copy of the discharge summary.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.4-6; 11.7.4-6; 12.7.4-6; 13.7.4-6; 15.7.4-6; 16.7.4-6; 17.7.4-6; 18.10.6-5; 19.8.5-5; 20.10.6-5;
101	A system of visitor control is maintained to ensure the safety of patients and personnel.	101	The hospital's policy on visitors to the emergency department is implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.4.1-1; 20.4.1-1;
102		102	There is a system to inform patients and family of the visitors' policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.4.1-2; 20.4.1-2;
103		103	Areas where access is denied to persons other than personnel are clearly marked.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.4.1-3; 20.4.1-3;
104		104	The discretionary powers of personnel in charge of the service relating to visitors under special circumstances are documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.4.1-4; 20.4.1-4;
105		105	Policies regarding media invasion are implemented to guide clinical and security personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.4.1-5; 20.4.1-5;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
106	The hospital has established processes for admitting inpatients and registering ambulatory patients.	106	Admission and registration processes are standardised throughout the hospital by means of the development and implementation of policies and procedures .	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.4-1;		
107		107	Policies and procedures for the management of patients deceased prior to arrival are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.4-2;		
108		108	General consent / acknowledgement of admission requirements is obtained when patients enter the hospital according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.4-3;		
109		109	Written consent for the taking and/or publishing of photographic images is obtained from personnel, volunteers, patients and visitors prior to such images being taken.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.4-4;		
110		110	Patients receive information on the hospital's level of responsibility for patients' possessions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.4-5;		
111	The hospital seeks to identify and reduce barriers to access and delivery of services.	111	The hospital has identified barriers to accessing healthcare services in its catchment population.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.1-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
112		112	There is a process to limit the impact of barriers on access to the services provided by the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.1-2;		
113		113	The hospital has access to ambulance services appropriate for the level of care provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.1-3;		

Table Number-9: Emergency Department (ED):

The Emergency Department Chapter has 10 Standards and 55 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	Emergency services are guided by documented policies, procedures, applicable laws and regulations.	1	There shall be an identified area in the organisation which is easily accessible to receive and manage emergency patients.	COP-2, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2		2	Policies and procedures for emergency care are documented and are in consonance with statutory requirements.	COP-2, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3		3	This also addresses the handling of medico-legal cases.	COP-2, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4		4	The patients receive care in consonance with the policies.	COP-2, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5		5	Staff are familiar with the policies and trained on the procedures for care of emergency patients.	COP-2, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
6		6	Admission or discharge to home or transfer to another organisation is also documented.	COP-2, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.3-7;		
7		7	In case of discharge to home or transfer to another organisation, a discharge note shall be given to the patient.	COP-2, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8		8	Quality assurance programmes are documented and implemented.	COP-2, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9		9	The documented policies and procedures guide management of patients found dead on arrival to the hospital.	COP-2, j			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	Patient registers are kept in accordance with country-specific requirements and/or hospital policy.	10	A register is kept of patients attending the emergency unit.				0	0	0	0	0	0	18.2.1-1; 20.2.1-1;		
11		11	The register contains at least the patient's name, patient-specific identification number, age, gender, date and time of admission, treatment, procedures, discharge, referral or death.				0	0	0	0	0	0	18.2.1-2; 20.2.1-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
12		12	The information in the register is used to monitor waiting periods from time of arrival to time of assessment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.2.1-3; 20.2.1-3;
13	During all phases of care, there are qualified individuals responsible for the patient's care.	13	During the hours of operation there is an adequate number of qualified professionals available to provide continuous cover to all sections at all times.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.3.1-5;
14		14	Emergency services personnel maintain skills in advanced life support in accordance with hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.3.1-6;
15		15	Medical cover is reflected on a roster and each practitioner on the roster is contactable by telephone, pager or other two-way communication method.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.3.1-7;
16	The hospital has a formal triage process which uses documented guidelines to determine urgency	16	Documented policies and procedures guide the triage of patients for initiation of appropriate care.	COP-2, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.3-3;
17		17	The unit implements an evidence-based triage system.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.3-3; 18.5.1-1; 20.5.1-1;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
18		18	All personnel responsible for patient triage have received training in the application of the triage system.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.5.1-2; 20.5.1-2;
19		19	Clinical records of emergency patients include the time of arrival.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.5.1-3; 20.5.1-3;
20		20	The triage category for each patient is recorded.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.5.1-4; 20.5.1-4;
21		21	Clinical records of emergency patients include time of referral to medical practitioner.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.5.1-5; 20.5.1-5;
22		22	Waiting times from triage categorisation to initial assessment are monitored.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.5.1-6; 20.5.1-6;
23		23	Patients identified by triage as having emergency or immediate needs are prioritised for assessment and intervention according to established criteria.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.3-4;
24	Patients being transferred from the Emergency Unit to the operating theatre are appropriately prepared.	24	The indication for surgery is recorded before anaesthesia.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.7.4-1;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
25		25	Policies that address nursing preparation of patients being transferred to the operating theatre are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.7.4-2;
26		26	Patients being transferred to the operating theatre are accompanied by an appropriately qualified person, as determined by hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.7.4-3;
27	The hospital implements policies for the management of patients requiring short-term observation and care.	27	Policies and procedures that address the holding of patients for observation are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.10.2-1; 20.10.2-1;
28		28	The hospital has established appropriate time frames which limit holding time in the emergency unit.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.10.2-2; 20.10.2-2;
29		29	Patients under observation are reassessed at appropriate intervals to determine their response to care and treatment and this is documented in the record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.10.2-3; 20.10.2-3;
30		30	Any significant changes in the patient's condition are noted in the patient's record and	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.10.2-4; 20.10.2-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			acted upon appropriately.												
31		31	Any patient care meetings or other discussions are noted in the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
32		32	Holding times are monitored and audited.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
33	Transport of patients who need a health professional person to accompany them so it is a safe transport with a competent health professional person.	33	Emergency patients who require transfer to another hospital for appropriate services are stabilised prior to transfer.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
34	The organisation plans for handling community emergencies, epidemics and other disasters.	34	The organisation identifies potential emergencies.	COP-4, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
35		35	The organisation has a documented disaster management plan.	COP-4, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
36		36	Provision is made for availability of medical supplies, equipment and materials during such emergencies.	COP-4, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
37		37	Staff are trained in the hospital's disaster management plan.	COP-4, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
38		38	The plan is tested at least twice a year.	COP-4, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
39	Where the hospital provides an ambulance service, this service is delivered in line with relevant laws and regulations.	39	The hospital has a written response and deployment plan including the identification of response areas and availability of response units.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.11.1-1; 20.11.1-1;		
40		40	Response time standards are monitored against national laws, regulations, policies or guidelines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.11.1-2; 20.11.1-2;		
41		41	The hospital designs and implements processes to provide coordination of services among other hospitals and agencies in the community.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.11.1-3; 20.11.1-3;		
42		42	The individuals responsible for management of the ambulance service develop a list of the equipment required for each ambulance in collaboration with other relevant services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.11.1-4; 20.11.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
43		43	The individuals who provide patient care in the ambulance service have the required training and experience.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.11.1-5; 20.11.1-5;		
44		44	The hospital plans and implements processes for inspecting, testing and maintaining equipment and supplies.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.11.1-6; 20.11.1-6;		
45		45	The hospital maintains its ambulance vehicles to reduce risk and promote safety.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.11.1-7; 20.11.1-7;		
46		46	Medical transport/ambulance vehicles are cleaned in accordance with hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.11.1-8; 20.11.1-8;		
47	The ambulance services are commensurate with the scope of the services provided by the organisation.	47	There is adequate access and space for the ambulance(s).	COP-3, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48		48	The ambulance adheres to statutory requirements.	COP-3, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
49		49	The ambulance(s) is appropriately equipped.	COP-3, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
50		50	The ambulance(s) is manned by trained and experienced	COP-3, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			personnel.												
51		51	The ambulance(s) is checked on a daily basis.	COP-3, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
52		52	Equipments are checked on a daily basis using a checklist.	COP-3, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
53		53	Emergency medications are checked daily and prior to dispatch using a checklist.	COP-3, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
54		54	The ambulance(s) has a proper communication system.	COP-3, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
55		55	The emergency department identifies opportunities to initiate treatment at the earliest when the patient is in transit to the organisation.	COP-3, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Table Number-10: Management of Information (MOI):

The Management of Information has 15 Standards and 103 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	Documented policies and procedures exist to meet the information needs of the care providers, management of the organisation as well as other agencies that require data and information from the organisation.	1	The information needs of the organisation are identified and are appropriate to the scope of the services being provided by the organisation.	IMS-1, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2		2	Documented policies and procedures to meet the information needs exist.	IMS-1, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3		3	All information management and technology acquisitions are in accordance with the documented policies and procedures.	IMS-1, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
4		4	Documented policies and procedures guide the use of Telemedicine facility in a safe and secure manner.	IMS-1, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5		5	The organisation contributes to external databases in accordance with the law and regulations.	IMS-1, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6		6	Information systems are developed and implemented in the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.1.1-1;
7		7	The senior management team, in collaboration with all departments, identify key indicators and other information required to monitor quality assurance and improvement processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.1.1-2;
8		8	Clinical and managerial personnel participate in information technology decisions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.1.1-3;
9	The organisation has processes in place for effective control and management of data.	9	The organisation has an effective process for document control.	IMS-2, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10		10	Formats for data collection are standardized.	IMS-2, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
11		11	Necessary resources are available for analyzing data.	IMS-2, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12		12	Documented procedures are laid down for timely and accurate dissemination of data.	IMS-2, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13		13	Documented procedures exist for storing and retrieving data.	IMS-2, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14		14	Appropriate clinical and managerial staff participates in selecting, integrating and using data.	IMS-2, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	The organisation has a complete and accurate medical record for every patient.	15	Every medical record has a unique identifier.	IMS-3, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16		16	Organisation policy identifies those authorized to make entries in medical record.	IMS-3, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17		17	Entry in the medical record is named, signed, dated and timed.	IMS-3, c			0	0	0	1.3.2-6;			0	0	0
18		18	The author of the entry can be identified.	IMS-3, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19		19	The contents of medical record are identified and documented.	IMS-3, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
20		20	The organisation has a documented policy for usage of abbreviations and develops a list	IMS-3, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			based on accepted practices.												
21		21	The record provides a complete, up-to-date and chronological account of patient care.	IMS-3, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
22		22	Provision is made for 24-hour availability of the patient's record to healthcare providers to ensure continuity of care.	IMS-3, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
23	The medical record reflects continuity of care.	23	The medical record contains information regarding reasons for admission, diagnosis and care plan.	IMS-4, a			0	0	0	1.3.2-3; 1.3.2-4;			0	0	
24		24	The medical record contains the results of tests carried out and the care provided.	IMS-4, b			0	0	0	1.3.2-3; 1.3.2-4;			0	0	
25		25	Operative and other procedures performed are incorporated in the medical record.	IMS-4, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
26		26	When patient is transferred to another hospital, the medical record contains the date of transfer, the reason for the transfer and the name of the receiving hospital.	IMS-4, d			0	0	0	1.3.2-3; 1.3.2-4;			0	0	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
27		27	The medical record contains a copy of the discharge summary duly signed by appropriate and qualified personnel.	IMS-4, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28		28	In case of death, the medical record contains a copy of the cause of death certificate.	IMS-4, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29		29	Whenever a clinical autopsy is carried out, the medical record contains a copy of the report of the same.	IMS-4, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30		30	Care providers have access to current and past medical record.	IMS-4, h			0	0	0	1.3.2-5;			0	0	0
31	Documented policies and procedures are in place for maintaining confidentiality, integrity and security of records, data and information.	31	A designated individual with appropriate training and experience is responsible for information management systems.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.1.2-1;		
32		32	Documented policies and procedures exist for maintaining confidentiality, security and integrity of records, data and information.	IMS-5, a			0	0	0	1.3.5-1;			0	0	0
33		33	Documented policies and procedures are in consonance with the applicable laws.	IMS-5, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
34		34	The policies and procedure(s) incorporate safeguarding of data/record against loss, destruction and tampering.	IMS-5, c			0	0	0	1.3.5-2; 1.3.5-4;			0	0	0
35		35	The organisation has an effective process of monitoring compliance of the laid down policy and procedure.	IMS-5, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
36		36	The organisation uses developments in appropriate technology for improving confidentiality, integrity and security.	IMS-5, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
37		37	Privileged health information is used for the purposes identified or as required by law and not disclosed without the patient's authorisation.	IMS-5, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
38		38	A documented procedure exists on how to respond to patients/physicians and other public agencies requests for access to information in the medical record in accordance with the local and national law.	IMS-5, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
39		39	Confidentiality of data and information is maintained	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.1.2-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
40		40	Security and integrity of data and information is maintained	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
41	Documented policies and procedures exist for retention time of records, data and information.	41	Documented policies and procedures are in place on retaining the patient's clinical records, data and information.	IMS-6, a			0	0	0	1.3.2-1;			0	0	0
42		42	The policies and procedures are in consonance with the local and national laws and regulations.	IMS-6, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
43		43	The retention process provides expected confidentiality and security.	IMS-6, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
44		44	The destruction of medical records, data and information is in accordance with the laid-down policy.	IMS-6, d			0	0	0	1.3.5-2;			0	0	0
45	The organisation regularly carries out review of medical records.	45	The medical records are reviewed periodically.	IMS-7, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
46		46	The review uses a representative sample based on statistical principles.	IMS-7, b			0	0	0	1.3.2-7;			0	0	0
47		47	The review is conducted by identified individuals. .	IMS-7, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48		48	The review focuses on the timeliness, legibility and completeness of the medical	IMS-7, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			records.												
49		49	The review process includes records of both active and discharged patients.	IMS-7, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
50		50	The review points out and documents any deficiencies in records.	IMS-7, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
51		51	Appropriate corrective and preventive measures are undertaken within a defined period of time and are documented.	IMS-7, g			0	0	0	1.3.2-8;			0	0	0
52	The organisation establishes, implements and maintains procedures for controlling relevant documents and data.	52	Documents and information are periodically reviewed and revised as necessary and approved by an authorised person.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.2-2;			21.7.2-2;		
53		53	Obsolete documents and information are promptly marked as such and removed from all points of issue and points of use or otherwise assured against unintended use.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.7.2-3;		
54		54	Archival documents and information retained for legal or knowledge preservation purposes or both are suitably identified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.7.2-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
55	The hospital minimises the consequences of failure of technical patient-critical supplies plus IT- and communication systems.	55	In each department there are guidelines describing tasks and duties in connection with failure of technical patient-critical supplies plus IT and communication systems.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.5-1;			0	0	0
56		56	Managers and staff are familiar with their own duties and responsibilities in case of breakdown of technical patient-critical supplies.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.5-2;			0	0	0
57		57	Managers and staff are familiar with their own duties and responsibilities in case of breakdown of patient critical IT systems.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.5-3;			0	0	0
58		58	Managers and staff are familiar with their own duties and responsibilities in case of breakdown of patient critical communication systems.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.5-4;			0	0	0
59		59	After events causing major breakdown of technical patient-critical supplies and IT- and communication systems, reports are prepared where the event is analysed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.5-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
60		60	If the reports show lacks in handling breakdown of technical patient-critical supplies and IT- and communication systems, initiatives have been implemented to improve the quality.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8.5-6;			0	0	0
61	Policies and Procedures	61	The hospital's leaders ensure that policies and procedures guide and support the activities and management of the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.1-1;			1.2.6-1; 29.3.1-1;		
62		62	The departmental manager ensures that policies and procedures are implemented in the department.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.3.1-1;		
63		63	Policies and procedures guide the retention and destruction of all hospital documentation, including patient-related information, legal, managerial and research documentation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.1-2;			1.2.6-2;		
64		64	A designated manager is responsible for compiling and indexing policies and procedures and ensuring their circulation, recall, archiving and review.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.1-3;			1.2.6-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
65		65	Policies and procedures are signed by persons authorised to do so.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.1-4;			1.2.6-4; 26.2.1-1; 29.3.1-2; 30.3.1-2;		
66		66	Policies and procedures are compiled into a comprehensive manual(s) or filing system (paper-based and/or electronic) which is indexed and easily accessible to all personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.1-4;			1.2.6-5; 26.2.1-2; 29.3.1-3; 30.3.1-3;		
67		67	All policies and procedures are reviewed at appropriate intervals, dated and signed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.1-3;			1.2.6-6; 26.2.1-3; 29.3.1-4; 30.3.1-4;		
68		68	There is a mechanism to ensure that policies are known and implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.1-5;			1.2.6-7;		
69		69	Outdated policies and procedures are recalled and archived according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.3.1-5; 30.3.1-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
70	Healthcare Records and Data Safety	70	The health service organisation has healthcare record systems that: a. Make the healthcare record available to clinicians at the point of care b. Support the workforce to maintain accurate and complete healthcare records c. Comply with security and privacy regulations d. Support systematic audit of clinical information e. Integrate multiple information systems, where they are used	0	0	0	CGS-1.16, a,b,c,d, e			0	0	0	0	0	0
71		71	The health service organisation works towards implementing systems that can provide clinical information that: a. Are designed to optimise the safety and quality of health care for patients b. Use national patient and provider identifiers c. Use standard national terminologies	0	0	0	CGS-1.17, a,b,c			1.3.5-3;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
72		72	The health service organisation providing clinical information that: a. Describe access to the system by the workforce, to comply with legislative requirements b. Maintain the accuracy and completeness of the clinical information the organisation uploads into the system	0	0	0	CGS-1.18, a,b			1.3.5-3;			0	0	0
73		73	There are guidelines for data safety. The guidelines are based on a risk assessment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.1.5-1;			0	0	0
74		74	Managers and staff are familiar with relevant parts of the guidelines and work accordingly.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.1.5-2;			0	0	0
75		75	There is documentation for completed backup of data systems.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.1.5-3;			0	0	0
76		76	It is documented that emergency procedures upon system failure are tested at regular intervals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.1.5-4;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
77		77	If there are lacks in the backup procedures or emergency procedures upon system failure, initiatives have been made to improve the quality. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed, and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.1.5-5;			0	0	0
78		78	The hospital maintains a clinical record for each patient.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.2-3		
79		79	The patients' clinical records are completed according to guidelines determined by the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.2-4		
80	There is a system for the management of health records, which meets confidentiality and safety requirements.	80	A designated individual with appropriate training and/or experience is responsible for the storage, maintenance and retrieval of health records.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.3.1-1;		
81		81	The health record manager ensures that policies and procedures are available to guide personnel and that they are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.3.1-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
82		82	All patient documents, including medical, nursing and other health professional notes, diagnostic test results, referral letters, etc. are filed in the correct record, chronologically and in a standardised manner.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.3.1-3;		
83		83	There is a system that allows for the rapid retrieval and distribution of health records.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.3.1-4;		
84		84	There is a communication system for the requesting of health records.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.3.1-5;		
85		85	There is an effective monitoring system whereby records can be traced within the facility at all times.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.3.1-6;		
86		86	The filing system allows for incorrectly filed records to be easily identified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.3.1-7;		
87		87	There is provision for authorised access to health records at all times.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.3.1-8;		
88		88	All storage areas for health records are secured against unauthorised entry.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.3.1-9;		
89		89	Quality management processes are designed and implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.3.1-10;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
90	Information management systems are implemented and supported by sufficient personnel and other resources.	90	Sufficient personnel support implementation of the information management system.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.1.3-1;
91		91	Decision-makers and others are provided with appropriate training in the principles of information management	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.1.3-2;
92	The hospital has a process to aggregate data for user needs.	92	The hospital has a process to aggregate data.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.2.1-1;
93		93	Clinical and managerial data and information are integrated as needed to support decision making.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.2.1-2;
94		94	Aggregated data and information are used to support patient care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.2.1-3;
95		95	Aggregated data and information are used to support management of the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.2.1-4;
96		96	Aggregated data and information are used to support the quality management programmes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.2.1-5;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
97		97	Appropriate data is collected and used to study areas targeted for improvement.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.2.1-6;		
98		98	Appropriate data is collected and used to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of interventions implemented to achieve improvements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.2.1-7;		
99		99	The results of these monitoring activities are communicated to the leaders and governance structure of the hospital and to other relevant stakeholders, such as departmental personnel responsible for the process under consideration.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.2.1-8;		
100	The hospital contributes to external databases	100	The hospital has a process to participate in and/or use information from external databases.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.2.2-1;		
101		101	Data or information is contributed to external databases as required by law or regulation, where applicable.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.2.2-2;		
102		102	Notifiable diseases are reported within an acceptable time frame, according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.2.2-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
103		103	The hospital compares its performance with that of other, similar hospitals, using external reference databases.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.2.2-4;		

Table Number-11: Patient and Family Rights (PFR):

The Patient and Family Rights have 27 Standards and 123 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	The organisation protects patient and family rights and informs them about their responsibilities during care.	1	Patient and family rights and responsibilities are documented and displayed.	PRE-1, a			0	0	0	2.2.2-3;			0	0	0
2		2	Patients and families are informed of their rights and responsibilities in a format and language that they can understand.	PRE-1, b			0	0	0	2.2.2-3;			4.6.1-4;		
3		3	The organisation's leaders protect patient and family rights.	PRE-1, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4		4	Staff are aware of their responsibility in protecting patient and family rights.	PRE-1, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
5		5	Violation of patient and family rights is recorded, reviewed and corrective/preventive measures taken.	PRE-1, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	Patient and family rights support individual beliefs, values and involve the patient and family in decision making processes.	6	Patients and family rights include respecting any special preferences, spiritual and cultural needs.	PRE-2, a			0	0	0	2.1.4-1;			0	0	0
7		7	Patient and family rights include respect for personal dignity and privacy during examination, procedures and treatment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.4-3;			0	0	0
8		8	Patient and family rights include protection from neglect or abuse.	PRE-2, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9		9	Patient and family rights include treating patient information as confidential.	PRE-2, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10		10	Patient and family rights include refusal of treatment.	PRE-2, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11		11	Patient and family have a right to seek an additional opinion regarding clinical care.	PRE-2, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
12		12	Patient and family rights include informed consent before transfusion of blood and blood components, anaesthesia, surgery, initiation of any research protocol and any other invasive / high risk procedures / treatment.	PRE-2, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13		13	Patient and family rights include right to complain and information on how to voice a complaint	PRE-2, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14		14	Patient and family rights include information on the expected cost of the treatment.	PRE-2, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.1-3;		
15		15	Patient and family rights include access to his / her clinical records.	PRE-2, j			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16		16	Patient and family rights include information on Care plan, progress and information on their health care needs.	PRE-2, k			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17		17	Relevant written material for patients and/or relatives will be handed out.				0	0	0	2.2.2-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
18	Patient and families have a right to information and education about their healthcare needs.	18	Patient and/or family are educated about the safe and effective use of medication and the potential side effects of the medication, when appropriate.	PRE-5, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19		19	Patient and/or family are educated about food-drug interaction	PRE-5, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
20		20	Patient and/or family are educated about diet and nutrition.	PRE-5, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	28.9.1-1;		
21		21	Patient and/or family are educated about immunisations.	PRE-5, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
22		22	Patient and/or family are educated about their specific disease process, complications and prevention strategies.	PRE-5, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
23		23	Patient and/or family are educated about preventing healthcare associated infections.	PRE-5, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
24		24	The patients and/or family members' special educational needs are identified and addressed.	PRE-5, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
25		25	Patient and/or family are educated in a language and format that they can understand.	PRE-5, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
26		26	Patient and/or family are receives information about the name of the healthcare professional contact person	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.3.2-2;			0	0	0
27	Patients and families have a right to information on expected costs.	27	There is a uniform pricing policy in a given setting (out-patient and ward category).	PRE-6, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28		28	The relevant tariff list is available to patients.	PRE-6, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29		29	The patient and/or family members are explained about the expected costs.	PRE-6, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
30		30	Patient and/or family are informed about the financial implications when there is a change in the patient condition or treatment setting.	PRE-6, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.1-3; 10.4.2.4; 11.4.2-4; 12.4.2.-4; 13.4.2-4; 15.4.2-4; 16.4.2-4; 17.4.2-4; 18.9.1-4; 19.7.1-4; 20.9.1-4; 26.5.1-3;			
31	The hospital informs patients and families about its process to receive and act on complaints, conflicts and differences of opinion about patient care and the patient's right to participate in these processes.	31	Policies and procedures relating to the reporting and investigation of complaints are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.5.1-1;			
32		32	The relevant hospital committee monitors adherence to the established time frame and takes appropriate action when	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.5.1-2;			

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			required.												
33		33	Patients are aware of their right to voice complaints and the processes by which to do so.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
34	The department/service implements processes that support patient and family rights during care.	34	There are processes that support patient and family rights during care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
35		35	Measures are taken to protect the patient's privacy, person and possessions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
36		36	The personnel respect the right of patients and families to receive treatment and the right to refuse treatment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.1-6; 9.9.1-3; 10.9.1-3; 11.9.1-3; 12.9.1-3; 13.9.1-3; 15.9.1-3; 16.10.1-3; 17.9.1-3; 14.5.1-3; 18.13.1-3; 19.10.1-3; 20.13.1-3; 26.7.1-3; 22.6.1-3; 23.6.1-3; 24.6.1-3; 25.7.1-3; 28.9.1-4; 33.5.1-3; 34.5.1-3;			
37		37	There are processes that support patient and family rights related to food and nutrition.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	28.9.1-1;			

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
38		38	Personnel respect the rights of patients and families and recognise cultural preferences related to meals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	28.9.1-2;		
39	Patients and their families receive sufficient information to make informed decisions regarding their care.	39	Policies and procedures that guide personnel in relation to informed consent are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.1-1;		
40		40	Patients and their families/ carers/guardians are provided with information on the proposed care and the expected results of care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.1-2; 26.5.1-1;		
41		41	Patients and their families are informed about their rights to refuse or discontinue treatment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.1-4;		
42		42	Patients and their families are informed about the consequences of such decisions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.1-5;		
43		43	The hospital respects the right of patients and families to refuse or discontinue treatment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.1-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
44		44	Legislative requirements are followed when patients with notifiable diseases refuse treatment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.1-7;		
45		45	Patients and their families/carers/guardians are informed about immunisations appropriate to their age and/or disease groups.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.1-8;		
46	The hospital is responsible for providing processes that support patient and family rights during care.	46	Patient and family rights are identified and documented in accordance with current relevant legislation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.6.1-1;		
47		47	Policies and procedures which guide and support the protection of patient and family rights in the hospital are developed in accordance with ethical and legal norms, and implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.6.1-2;		
48		48	Documented evidence of personnel training in relation to these policies and procedures is available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.6.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
49		49	There are processes in place to respond to the patient's and their family's social, spiritual and cultural values, beliefs and needs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.4-4;			4.6.1-5;		
50	The department/service implements processes that support patient and family rights during care.	50	There are processes that support patient and family rights related to the provision of bed linen to promote patient comfort.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.5.1-1;		
51		51	Appropriate hospital attire is provided to patients to ensure that their right to dignity is preserved.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.5.1-2;		
52		52	There are processes that support patient and family rights related to a clean environment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.6.1-1;		
53		53	Personnel respect the rights of patients and families related to protection from healthcare-associated infections by means of appropriate waste management.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.6.1-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
54	Healthcare rights and informed consent	54	The health service organisation uses a charter of rights that is: a. Consistent with the National Charter of Healthcare Rights16 b. Easily accessible for patients, carers, families and consumers	0	0	0	PCS-2.3, a,b			0	0	0	0	0	0
55		55	The health service organisation ensures that its informed consent processes comply with legislation and best practice	0	0	0	PCS-2.4			0	0	0	0	0	0
56		56	The health service organisation has processes to identify: a. The capacity of a patient to make decisions about their own care b. A substitute decision-maker if a patient does not have the capacity to make decisions for themselves	0	0	0	PCS-2.5, a,b			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
57	The hospital respects and supports the patient's and the relatives' cultural and religious needs and wishes about existential and spiritual support.	57	There are guidelines on how the hospital identifies and supports the patient's and relatives' religious and cultural needs and existential or spiritual support.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.2-1;		
58		58	The hospital's dietary offers take the patient's religious background into consideration.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.2-2;		
59		59	The hospital takes the patient's shyness into consideration.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.2-3;		
60		60	The hospital offers existential or spiritual support to patients and relatives during hospitalisation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.2-4;		
61	The hospital takes measures to protect patient privacy and maintain confidentiality of patient information.	61	The patient's need for privacy is protected when providing personal information.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.3.1-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
62		62	The patient's need for privacy is protected during all examinations, procedures, treatments and carerelated discussions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.3.1-2; 28.9.1-2;		
63		63	Policies and procedures to guide personnel in maintaining confidentiality of patient information are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.3.1-3;		
64	Patients are protected from assault and harm.	64	The hospital has documented processes to protect patients from assault and harm.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.4.1-1;		
65		65	Remote or isolated areas of the hospital are monitored.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.4.1-2;		
66		66	The hospital has processes to protect patients from abuse and negligence, both within the hospital and in the community.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.4.1-3;		
67	Partnering with consumers	67	Clinicians use organisational processes from the Partnering with Consumers Standard when providing comprehensive care to: a. Actively involve patients in their own careb. Meet the patient's information needsc.	0	0	0	CCS-5.3, a,b,c; CCS-6.3, a,b,c					0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			Share decision-making.												
68	Integrating clinical governance	68	Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Implementing policies and procedures for partnering with consumers b. Managing risks associated with partnering with consumers c. Identifying training requirements for partnering with consumers	0	0	0	PCS-2.1,a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
69	Sharing decisions and planning care	69	The health service organisation has processes for clinicians to partner with patients and/or their substitute decision-maker to plan, communicate, set goals, and make decisions about their current and future care	0	0	0	PCS-2.6			2.1.2-1; 2.1.2-2; 2.1.2-3;			0	0	0
70		70	The health service organisation supports the workforce to form partnerships with patients and carers so that patients can be actively involved in	0	0	0	PCS-2.7			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			their own care.												
71	The organisation has a mechanism to capture patient's feedback and redressal of complaints.	71	The organisation has a mechanism to capture feedbacks from patients which includes patient satisfaction and patient experience.	PRE-7, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	4.5.1-1;		
72		72	The organisation has a documented complaint redressal procedure.	PRE-7, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	4.5.1-1;		
73		73	Patient and/or family members are made aware of the procedure for giving feedback and /or lodging complaints.	PRE-7, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
74		74	All feedback and complaints are reviewed and/or analysed within a defined time frame.	PRE-7, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75		75	Corrective and/or preventive action(s) are taken based on the analysis where appropriate.	PRE-7, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
76	The hospital manages and follows up on patient complaints and patient compensation cases.	76	There are guidelines for managing both verbal and written complaints from patients, relatives and other partners.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.10-1;			4.5.1-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
77		77	There are guidelines for case handling of patient compensation cases.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.10-2;			0	0	0
78		78	The hospital has a determined process for analysis and communication of learning from patients' complaints and patient compensation cases.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.10-3;			4.5.1-1;		
79		79	There is written information material describing the opportunities for patient complaints and compensation according to current legislation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.10-4;			0	0	0
80		80	Patient complaints are handled according to the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.10-5;			0	0	0
81		81	Patient compensation cases are handled according to the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.10-6;			0	0	0
82		82	There are guidelines for assessment and analysis of patient complaints and patient compensation cases. The analyses are used for learning in the organisation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.10-7;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
83		83	The analyses are used to determine goals and prioritisations for the hospital's quality improvement work.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.10-8;			0	0	0
84	Feedback and complaints management	84	The health service organisation: a. Has processes to seek regular feedback from patients, carers and families about their experiences and outcomes of care b. Has processes to regularly seek feedback from the workforce on their understanding and use of the safety and quality systems c. Uses this information to improve safety and quality systems	0	0	0	CGS-1.13, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
85		85	The health service organisation has an organisation-wide complaints management system, and: a. Encourages and supports patients, carers and families, and the workforce to report complaints b. Involves the workforce and consumers in the review of complaints c. Resolves complaints in a timely way d. Provides timely feedback to the governing body, the workforce and consumers on the analysis of complaints and actions taken e. Uses information from the analysis of complaints to inform improvements in safety and quality systems f. Records the risks identified from the analysis of complaints in the risk management system g. Regularly reviews and acts to improve the effectiveness of the complaints management system	0	0	0	CGS-1.14, a,b,c,e,f, g			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
86	The hospital systematically collects information about patients and relatives' experiences with the hospital and uses the information to develop the quality of the hospital's services.	86	There is a plan for involvement of patients and relatives' experiences with the hospital. The plan includes participation in the national patient satisfaction surveys and how to supplement this with other local or regional activities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.11-1;			0	0	0
87		87	Local and regional activities are implemented in accordance with the plan.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.11-2;			0	0	0
88		88	Data collected from national patient satisfaction surveys and from local or regional activities are analysed and assessed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.11-3;			0	0	0
89		89	The collected data are used to determine goals and prioritisations for the hospital's quality improvement work.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.11-4;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
90	The patient and/ or family members are educated to make informed decisions and are involved in the care planning and delivery process.	90	Informed consent includes information regarding the procedure, it's risks, benefits, alternatives and as to who will perform the procedure in a language that they can understand.	PRE-4, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
91		91	The procedure describes who can give consent when patient is incapable of independent decision making.	PRE-4, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
92		92	Informed consent is taken by the person performing the procedure.	PRE-4, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
93		93	Informed consent process adheres to statutory norms.	PRE-4, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
94		94	Staff are aware of the informed consent procedure.	PRE-4, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
95		95	The patient and/or family members are explained about the proposed care including the risks, alternatives and benefits.	PRE-3, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
96		96	The patient and/or family members are explained about the expected results.	PRE-3, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
97		97	The patient and/or family members are explained about the possible complications.	PRE-3, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
98		98	The care plan is prepared and modified in consultation with patient and/or family members.	PRE-3, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
99		99	The care plan respects and where possible incorporates patient and/or family concerns and requests.	PRE-3, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
100		100	The patient and/or family members are informed about the results of diagnostic tests and the diagnosis.	PRE-3, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
101		101	The patient and/or family members are explained about any change in the patient's condition in a timely manner.	PRE-3, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
102	A documented procedure for obtaining patient and/ or family's consent exists for informed decision making about their care.	102	Documented procedure incorporates the list of situations where informed consent is required and the process for taking informed consent.	PRE-4, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
103		103	General consent for treatment is obtained when the patient enters the organisation.	PRE-4, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
104		104	Patient and/or his family members are informed of the scope of such general consent.	PRE-4, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
105	The patient's informed consent is obtained prior to treatment unless otherwise stipulated by the legislation. Informed consent is also obtained prior to communication of statement of health unless otherwise stipulated by the legislation.	105	There are guidelines for obtainment of informed consent for treatment which complies with current legislation.	PRE-4, a			0	0	0	2.1.1-1:			0	0	0
106		106	There are guidelines for obtainment of informed consent for research projects which complies with current legislation.	PRE-4, a			0	0	0	2.1.1-2:			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
107		107	There are guidelines for obtainment of informed consent for disclosure of health information, which complies with current legislation.	PRE-4, a			0	0	0	2.1.1-3:			0	0	0
108		108	Obtainment of informed consent for treatment must be documented in the patient health record.	PRE-4, a			0	0	0	2.1.1-4:			0	0	0
109		109	There is separate documentation for obtainment of informed consent for research projects.	PRE-4, a			0	0	0	2.1.1-5:			0	0	0
110		110	There is documentation for obtainment of informed consent for disclosure of health information when there are legal requirements about this.	PRE-4, a			0	0	0	2.1.1-6:			0	0	0
111		111	The hospital has targets for the quality of documentation of informed consent. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. Data are analysed and assessed.	PRE-4, a			0	0	0	2.1.1-7:			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
112		112	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the documentation of informed consent. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	PRE-4, a			0	0	0	2.1.1-8:			0	0	0	
113	Adequate information is provided when obtaining informed consent from patients or their legal representatives.	113	There is a documented process for obtaining or confirming informed consent.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.3-1; 10.4.3-1; 11.4.3-1; 12.4.3-1; 13.4.3-1; 15.4.3-1; 16.4.3-1; 17.4.3-1; 18.7.2-1; 19.5.2-1; 20.7.2-1;			

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
114		114	Consent forms or the form confirming consent are completed comprehensively and available in patient records.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.3-2; 10.4.3-2; 11.4.3-2; 12.4.3-2; 13.4.3-2; 15.4.3-2; 16.4.3-2; 17.4.3-2; 18.7.2-2; 19.5.2-2; 20.7.2-2;		
115		115	Verbal consent is obtained and recorded according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.3-3; 10.4.3-3; 11.4.3-3; 12.4.3-3; 13.4.3-3; 15.4.3-3; 16.4.3-3; 17.4.3-3; 18.7.2-3; 19.5.2-3; 20.7.2-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
116	The hospital respects patients' wishes and preferences to withhold resuscitative services and forgo or withdraw life-sustaining treatment.	116	The hospital has identified its position on withholding resuscitative services and forgoing or withdrawing life-sustaining treatments, which conforms to the religious and cultural norms of the catchment population and any legal or regulatory requirements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.2-1;		
117		117	Policies and procedures that guide the processes for patients to make their decisions known to the hospital and for modifying decisions during the course of care are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.2-2;		
118		118	Policies and procedures that guide the hospital's response to patient decisions are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.2-3;		
119		119	The hospital guides health professionals on the ethical and legal issues in carrying out such wishes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.2-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
120	Partnering with consumers	120	Clinicians use organisational processes from the Partnering with Consumers Standard when recognising and responding to acute deterioration to: a. Actively involve patients in their own care b. Meet the patient's information needs c. Share decision-making	0	0	0	RRADS -8.3, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
121	The staff treats the deceased person and his/her relatives in a correct and dignified manner.	121	There are guidelines ensuring observance of the legislation in connection with a death.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.19.2-1;			0	0	0
122		122	There are guidelines supporting correct and dignified treatment of the deceased person and his/her relatives.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.19.2-2;			0	0	0
123		123	Managers and staff are familiar with relevant parts of the guidelines and work accordingly.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.19.2-3;			0	0	0

Table Number-12: Patient and Family Education (PFE):

The Patient and Family Education have 9 Standards and 38 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
1	Patients are assessed on arrival to ensure their healthcare needs are met efficiently.	1	Information on services, hours of operation and processes to obtain care are available to agencies and referral sources in the community and to the catchment population.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.3-1;
2		2	Assessment is initiated at the point of first contact with the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.3-2;
3		3	Patients attending for emergency care are triaged using an evidence-based triage process.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.3-3;
4		4	Patients identified by triage as having emergency or immediate needs are prioritised for assessment and intervention according to established criteria.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.3-4;
5		5	Patients are received into the hospital only if the hospital has the ability to provide the necessary services and settings for	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.3-5;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			care.												
6		6	Access to services not offered by the hospital is facilitated by providing patients with information on how to access these services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7		7	Emergency patients who require transfer to another hospital for appropriate services are stabilised prior to transfer.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	Partnerships in healthcare governance planning, design, measurement and evaluation	8	The health service organisation: a. Involves consumers in partnerships in the governance of, and to design, measure and evaluate, health care b. Has processes so that the consumers involved in these partnerships reflect the diversity of consumers who use the service or, where relevant, the diversity of the local community	0	0	0	PCS-2.11, a,b			2.1.2-1; 2.1.2-2; 2.1.2-3;			0	0	0
9		9	The health service organisation provides orientation, support and education to consumers who are partnering in the governance, design, measurement and evaluation of the organisation	0	0	0	PCS-2.12			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
10		10	The health communities to meet their healthcare needs	0	0	0	PCS-2.13			0	0	0	0	0	0
11		11	The health service organisation works in partnership with consumers to incorporate their views and experiences into training and education for the workforce	0	0	0	PCS-2.14			0	0	0	0	0	0
12	The hospital seeks to identify and reduce barriers to access and delivery of services.	12	The hospital has identified barriers to accessing healthcare services in its catchment population.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.2.1-4;			0	0	0
13		13	There is a process to limit the impact of barriers on access to the services provided by the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14		14	The hospital has access to ambulance services appropriate for the level of care provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	Communication that supports effective partnerships	15	The health service organisation uses communication mechanisms that are tailored to the diversity of the consumers who use its services and, where relevant, the diversity of the local community	0	0	0	PCS-2.8			2.2.2-1;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
16		16	Where information for patients, carers, families and consumers about health and health services is developed internally, the organisation involves consumers in its development and review	0	0	0	PCS-2.9			2.2.2-2;			0	0	0
17		17	The health service organisation supports clinicians to communicate with patients, carers, families and consumers about health and health care so that: a. Information is provided in a way that meets the needs of patients, carers, families and consumers b. Information provided is easy to understand and use c. The clinical needs of patients are addressed while they are in the health service organisation d. Information needs for ongoing care are provided on discharge	0	0	0	PCS-2.10, a,b,c,d			0	0	0	0	0	0
18	The organisation has a system for effective communication with patients and /or families.	18	Documented policies and procedures guide the effective communication with the patients and/or families.	PRE-8, a			0	0	0	2.2.1-1;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
19		19	The organisation shall identify special situations where enhanced communication would be required.	PRE-8, b			0	0	0	2.2.1-2;			0	0	0
20		20	The organisation lays down an approach for effective communication in these identified situations.	PRE-8, c			0	0	0	2.2.1-3;			0	0	0
21		21	The organisation also defines what constitutes an unacceptable communication and sensitizes the staff about the same.	PRE-8, d			0	0	0	2.2.1-4;			0	0	0
22		22	The organisation has a system to monitor and review the implementation of effective communication	PRE-8, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
23		23	The staff are trained in healthcare communication techniques periodically.	PRE-8, f			0	0	0	2.2.1-3;			0	0	0
24	The hospital plans and conducts the treatment involving the patient and relatives as partners.	24	The hospital has a policy on how to actively involve patients and relatives as partners when planning and implementing the treatment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.2.1-2;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
25		25	The policy is supplemented with guidelines describing the handling of Involvement of adolescents under the age of 15 years plus the group of 15-a) 17-year-olds Special conditions of the national Mental Health b) patient categories who are unable to make decisions themselves, e.g. unconscious patients and patients with dementia Measures which consider patient categories with a hearing and formulation d) disability Previous de-selection of life-sustaining treatment e) Information and involvement of relatives in respect of the patient's rights to f) confidentiality about statements of health Relatives independent rights for general information about the disease	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.2-2;			0	0	0
26		26	The hospital plans and conducts the treatment involving the patient and the relatives as partners in accordance with the policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.2-3; 2.2.1-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
27		27	The hospital has targets for the quality of the involvement of patients and relatives as partners, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.2-4; 2.2.1-6; 2.2.2-6;			0	0	0
28		28	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the involvement of patients and relatives as partners. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.2-5; 2.1.2-4; 2.2.1-6; 2.2.2-6;			0	0	0
29	Health education supports patient and family participation in care decisions and care processes.	29	The hospital plans patient education consistent with its mission, services and patient population.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.3-1;		
30		30	There is an appropriate structure or mechanism for education throughout the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.2.3-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
31		31	Patients and families indicate that they have received health education appropriate to their condition.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10.4.2.-1; 11.4.2.-1; 12.4.2.-1; 13.4.2.-1; 15.4.2.-1; 16.4.2.-1; 17.4.2.-1; 18.9.1.-1; 19.7.1.-1; 20.9.1.-1; 28.7.1.-1;		
32		32	Patients indicate that they have been informed about the clinical management of their condition.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10.4.2.-2; 11.4.2.-2; 12.4.2.-2; 13.4.2.-2; 15.4.2.-2; 16.4.2.-2; 17.4.2.-2; 18.9.1.-2; 19.7.1.-2; 20.9.1.-2; 26.5.1.-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
33		33	Patients are educated about their diagnosis and relevant health risks, e.g. safe use of medication and medical equipment, medicine and food interaction, therapeutic diet and food interactions, defaulting on medication use, etc.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10.4.2.-3; 11.4.2.-3; 12.4.2.-3; 13.4.2.-3; 15.4.2.-3; 16.4.2.-3; 17.4.2.-3; 18.9.1-3; 19.7.1-3; 20.9.1-3; 28.7.1-2;		
34		34	When appropriate, patients and families indicate that they have been educated about the use of rehabilitation techniques and/or equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.5.1-4;		
35		35	Interaction between personnel, the patient and the family is noted in the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	28.7.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
36	Organisational processes to support effective communication	36	The health service organisation has clinical communications processes to support effective communication when: a. Identification and procedure matching should occur b. All or part of a patient's care is transferred within the organisation, between multidisciplinary teams, between clinicians or between organisations; and on discharge c. Critical information about a patient's care, including information on risks, emerges or changes	0	0	0	CSS-6.4, a,b,c				0	0	0	0	0	0
37	Communicating critical information	37	Clinicians and multidisciplinary teams use clinical communication processes to effectively communicate critical information, alerts and risks, in a timely way, when they emerge or change to: a. Clinicians who can make decisions about care b. Patients, carers and families, in accordance with the wishes of the patient	0	0	0	CSS-6.9, a,b				0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
38		38	The health service organisation ensures that there are communication processes for patients, carers and families to directly communicate critical information and risks about care to clinicians	0	0	0	CSS-6.10			0	0	0	0	0	0

Table Number-13: Laboratory (LAB):

The Laboratory has 29 Standards and 132 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	Laboratory services are available to meet the needs of patients in compliance with local and national laws, regulations and standards.	1	Adequate, convenient and regular laboratory services are available to meet the hospital's needs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.1-1;
2		2	Where laboratory services are outsourced, the hospital has a valid service level agreement with an accredited laboratory.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.1-2;
3		3	The laboratory services are organised and provided in a manner that meets applicable local and national standards, laws and regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.1-3;
4		4	Emergency laboratory services are available, including after-hours services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.1-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
5		5	The hospital has established the expected turnaround times for results.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.1-5;		
6		6	Laboratory results are reported within the agreed turnaround times.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.1-6;		
7	A qualified individual is responsible for managing the Laboratory Service.	7	The laboratory is under the direction of a qualified individual.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.2-1;		
8		8	The responsibilities of this person include maintaining quality control programmes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.2-2;		
9		9	The responsibilities of this person include administrative supervision.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.2-3;		
10		10	The responsibilities of this person include the monitoring and reviewing of all laboratory services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.2-4;		
11	Individuals with adequate training, skills, orientation and experience administer tests and interpret the results.	11	Those individuals who may perform testing and those who may direct or supervise testing are identified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.3-1;		
12		12	Appropriately trained and experienced personnel administer tests.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.3-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
13		13	Appropriately trained and experienced personnel interpret tests.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.3-3;		
14		14	Laboratory results are validated and include unique patient identities, the date of testing/reporting, name and location of requesting physician.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.3-4;		
15		15	The validating officer is identified and recorded.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.3-5;		
16		16	There is an adequate number of personnel to meet patient needs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.3-6;		
17		17	A roster of experts for specialised diagnostic areas is maintained.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.3-7;		
18		18	There is a record of each test done, by whom, the result thereof and a monthly summary.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.1.3-8;		
19	Laboratory services are provided as per the scope of services of the organisation.	19	Scope of the laboratory services commensurate to the services provided by the organisation.	ACC-6, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
20		20	The infrastructure (physical and equipment) is adequate to provide the defined scope of	ACC-6, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			services.												
21		21	The manpower is adequate to provide the defined scope of services.	ACC-6, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
22		22	Qualified and trained personnel perform, supervise and interpret the investigations.	ACC-6, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
23		23	Documented procedures guide ordering of tests, collection, identification, handling, safe transportation, processing and disposal of specimens.	ACC-6, e			0	0	0	2.8.2-1; 2.8.2-2; 2.8.2-3; 2.8.2-4; 2.8.2-5; 2.8.2-6;			0	0	0
24		24	Laboratory results are available within a defined time frame.	ACC-6, f			0	0	0	2.8.6-1; 2.8.6-2; 2.8.6-3; 2.8.6-4; 2.8.6-6;			0	0	0
25		25	Critical results are intimated immediately to the personnel concerned.	ACC-6, g			0	0	0	2.8.6-5;			0	0	0
26		26	Results are reported in a standardised manner.	ACC-6, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
27		27	There is a mechanism to address recall / amendment of reports whenever applicable.	ACC-6, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28		28	Laboratory tests not available in the organisation are outsourced to organisation(s) based on their quality assurance system.	ACC-6, j			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29	Laboratory buildings are adequate to provide a safe and effective laboratory service.	29	The laboratory is a separate designated area within, or in close proximity to, the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.1-1;		
30		30	The size of the laboratory is appropriate to the services provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.1-2;		
31		31	The walls, ceilings and floors are smooth, easy to clean, impermeable to liquids and resistant to chemicals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.1-3;		
32		32	Hand washing facilities with running water are provided in each laboratory room, preferably near the exit door.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.1-4;		
33		33	Separate facilities are provided for personnel to store personal items.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.1-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
34		34	Separate rest-room facilities where personnel can eat and drink are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.1-6;		
35	Laboratory fixtures and fittings are adequate to provide a safe and effective laboratory service.	35	There are sufficient laboratory benches for the projected activities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.2-1;		
36		36	Laboratory benches are strong enough for the projected activities (e.g. large instruments).	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.2-1;		
37		37	Space around and under benches should allow for ease of cleaning and maintenance.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.2-2;		
38		38	Storage space is adequate to hold supplies for immediate use and to prevent clutter of bench tops.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.2-3;		
39		39	There is either an uninterrupted power supply (UPS) or battery backup system, and an automated voltage stabiliser (AVS) present for critical equipment, which are tested regularly and the results of testing are fully documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.2-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
40		40	Each laboratory compartment has adequate ventilation, room temperature is maintained below 25°C and a temperature record is kept.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.2-5;		
41	There is adequate laboratory equipment to provide a safe and effective laboratory service.	41	Sufficient equipment is available to provide the required laboratory services for the projected activities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.3-1;		
42		42	All equipment is in good working order, operated appropriately and functioning well.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.3-2;		
43		43	There are laboratory equipment management processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.3-3;		
44		44	The processes include selecting, acquiring and replacing of equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.3-4;		
45		45	The processes include taking an inventory of the equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.3-5;		
46		46	The processes include monitoring and follow-up.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.3-6;		
47		47	There is adequate documentation of all testing, maintenance and calibration of equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2.3-7;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
48	The supplies of laboratory consumables, reagents, chemicals and kits are adequate to provide a safe and effective laboratory service.	48	The available supplies, consumables, reagents, chemicals and kits are sufficient for projected activities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.3.1-1;		
49		49	Specific laboratory reagents, chemicals and kits are used appropriately.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.3.1-2;		
50		50	All reagents and chemicals are stored and dispensed according to guidelines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.3.1-3;		
51		51	All reagents and solutions are completely and accurately labelled.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.3.1-4;		
52		52	All reagents are periodically evaluated for accuracy and results.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.3.1-5;		
53		53	All reagents are stored in a lockable storage room or cupboard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.3.1-6;		
54		54	A named person is responsible for the specimen and reagent fridges.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.3.1-7;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
55	Procedures are followed for collecting, identifying, transporting and tracking specimens or samples and reporting the results.	55	Policies and procedures or standard operating procedures (SOPs) for handling specimens are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.1-1;		
56		56	Request forms and specimen labels include unique patient identifiers and adequate supporting information.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.1-2;		
57		57	There is a collection and delivery service for specimens from the hospital, every weekday.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.1-3;		
58		58	Specimens are given a laboratory specimen accession number.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.1-4;		
59		59	Procedures guide the ordering of tests.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.1-5;		
60		60	Procedures guide the collection and identification of specimens.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.1-6;		
61		61	Procedures guide the transport, storage and preservation of specimens.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.1-7;		
62		62	Procedures guide receiving, logging-in and tracking of	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.1-8;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			specimens.												
63		63	Emergency results may be obtained by telephone.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.1-9;		
64	Established norms and ranges are used to interpret and report clinical laboratory results.	64	Policies and procedures or standard operating procedures regarding reporting and reviewing results are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.2-1;		
65		65	The laboratory has established reference ranges for each test performed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.2-2;		
66		66	The range is included in the clinical record at the time test results are reported.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.2-3;		
67		67	Ranges are provided when tests are performed by outside sources.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.2-4;		
68		68	Ranges are appropriate to the hospital's catchment population.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.2-5;		
69		69	Ranges are reviewed and updated, as needed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.4.2-6;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
70	Quality control procedures are implemented and documented.	70	There is a quality control process for the clinical laboratory.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.5.1-1;		
71		71	The process includes the validation of test methods.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.5.1-2;		
72		72	The process includes the daily surveillance of test results.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.5.1-3;		
73		73	The process includes the rapid correction of deficiencies.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.5.1-4;		
74		74	There is a current register of quality control results and of the corrective and preventive actions taken.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.5.1-5;		
75		75	The laboratory participates in a proficiency testing programme, or an alternative, for all speciality laboratory services and tests.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.5.1-6;		
76		76	A cumulative record of participation is maintained.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.5.1-7;		
77		77	The hospital regularly reviews quality control results from all outside sources of laboratory services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.5.1-8;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
78		78	Copies of the quality control audits for the past six months verify that accurate/reliable results are being provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.5.1-9;		
79	There is an established laboratory quality assurance programme.	79	The laboratory quality assurance programme is documented.	ACC-7, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
80		80	The programme addresses verification and / or validation of test methods.	ACC-7, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
81		81	The programme addresses surveillance of test results.	ACC-7, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
82		82	The programme includes periodic calibration and maintenance of all equipment.	ACC-7, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
83		83	The programme includes the documentation of corrective and preventive actions.	ACC-7, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
84	Diagnostic examinations with equipment and/or staff attached to nondiagnostic departments are subject to the same quality control as examinations performed at diagnostic departments.	84	There are guidelines for quality control of diagnostic examinations which are performed outside diagnostic department.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.5-1;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
85		85	Staff performing diagnostic examinations outside diagnostic departments obtain and maintain the right competences.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.5-2;			0	0	0
86		86	The responsibility for quality control, calibration and correct use of equipment is clearly assigned and known by relevant staff.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.5-3;			0	0	0
87		87	The responsibility for interpretation and documentation of the results of the examinations is clearly assigned and known by relevant staff.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.5-4;			0	0	0
88		88	The hospital has targets for the quality of the examinations performed outside diagnostic department and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.5-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
89		89	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the examinations performed outside diagnostic department. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.5-6;			0	0	0
90	Early follow-up on test results and results of examinations are performed.	90	The hospital has targets for the quality of early reaction to test results. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. The quality monitoring includes deadlines for responses. Data are analysed and assessed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.6-7;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
91		91	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of early reaction to test results. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element is not relevant if the hospital meets the stipulated quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.6-8;			0	0	0
92	The department/service implements infection prevention and control processes.	92	Personal protective equipment, including eye protection, is available to all personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.7.1-2;		
93		93	Individuals who handle specimens are trained in the correct handling of dangerous specimens.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.7.1-3;		
94		94	Suitable processes are followed for cleaning and decontamination of laboratory surfaces and equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.7.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
95	There is an established laboratory safety programme.	95	The laboratory safety programme is documented.	ACC-8, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
96		96	This programme is aligned with the organisation's safety programme.	ACC-8, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
97		97	Written procedures guide the handling and disposal of infectious and hazardous materials.	ACC-8, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
98		98	Laboratory personnel are appropriately trained in safe practices.	ACC-8, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
99		99	Laboratory personnel are provided with appropriate safety equipment / devices.	ACC-8, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
100	The outpatient department is adequately supported by clinical laboratory services.	100	Laboratory services are available at all times.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.6.2-1; 19.4.2-1; 20.6.2-1;		
101		101	Established waiting times for laboratory tests to be done according to triage status are monitored.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.6.2-2; 19.4.2-2; 20.6.2-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
102		102	Established waiting times for laboratory results to be available are monitored.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.6.2-3; 19.4.2-3; 20.6.2-3;		
103		103	Laboratory services are available to meet the needs of employees.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.1.1-5;		
104		104	A register is kept of all laboratory specimens sent and results received.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.1.1-6;		
105	Documented policies and procedures define rational use of blood and blood components.	105	Documented policies and procedures are used to guide the rational use of blood and blood components.	COP-8, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
106		106	Documented procedures govern transfusion of blood and blood components	COP-8, b			0	0	0	2.11.6-2; 2.11.6-5;			0	0	0
107		107	The transfusion services are governed by the applicable laws and regulations.	COP-8, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
108		108	Informed consent is obtained for donation and transfusion of blood and blood components.	COP-8, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
109		109	Informed consent also includes patient and family education about the donation.	COP-8, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
110		110	The organisation defines the process for availability and transfusion of blood/ blood components for use in emergency situations.	COP-8, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
111		111	Post-transfusion form is collected, reactions if any identified and are analysed for preventive and corrective actions.	COP-8, g			0	0	0	2.11.6-3;			0	0	0
112		112	Staff are trained to implement the policies.	COP-8, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
113		113	There are guidelines for procedure for identification of patient and blood sample/blood components.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.6-1;			0	0	0
114		114	Indication for blood transfusion is documented in the patient health record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.6-4;			0	0	0
115		115	The hospital has targets for the quality of infusion with blood components. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.6-6;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
116		116	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of infusion with blood components. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.6-7;			0	0	0
117	Optimising and conserving patients' own blood	117	Clinicians use the blood and blood products processes to manage the need for, and minimise the inappropriate use of, blood and blood products by: a. Optimising patients' own red cell mass, haemoglobin and iron stores b. Identifying and managing patients with, or at risk of, bleeding c. Determining the clinical need for blood and blood products, and related risks	0	0	0	BMS-7.4, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
118	Partnering with consumers	118	Clinicians use organisational processes from the Partnering with Consumers Standard when providing safe blood management to: a. Actively involve patients in their own care b. Meet the patient's information needs c. Share decision-making	0	0	0	BMS-7.3, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
119	Documenting	119	Clinicians document decisions relating to blood management, transfusion history and transfusion details in the healthcare record	0	0	0	BMS-7.5			0	0	0	0	0	0
120	Prescribing and administering blood and blood products	120	The health service organisation supports clinicians to prescribe and administer blood and blood products appropriately, in accordance with national guidelines and national criteria	0	0	0	BMS-7.6			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
121	Storing, distributing and tracing blood and blood products	121	The health service organisation has processes: a. That comply with manufacturers' directions, legislation, and relevant jurisdictional requirements to store, distribute and handle blood and blood products safely and securely b. To trace blood and blood products from entry into the organisation to transfusion, discard or transfer	0	0	0	BMS-7.9, a,b,			0	0	0	0	0	0
122	Availability of blood	122	The health service organisation has processes to: a. Manage the availability of blood and blood products to meet clinical need b. Eliminate avoidable wastage c. Respond in times of shortage	0	0	0	BMS-7.10, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
123	Blood Bank-Integrating clinical governance	123	Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Implementing policies and procedures for blood management b. Managing risks associated with blood management c. Identifying training requirements for blood management	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
124	Applying quality improvement systems	124	The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Monitoring the performance of the blood management system b. Implementing strategies to improve blood management and associated processes c. Reporting on the outcomes of blood management	0	0	0	BMS-7.2, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
125	There is access to emergency blood and blood products in	125	Emergency blood is available at all times.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.7.7-1; 20.7.6-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
	accordance with hospital policy.														
126		126	There is a designated refrigerator for emergency blood and blood products.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
127		127	The temperature of the refrigerator is monitored and recorded according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
128		128	Appropriate action is taken and recorded when the temperature of the refrigerator is outside the recommended range.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
129		129	Banked emergency blood is subject to stock control, which includes the replacement of stock before its expiry date.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
130	Reporting adverse events	130	The health service organisation uses processes for reporting transfusionrelated adverse events, in accordance with national guidelines and criteria	0	0	0	BMS-7.7			0	0	0	0	0	0
131		131	The health service organisation participates in haemovigilance activities, in accordance with the national framework	0	0	0	BMS-7.8			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
132	Integrating clinical governance	132	Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Implementing policies and procedures for blood management b. Managing risks associated with blood management c. Identifying training requirements for blood management	0	0	0	BMS-7.1, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0

Table Number-14: Radiology (RAD):

The Radiology has 17 Standards and 105 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
1	A radiology and diagnostic imaging service is provided by the hospital, or is readily available through arrangements with outside sources, to meet the needs of its catchment population.	1	An adequate, convenient and regular radiology and diagnostic imaging service is available to meet patient needs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.1-1;
2		2	Where radiology and diagnostic imaging services are outsourced, the hospital has a valid service level agreement with an accredited radiology service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.1-2;
3		3	The selection of an outside source is based on an acceptable record of accurate, timely service and compliance with applicable laws and regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.1-3;
4		4	An emergency radiology and diagnostic imaging service is	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.1-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			available after hours.												
5	The radiology and diagnostic imaging service meets applicable local and national standards and legislation.	5	Documented policies and procedures that address compliance with applicable standards, laws and regulations are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6		6	A copy of the local rules relating to current Ionising Radiation regulations is available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7		7	A copy of the most recent radiation safety report is held.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8		8	The hospital satisfies the statutory requirements under Ionising Radiation regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9		9	A radiation protection supervisor is identified and available to assist a radiation protection adviser in complying with the Ionising Radiation regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10		10	A patient register is held in the radiology and diagnostic imaging department.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	Imaging services are provided as per the scope of services of the	11	Imaging services comply with legal and other requirements.	ACC-9.a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
	organisation.														
12		12	Scope of the imaging services is commensurate to the services provided by the organisation.	ACC-9.b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
13		13	The infrastructure (physical and equipment) and manpower is adequate to provide for its defined scope of services.	ACC-9.c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14		14	Adequately qualified and trained personnel perform, supervise and interpret the investigations.	ACC-9.d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15		15	Documented policies and procedures exist to ensure correct identification and safe and timely transportation of patients to and from the imaging services.	ACC-9.e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
16		16	Imaging results are available within a defined timeframe.	ACC-9.f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
17		17	Critical results are intimated immediately to the personnel concerned.	ACC-9.g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
18		18	Results are reported in a standardised manner.	ACC-9.h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
19		19	There is a mechanism to address recall / amendment of reports whenever applicable.	ACC-9.i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
20		20	Imaging tests not available in the organisation are outsourced to organisation(s) based on their quality assurance system.	ACC-9.j			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
21	A qualified individual is responsible for managing the radiology and diagnostic imaging service.	21	A radiologist or radiographer, who is qualified by education, training and experience, manages the radiology and diagnostic imaging service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.2-1;		
22		22	The responsibilities of this person include developing, implementing and maintaining relevant policies and procedures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.2-2;		
23		23	The responsibilities of this person include administrative control.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.2-3;		
24		24	The responsibilities of this person include maintaining quality control programmes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.2-4;		
25		25	The responsibilities of this person include recommending outside sources of radiology and diagnostic imaging services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.2-5;		
26		26	The responsibilities of this person include monitoring and reviewing all radiology and diagnostic imaging services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.2-6;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
27	Individuals with adequate training, skills and experience perform diagnostic procedures and interpret the results.	27	Those individuals who may perform diagnostic imaging procedures and those who may interpret and report the results are identified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.3-1;
28		28	A system is in place to ensure that procedures are performed only by radiographers, radiologists, or specially trained doctors and other persons, authorised to do so by a radiation protection advisor.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.3-2;
29		29	Diagnostic imaging is done only upon a signed request from a qualified medical practitioner.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.3-3;
30		30	Diagnostic images are interpreted and reported on by appropriately trained and experienced personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.3-4;
31		31	There is an adequate number of personnel to meet patient needs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.3-5;
32		32	Experts in specialised diagnostic areas are contacted, when needed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.3-6;
33		33	A roster of experts for specialised diagnostic areas is maintained.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.1.3-7;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
34	Measures to protect patients and personnel from unnecessary exposure are applied.	34	Warning signs are placed at the entrances to X-ray rooms.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.2.1-1;		
35		35	Notices encouraging women to inform the radiographer of pregnancy are prominently displayed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.2.1-2;		
36		36	Dosimeter badges are worn and handled according to Ionising Radiation regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.2.1-3;		
37		37	Documented systems are in place to ensure that pregnant radiographers/technicians are provided with additional radiation monitoring devices and are restricted to work in low risk areas.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.2.1-4;		
38		38	Protective clothing and appliances for personnel and patients are available and in good order.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.2.1-5;		
39		39	A documented system is in place to ensure that doors are closed during radiographic examinations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.2.1-6;		
40		40	Beam restricting devices are used.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.2.1-7;		
41		41	Each X-ray room is provided with an exposure chart.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.2.1-8;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
42		42	Each X-ray machine is provided with a log-book, which includes quality control information on the device.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.2.1-9;		
43	Essential resuscitation equipment and medications are available.	43	There is a mechanism for the summoning of medical help in an emergency.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.2.2-1;		
44		44	Resuscitation equipment is available in accordance with hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.2.2-2;		
45		45	Resuscitation equipment and drugs are checked daily or immediately after use, whichever is the sooner, by persons identified to be responsible for this.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.2.2-3;		
46	Reporting and recording policies and procedures within the radiology and diagnostic imaging service ensure safety and legality.	46	Diagnostic imaging request forms contain the patient's name, examination requested, relevant previous examinations and clinical information to explain the request.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.3.1-1;		
47		47	The request form includes information regarding previous investigations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.3.1-2;		
48		48	The hospital has established the expected report time for results.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.3.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
49		49	Radiology and diagnostic imaging results are reported on within a time frame to meet patient needs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.3.1-4;		
50		50	There is a method of checking the reports against the clinical records.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.3.1-5;		
51		51	Reports contain a clear conclusion and recommendations for future treatment where appropriate.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.3.1-6;		
52		52	A copy of the report is filed in the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.3.1-7;		
53		53	Images are available at each visit of the patient.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.3.1-8;		
54		54	A policy that defines the duration and method of storage of images is implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.3.1-9;		
55		55	Where digital imaging is used, appropriate back-up services are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.3.1-10;		
56	X-ray film and other supplies are regularly available.	56	Essential quantities of film, reagents and supplies are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.3.3-1;		
57		57	All film and reagents are stored and disposed of according to guidelines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.3.3-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
58		58	All reagents and solutions are completely and accurately labelled.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.3.3-3;
59	Quality control procedures are implemented and documented.	59	There is a quality control process for the radiology and diagnostic imaging service which is implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.5.1-1;
60		60	Quality control includes daily surveillance of imaging results.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.5.1-2;
61		61	Quality control includes rapid correction when a deficiency is identified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.5.1-3;
62		62	Quality control includes equipment maintenance/testing/safety.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.5.1-4;
63		63	Quality control includes documenting results and corrective actions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.5.1-5;
64	There is an established quality assurance programme for imaging services.	64	The quality assurance programme for imaging services is documented.	ACC-10,a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
65		65	The programme addresses periodic internal / external peer review of imaging protocols and results using appropriate sampling.	ACC-10,b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
66		66	The programme addresses surveillance of imaging results in collaboration with referring clinicians for follow up wherever applicable	ACC-10,c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
67		67	A system is in place to ensure the appropriateness of the investigations and procedures for the clinical indication.	ACC-10,d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
68		68	The programme includes periodic calibration and maintenance of all equipment.	ACC-10,e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
69		69	The programme includes the documentation of corrective and preventive actions.	ACC-10,f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
70	There is an established safety programme in the imaging services.	70	The radiation-safety programme is documented.	ACC-11, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
71		71	This programme is aligned with the organisation's safety programme.	ACC-11, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
72		72	Patients are appropriately screened for safety / risk prior to undergoing an imaging on a particular modality.	ACC-11, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
73		73	Handling, usage and disposal of radio-active and hazardous materials are as per statutory requirements.	ACC-11, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
74		74	Imaging personnel and patients are provided with appropriate radiation safety and monitoring devices where applicable.	ACC-11, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75		75	Radiation-safety and monitoring devices are periodically tested and results are documented.	ACC-11, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
76		76	Imaging and ancillary personnel are trained in imaging safety practices and radiation-safety measures.	ACC-11, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
77		77	Imaging signage are prominently displayed in all appropriate locations.	ACC-11, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
78	Requisition of paraclinical examinations and handling of samples take place in a correct and safe manner.	78	There are guidelines from each paraclinical department for ordering examination.		0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.2-1;		0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
79		79	There are guidelines from each paraclinical department for sampling for examination.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.2-2;			0	0	0
80		80	There are guidelines from each paraclinical department for handling diagnostic material after sampling.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.2-3;			0	0	0
81		81	Paraclinical examinations are ordered in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.2-4;			0	0	0
82		82	Samples for paraclinical examinations are extracted in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.2-5;			0	0	0
83		83	Diagnostic material is handled in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.2-6;			0	0	0
84	Diagnostic examinations with equipment and/or staff attached to nondiagnostic departments are subject to the same quality control as examinations performed at diagnostic departments.	84	There are guidelines for quality control of diagnostic examinations which are performed outside diagnostic department.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.5-7;			0	0	0
85		85	Staff performing diagnostic examinations outside diagnostic departments obtain and maintain the right competences.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.5-2;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
86		86	The responsibility for quality control, calibration and correct use of equipment is clearly assigned and known by relevant staff.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.5-3;			0	0	0
87		87	The responsibility for interpretation and documentation of the results of the examinations is clearly assigned and known by relevant staff.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.5-4;			0	0	0
88		88	The hospital has targets for the quality of the examinations performed outside diagnostic department and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.5-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
89		89	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the examinations performed outside diagnostic department. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.5-6;			0	0	0
90	Early follow-up on test results and results of examinations are performed.	90	There are guidelines for giving test results and results of examinations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.6-1;			0	0	0
91		91	There are guidelines for receiving test results and results of examinations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.6-2;			0	0	0
92		92	Test results and results of examinations are in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.6-3;			0	0	0
93		93	Acknowledge the receipt of test results and results of examinations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.6-4;			0	0	0
94		94	On reception of test results and results of examination, which require acute efforts, the reaction is early.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.6-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
95		95	For each patient it has been registered which tests and examinations have been requested and which results have been received.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.6-6;			0	0	0
96		96	The hospital has targets for the quality of early reaction to test results. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. The quality monitoring includes deadlines for responses. Data are analysed and assessed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.6-7;			0	0	0
97		97	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of early reaction to test results. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.8.6-8;			0	0	0
98	Diagnostic imaging services are available to meet patient needs (ER)	98	Adequate and convenient diagnostic imaging services are available at all times.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.6.1-1; 19.4.1-1; 20.6.1-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
99		99	Established waiting times for diagnostic imaging studies to be done according to triage status are monitored.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.6.1-2; 19.4.1-2; 20.6.1-2;		
100		100	Established waiting times for diagnostic images to be available are monitored.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.6.1-3; 19.4.1-3; 20.6.1-3;		
101		101	Where X-rays are initially interpreted by emergency unit medical personnel, there is a system for review by appropriately qualified diagnostic imaging personnel, when required.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.6.1-4; 19.4.1-4; 20.6.1-4;		
102	Diagnostic imaging services are available to meet patient needs (ER)	102	Adequate and convenient diagnostic imaging services are available at all times.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.6.1-1; 19.4.1-1; 20.6.1-1;		
103		103	Established waiting times for diagnostic imaging studies to be done according to triage status are monitored.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.6.1-2; 19.4.1-2; 20.6.1-2;		
104		104	Established waiting times for diagnostic images to be available are monitored.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.6.1-3; 19.4.1-3; 20.6.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
105		105	Where X-rays are initially interpreted by emergency unit medical personnel, there is a system for review by appropriately qualified diagnostic imaging personnel, when required.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.6.1-4; 19.4.1-4; 20.6.1-4;

Table Number-15: Human Resource (HR):

The Human Resource has 22 Standards and 128 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	Human resource management support	1	A designated individual is responsible for providing support for the hospital's human resource strategy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.4.1-2;			2.1.1-1;		
2		2	The human resource manager is suitably qualified and experienced in human resource management.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.1-2;		
3		3	The human resource manager ensures that policies and procedures are available to guide personnel and that they are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.1-3;		
4		4	The responsibilities of the human resource manager include ensuring compliance with labour legislation and regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
5		5	The human resource manager uses information on staffing needs provided by clinical and managerial personnel to ensure adequate provision of personnel for service delivery.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.4.1-2;			2.1.1-5;		
6		6	Details of the hospital's absenteeism, sickness rates and personnel turnover rates are recorded, analysed and presented to senior management to inform relevant decision-making processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.1-6;		
7		7	Details of the personnel establishment are recorded and analysed to allow for informed decisionmaking by the hospital's management.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.1-7;		
8		8	Receptionists, telephonists, clerical support personnel and porters are allocated to wards and departments in accordance with service delivery requirements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.1-8;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
9	Human Resource Planning	9	Human resource planning supports the organisation's current and future ability to meet the care, treatment and service needs of the patient.	HRM-1, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10		10	The organisation maintains an adequate number and mix of staff to meet the care, treatment and service needs of the patient.	HRM-1, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11		11	The required job specification and job description are well defined for each category of staff.	HRM-1, c			0	0	0	2.3.2-1; 2.3.2-2;			0	0	0
12		12	The organisation verifies the antecedents of the potential employee with regards to criminal/negligence background.	HRM-1, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13		13	There are documented processes for staffing the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.4.1-1;			2.2.1-1;		
14		14	The processes include personnel recruitment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.2.1-2;		
15		15	The processes include the numbers and categories of personnel required.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.2.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
16		16	The processes include the selection and documentation of desired education, qualifications, experience, skills and knowledge for each personnel member to be recruited.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.2.1-4;		
17		17	The processes include assignment and reassignment of personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.2.1-5;		
18		18	The processes include personal development of personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.2.1-6;		
19		19	The processes include measures to improve personnel retention.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.2.1-7;		
20		20	The processes include succession planning.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.2.1-8;		
21	Recruitment/ Employment of staff	21	There is a documented procedure for recruitment/employment.	HRM-2, a			0	0	0	1.4.1-1;			0	0	0
22		22	Recruitment is based on pre-defined criteria.	HRM-2, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
23		23	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the employment process. The effect has been assessed and it has either been concluded that the initiatives either had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.4.1-5; 1.4.1-5;				0	0	0
24	Verification of personnel credentials	24	Those permitted to provide patient care without supervision are identified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.5.1-1;			
25		25	The registration, education, training and experience of all healthcare professionals is verified from the original sources where possible.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.5.1-2;			
26		26	The services to be provided by each personnel member are made known to appropriate individuals and units within the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.5.1-3;			
27	Credentialing and privileging of medical (Doctors, dentists and chiropractors) professionals	27	Medical professionals permitted by law, regulation and the organisation to provide patient care without supervision are identified.	HRM-9, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
28		28	The education, registration, training and experience of the identified medical professionals is documented and updated periodically.	HRM-9, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29		29	All such information pertaining to the medical professionals is appropriately verified when possible.	HRM-9, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30		30	Medical professionals are granted privileges to admit and care for patients in consonance with their qualification, training, experience and registration.	HRM-9, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31		31	The requisite services to be provided by the medical professionals are known to them as well as the various departments/units of the organisation.	HRM-9, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
32		32	Medical professionals admit and care for patients as per their privileging.	HRM-9, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
33		33	The hospital has a policy for authorisation describing how to determine the employees assigned to clinical privileges with the necessary competences to deliver clinical services of special risk. As regards the individual employee, the policy ensures that this is assessed in connection with new appointment, and then a re-assessment takes place after set intervals. The policy describes how to relate when the hospital adopt significant new types of treatment. The policy describes how to ensure the authenticity of the documentation which makes the basis for the authorisation.	2.3.2-1:			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
34	Credentialing and privileging of nursing professionals	34	Nursing staff permitted by law, regulation and the organisation to provide patient care without supervision are identified.	HRM-10, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
35		35	The education, registration, training and experience of nursing staff is documented and updated periodically.	HRM-10, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
36		36	All such information pertaining to the nursing staff is appropriately verified when possible.	HRM-10, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
37		37	Nursing staff are granted privileges in consonance with their qualification, training, experience and registration.	HRM-10, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
38		38	The requisite services to be provided by the nursing staff are known to them as well as the various departments/units of the organisation.	HRM-10, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
39		39	Nursing professionals care for patients as per their privileging.	HRM-10, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
40	Clinical performance and effectiveness-Credentialing and Privileges	40	The health service organisation: a. Conducts processes to ensure that clinicians are credentialed, where relevant b. Monitors and improves the effectiveness of the credentialing process.	CGS-1.24,a,b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
41	Delegation of assigned clinical privileges	41	The hospital has a policy for delegation of healthcare professional tasks The policy describes the hospital's overall principles for what can be delegated and how the legislation's requirements are observed.	CGS-1.23,a,b,c			0	0	0	1.4.6-1; 1.4.7-1:			0	0	0
42		42	The delegation takes place in accordance with the hospital's policy.		0	0	0	0	0	1.4.6-2; 1.4.7-1:			0	0	0
43		43	There are lists stating who is delegated for what and on which conditions.		0	0	0	0	0	1.4.6-3; 1.4.7-1:			0	0	0
44	Work planning	44	The hospital defines the staff resources and competences that have present to solve specific tasks in the patient treatment.		0	0	0	0	0	1.4.4-1;			0	0	0
45		45	The individual departments have methods in relation to staffing in extraordinary situations where the desired staff resources and competences are not present or in case of workloads.		0	0	0	0	0	1.4.4-2;			0	0	0
46		46	The daily staffing is based on the determined framework		0	0	0	0	0	1.4.4-3;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			defined by the hospital.												
47		47	Extraordinary situations are handled in accordance with the determined methods.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.4.4-4;			0	0	0
48	Job Description	48	There are satisfactory job descriptions and descriptions of function.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.4.1-3;			2.3.1-1;		
49		49	Managers and staff are familiar with their job descriptions and descriptions of function.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.4.1-4;			2.3.1-3;		
50		50	Job descriptions are reviewed according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.3.1-2;		
51	Clinical performance and effectiveness-Safety and quality roles and responsibilities	51	The health service organisation has processes to: a. Support the workforce to understand and perform their roles and responsibilities for safety and quality b. Assign safety and quality roles and responsibilities to the workforce, including locums and agency staff				0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
52		52	The health service organisation provides supervision for clinicians to ensure that they can safely fulfil their designated roles, including				0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			access to after-hours advice, where appropriate.												
53	Staff Orientation and induction	53	There are documented programmes for personnel orientation and induction to the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.4.1-1;
54		54	New personnel members are orientated to the hospital within a time frame determined by hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.4.1-2;
55		55	Every staff member entering the organisation is provided induction training.	HRM-2, c			0	0	0	1.4.3-1;			0	0	0
56		56	The induction training includes orientation to the organisation's vision, mission and values.	HRM-2, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
57		57	The induction training includes awareness on employee rights and responsibilities.	HRM-2, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
58		58	The induction training includes awareness on patient's rights and responsibilities.	HRM-2, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
59		59	The induction training includes orientation to the service standards of the organisation.	HRM-2, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
60		60	Every staff member is made aware of organisation's wide policies and procedures as well as relevant department/ unit/ service/ programme's policies and procedures.	HRM-2, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
61		61	Departmental and service managers implement orientation programmes for departmental and service personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.4.1-3;		
62	Personnel information/ Personnel file for each staff member	62	Personnel files are maintained with respect to all staff.	HRM-8, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
63		63	Personnel files contain the personal information of the personnel member.	HRM-8, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.2-3;		
64		64	All records of in-service training and education are contained in the personal files.	HRM-8, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
65		65	Personnel files contain the work history of the personnel member.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.2-4;		
66		66	Personnel files contain job descriptions which include scope of practice.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.2-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
67		67	Personnel files contain the qualifications of the personnel member.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.2-6;		
68		68	Personnel files contain copies of any required registration certificate(s).	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.2-7;		
69		69	Personnel files contain results of all evaluations.	HRM-8, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.2-8;		
70		70	A designated personnel member is responsible for the storage and retrieval of personnel files.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.2-1;		
71		71	Only authorised persons have access to personnel files.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.2-2;		
72		72	Personnel files are standardised.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.2-9;		
73		73	Personnel files are reviewed at least annually.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1.2-10;		
74	On-going programme for professional training (including various safety-related aspects), development and Competence development of staff	74	A documented training and development policy exists for the staff.	HRM-3, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.4.2-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
75		75	The organisation maintains the training record.	HRM-3, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	2.4.2-4;		
76		76	Training also occurs when job responsibilities change/new equipment is introduced.	HRM-3, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
77		77	Evaluation of training effectiveness is done by the organisation	HRM-3, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
78		78	Feedback mechanisms are in place for improvement of training and development programme.	HRM-3, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
79	Training on various safety-related aspects	79	Staff are trained on the risks within the organisation's environment.	HRM-4, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
80		80	Staff members can demonstrate and take actions to report, eliminate, or minimise risks.	HRM-4, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
81		81	Staff members are made aware of procedures to follow in the event of an incident.	HRM-4, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
82		82	Staff are trained on occupational safety aspects.	HRM-4, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
83		83	The hospital has targets for the quality of the training and competence development of the staff, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.4.5-5;			0	0	0
84		84	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the training and competence development of the staff. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.4.5-6;			0	0	0
85		85	The hospital has a coordinated plan for in-service training and development which is	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.4.2-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			implemented.												
86		86	Department and service managers have established in-service training/ education programmes relevant to departmental and service personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.4.2-2;		
87		87	The hospital uses various sources of data and information to identify the in-service training/education needs of the personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.4.2-3;		
88		88	Records of in-service training are kept for each personnel member.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.4.2-4;		
89		89	There are guidelines for training and competence development.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.4.5-1;				0	0
90		90	Personnel competencies are assessed and recorded after in-service training according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.4.2-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
91	Clinical performance and effectiveness-Quality Improvement, Patient Safety education and training	91	The health service organisation provides orientation to the organisation that describes roles and responsibilities for safety and quality for: a. Members of the governing body b. Clinicians, and any other employed, contracted, locum, agency, student or volunteer members of the organisation	CGS-1.19,a,b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
92		92	The health service organisation uses its training systems to: a. Assess the competency and training needs of its workforce b. Implement a mandatory training program to meet its requirements arising from these standards c. Provide access to training to meet its safety and quality training needs d. Monitor the workforce's participation in training	CGS-1.20,a,b,c,d	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.4.3-4;				

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
93		93	The health service organisation has strategies to improve the cultural awareness and cultural competency of the workforce to meet the needs of its Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander patients	CGS-1.21			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
94	Continuing education, research and other educational experiences to acquire new skills and knowledge and to support job advancement.	94	There is a development strategy for the hospital which ensures that managers receive the training required to fulfil their responsibilities.		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.4.3-1;
95		95	There is a training strategy for the hospital which ensures that all personnel update their knowledge and skills regularly.		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.4.3-2;
96		96	Personnel are informed of opportunities to participate in advanced education, ongoing training and research, and acquire postgraduate qualifications relevant to the services provided by the hospital.		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.4.3-3;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
97	Performance appraisal	97	A documented performance appraisal system exists in the organisation.	HRM-5, a			CGS-1.22,a,b,c			1.4.5-2; 1.4.5-1;			0	0	0
98		98	The employees are made aware of the system of appraisal at the time of induction.	HRM-5, b			0	0	0	1.4.5-3;			0	0	0
99		99	Performance is evaluated based on the pre-determined criteria.	HRM-5, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
100		100	The appraisal system is used as a tool for further development.	HRM-5, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
101		101	Performance appraisal is carried out at pre-defined intervals and is documented.	HRM-5, e			0	0	0	1.4.3-4			0	0	0
102		102	Key performance areas for each personnel member are identified in their job descriptions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.3.2-1;		
103		103	The performance of individual personnel members is reviewed when indicated by the findings of quality improvement activities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.4.5-5;			2.3.2-2;		
104		104	There is at least one documented evaluation of each personnel member each year or	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.3.2-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			more frequently as defined by hospital policy.												
105		105	New personnel members are evaluated as defined by hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.3.2-4;		
106	Industrial relations based on current labour legislation	106	There are mutually agreed processes for the satisfactory conduct of industrial relations activities, which meet the requirements of current legislation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.3.3-1;		
107		107	There are recognition agreements with trade unions and/or health professional organisations, where applicable.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.3.3-2;		
108		108	Disciplinary procedures are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.3.3-3;		
109		109	Grievance procedures are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.3.3-4;		
110		110	Dispute and appeal procedures are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.3.3-5;		
111	Disciplinary and grievance handling policies and procedures	111	Documented policies and procedures exist.	HRM-6, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
112		112	The policies and procedures are known to all categories of	HRM-6, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			staff of the organisation.												
113		113	The disciplinary policy and procedure is based on the principles of natural justice.	HRM-6, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
114		114	The disciplinary and grievance procedure is in consonance with the prevailing laws.	HRM-6, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
115		115	There is a provision for appeals in all disciplinary cases.	HRM-6, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
116		116	The redress procedure addresses the grievance.	HRM-6, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
117		117	Actions are taken to redress the grievance.	HRM-6, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
118	Health needs of the employees	118	A pre-employment medical examination is conducted on all the staff	HRM-7, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
119		119	Health problems of the employees are taken care of in accordance with the organisation's policy.	HRM-7, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
120		120	Regular health checks of staff dealing with direct patient care are done at least once a year and the findings/results are documented.	HRM-7, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
121		121	Occupational health hazards are adequately addressed.	HRM-7, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
122	The department/ service implements processes that support employee rights during care.	122	There are processes that support employee rights during care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.9.1-1;
123		123	Measures are taken to protect the employee's privacy, person and possessions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.9.1-2;
124		124	The personnel respect the rights of employees to treatment and to refuse treatment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.9.1-3;
125	Each service is managed to ensure the provision of a safe and effective service	125	A designated individual is responsible for each service	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.1.1-1;
126		126	The service manager ensures that policies and procedures are available to guide the personnel and that they are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.1.1-2;
127		127	The manager plans and implements an effective organisational structure to support his/her responsibilities and authority.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.1.1-3;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
128		128	The responsibilities of the manager and personnel are defined in writing.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.1.1-4;		

Table Number-16: Pharmacy:

The Pharmacy has 38 Standards and 167 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	Documented policies and procedures guide the organisation of pharmacy services and usage of medication.	1	There is a documented policy and procedure for pharmacy services and medication usage.	MOM-1, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2		2	Policies and procedures comply with the applicable laws and regulations.	MOM-1, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3		3	A multidisciplinary committee guides the formulation and implementation of these policies and procedures.	MOM-1, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4		4	There is a procedure to obtain medication when the pharmacy is closed.	MOM-1, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
5	There is a hospital formulary.	5	A list of medications appropriate for the patients and as per the scope of the organisation's clinical services is developed collaboratively by the multidisciplinary committee.	MOM-2, a			0	0	0	2.9.3-1; 2.9.7-1;			0	0	0
6		6	The list is reviewed and updated collaboratively by the multidisciplinary committee at least annually.	MOM-2, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7		7	The formulary is available for clinicians to refer and adhere to.	MOM-2, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8		8	There is a defined process for acquisition of these medications.	MOM-2, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9		9	There is a process to obtain medications not listed in the formulary.	MOM-2, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	Documented policies and procedures guide the storage of medication.	10	Documented policies and procedures exist for storage of medication.	MOM-3, a			0	0	0	2.9.5-1;			0	0	0
11		11	Medications are stored in a clean, safe and secure environment; and incorporating manufacturer's recommendation(s).	MOM-3, b			0	0	0	2.9.5-3;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
12		12	Sound inventory control practices guide storage of the medications in all areas throughout the organisation.	MOM-3, c			0	0	0	2.9.5-5;			0	0	0
13		13	Look-alike and Sound-alike medications are identified and stored physically apart from each other.	MOM-3, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	The hospital stores medicine in a correct and safe manner.	14	Patient-administered medicine is only available to the specific patient and the staff.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.5-4;			0	0	0
15		15	The department documents that medicine cupboards are checked at regular intervals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.5-6;			0	0	0
16		16	If the inspection of the medicine cupboard shows lacks, initiatives have been made to improve the quality. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.5-7;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
17	Documented policies and procedures guide the safe and rational prescription of medications.	17	Documented policies and procedures exist for prescription of medications.	MOM-4, a			0	0	0	2.9.1-1; 2.9.1-2;			9.5.2-1; 10.5.2-1; 11.5.2-1; 12.5.2-1; 13.5.2-1; 15.5.2-1; 16.5.2-1; 17.5.2-1; 18.8.2-1; 19.6.2-1; 20.8.2-1; 23.4.2-1;			
18		18	These incorporate inclusion of good practices/guidelines for rational prescription of medications.	MOM-4, b			0	0	0	2.9.1-1;			0	0	0	
19		19	The organisation determines the minimum requirements of a prescription.	MOM-4, c			0	0	0	2.9.1-1;			0	0	0	
20		20	Known drug allergies are ascertained before prescribing.	MOM-4, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
21		21	The organisation determines who can write orders.	MOM-4, e			0	0	0	2.9.1-6; 2.9.1-1;			0	0	0	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
22		22	Orders are written in a uniform location in the medical records which also reflects patient's name and unique identification number.	MOM-4, f			0	0	0	2.9.1-3;			0	0	0
23		23	Medication orders are clear, legible, dated, timed, named and signed.	MOM-4, g			0	0	0	2.9.1-5;			0	0	0
24		24	Medication orders contain the name of the medicine, route of administration, dose to be administered and frequency/time of administration.	MOM-4, h			0	0	0	2.9.1-4;			0	0	0
25		25	Documented policy and procedure on verbal orders is implemented.	MOM-4, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
26		26	The organisation defines a list of high-risk medication(s).	MOM-4, j			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
27		27	Audit of medication orders/prescription is carried out to check for safe and rational prescription of medications.	MOM-4, k			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28		28	Reconciliation of medications occur at transition points of patient care.	MOM-4, l			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
29		29	Corrective and/or preventive action(s) is taken based on the analysis, where appropriate.	MOM-4, m			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30	Documented policies and procedures guide the safe dispensing of medications.	30	Documented policies and procedures guide the safe dispensing of medications.	MOM-5, a			0	0	0	2.9.2-1;			0	0	0
31		31	The procedure addresses medication recall.	MOM-5, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
32		32	Expiry dates are checked prior to dispensing.	MOM-5, c			0	0	0	2.9.5-5;			0	0	0
33		33	There is a procedure for near expiry medications.	MOM-5, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
34		34	Labelling requirements are documented and implemented by the organisation.	MOM-5, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
35		35	High-risk medication orders are verified prior to dispensing.	MOM-5, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
36	The hospital has a process for correct dispensing of medicine.	36	Control of difficult, individual dose calculations is conducted.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.2-2;			0	0	0
37		37	Medicine poured and injection fluids/infusion fluids are labelled.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.2-3;			0	0	0
38		38	Dispensing of medicine is documented in the unified pharmaceutical documentation	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.2-4;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			system.												
39	There are documented policies and procedures for medication administration.	39	Medications are administered by those who are permitted by law to do so.	MOM-6, a			0	0	0	2.9.3-2;			0	0	0
40		40	Prepared medication is labelled prior to preparation of a second drug.	MOM-6, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
41		41	Patient is identified prior to administration.	MOM-6, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.2-6; 10.5.2-6; 11.5.2-6; 12.5.2-6; 13.5.2-6; 15.5.2-6; 16.5.2-6; 17.5.2-6; 18.8.2-6; 19.6.2-6; 20.8.2-6; 23.4.2-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
42		42	Medication is verified from the order and physically inspected prior to administration.	MOM-6, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.2-7; 10.5.2-7; 11.5.2-7; 12.5.2-7; 13.5.2-7; 15.5.2-7; 16.5.2-7; 17.5.2-7; 18.8.2-7; 19.6.2-7; 20.8.2-7; 23.4.2-6;			
43		43	Dosage is verified from the order prior to administration.	MOM-6, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
44		44	Route is verified from the order prior to administration.	MOM-6, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
45		45	Timing is verified from the order prior to administration.	MOM-6, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
46		46	Medication administration is documented.	MOM-6, h			0	0	0	2.9.3-3;			9.5.2-8; 10.5.2-8; 11.5.2-8; 12.5.2-8; 13.5.2-8; 15.5.2-8; 16.5.2-8; 17.5.2-8; 18.8.2-8; 19.6.2-8; 20.8.2-8; 23.4.2-7;			
47		47	Documented policies and procedures govern patient's self-administration of medications.	MOM-6, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48		48	Documented policies and procedures govern patient's own medications brought from outside the organisation.	MOM-6, j			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
49	Medication use throughout the hospital complies with applicable laws and regulations.	49	Only those permitted by the hospital and by relevant laws and regulations prescribe medication.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.2-2; 10.5.2-2; 11.5.2-2; 12.5.2-2; 13.5.2-2; 15.5.2-2; 16.5.2-2; 17.5.2-2; 18.8.2-2; 19.6.2-2; 20.8.2-2; 23.4.2-2;
50		50	On admission, all current medication taken by the patient is documented in the patient record, including herbal and over-the-counter medication.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.2-4; 10.5.2-4; 11.5.2-4; 12.5.2-4; 13.5.2-4; 15.5.2-4; 16.5.2-4; 17.5.2-4; 18.8.2-4; 19.6.2-4; 20.8.2-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
51		51	Verbal and telephonic medication prescriptions are documented according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
52	Patients are monitored after medication administration.	52	Documented policies and procedures guide the monitoring of patients after medication administration.	MOM-7, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
53		53	The organisation defines those situations where close	MOM-7, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			monitoring is required.												
54		54	Monitoring is done in a collaborative manner.	MOM-7, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
55		55	Medications are changed where appropriate based on the monitoring.	MOM-7, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
56	Near misses, medication errors and adverse drug events are reported and analysed.	56	Documented procedure exists to capture near miss, medication error and adverse drug event.	MOM-8, a			0	0	0	2.9.3-4;			0	0	
57		57	Near miss, medication error and adverse drug event are defined.	MOM-8, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.2-10; 10.5.2-10; 11.5.2-10; 12.5.2-10; 13.5.2-10; 15.5.2-10; 16.5.2-10; 17.5.2-10; 18.8.2-10; 19.6.2-10; 20.8.2-10; 23.4.2-9;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
58		58	These are reported within a specified time frame.	MOM-8, c			0	0	0	2.9.3-5;			9.5.2-11; 10.5.2-11; 11.5.2-11; 12.5.2-11; 13.5.2-11; 15.5.2-11; 16.5.2-11; 17.5.2-11; 18.8.2-11; 19.6.2-11; 20.8.2-11; 23.4.2-10;			
59		59	They are collected and analysed.	MOM-8, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
60		60	Corrective and/or preventive action(s) are taken based on the analysis where appropriate.	MOM-8, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
61	Documented procedures guide the use of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances.	61	Documented procedures guide the use of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances which are in consonance with local and national regulations.	MOM-9, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
62		62	These drugs are stored in a secure manner.	MOM-9, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
63		63	A proper record is kept of the usage, administration and	MOM-9, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			disposal of these drugs.												
64		64	These drugs are handled by appropriate personnel in accordance with the documented procedure.	MOM-9, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
65	Documented policies and procedures guide the usage of chemotherapeutic agents.	65	Documented policies and procedures guide the usage of chemotherapeutic agents.	MOM-10, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5.1-1;		
66		66	Chemotherapy is prescribed by those who have the knowledge to monitor and treat the adverse effect of chemotherapy.	MOM-10, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
67		67	Chemotherapy is prepared in a proper and safe manner and administered by qualified personnel.	MOM-10, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
68		68	Chemotherapy drugs are disposed in accordance with legal requirements.	MOM-10, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
69		69	Patient and family are educated regarding benefits/risks of chemotherapy, precautions to be taken and possible adverse reactions.	MOM-10, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
70	Medication and chemotherapy are safely administered.	70	Only those permitted by the hospital and by relevant laws and regulations administer medication/chemotherapy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.2-3; 10.5.2-3; 11.5.2-3; 12.5.2-3; 13.5.2-3; 15.5.2-3; 16.5.2-3; 17.5.2-3; 18.8.2-3; 19.6.2-3; 20.8.2-3; 23.4.2-3;
71	Medication/ chemotherapy is stored in a safe and clean environment.	71	Medication/ chemotherapy is stored in a locked storage device or cabinet that is accessible only to authorised personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5.3-1;
72		72	Medication identified for special control (by law or hospital policy) is stored in a cabinet of substantial construction, for which only authorised personnel have the keys.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5.3-2;
73		73	Medication identified for special control (by law or hospital policy) is accurately	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5.3-3;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			accounted for.												
74		74	Medication/chemotherapy agents are securely and legibly labelled with relevant information as required by law and hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5.3-4;
75		75	Medication/chemotherapy is stored in a clean environment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5.3-5;
76		76	Medication/chemotherapy is stored in accordance with manufacturer's instructions relating to temperature, light and humidity.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5.3-6;
77		77	A refrigerator is available for medication/ chemotherapy requiring storage at low temperatures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5.3-7;
78		78	The temperature of the refrigerator is monitored and recorded.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5.3-8;
79		79	Appropriate action is taken and recorded when the temperature of the refrigerator is outside the recommended range.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5.3-9;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
80		80	Chemotherapy preparation is undertaken with protective gear and in an appropriate environment to protect the workers against possible adverse effects.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5.3-11;
81	Documented policies and procedures govern usage of radioactive drugs.	81	Documented policies and procedures govern usage of radioactive drugs.	MOM-11, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
82		82	These policies and procedures are in consonance with laws and regulations.	MOM-11, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
83		83	The policies and procedures include the safe storage, preparation, handling, distribution and disposal of radioactive drugs.	MOM-11, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
84		84	Staff, patients and visitors are educated on safety precautions.	MOM-11, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
85	Documented policies and procedures guide the use of implantable prosthesis and medical devices.	85	Usage of implantable prosthesis and medical devices is guided by scientific criteria for each individual item and national/international recognised guidelines/approvals for such specific	MOM-12, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			item(s).												
86		86	Documented policies and procedures govern procurement, storage/stocking, issuance and usage of implantable prosthesis and medical devices incorporating manufacturer's recommendation(s).	MOM-12, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
87		87	Patient and his/her family are counselled for the usage of implantable prosthesis and medical device including precautions, if any.	MOM-12, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
88		88	The batch and serial number of the implantable prosthesis and medical devices are recorded in the patient's medical record, the master logbook and the discharge summary.	MOM-12, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
89	Documented policies and procedures guide the use of medical supplies and consumables.	89	There is a defined process for acquisition of medical supplies and consumables.	MOM-13, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
90		90	Medical supplies and consumables are used in a safe	MOM-13, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
			manner, where appropriate.													
91		91	Medical supplies and consumables are stored in a clean, safe and secure environment; and incorporating manufacturer's recommendation(s).	MOM-13, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
92		92	Sound inventory control practices guide storage of medical supplies and consumables.	MOM-13, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
93		93	There is a mechanism in place to verify the condition of medical supplies and consumables.	MOM-13, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
94	Integrating clinical governance	94	Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Implementing policies and procedures for medication management b. Managing risks associated with medication management c. Identifying training requirements for medication management				0	0	0	MSS-4.1, a,b,c				0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
95	Applying quality improvement systems	95	The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Monitoring the effectiveness and performance of medication management b. Implementing strategies to improve medication management outcomes and associated processes c. Reporting on outcomes for medication management	0	0	0	MSS-4.2, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
96	Partnering with consumers	96	Clinicians use organisational processes from the Partnering with Consumers Standard in medication management to: a. Actively involve patients in their own care b. Meet the patient's information needs c. Share decision-making	0	0	0	MSS-4.3, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
97	Medicines scope of clinical practice	97	The health service organisation has processes to define and verify the scope of clinical practice for prescribing, dispensing and	0	0	0	MSS-4.4			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			administering medicines for relevant clinicians.												
98	Medication reconciliation	98	Clinicians take a best possible medication history, which is documented in the healthcare record on presentation or as early as possible in the episode of care	0	0	0	MSS-4.5			0	0	0	0	0	0
99		99	Clinicians review a patient's current medication orders against their best possible medication history and the documented treatment plan, and reconcile any discrepancies on presentation and at transitions of care	0	0	0	MSS-4.6			0	0	0	0	0	0
100	Adverse drug reactions	100	The health service organisation has processes for documenting a patient's history of medicine allergies and adverse drug reactions in the healthcare record on presentation	0	0	0	MSS-4.7			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
101		101	The health service organisation has processes for documenting adverse drug reactions experienced by patients during an episode of care in the healthcare record and in the organisation-wide incident reporting system	0	0	0	MSS-4.8			0	0	0	0	0	0
102		102	The health service organisation has processes for reporting adverse drug reactions experienced by patients to the Therapeutic Goods Administration, in accordance with its requirements	0	0	0	MSS-4.9			0	0	0	0	0	0
103	Provision of a medicines list	103	The health service organisation has processes to: a. Generate a current medicines list and the reasons for any changes b. Distribute the current medicines list to receiving clinicians at transitions of care c. Provide patients on discharge with a current medicines list and the reasons for any changes	0	0	0	MSS-4.12, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
104	Information and decision support tools for medicines	104	The health service organisation ensures that information and decision support tools for medicines are available to clinicians	0	0	0	MSS-4.13			0	0	0	0	0	0
105	Safe and secure storage and distribution of medicines	105	The health service organisation complies with manufacturers' directions, legislation, and jurisdictional requirements for the: a. Safe and secure storage and distribution of medicines b. Storage of temperature-sensitive medicines and cold chain management c. Disposal of unused, unwanted or expired medicines	0	0	0	MSS-4.14, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
106	Medication is stored in a secure and clean environment.	106	Separate designated storage areas for the receipt and unpacking of incoming goods are provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.5.1-1;
107		107	Hazardous and flammable materials are stored in accordance with relevant regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.5.1-2;
108		108	Separate designated storage areas for materials under	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.5.1-3;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			quarantine are provided.												
109		109	Safe and secure storage facilities are available, including smoke detectors, security alarm systems and/or barriers.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.5.1-4;
110		110	Stock control systems are managed in the pharmacy and other related departments.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.5.1-5;
111		111	A management information system is available, which provides accurate statistics relating to pharmaceutical receipts and issues.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.5.1-6;
112		112	Medication is stored in a clean environment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.5.1-7;
113		113	The cold chain is maintained for medication where necessary.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.5.1-8;
114		114	Medication storage areas are protected from heat, light and moisture and temperatures are monitored and recorded.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.5.1-9;
115		115	Appropriate action is taken when temperatures are higher or lower than recommended limits.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.5.1-10;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
116		116	Medication identified for special control by law or hospital policy are stored in a cabinet of substantial construction, for which only authorised personnel have a key.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.5.1-11;
117		117	Medication identified for special control by law or hospital policy are accurately accounted for.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.5.1-12;
118	High-risk medicines	118	The health service organisation: a. Identifies high-risk medicines used within the organisation b. Has a system to store, prescribe, dispense and administer high-risk medicines safely	0	0	0	MSS-4.15, a,b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0
119	Medicine used in emergency situations is easily accessible.	119	There are guidelines describing how the availability of medicine for use in emergency situations is secured.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.6-1;			0	0	0	
120		120	The emergency trays are available and are controlled in accordance with the	MOM-3, e			0	0	0	2.9.6-2;			0	0	0	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
			guidelines.													
121		121	The emergency trays are available for relevant staff in emergency situations.	MOM-3, f			0	0	0	2.9.6-3;			0	0	0	
122		122	The control of the emergency trays is documented in the logbook and in particular it is noted that emergency trays are full after opening.	MOM-3, g			0	0	0	2.9.6-4;			0	0	0	
123		123	If the inspection shows lacks in relation to availability and content of emergency trays, initiatives have been made to improve the quality. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	MOM-3, g			0	0	0	2.9.6-5;			0	0	0	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
124	The hospital uses medicine review for defined risk patients.	124	There are guidelines describing how, when and whom makes and documents medicine review which are common for the hospital. Likewise, the guidelines document criteria for when patients should have medicine reviews performed. The guidelines furthermore define criteria when to perform medicine reviews among outpatients with a chronic disease. If the responsibility is shared with the primary sector, the division of responsibility and tasks is documented.	0	0	0	MSS-4.10,a,b,c			2.9.7-1;			0	0	0
125		125	Medicine review is made in accordance with the hospital's guidelines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.7-2;			0	0	0
126		126	The medicine review is documented in the patient health record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.7-3;			0	0	0
127		127	The hospital has targets for the quality of medicine review. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. Data are analysed and assessed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.7-4;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
128		128	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of medicine review. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.7-5;			0	0	0
129	The hospital receives medicine of an appropriate amount in relation to the handling of tasks.	129	There are guidelines for ordering and receiving medicine both in connection with planned and acute situations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.8-1;			0	0	0
130		130	The hospital describes precautionary measures for situations where the supply of medicine fails.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.8-2;			0	0	0
131		131	Medicine is ordered and requested in accordance with the guidelines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.8-3;			0	0	0
132		132	Follow-up on breakdown in deliveries and faulty deliveries on reception of medicine is conducted.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.8-4;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
133		133	Relevant managers and staff are familiar with the precautionary measures for situations where the supply of medicine fails.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.9.8-5;			0	0	0
134	Medication use is organised throughout the hospital to meet the needs of patients.	134	The pharmaceutical service is managed by a registered pharmacist with clearly defined responsibilities and accountability for all aspects of the service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.1.1-1;		
135		135	A registered pharmacist is designated as deputy to act in the absence of the manager.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.1.1-2;		
136		136	The responsibilities of the pharmacy manager include ensuring compliance with laws and regulations relating to the service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.1.1-3;		
137		137	The responsibilities of the pharmacy manager include ensuring compliance with pharmacy practice and current pharmaceutical and other health professional guidelines, e.g. medical and nursing.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.1.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
138		138	The pharmacy manager facilitates collaboration between pharmacy personnel and other relevant personnel in the hospital to ensure safe prescribing, ordering, storage, preparation, dispensing and administration of medications.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.1.1-5;
139		139	The manager ensures that reliable drug information is readily accessible.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.1.1-6;
140	An appropriate selection of medication for prescribing or ordering is stocked or readily available.	140	Medication available for prescribing and ordering is appropriate for the hospital's mission, patient needs and services provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.2.1-1;
141		141	There is a list of medication stocked in the hospital or readily available from outside sources.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.2.1-2;
142		142	There is a method for control of medication use within the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.2.1-3;
143		143	There is a process to obtain required medication which is not routinely stocked or normally available to the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.2.1-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
144		144	There is a process to obtain required medication when the pharmacy is closed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.2.1-5;		
145		145	Emergency medication is available in the hospital within a time frame to meet emergency needs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.2.1-6;		
146		146	Emergency medication is monitored and replaced in a timely manner, after use or when expired or damaged.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.2.1-7;		
147		147	In the event of medication stock outs, prescribers are informed of the stock out and advised of suitable alternatives.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.2.1-8;		
148	There is a collaborative process to develop and monitor policies and procedures for the pharmaceutical service.	148	Policies and procedures, which include the standard intent are developed and implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.3.1-1;		
149		149	There is evidence that policies and procedures have been developed collaboratively with all relevant departments.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.3.1-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
150	Medication is dispensed in accordance with legislation, regulations and professional standards of practice.	150	Medication is prepared and dispensed in a safe and clean environment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.4.1-3;		
151		151	There is a uniform medication dispensing and distribution system throughout the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.4.1-4;		
152		152	The system supports accurate and timely dispensing.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.4.1-5;		
153		153	Where computer programs are used to check for contra-indications and potential drug interactions for prescribed medication, there is a process to ensure that the program is current and updated according to the manufacturer's recommendations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.4.1-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
154	Medication is ordered according to hospital policy and stored in a secure and clean environment.	154	Medication is ordered according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.1-1; 10.5.2-1; 11.5.2-1; 12.5.2-1; 13.5.2-1; 15.5.2-1; 16.5.2-1; 18.8.1-1; 19.6.1-1; 20.8.2-1; 18.8.1-1; 19.6.1-1; 20.8.2-1; 23.4.1-1;
155		155	All storage areas for medicines and pharmaceutical supplies comply with current pharmaceutical acts and regulations and manufacturer guidelines (e.g. security, temperature control).	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.1-2; 10.5.2-2; 11.5.2-2; 12.5.2-2; 13.5.2-2; 15.5.2-2; 16.5.2-2; 18.8.1-2; 19.6.1-2; 20.8.2-2; 23.4.1-2;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
156		156	Medication is stored in a locked storage device or cabinet that is accessible only to authorised personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.1-3; 10.5.2-3; 11.5.2-3; 12.5.2-3; 13.5.2-3; 15.5.2-3; 16.5.2-3; 18.8.1-3; 19.6.1-3; 20.8.2-3; 23.4.1-3;		
157		157	Medication identified for special control by legislation or hospital policy is stored in a cabinet of substantial construction, for which only authorised personnel have the keys.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.1-4; 10.5.2-4; 11.5.2-41; 12.5.2-4; 13.5.2-4; 15.5.2-4; 16.5.2-4; 18.8.1-4; 19.6.1-4; 20.8.2-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
158		158	Medication identified for special control by legislation or hospital policy is accurately accounted for.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.1-5; 10.5.2-5; 11.5.2-5; 12.5.2-5; 13.5.2-5; 15.5.2-5; 16.5.2-5; 18.8.1-5; 19.6.1-5; 20.8.2-5;		
159		159	Medication is securely and legibly labelled with relevant information as required by legislation and hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.1-6; 10.5.2-6; 11.5.2-6; 12.5.2-6; 13.5.2-6; 15.5.2-6; 16.5.2-6; 18.8.1-6; 19.6.1-6; 20.8.2-6; 23.4.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
160		160	Medication is stored in a clean environment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.1-7; 10.5.2-7; 11.5.2-7; 12.5.2-7; 13.5.2-7; 15.5.2-7; 16.5.2-7; 18.8.1-7; 19.6.1-7; 20.8.2-7; 23.4.1-5;
161		161	A dedicated refrigerator is available for medication requiring storage at low temperatures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.1-8; 10.5.2-8; 11.5.2-8; 12.5.2-8; 13.5.2-8; 15.5.2-8; 16.5.2-8; 18.8.1-8; 19.6.1-8; 20.8.2-8;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
162		162	The temperature of the refrigerator is monitored and recorded according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.1-9; 10.5.2-9; 11.5.2-9; 12.5.2-9; 13.5.2-9; 15.5.2-9; 16.5.2-9; 18.8.1-9; 19.6.1-9; 20.8.2-9;
163		163	Appropriate action is taken and recorded when the temperature of the refrigerator is outside the recommended range.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.5.1-10; 10.5.2-10; 11.5.2-10; 12.5.2-10; 13.5.2-10; 15.5.2-10; 16.5.2-10; 18.8.1-10; 19.6.1-10; 20.8.2-10;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
164		164	Expiry dates (including those of emergency drugs) are checked regularly at defined intervals according to hospital policy and drugs are replaced before the expiry date.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10.5.2-11; 11.5.2-11; 12.5.2-11; 13.5.2-11; 15.5.2-11; 16.5.2-11; 17.5.3-10; 18.8.1-11; 19.6.1-11; 20.8.2-11; 23.4.1-6;
165	Medication and chemotherapy use in the hospital complies with applicable laws and regulations.	165	The use of verbal/telephonic medication orders is documented according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5.1-2;
166		166	Only those permitted by the hospital and by relevant laws and regulations prescribe medication and chemotherapy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5.1-3;
167		167	Medication, including herbal and over-the-counter medication, brought into the hospital by the patient or the family is known to the patient's medical practitioner and is noted in the patient's	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.5.1-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			record.												

Table Number-17: Prevention and Control of Infection (PCI):

The Prevention and Control of Infection has 32 Standards and 132 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	The organisation has a well-designed, comprehensive and coordinated Hospital Infection Prevention and Control (HIC) programme aimed at reducing/eliminating risks to patients, visitors and providers of care.	1	The hospital infection prevention and control programme is documented which aims at preventing and reducing risk of healthcare associated infections in all areas of the hospital.	HIC-1, a			0	0	0	1.5.1 -1; 1.5.3 -1;			8.1.1-1; 8.2.2-3; 8.2.2-4; 8.2.2-5; 21.10.1-3;		
2		2	The infection prevention and control programme is a continuous process and updated at least once in a year.	HIC-1, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3		3	The hospital has a multi-disciplinary infection control committee, which coordinates all infection prevention and control activities.	HIC-1, c			0	0	0	1.5.1 -2;			8.2.2-3; 8.2.2-4; 8.2.2-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
4		4	The hospital has an infection control team, which coordinates implementation of all infection prevention and control activities.	HIC-1, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	8.2.2-3; 8.2.2-4; 8.2.2-5;		
5		5	The hospital has designated infection control officer as part of the infection control team.	HIC-1, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6		6	The hospital has designated infection control nurse(s) as part of the infection control team.	HIC-1, f			0	0	0	1.5.1 -3;			0	0	0
7	Infection control management	7	The programme is appropriate to the size and geographic location of the hospital, the services offered and the patients served.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.1 -1;			8.1.1-2;		
8		8	Coordination of infection control activities involves medical, nursing and other personnel as appropriate to the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.1 -2;			8.1.1-3;		
9		9	All patient, personnel and visitor areas of the hospital are included in the infection control activities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.1 -3;			8.1.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
10		10	Responsibility for coordinating the activities is assigned to one individual or a committee.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.1 -3;			8.1.1-5;		
11		11	The individuals are competent to manage the scope and complexity of the activities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.1 -4;			8.1.1-6;		
12		12	The infection control activities are based on current scientific knowledge, accepted practice guidelines and applicable laws and regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.1.1-7;		
13		13	Information management systems support the infection control activities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.1.1-8; 8.2.2-3; 8.2.2-4; 8.2.2-5;		
14	The organisation implements the policies and procedures laid down in the Infection Control Manual in all areas of the hospital.	14	The organisation identifies the various high-risk areas and procedures and implements policies and/or procedures to prevent infection in these areas.	HIC-2, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	8.2.2-3; 8.2.2-4; 8.2.2-5;		
15		15	The organisation adheres to standard precautions at all times.	HIC-2, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16		16	The organisation adheres to hand-hygiene guidelines.	HIC-2, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
17		17	<p>Clinicians assess infection risks and use transmission-based precautions based on the risk of transmission of infectious agents, and consider:</p> <p>a. Patients' risks, which are evaluated at referral, on admission or on presentation for care, and re-evaluated when clinically required during care</p> <p>b. Whether a patient has a communicable disease, or an existing or a pre-existing colonisation or infection with organisms of local or national significance</p> <p>c. Accommodation needs to manage infection risks</p> <p>d. The need to control the environment</p> <p>e. Precautions required when the patient is moved within the facility or to external services</p> <p>f. The need for additional environmental cleaning or disinfection</p> <p>g. Equipment requirements</p>	HIC-2, d			PCH AIS-3.5; PCH AIS-3.6, a,b,c,d,e,f, g			1.5.6-2;			22.7.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
18		18	The organisation adheres to safe injection and infusion practices.	HIC-2, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19		19	The organisation adheres to cleaning, disinfection and sterilization practices.	HIC-2, f			0	0	0	1.5.6-2;			0	0	0
20		20	An appropriate antibiotic policy is established and documented	HIC-2, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
21		21	The organisation implements the antibiotic policy and monitors rational use of antimicrobial agents.	HIC-2, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
22		22	The organisation adheres to laundry and linen management processes.	HIC-2, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
23		23	The organisation adheres to kitchen sanitation and food-handling issues.	HIC-2, j			0	0	0	0	0	0	22.7.1-3;		
24		24	The organisation has appropriate engineering controls to prevent infections.	HIC-2, k			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25		25	The organisation adheres to housekeeping procedures.	HIC-2, l			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
26	The organisation performs surveillance activities to capture and monitor infection prevention and control data.	26	Surveillance activities are appropriately directed towards the identified high-risk areas and procedures.	HIC-3, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	8.2.1-1;		
27		27	A Collection of surveillance data is an on-going process.	HIC-3, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28		28	Verification of data is done on a regular basis by the infection control team.	HIC-3, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29		29	The scope of surveillance activities incorporates tracking and analyzing of infection risks, rates and trends.	HIC-3, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30		30	Surveillance activities include monitoring the compliance with hand-hygiene guidelines.	HIC-3, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31		31	Surveillance activities include mechanisms to capture the occurrence of epidemiological significant diseases, multi-drug-resistant organisms and highly virulent infections.	HIC-3, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
32		32	Surveillance activities include monitoring the effectiveness of housekeeping services.	HIC-3, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
33		33	Appropriate feedback regarding Healthcare Associated Infection (HAI) rates is provided on a regular basis to appropriate personnel.	HIC-3, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
34		34	In cases of notifiable diseases, information (in relevant format) is sent to appropriate authorities.	HIC-3, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
35	Surveillance	35	The health service organisation has a surveillance strategy for healthcare associated infections and antimicrobial use that: a. Collects data on healthcare-associated infections and antimicrobial use relevant to the size and scope of the organisation b. Monitors, assesses and uses surveillance data to reduce the risks associated with healthcare-associated infections and support appropriate antimicrobial prescribing c. Reports surveillance data on healthcare-associated infections and antimicrobial	0	0	0	PCH AIS-3.4, a,b,c			0	0	0	8.2.1-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			use to the workforce, the governing body, consumers and other relevant groups.												
36	The organisation takes actions to prevent and control Healthcare Associated Infections (HAI) / Nosocomial Infections in patients.	36	The organisation takes action to prevent catheter-associated urinary tract Infections.	HIC-4, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
37		37	The organisation takes action to prevent Ventilator Associated Pneumonia.	HIC-4, b			0	0	0	1.5.3-6;			0	0	0
38		38	The organisation takes action to prevent catheter linked blood stream infections.	HIC-4, c			0	0	0	1.5.3-5;			0	0	0
39		39	The organisation takes action to prevent surgical site infections.	HIC-4, d			0	0	0	1.5.3-7;			0	0	0
40	Infection control processes	40	The hospital has identified those processes associated with the risk of infection and implemented strategies to reduce such risk.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.2.1-2;		
41		41	Policies and procedures to guide personnel in the implementation of adequate infection prevention and	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.2.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			control measures are readily accessible and implemented.												
42		42	Processes associated with risk are documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.2.1-4;		
43		43	Epidemiologically significant diseases and organisms are included as appropriate to the hospital and its community.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.2.1-6;		
44		44	Emerging or re-emerging infections are included as appropriate to the hospital and its community.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.2.1-7;		
45	The organisation provides adequate and appropriate resources for prevention and control of Healthcare Associated Infections (HAI).	45	Adequate and appropriate personal protective equipment, soaps, and disinfectants are available and used correctly.	HIC-5, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	8.2.2-1; 22.7.1-1; 32.6.1-2;		
46		46	Adequate and appropriate facilities for hand hygiene in all patient-care areas are accessible to healthcare providers.	HIC-5, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
47		47	Isolation/barrier nursing facilities are available.	HIC-5, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48		48	Appropriate pre- and post-exposure prophylaxis is provided to all staff members	HIC-5, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	21.10.1-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			concerned.												
49	The organisation identifies and takes appropriate action to control outbreaks of infections.	49	Organisation has a documented procedure for identifying an outbreak.	HIC-6, a			0	0	0	1.5.3 -2; 1.5.3 -3; 1.5.3 -4;			0	0	0
50		50	The hygiene organisation prepares an annual report describing handling of outbreak of infectious diseases, screening for resistant bacteria and other nationally and locally specified focus areas set out in the hospital's hygiene policy. The report includes targets for the hospital's handling of nosocomial infections.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.3-8;			22.7.1-3;		
51		51	Organisation has a documented procedure for handling such outbreaks.	HIC-6, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	8.2.1-5;		
52		52	This procedure is implemented during outbreaks.	HIC-6, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	8.2.1-5;		
53		53	After the outbreak is over appropriate corrective actions are taken to prevent recurrence.	HIC-6, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	8.2.1-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
54	There are documented policies and procedures for sterilization activities in the organisation.	54	The organisation provides adequate space and appropriate zoning for sterilization activities.	HIC-7, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
55		55	Documented procedure guides the cleaning, packing, disinfection and/or sterilization, storing and issue of items.	HIC-7, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
56		56	Reprocessing of instruments and equipment are covered.	HIC-7, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
57		57	The organisation shall have a documented policy and procedure for reprocessing of devices whenever applicable.	HIC-7, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
58		58	Regular validation tests for sterilization are carried out and documented.	HIC-7, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
59		59	There is an established recall procedure when breakdown in the sterilization system is identified.	HIC-7, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
60	Biomedical waste (BMW) is handled in an appropriate and safe manner.	60	The organisation adheres to statutory provisions with regard to biomedical waste.	HIC-8, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
61		61	Proper segregation and collection of biomedical waste from all patient-care areas of the hospital is implemented and monitored.	HIC-8, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	21.10.1-2;		
62		62	The organisation ensures that biomedical waste is stored and transported to the site of treatment and disposal in properly covered vehicles within stipulated time limits in a secure manner.	HIC-8, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
63		63	The biomedical waste treatment facility is managed as per statutory provisions (if in-house) or outsourced to authorized contractor(s).	HIC-8, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
64		64	Appropriate personal protective measures are used by all categories of staff handling biomedical waste.	HIC-8, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	8.2.2-1; 22.7.1-3;		
65	The infection control programme is supported by the management and includes training of staff.	65	The management makes available resources required for the infection control programme.	HIC-9, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	8.2.2-1; 22.7.1-1;		
66		66	The organisation earmarks adequate funds from its annual	HIC-9, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			budget in this regard.												
67		67	The organisation conducts induction training for all staff.	HIC-9, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
68		68	The organisation conducts appropriate —in-service training sessions for all staff at least once in a year.	HIC-9, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	21.10.1-2		
69	Integrating clinical governance	69	The workforce uses the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Implementing policies and procedures for healthcare-associated infections and antimicrobial stewardship b. Managing risks associated with healthcare-associated infections and antimicrobial stewardship c. Identifying training requirements for preventing and controlling healthcare-associated infections, and antimicrobial stewardship	0	0	0	PCHAIS-3.1, a,b,c			0	0	0	21.10.1-2		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
70	Applying quality improvement systems	70	The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Monitoring the performance of systems for prevention and control of healthcare-associated infections, and the effectiveness of the antimicrobial stewardship program b. Implementing strategies to improve outcomes and associated processes of systems for prevention and control of healthcareassociated infections, and antimicrobial stewardship c. Reporting on the outcomes of prevention and control of healthcareassociated infections, and the antimicrobial stewardship program	0	0	0	PCH AIS-3.2, a,b,c			0	0	0	21.10.1-2;			

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
71	Partnering with consumers	71	Clinicians use organisational processes from the Partnering with Consumers Standard when preventing and managing healthcare-associated infections, and implementing the antimicrobial stewardship program to: a. Actively involve patients in their own care b. Meet the patient's information needs c. Share decision-making	0	0	0	PCHAIS-3.3, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
72		72	The health service organisation has processes for communicating relevant details of a patient's infectious status whenever responsibility for care is transferred between clinicians or health service organisations	0	0	0	PCHAIS-3.7			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
73	Hand hygiene is correctly performed and correct uniform is used.	73	The health service organisation has a hand hygiene program that: a. Is consistent with the current National Hand Hygiene Initiative, b. Addresses noncompliance or inconsistency with the current National Hand Hygiene Initiative	0	0	0	PCHAI-3.8			1.5.5-1;			0	0	0
74		74	Hand hygiene is implemented in accordance with the hospital's guidelines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.5-3;			0	0	0
75		75	Uniform and use of hand jewellery and wrist watches are in accordance with the hospital's guidelines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.5-4;			0	0	0
76		76	The hospital has goals for the quality of hand and uniform hygiene. The goals could be process goals (implementation of correct procedures) and outcomes (occurrence of infections related to lacks in hand and uniform hygiene). The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.5-2; 1.5.5-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			of the goals. Data are analysed and assessed.												
77		77	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of hand and uniform hygiene. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.5-6;			0	0	0
78	Aseptic technique	78	The health service organisation has processes for aseptic technique that: a. Identify the procedures where aseptic technique applies b. Assess the competence of the workforce in performing aseptic technique c. Provide training to address gaps in competency d. Monitor compliance with the organisation's policies on aseptic technique	0	0	0	PCHAIS-3.9, a,b,c,d			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
79	Invasive medical devices	79	The health service organisation has processes for the appropriate use and management of invasive medical devices that are consistent with the current standard.	0	0	0	PCHAIS-3.10			0	0	0	0	0	0
80	Clean environment	80	The health service organisation has processes to maintain a clean and hygienic environment that: a. Respond to environmental risks b. Require cleaning and disinfection in line with recommended cleaning frequencies c. Include training in the appropriate use of specialised personal protective equipment for the workforce	0	0	0	PCHAIS-3.11, a,b,c,			1.5.6-2;			8.2.2-1; 22.7.1-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
81		81	The health service organisation has processes to evaluate and respond to infection risks for: a. New and existing equipment, devices and products used in the organisation b. Maintaining, repairing and upgrading buildings, equipment, furnishings and fittings c. Handling, transporting and storing linen	0	0	0	PCHAIS-3.12, a,b,c,			0	0	0	22.7.1-3;			
82	Workforce immunisation	82	The health service organisation has a risk-based workforce immunisation program that: a. Is consistent with the current edition of the national Immunisation Handbook b. Is consistent with jurisdictional requirements for vaccine-preventable diseases c. Addresses specific risks to the workforce and patients	0	0	0	PCHAIS-3.13, a,b,c,			0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
83	Reprocessing of reusable devices	83	Where reusable equipment, instruments and devices are used, the health service organisation has: a. Processes for reprocessing that are consistent with relevant national and international standards, in conjunction with manufacturers' guidelines b. A traceability process for critical and semi-critical equipment, instruments and devices that is capable of identifying <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the patient • the procedure • the reusable equipment, instruments and devices that were used for the procedure 	0	0	0	PCH AIS-3.14, a,b			0	0	0	0	0	0
84	The hospital prevents nosocomial infections while reprocessing equipment and textiles.	84	There are guidelines for procedures and working procedures while reprocessing of medical equipment for reuse.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.4-1;			0	0	0
85		85	There are joint guidelines for the entire hospital for handling, storing and washing of textiles for reuse.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.4-2;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
86		86	Medical equipment for reuse is reprocessed in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.4-3;			0	0	0
87		87	Textiles are handled and stored in a correct manner in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.4-4;			0	0	0
88		88	The hospital has targets for the quality of reprocessing medical equipment and textiles. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. The quality monitoring includes cleaning and disinfection of flexible endoscopes. Data are analysed and assessed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.4-5;			0	0	0
89		89	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of reprocessing medical equipment and textiles. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.4-6;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
			the hospital meets the quality goals.													
90	Antimicrobial stewardship	90	<p>The health service organisation has an antimicrobial stewardship program that:</p> <p>a. Includes an antimicrobial stewardship policy</p> <p>b. Provides access to, and promotes the use of, current evidence-based national therapeutic guidelines and resources on antimicrobial prescribing</p> <p>c. Has an antimicrobial formulary that includes restriction rules and approval processes</p> <p>d. Incorporates core elements, recommendations and principles from the current Antimicrobial Stewardship Clinical Care Standard</p>	0	0	0	PCHAIS-3.15, a,b,c,d				0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
91		91	<p>The antimicrobial stewardship program will:</p> <p>a. Review antimicrobial prescribing and use</p> <p>b. Use surveillance data on antimicrobial resistance and use to support appropriate prescribing</p> <p>c. Evaluate performance of the program, identify areas for improvement, and take action to improve the appropriateness of antimicrobial prescribing and use</p> <p>d. Report to clinicians and the governing body regarding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • compliance with the antimicrobial stewardship policy • antimicrobial use and resistance • appropriateness of prescribing and compliance with current evidence-based national therapeutic guidelines or resources on antimicrobial prescribing 	0	0	0	PCH AIS-3.16, a,b,c,d			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
92	Building, facilities and fixtures are cleaned in accordance with stipulated quality requirements.	92	There are plans for cleaning the hospital's buildings, facilities and fixtures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.6-1;			0	0	0
93	Obtaining of laboratory cultures	93	The hospital identifies those environmental sites from which specimens are to be collected.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.3.1.1		
94		94	The hospital identifies the frequency with which specimens are collected.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.3.1-2;		
95		95	Procedures which describe how specimens are taken and sent to the laboratory, and action to be taken when laboratory reports identify pathogenic organisms, are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.3.1-3;		
96	Infection control education for personnel	96	The hospital provides ongoing in-service training in infection control to all personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.4.1-1;		
97		97	Personnel are educated in infection control processes when new policies are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.4.1-2;		
98		98	Personnel are provided with additional education in relevant aspects of the infection control processes when significant trends are noted in surveillance	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.4.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			data.												
99		99	Patients and families are educated when appropriate to the patient's needs and condition.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
100	Infection control quality management	100	The hospital tracks infection risks, infection rates and trends in healthcare-associated infections.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.3-9;			8.2.2-2; 8.5.1-1;		
101		101	Monitoring includes the use of indicators related to infections that are epidemiologically important to the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.5.1-2;		
102		102	The hospital uses risk, rate and trend information to design or modify processes to reduce healthcare-associated infections to the lowest possible levels.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.3-10;			8.5.1-3;		
103		103	The hospital compares its infection rates with other hospitals through comparative databases.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.5.1-4;		
104		104	The results of infection monitoring in the hospital are regularly communicated to medical and nursing personnel and to the management of the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.5.1-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
105		105	The hospital reports information on infections to appropriate external public health agencies.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.5.1-6;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
106	The department/service implements infection prevention and control processes.	106	The department identifies the procedures and processes associated with the risk of infection and implements strategies to reduce risk.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
107		107	Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of respiratory tract infections.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.10.1-2; 10.10.1-2; 11.10.1-2; 12.10.1-2; 13.10.1-2; 14.6.1-2; 15.10.1-2; 16.11.1-2; 17.10.1-2; 18.14.1-2; 19.11.1-2; 20.14.1-2; 26.8.1-2; 23.7.1-2; 31.5.1-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
108		108	Personnel are trained in correct hand washing procedures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.5-1;			9.10.1-3; 10.10.1-3; 11.10.1-3; 12.10.1-3; 13.10.1-3; 14.6.1-3; 15.10.1-3; 16.11.1-3; 17.10.1-3; 18.14.1-3; 19.11.1-3; 20.14.1-3; 31.5.1-3;		
109		109	Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of urinary tract infections.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.10.1-4; 10.10.1-4; 11.10.1-4; 12.10.1-4; 13.10.1-4; 14.6.1-4; 15.10.1-4; 17.10.1-4; 18.14.1-4; 19.11.1-4; 20.14.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
110		110	Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection through intravascular invasive devices.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.10.1-5; 10.10.1-5; 11.10.1-5; 12.10.1-5; 13.10.1-5; 14.6.1-5; 15.10.1-5; 17.10.1-5; 18.14.1-5; 19.11.1-5; 20.14.1-5; 23.7.1-3; 24.7.1-2; 33.6.1-2; 34.6.1-2;		
111		111	Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection through surgical wounds.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.10.1-6; 10.10.1-6; 11.10.1-6; 12.10.1-6; 13.10.1-6; 14.6.1-6; 15.10.1-6; 17.10.1-6; 18.14.1-6; 19.11.1-6; 20.14.1-6;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
112		112	Infection control processes include safe injection practices, including single-use injection devices.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.10.1-7; 10.10.1-7; 11.10.1-7; 12.10.1-7; 13.10.1-7; 14.6.1-7; 15.10.1-7; 16.11.1-4; 17.10.1-7; 18.14.1-7; 19.11.1-7; 20.14.1-7; 24.7.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
113		113	Personnel responsible for sluicing are appropriately trained and made aware of the potential hazards associated with sluicing.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.10.1-8; 10.10.1-8; 11.10.1-8; 12.10.1-8; 13.10.1-8; 14.6.1-8; 15.10.1-8; 16.11.1-5; 17.10.1-8; 18.14.1-8; 19.11.1-8; 20.14.1-8; 24.7.1-4; 29.6.1-5;		
114		114	Infection control measures of particle counts and bacterial growth are performed in each theatre according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.6.1-7		
115		115	Policies and procedures address the correct management of sharps within the department	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.10.1-4		
116		116	Post exposure prophylaxis kits are readily available for personnel and employees who sustain needlestick injuries.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.10.1-5		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
117		117	Information regarding needlestick injuries is recorded and action taken as appropriate	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.10.1-6		
118		118	Personnel and employees are routinely offered BCG and vaccination for Hepatitis B.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.10.1-7		
119		119	Sero-conversion is measured and recorded in personnel folders	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.10.1-8		
120		120	Booster vaccinations are offered as appropriate	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.10.1-9		
121		121	Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection through use of medical and rehabilitation equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.8.1-3		
122		122	Infection control processes include prevention of infection from contaminated instruments.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.4.1-2		
123		123	Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of food-related infections.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	28.10.1-2		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
124		124	Infection control processes include in-service training on appropriate disinfection of medical equipment as part of the maintenance process.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32.6.1-4;
125	The department/service implements infection prevention and control processes.	125	Infection control processes include prevention of infection while undertaking sterile procedures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.8.1-2;
126		126	Infection control processes include prevention of infection during the process of preparation and dispensing of medication.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.8.1-3;
127		127	Infection control processes include prevention of water contamination during the preparation of suspensions/ liquid medications.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.8.1-4;
128	The Occupational Health Service undertakes monitoring and prevention measures for notifiable medical conditions and communicable diseases where relevant.	128	The Occupational Health Service identifies, investigates and monitors the outbreak of communicable disease when indicated.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.6.1-1

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
129		129	The Occupational Health Service institutes the necessary corrective and preventive occupational health measures when required.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.6.1-2		
130		130	The Occupational Health Service participates in the development of necessary reaction teams in relation to municipal health measures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.6.1-3		
131		131	The Occupational Health Service promotes health and hygiene aimed at the prevention of occupational conditions that lead to communicable diseases.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.6.1-4		
132		132	The Occupational Health Service gathers, analyses and distributes epidemiological data and information.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.6.1-5		
133		133	There is an appropriate system in place for the prompt reporting of notifiable medical conditions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.6.1-6		
134		134	There is a system in place to ensure the referral and uptake of confirmed cases of relevant communicable diseases into	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.6.1-7		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			appropriate treatment programmes.												
135	The department/service implements infection prevention and control processes.	135	Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection related to infected linen.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.6.1-2;
136		136	Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection related to the separation of soiled and clean linen.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.6.1-3;
137		137	The sluicing process has been approved by a hospital's infection control coordinator.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.6.1-4;
138		138	Infection control processes include effective hand washing procedures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	28.10.1-3; 29.6.1-6; 30.7.1-5; 32.6.1-3;
139		139	No eating, drinking or smoking is permitted in the laundry areas.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.6.1-7
140	Infection Control in Housekeeping	140	Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection related to the cleaning and storage of cleaning equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.6-3			30.7.1-2

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
141		141	Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection related to the correct dilution of cleaning chemicals	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.5.6-4			30.7.1-3		
142		142	Infection control processes include prevention of the spread of infection related to implementing the colour-coded identification of mops for different areas	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.7.1-4		

Table Number-18: Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI):

The Continuous Quality Improvement has 36 Standards and 192 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
1	There is a structured quality improvement and continuous monitoring programme in the organisation.	1	The quality improvement programme is developed, implemented and maintained by a multi-disciplinary committee.	CQI-1, a	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.1-1; 1.2.1-2;	0	0	5.3.1-1;	0	0
2		2	The quality improvement programme is documented which is comprehensive and covers all the major elements related to quality assurance.	CQI-1, b	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.1-1;	0	0	0	0	0
3		3	There is a designated individual for coordinating and implementing the quality improvement programme.	CQI-1, c	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.1-3; 1.2.1-4;	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
4		4	The quality improvement programme promotes and demonstrates use of innovations to improve process efficiency and effectiveness.	CQI-1, d	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5		5	The designated programme is communicated and coordinated amongst all the staff of the organisation through appropriate training mechanism.	CQI-1, e	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6		6	The quality improvement programme identifies opportunities for improvement based on review at pre-defined intervals.	CQI-1, f	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7		7	The quality improvement programme is a continuous process and updated at least once in a year.	CQI-1, g	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8		8	Audits are conducted at regular intervals as a means of continuous monitoring.	CQI-1, h	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9		9	There is an established process in the organisation to monitor and improve quality of nursing care.	CQI-1, i	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M	
10	There is a structured patient-safety programme in the organisation.	10	The patient-safety programme is developed, implemented and maintained by a multi-disciplinary committee.	CQI-2, a	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-1;	0	0	0	0	0	0
11		11	The patient-safety programme is documented.	CQI-2, b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12		12	The patient-safety programme is comprehensive and covers all the major elements related to patient safety and risk management.	CQI-2, c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13		13	The scope of the programme is defined to include adverse events ranging from "no harm" to sentinel events.	CQI-2, d	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14		14	There is a designated individual for coordinating and implementing the patient safety programme.	CQI-2, e	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15		15	The designated programme is communicated and coordinated amongst all the staff of the organisation through appropriate training mechanism.	CQI-2, f	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
16		16	The patient-safety programme identifies opportunities for improvement based on review at pre-defined intervals.	CQI-2, g	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17		17	The patient-safety programme is a continuous process and updated at least once in a year.	CQI-2, h	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
18		18	The organisation adapts and implements national/international patient-safety goals/solutions.	CQI-2, i	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-2;	0	0	0	0	0
19	Managers and leaders work collaboratively to develop, implement and maintain effective risk management systems in the hospital.	19	Hospital-wide risk management systems are developed and implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-1;	0	0	5.1.1-1;	0	0
20		20	The risk management team develops and maintains a risk register for the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-2;	0	0	5.1.1-2;	0	0
21		21	Risk management processes include documented plans and actions to eliminate or reduce the identified risks.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-2;	0	0	5.1.1-3;	0	0
22		22	Risk management processes include ongoing documented monitoring of risks.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-2;	0	0	5.1.1-4;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
23		23	Management and leaders ensure the development and implementation of documented policies and procedures for risk management processes and activities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-2; 1.2.6-3;	0	0	5.1.1-5;	0	0
24		24	Ongoing in-service training of all personnel in these policies, procedures and risk management principles, including reporting of adverse events, is documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-4;	0	0	5.1.1-6;	0	0
25		25	One or more qualified and/or skilled and/or experienced individuals supervise the implementation of the risk management system.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.1.1-7;	0	0
26		26	A system for monitoring near misses/adverse events/sentinel events is available and includes the documentation of responses to recorded incidents and interventions to prevent recurrence of the incident or minimise harm in the event of a recurrence.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-5; 1.2.6-6; 1.2.6-7; 1.2.6-8; 1.2.6-9;	0	0	5.1.1-8;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
27		27	The hospital has a policy for communicating relevant information to patients affected by adverse events and sentinel events, including the outcome of investigations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-5; 1.2.6-6; 1.2.6-7; 1.2.6-8; 1.2.6-9;	0	0	5.1.1-9;	0	0
28		28	Analysed data, including near misses, adverse events and sentinel events is used to monitor the effectiveness of the risk management system.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-5; 1.2.6-6; 1.2.6-7; 1.2.6-8; 1.2.6-9;	0	0	5.1.1-10;	0	0
29		29	Risk management systems are reviewed and the risk register updated whenever there are changes in hospital systems and processes, or physical facilities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-5; 1.2.6-6; 1.2.6-7; 1.2.6-8; 1.2.6-9;	0	0	5.1.1-11;	0	0
30	As part of risk management, an occupational health and safety system is implemented in accordance with current legislation.	30	Policies and procedures on all aspects of health and safety that guide personnel in maintaining a safe work environment are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.3.1-2;	0	0
31		31	Management makes provision for occupational health services according to a documented policy framework.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.3.1-3;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
32		32	The person(s) providing the Occupational Health Service has access to a qualified Occupational Health practitioner.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.3.1-4;	0	0
33		33	The hospital provides information and training on risks specific to the healthcare workers.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.3.1-5;	0	0
34	A formalised proactive quality improvement approach is maintained in the service.	34	Indicators of performance are identified to evaluate the quality of treatment and patient care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.4.1-2;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
35		35	There are formalised quality improvement processes for the service that have been developed and agreed upon by the personnel of the service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
36		36	Indicators of performance are identified to evaluate the quality of the service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
37		37	The quality improvement cycle includes the monitoring and evaluation of the standards set and the remedial action implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
38		38	A documentation audit system is in place.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
													6.4.1-4; 9.8.1-4; 10.8.1-4; 11.8.1-4; 12.8.1-4; 13.8.1-4; 15.8.1-4; 17.8.1-4; 16.9.1-4; 14.4.1-5; 18.12.1-4; 19.9.1-4; 20.12.1-4; 21.8.1-4; 26.6.1-4; 22.5.2-4; 23.5.2-4; 24.5.1-4; 25.6.1-6; 28.8.1-4; 33.4.2-4; 34.4.2-4;		
39		39	Incidents relating to complaints about the linen management are recorded and acted upon using quality improvement	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
													29.4.1-4; 29.4.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
			methodology.												
40		40	The pharmacy has a system in place to monitor the appropriate use of antibiotics within the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.6.1-3;	0	0
41		41	Data relating to medication errors and adverse drug reactions is used to improve medication management within the hospital and monitor the effectiveness of actions taken to prevent recurrence of such events.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.6.1-4;	0	0
42		42	The quality improvement cycle includes the monitoring and evaluation of the standards set and the remedial action implemented	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.6.1-5;	0	0
43	The department/service implements risk management processes.	43	The department conducts ongoing monitoring of risks through documented assessments as part of the hospital's risk management processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.1-1; 3.6.1-1; 9.11.1-1; 10.11.1-3; 11.11.1-3; 12.11.1-3; 13.11.1-3; 15.11.1-3; 17.11.1-3; 16.12.1-1;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
													14.7.1-1; 18.15.1-1; 19.12.1-1; 20.15.1-1; 21.11.1-1; 26.9.1-1; 22.8.1-1; 23.7.1-1; 24.8.1-1; 25.9.1-1; 27.5.1-1; 28.11.1-1; 29.7.1-1; 30.8.1-1; 31.6.1-1; 32.7.1-1; 33.7.1-1; 34.7.1-1;		
44		44	A system for monitoring near misses/adverse events/sentinel events is implemented, which includes the documentation of responses to recorded incidents and interventions to prevent recurrence of the incident or minimise harm in the event of a recurrence.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.1-2; 3.6.1-1; 9.11.1-2; 10.11.1-2; 11.11.1-2; 12.11.1-2; 13.11.1-2; 15.11.1-2; 17.11.1-2; 16.12.1-2;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
													14.7.1-2; 18.15.1-2; 19.12.1-2; 20.15.1-2; 26.9.1-2; 22.8.1-2; 23.7.1-2; 24.8.1-2; 25.9.1-2; 27.5.1-1; 28.11.1-2; 29.7.1-2; 30.8.1-2; 31.6.1-2; 32.7.1-2; 33.7.1-2; 34.7.1-2;		
45		45	Relevant personnel are trained in the procedures relating to the reporting and investigation of near misses/adverse events/sentinel events.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.1-3; 9.11.1-3; 10.11.1-3; 11.11.1-3; 12.11.1-3; 13.11.1-3; 15.11.1-3; 17.11.1-3; 16.12.1-3; 14.7.1-3; 18.15.1-3;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
													19.12.1-3; 20.15.1-3; 26.9.1-3; 22.8.1-3; 24.8.1-3; 29.7.1-3; 30.8.1-3; 32.7.1-3;		
46		46	Security measures are implemented to ensure the safety of patients, personnel and visitors.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.1-4; 3.6.1-5; 9.11.1-4; 10.11.1-4; 11.11.1-4; 12.11.1-4; 13.11.1-4; 15.11.1-4; 17.11.1-4; 16.12.1-4; 14.7.1-4; 18.15.1-4; 19.12.1-4; 20.15.1-4; 26.9.1-4; 22.8.1-4; 23.7.1-3; 24.8.1-4; 25.9.1-3; 27.5.1-3;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
													28.11.1-3; 29.7.1-4; 30.8.1-4; 31.6.1-3; 32.7.1-3; 33.7.1-3; 34.7.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
47		47	Fire safety measures are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
													2.7.1-5; 3.6.1-6; 9.11.1-5; 10.11.1-5; 11.11.1-5; 12.11.1-5; 13.11.1-5; 15.11.1-5; 17.11.1-5; 16.12.1-5; 14.7.1-5; 18.15.1-5; 19.12.1-5; 20.15.1-5; 26.9.1-5; 22.8.1-5; 23.7.1-4; 24.8.1-5; 25.9.1-4; 27.5.1-4; 28.11.1-4; 29.7.1-5; 30.8.1-5; 31.6.1-4; 32.7.1-4; 33.7.1-4; 34.7.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
48		48	Hospital policy on handling, storage and disposal of healthcare waste is implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
49		49	Aids are available for manual handling of heavy goods.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.6.1-3;	0	0
50		50	Ladders are available where	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.6.1-4;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
			required.												
51		51	The operating department team participates in the hospital's surveillance of surgical capacity, volume and results.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.4.1-4;	0	0
52	Risks to the health and safety of personnel, employees or visitors are assessed and control measures introduced in order to minimise or eliminate risk and promote safety.	52	Occupational health personnel are included in the assessment of risks to the health of employees attached to any work.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-2;	0	0
53		53	Occupational health personnel have access to and utilise consultative services associated with evaluating workplace hazards such as industrial hygiene, workplace toxicology, ergonomics and epidemiology.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-3;	0	0
54		54	There are monitoring mechanisms to ensure that employees adhere to safe systems of work, including the use of protective clothing.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-4;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
55		55	Vulnerable groups of workers are identified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-5;	0	0
56		56	Where there is risk of injury, it has been determined whether it is possible to avoid manual handling, or to provide mechanical aids in place of the latter.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-6;	0	0
57		57	There is a mechanism to ensure that employees are aware of risks and their consequences.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-7;	0	0
58		58	Documented information on the safe handling and storage of hazardous substances is available and provided to the management of the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-8;	0	0
59		59	First aid is available to employees.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-9;	0	0
60		60	A system for the monitoring of near misses/adverse events/sentinel events is available, which includes the documentation of interventions and responses to recorded incidents.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-10;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
61		61	Security measures are in place and implemented to safeguard and protect employees, personnel and visitors.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-11;	0	0
62		62	Fire safety measures are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-12;	0	0
63		63	Hospital policy on handling, storage and disposal of healthcare waste is implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-13;	0	0
64	Patient Safety in patient care	64	Management ensures proactive risk management across the organisation.	ROM-6, a	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
65		65	Management provides resources for proactive risk assessment and risk reduction activities.	ROM-6, b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
66		66	Management ensures implementation of systems for internal and external reporting of system and process failures.	ROM-6, c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
67		67	Management ensures that appropriate corrective and preventive actions are taken to address safety-related incidents.	ROM-6, d	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
68	Patient safety and quality systems and Policies and procedures	68	The health service organisation uses a risk management approach to: a. Set out, review, and maintain the currency and effectiveness of, policies, procedures and protocols b. Monitor and take action to improve adherence to policies, procedures and protocols c. Review compliance with legislation, regulation and jurisdictional requirements.	0	0	0	CGS-1.7-a,b,c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
69	The hospital improves the safety and prevents injuries at patients. This includes that the hospital identifies and prevents risks and injuries and that the hospital learns from adverse events.	69	The hospital has a policy for patient safety and risk management. The policy describes risk management and the effort of reporting and learning from adverse events, including near-misses. Furthermore, the policy describes how intersectorial events are handled.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.9-1;	0	0	0	0	0
70		70	The hospital describes and substantiates which risks are made subject of a special assessment and effort.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.9-1; 1.2.9-2;	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
71		71	The hospital conducts risk assessments of the selected risks and launches initiatives based on the analyses.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.9-2;	0	0	0	0	0
72	The quality improvement programme is supported by the management.	72	The leaders at all levels in the organisation are aware of the intent of the quality improvement program and the approach to its implementation.	CQI-6, a	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
73		73	The management makes available adequate resources required for quality improvement programme.	CQI-6, b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
74		74	Organisation earmarks adequate funds from its annual budget in this regard.	CQI-6, c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75		75	The management identifies organisational performance improvement targets.	CQI-6, d	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
76	Applying quality improvement systems	76	The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Monitoring the delivery of comprehensive care b. Implementing strategies to improve the outcomes from comprehensive care and	0	0	0	CCS- 5.2, a,b,c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
			associated processes c. Reporting on delivery of comprehensive care												
77		77	The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Monitoring the effectiveness of clinical communication and associated processes b. Implementing strategies to improve clinical communication and associated processes c. Reporting on the effectiveness and outcomes of clinical communication processes	0	0	0	CSS-6.2, a,b,c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
78		78	The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Monitoring processes for partnering with consumers b. Implementing strategies to improve processes for partnering with consumers c. Reporting on partnering with consumers	0	0	0	PCS-2.2, a,b,c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

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				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
79	The organisation identifies key indicators to monitor the clinical structures, processes and outcomes, which are used as tools for continual improvement.	79	Monitoring includes appropriate patient assessment.	CQI-3, a	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-1;	0	0	0	0	0
80		80	Monitoring includes safety and quality-control programmes of all the diagnostic services.	CQI-3, b	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-1;	0	0	0	0	0
81		81	Monitoring includes medication management.	CQI-3, c	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-1;	0	0	0	0	0
82		82	Monitoring includes use of anaesthesia.	CQI-3, d	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-1;	0	0	0	0	0
83		83	Monitoring includes surgical services.	CQI-3, e	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-1;	0	0	0	0	0
84		84	Monitoring includes use of blood and blood components.	CQI-3, f	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-1;	0	0	0	0	0
85		85	Monitoring includes infection control activities.	CQI-3, g	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-1;	0	0	0	0	0
86		86	Monitoring includes review of mortality and morbidity indicators.	CQI-3, h	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-1;	0	0	0	0	0
87		87	Monitoring includes clinical research.	CQI-3, i	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-1;	0	0	0	0	0

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				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
88		88	Monitoring includes patient safety goals.	CQI-3, j	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-1;	0	0	0	0	0
89		89	The organisation identifies and monitors priority aspects of patient care.	CQI-3, k	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-1;	0	0	0	0	0
90	The organisation identifies key indicators to monitor the managerial structures, processes and outcomes, which are used as tools for continual improvement.	90	Monitoring includes procurement of medication essential to meet patient needs.	CQI-4, a	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
91		91	Monitoring includes risk management.	CQI-4, b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
92		92	Monitoring includes utilisation of space, manpower and equipment.	CQI-4, c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
93		93	Monitoring includes patient satisfaction which also incorporates waiting time for services.	CQI-4, d	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
94		94	Monitoring includes employee satisfaction.	CQI-4, e	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
95		95	Monitoring includes adverse events and near misses.	CQI-4, f	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
96		96	Monitoring includes availability and content of medical records.	CQI-4, g	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
97		97	The organisation identifies and monitors priority managerial activities in the organisation.	CQI-4, h	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.4-1;	0	0	0	0	0
98	There is a mechanism for validation and analysis of quality indicators to facilitate quality improvement.	98	There is a mechanism for validation of data.	CQI-5, a	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-4; 1.2.3-5;	0	0	0	0	0
99		99	There is a mechanism for analysis of data which results in identifying opportunities for improvement.	CQI-5, b	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-4; 1.2.3-5;	0	0	0	0	0
100		100	The opportunities for improvement are implemented and evaluated.	CQI-5, c	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-8; 1.2.3-9;	0	0	0	0	0
101		101	The organisation uses appropriate quality improvement, statistical and management tools in its quality improvement programme.	CQI-5, d	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-8; 1.2.3-9;	0	0	0	0	0
102		102	Feedback about care and service is communicated to staff.	CQI-5, e	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.3-7;	0	0	0	0	0
103	There is an established system for clinical	103	Medical and nursing staff participates in this system.	CQI-7, a	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
	audit.														
104		104	The parameters to be audited are defined by the organisation.	CQI-7, b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
105		105	Patient and staff anonymity is maintained.	CQI-7, c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
106		106	All audits are documented.	CQI-7, d	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
107		107	Remedial measures are implemented.	CQI-7, e	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
108	Incidents are collected and analysed to ensure continual quality improvement.	108	The organisation has an incident reporting system.	CQI-8, a	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
109		109	The organisation has established processes for analysis of incidents.	CQI-8, b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
110		110	Corrective and preventive actions are taken based on the findings of such analysis.	CQI-8, c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
111		111	The organisation shall have a process for informing various stakeholders in case of a near miss / adverse event.	CQI-8, d	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
112	Sentinel events are intensively analysed.	112	The organisation has defined sentinel events.	CQI-9, a	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
113		113	The organisation has established processes for intense analysis of such events.	CQI-9, b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
114		114	Sentinel events are intensively analysed when they occur.	CQI-9, c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
115		115	Corrective and preventive actions are taken based on the findings of such analysis.	CQI-9, d	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
116	Integrating clinical governance	116	Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Implementing policies and procedures for recognising and responding to acute deterioration b. Managing risks associated with recognising and responding to acute deterioration c. Identifying training requirements for recognising and responding to acute deterioration	0	0	0	CGS-8.1-a,b,c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
117	The patient is identified prior to any health activity.	117	There are guidelines for patient identification	0	0	0	CSS-6.6, a,b	0	0	1.2.7-1;	0	0	5.2.1-1;	0	0

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				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
118		118	There are guidelines determining method and responsibility to ensure correct page and indication of right and left-sided image in accordance with referral before image is produced.	0	0	0	CSS-6.5, a,b	0	0	1.2.7-2;	0	0	0	0	0
119		119	The staff knows when to make patient identification.	0	0	0	CSS-6.6, a,b	0	0	1.2.7-3;	0	0	0	0	0
120		120	Patients are identified according to the described procedure and method.	0	0	0	CSS-6.6, a,b	0	0	1.2.7-4;	0	0	0	0	0
121		121	Correct page and indication of right or left-sided image are secured in connection with imaging in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.7-5;	0	0	0	0	0	0
122		122	The policies and/or procedures require the use of two patient identifiers unique to the patient, not including the use of the patient's room number or locations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.1-2;	0	0	0
123		123	Patients are identified before administering medications, blood or blood products.	0	0	0	CSS-6.5, a,b	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.1-3;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
124		124	Patients are identified before taking blood and other specimens for clinical testing.	0	0	0	CSS-6.5, a,b	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.1-4;	0	0
125		125	Patients are identified before providing treatments and procedures.	0	0	0	CSS-6.5, a,b	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.1-5;	0	0
126	The hospital develops an approach to improve the safety of verbal orders among caregivers.	126	Policies and procedures that address the accuracy of verbal and telephone orders are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.2-1;	0	0
127		127	The complete verbal or telephone order or test result is written down by the receiver of the order or test result, who signs as having done so.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.2-2;	0	0
128		128	The complete verbal and telephone order or test result is read back by a second person, who signs as having done so.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.2-3;	0	0
129		129	The order is confirmed by the individual who gave it by signing the relevant document as per hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.2-4;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
130	Clinical handover	130	The health service organisation, in collaboration with clinicians, defines the: a. Minimum information content to be communicated at clinical handover, based on best-practice guidelines b. Risks relevant to the service context and the particular needs of patients, carers and families c. Clinicians who are involved in the clinical handover	0	0	0	CSS-6.7, a,b,c; CSS-6.6, a,b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
131		131	Clinicians use structured clinical handover processes that include: a. Preparing and scheduling clinical handover b. Having the relevant information at clinical handover c. Organising relevant clinicians and others to participate in clinical handover d. Being aware of the patient's goals and preferences e. Supporting patients, carers and families to be involved in clinical handover, in accordance with the wishes of the patient f. Ensuring that clinical handover results in the transfer of	0	0	0	CSS-6.8, a,b,c,d, e,f; CSS-6.6, a,b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
			responsibility and accountability for care												
132	The hospital develops an approach to improve the safety of high-alert medications.	132	Policies and/or procedures that address the identification, location, labelling and storage of high-alert medications are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.3-1;	0	0
133		133	High-alert medications are available only in designated departments.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.3-2;	0	0
134		134	Measures to prevent the inadvertent administration of high-alert medications are implemented, e.g. hazard labels.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.3-3;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
135		135	Clinical practice guidelines are available to guide prescribing of high-alert medications.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.3-4;	0	0
136		136	Patients prescribed high-alert medications are monitored for side effects or adverse drug reactions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.3-5;	0	0
137		137	Policies and procedures that address the management of look-alike, sound-alike medications are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.3-6;	0	0
138	The hospital develops an approach to ensuring correct site, correct procedure and correct patient surgery.	138	Policies and procedures that establish uniform processes to ensure the identification of the correct site, correct procedure and correct patient are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.4-1;	0	0
139		139	The hospital uses a clearly understood mark for surgical site identification and involves the patient in the marking process.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.4-2;	0	0
140		140	The mark is made using ink that will not be washed away when the patient's skin is prepared for surgery.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.4-3;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
141		141	The hospital uses a process to verify that all documents and items required to perform the marking are available, correct and functional.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.4-4;	0	0
142	The hospital develops an approach to reduce the risk of patient harm resulting from falls.	142	Policies and procedures to reduce the risk of patient harm resulting from falls in the hospital are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.5-1;	0	0
143		143	Patients identified as being at high risk of falls due to their condition, diagnosis or location undergo a falls risk assessment as part of their initial assessment and following a change in condition, medication, etc. according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.5-2;	0	0
144		144	Measures are implemented to reduce fall risk for those assessed to be at risk.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.5-3;	0	0
145		145	All falls are reported, recorded and monitored as part of the quality management system in each patient care unit.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.5-4;	0	0

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				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
146	Quality control procedures are in place, followed and documented in Medical Physics and Radiation Oncology.	146	There is a quality control process for the medical physics imaging / Radiation Oncology service, which is implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
147		147	Quality control of radiation treatments and planning are done according to accepted international and local standards. (ICRU, IAEA, etc.)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
148		148	Quality control includes validating test methods.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
149		149	Quality control includes daily surveillance of imaging results.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
150		150	Quality control includes rapid correction when a deficiency is identified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
151		151	Quality control includes equipment maintenance/testing/safety.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
152		152	Quality control includes documenting results and corrective actions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
153		153	External audits for quality assurance are utilised to periodically evaluate the medical physics /Radiation Oncology service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.4.1-8; 34.4.1-8;	0	0
154	Quality Improvement, Patient Safety and Performance Measurement	154	The health service organisation uses organisation-wide quality improvement systems that: a. Identify safety and quality measures, and monitor and report performance and outcomes b. Identify areas for improvement in safety and quality c. Implement and monitor safety and quality improvement strategies d. Involve consumers and the workforce in the review of safety and quality performance and systems	0	0	0	CGS- 1.8- a,b,c,d	0	0	1.2.4-2; 1.2.4-3; 1.2.4-4; 1.2.4-5; 1.2.4-6; 1.2.4-7;	0	0	2.1.2-4; 2.1.2-5;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M	
155		155	The health service organisation ensures that timely reports on safety and quality systems and performance are provided to: a. The governing body b. The workforce c. Consumers and the local community d. Other relevant health service organizations	0	0	0	CGS-1.9-a,b,c,d	0	0	1.2.4-2; 1.2.4-3; 1.2.4-4; 1.2.4-5; 1.2.4-6; 1.2.4-7;	0	0	0	0	0	0
156		156	The health service organisation has valid and reliable performance review processes that: a. Require members of the workforce to regularly take part in a review of their performance b. Identify needs for training and development in safety and quality c. Incorporate information on training requirements into the organisation's training system	0	0	0	CGS-1.22-a,b,c	0	0	1.2.4-2; 1.2.4-3; 1.2.4-4; 1.2.4-5; 1.2.4-6; 1.2.4-7;	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
157	Risk management (Incident Reports management systems)	157	The health service organisation: a. Identifies and documents organisational risks b. Uses clinical and other data collections to support risk assessments c. Acts to reduce risks d. Regularly reviews and acts to improve the effectiveness of the risk management system e. Reports on risks to the workforce and consumers f. Plans for, and manages, internal and external emergencies and disasters	0	0	0	CGS-1.10-a,b,c,d,e,f	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
158		158	The health service organisation has organisation-wide incident management and investigation systems, and: a. Supports the workforce to recognise and report incidents b. Supports patients, carers and families to communicate concerns or incidents c. Involves the workforce and consumers in the review of incidents d. Provides timely feedback on the analysis of incidents to the governing body, the workforce and consumers e. Uses the information from the analysis of incidents to improve safety and quality f. Incorporates risks identified in the analysis of incidents into the risk management system g. Regularly reviews and acts to improve the effectiveness of the incident management and investigation systems	0	0	0	CGS-1.11-a,b,c,d,e,f,g	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
159		159	The health service organisation: a. Uses an open disclosure program that is consistent with the national laws and regulations. b. Monitors and acts to improve the effectiveness of open disclosure processes	0	0	0	CGS-1.12-a,b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
160	Applying quality improvement systems	160	The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Monitoring recognition and response systems b. Implementing strategies to improve recognition and response systems c. Reporting on effectiveness and outcomes of recognition and response systems	0	0	0	RRAD S-8.2, a,b,c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
161	There are documented quality management and improvement processes which are implemented throughout the hospital.	161	There is a system for the implementation of quality management and improvement processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.1-1;	0	0

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				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
162		162	Managerial and clinical leaders and relevant stakeholders participate in the implementation of the quality management and improvement processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.1-2;	0	0
163		163	The processes reflect the scope of service delivery in relation to managerial, clinical and support services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.1-3;	0	0
164		164	The leaders identify priorities for monitoring activities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.1-4;	0	0
165		165	The documented quality improvement processes include all components of quality management activities, i.e. standard and indicator selection, monitoring, evaluation and remedial action.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.1-5;	0	0
166	The leaders coordinate the quality management and improvement processes and provide technological and other support.	166	Quality management and improvement processes are coordinated among all relevant services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.2-1;	0	0

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				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
167		167	The leaders provide the required technology and support.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.2-2;	0	0
168		168	There are relevant training processes to equip personnel with the necessary competencies for the design, implementation and evaluation of quality management and improvement processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.2-3;	0	0
169	Clinical processes are reviewed and the data obtained is used to drive improvements in patient care.	169	The leaders identify key measures to monitor the quality of clinical processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.1-1;	0	0
170		170	Leaders use clinical practice guidelines to guide patient care processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.1-2;	0	0
171		171	Clinical audits are performed to evaluate the quality of care provided, drive improvements in service provision and monitor performance over time.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.1-3;	0	0
172		172	Clinical processes are evaluated and the results used to drive improvements in patient care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.1-4;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
173		173	Medical, nursing and other clinical leaders use available and relevant clinical practice guidelines in clinical monitoring as part of a structured clinical audit.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.1-5;	0	0
174		174	Professional performance is monitored as part of clinical monitoring.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.1-6;	0	0
175	The quality of clinical record keeping is monitored by means of patient record audit.	175	Patient clinical records are reviewed regularly.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.2-1;	0	0
176		176	The review is conducted by medical, nursing and other personnel, who are authorised to make entries in patient records or to manage patient information.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.2-2;	0	0
177		177	Records of active and discharged patients are included in the review process.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.2-3;	0	0
178		178	Deficiencies in the quality of record keeping are addressed by appropriate interventions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.2-4;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
179		179	The effectiveness of these interventions is evaluated as part of the ongoing monitoring of the quality of patient records.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.2-5;	0	0
180		180	Where the use of abbreviations is permitted, a standardised abbreviation list is available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.2-6;	0	0
181		181	Standardised diagnosis and procedure codes are used as required by country-specific directives.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.2-7;	0	0
182	There are relevant managerial monitoring quality systems.	182	Appropriate data is collected and used to study areas targeted for improvement.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.3-1;	0	0
183		183	Appropriate data is collected and used to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of interventions implemented to achieve improvements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.3-2;	0	0
184		184	The results of these monitoring activities are communicated to the leaders and governance structure of the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.3-3;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
185	Analysed data is used to improve the quality of managerial and clinical services.	185	Clinical monitoring data is used to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of improvements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.4-1;	0	0
186		186	Managerial monitoring data is used to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of improvements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.4-2;	0	0
187		187	Clinical and managerial data and information are integrated as needed to support decision making.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.4-3;	0	0
188		188	Comparisons are made over time within the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.4-4;	0	0
189		189	Comparisons are made with similar hospitals, when possible.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.4-5;	0	0
190		190	Comparisons are made with standards and desirable practices.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.4-6;	0	0
191	Improvement in quality is achieved and sustained.	191	The hospital documents the improvements achieved and sustained over time.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.5.1-1;	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P D	N D	FD	P M	N M
192		192	The data collected for monitoring and evaluation purposes is used to inform the development of processes to ensure that improvements are sustained over time.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.5.1-2;	0	0

Table Number-19: Governance, Leadership and Direction (GLD):

The Governance, Leadership and Direction have 22 Standards and 162 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	There is a structured quality improvement and continuous monitoring programme in the organisation.	1	The quality improvement programme is developed, implemented and maintained by a multi-disciplinary committee.	CQI-1, a			0	0	0	1.2.1-1; 1.2.1-2;			5.3.1-1;		
2		2	The quality improvement programme is documented which is comprehensive and covers all the major elements related to quality assurance.	CQI-1, b			0	0	0	1.2.1-1;			0	0	0
3		3	There is a designated individual for coordinating and implementing the quality improvement programme.	CQI-1, c			0	0	0	1.2.1-3; 1.2.1-4;			0	0	0
4		4	The quality improvement programme promotes and demonstrates use of innovations to improve process efficiency and effectiveness.	CQI-1, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
5		5	The designated programme is communicated and coordinated amongst all the staff of the organisation through appropriate training mechanism.	CQI-1, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6		6	The quality improvement programme identifies opportunities for improvement based on review at pre-defined intervals.	CQI-1, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7		7	The quality improvement programme is a continuous process and updated at least once in a year.	CQI-1, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8		8	Audits are conducted at regular intervals as a means of continuous monitoring.	CQI-1, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9		9	There is an established process in the organisation to monitor and improve quality of nursing care.	CQI-1, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	There is a structured patient-safety programme in the organisation.	10	The patient-safety programme is developed, implemented and maintained by a multi-disciplinary committee.	CQI-2, a			0	0	0	1.2.6-1;			0	0	0
11		11	The patient-safety programme is documented.	CQI-2, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
12		12	The patient-safety programme is comprehensive and covers all the major elements related to patient safety and risk management.	CQI-2, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13		13	The scope of the programme is defined to include adverse events ranging from "no harm" to sentinel events.	CQI-2, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14		14	There is a designated individual for coordinating and implementing the patientsafety programme.	CQI-2, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15		15	The designated programme is communicated and coordinated amongst all the staff of the organisation through appropriate training mechanism.	CQI-2, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16		16	The patient-safety programme identifies opportunities for improvement based on review at pre-defined intervals.	CQI-2, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17		17	The patient-safety programme is a continuous process and updated at least once in a year.	CQI-2, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
18		18	The organisation adapts and implements national/international patient-safety goals/solutions.	CQI-2, i			0	0	0	1.2.3-2;			0	0	0
19	Managers and leaders work collaboratively to develop, implement and maintain effective risk management systems in the hospital.	19	Hospital-wide risk management systems are developed and implemented.		0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-1;			5.1.1-1;	
20		20	The risk management team develops and maintains a risk register for the hospital.		0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-2;			5.1.1-2;	
21		21	Risk management processes include documented plans and actions to eliminate or reduce the identified risks.		0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-2;			5.1.1-3;	
22		22	Risk management processes include ongoing documented monitoring of risks.		0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-2;			5.1.1-4;	
23		23	Management and leaders ensure the development and implementation of documented policies and procedures for risk management processes and activities.		0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-2; 1.2.6-3;			5.1.1-5;	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
24		24	Ongoing in-service training of all personnel in these policies, procedures and risk management principles, including reporting of adverse events, is documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-4;			5.1.1-6;		
25		25	One or more qualified and/or skilled and/or experienced individuals supervise the implementation of the risk management system.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.1.1-7;		
26		26	A system for monitoring near misses/adverse events/sentinel events is available and includes the documentation of responses to recorded incidents and interventions to prevent recurrence of the incident or minimise harm in the event of a recurrence.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-5; 1.2.6-6; 1.2.6-7; 1.2.6-8; 1.2.6-9;			5.1.1-8;		
27		27	The hospital has a policy for communicating relevant information to patients affected by adverse events and sentinel events, including the outcome of investigations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-5; 1.2.6-6; 1.2.6-7; 1.2.6-8; 1.2.6-9;			5.1.1-9;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
28		28	Analysed data, including near misses, adverse events and sentinel events is used to monitor the effectiveness of the risk management system.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-5; 1.2.6-6; 1.2.6-7; 1.2.6-8; 1.2.6-9;			5.1.1-10;		
29		29	Risk management systems are reviewed and the risk register updated whenever there are changes in hospital systems and processes, or physical facilities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.6-5; 1.2.6-6; 1.2.6-7; 1.2.6-8; 1.2.6-9;			5.1.1-11;		
30	As part of risk management, an occupational health and safety system is implemented in accordance with current legislation.	30	Policies and procedures on all aspects of health and safety that guide personnel in maintaining a safe work environment are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.3.1-2;		
31		31	Management makes provision for occupational health services according to a documented policy framework.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.3.1-3;		
32		32	The person(s) providing the Occupational Health Service has access to a qualified Occupational Health practitioner.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.3.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
33		33	The hospital provides information and training on risks specific to the healthcare workers.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.3.1-5;		
34	A formalised proactive quality improvement approach is maintained in the service.	34	Indicators of performance are identified to evaluate the quality of treatment and patient care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.4.1-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
35		35	There are formalised quality improvement processes for the service that have been developed and agreed upon by the personnel of the service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
													2.6.1-1; 6.4.1-1; 9.8.1-1; 10.8.1-1; 11.8.1-1; 12.8.1-1; 13.8.1-1; 15.8.1-1; 17.8.1-1; 16.9.1-1; 14.4.1-1; 18.12.1-1; 19.9.1-1; 20.12.1-1; 21.8.1-1; 26.6.1-1; 22.5.2-1; 23.5.2-1; 24.5.1-1; 25.6.1-1; 28.8.1-1; 29.4.1-1; 30.5.1-1; 31.4.1-1; 32.5.1-1; 33.4.2-1; 34.4.2-1;			

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
36		36	Indicators of performance are identified to evaluate the quality of the service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
37		37	The quality improvement cycle includes the monitoring and evaluation of the standards set and the remedial action implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
38		38	A documentation audit system is in place.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.4.1-4; 9.8.1-4; 10.8.1-4; 11.8.1-4; 12.8.1-4; 13.8.1-4; 15.8.1-4; 17.8.1-4; 16.9.1-4; 14.4.1-5; 18.12.1-4; 19.9.1-4; 20.12.1-4; 21.8.1-4; 26.6.1.-4; 22.5.2-4; 23.5.2-4; 24.5.1-4; 25.6.1-6; 28.8.1-4; 33.4.2-4; 34.4.2-4;			
39		39	Incidents relating to complaints about the linen management are recorded and acted upon using quality improvement	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.4.1-4; 29.4.1-4;			

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			methodology.												
40		40	The pharmacy has a system in place to monitor the appropriate use of antibiotics within the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.6.1-3;		
41		41	Data relating to medication errors and adverse drug reactions is used to improve medication management within the hospital and monitor the effectiveness of actions taken to prevent recurrence of such events.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.6.1-4;		
42		42	The quality improvement cycle includes the monitoring and evaluation of the standards set and the remedial action implemented	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.6.1-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
43	The department/service implements risk management processes - Human Resource, Medical/Surgical/ Paediatric and Obstetric Care)	43	The department conducts ongoing monitoring of risks through documented assessments as part of the hospital's risk management processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
44		44	A system for monitoring near misses/adverse events/sentinel events is implemented, which includes the documentation of responses to recorded incidents and interventions to prevent recurrence of the incident or minimise harm in the event of a recurrence.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
													2.7.1-2; 3.6.1-1; 9.11.1-2; 10.11.1-2; 11.11.1-2; 12.11.1-2; 13.11.1-2; 15.11.1-2; 17.11.1-2; 16.12.1-2; 14.7.1-2; 18.15.1-2; 19.12.1-2; 20.15.1-2; 26.9.1-2; 22.8.1-2; 23.7.1-2; 24.8.1-2; 25.9.1-2; 27.5.1-1; 28.11.1-2; 29.7.1-2; 30.8.1-2; 31.6.1-2; 32.7.1-2; 33.7.1-2; 34.7.1-2;			

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
45		45	Relevant personnel are trained in the procedures relating to the reporting and investigation of near misses/adverse events/sentinel events.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.1-3; 9.11.1-3; 10.11.1-3; 11.11.1-3; 12.11.1-3; 13.11.1-3; 15.11.1-3; 17.11.1-3; 16.12.1-3; 14.7.1-3; 18.15.1-3; 19.12.1-3; 20.15.1-3; 26.9.1-3; 22.8.1-3; 24.8.1-3; 29.7.1-3; 30.8.1-3; 32.7.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
46		46	Security measures are implemented to ensure the safety of patients, personnel and visitors.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
47		47	Fire safety measures are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
													2.7.1-5; 3.6.1-6; 9.11.1-5; 10.11.1-5; 11.11.1-5; 12.11.1-5; 13.11.1-5; 15.11.1-5; 17.11.1-5; 16.12.1-5; 14.7.1-5; 18.15.1-5; 19.12.1-5; 20.15.1-5; 26.9.1-5; 22.8.1-5; 23.7.1-4; 24.8.1-5; 25.9.1-4; 27.5.1-4; 28.11.1-4; 29.7.1-5; 30.8.1-5; 31.6.1-4; 32.7.1-4; 33.7.1-4; 34.7.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
48		48	Hospital policy on handling, storage and disposal of healthcare waste is implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
49		49	Aids are available for manual handling of heavy goods.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.6.1-3;		
50		50	Ladders are available where required.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.6.1-4;		
51		51	The operating department team participates in the hospital's surveillance of surgical capacity, volume and results.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.4.1-4;		
52	Risks to the health and safety of personnel, employees or visitors are assessed and control measures introduced in order to minimise or eliminate risk and promote safety.	52	Occupational health personnel are included in the assessment of risks to the health of employees attached to any work.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-2;		
53		53	Occupational health personnel have access to and utilise consultative services associated with evaluating workplace hazards such as industrial hygiene, workplace toxicology, ergonomics and epidemiology.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
54		54	There are monitoring mechanisms to ensure that employees adhere to safe systems of work, including the use of protective clothing.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-4;		
55		55	Vulnerable groups of workers are identified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-5;		
56		56	Where there is risk of injury, it has been determined whether it is possible to avoid manual handling, or to provide mechanical aids in place of the latter.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-6;		
57		57	There is a mechanism to ensure that employees are aware of risks and their consequences.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-7;		
58		58	Documented information on the safe handling and storage of hazardous substances is available and provided to the management of the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-8;		
59		59	First aid is available to employees.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-9;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
60		60	A system for the monitoring of near misses/adverse events/sentinel events is available, which includes the documentation of interventions and responses to recorded incidents.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-10;		
61		61	Security measures are in place and implemented to safeguard and protect employees, personnel and visitors.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-11;		
62		62	Fire safety measures are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-12;		
63		63	Hospital policy on handling, storage and disposal of healthcare waste is implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.11.1-13;		
64	Patient Safety in patient care	64	a) Management ensures proactive risk management across the organisation.	ROM-6, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
65		65	b) Management provides resources for proactive risk assessment and riskreduction activities.	ROM-6, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
66		66	c) Management ensures implementation of systems for internal and external reporting of system and process failures.	ROM-6, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
67		67	d) Management ensures that appropriate corrective and preventive actions are taken to address safety-related incidents.	ROM-6, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
68	Patient safety and quality systems Policies and procedures	68	The health service organisation uses a risk management approach to: a. Set out, review, and maintain the currency and effectiveness of, policies, procedures and protocols b. Monitor and take action to improve adherence to policies, procedures and protocols c. Review compliance with legislation, regulation and jurisdictional requirements	0	0	0	CGS-1.7-a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
69	The hospital improves the safety and prevents injuries at patients. This includes that the hospital identifies and prevents risks and injuries and that the hospital learns from adverse events.	69	The hospital has a policy for patient safety and risk management. The policy describes risk management and the effort of reporting and learning from adverse events, including near-misses. Furthermore, the policy describes how intersectorial events are handled.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.9-1;			0	0	0
70		70	The hospital describes and substantiates which risks are made subject of a special assessment and effort.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.9-1; 1.2.9-2;			0	0	0
71		71	The hospital conducts risk assessments of the selected risks and launches initiatives based on the analyses.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.9-2;			0	0	0
72	The quality improvement programme is supported by the management.	72	The leaders at all levels in the organisation are aware of the intent of the quality improvement program and the approach to its implementation.	CQI-6, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
73		73	The management makes available adequate resources required for quality improvement programme.	CQI-6, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
74		74	Organisation earmarks adequate funds from its annual budget in this regard.	CQI-6, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75		75	The management identifies organisational performance improvement targets.	CQI-6, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
76	Applying quality improvement systems	76	The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Monitoring the delivery of comprehensive care b. Implementing strategies to improve the outcomes from comprehensive care and associated processes c. Reporting on delivery of comprehensive care	0	0	0	CCS-5.2, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
77		77	The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Monitoring the effectiveness of clinical communication and associated processes b. Implementing strategies to improve clinical communication and associated processes c.	0	0	0	CSS-6.2, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			Reporting on the effectiveness and outcomes of clinical communication processes.												
78		78	The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Monitoring processes for partnering with consumers b. Implementing strategies to improve processes for partnering with consumers c. Reporting on partnering with consumers	0	0	0	PCS-2.2, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
79	The organisation identifies key indicators to monitor the clinical structures, processes and outcomes, which are used as tools for continual improvement.	79	Monitoring includes appropriate patient assessment.	CQI-3, a			0	0	0	1.2.3-1;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
80		80	Monitoring includes safety and quality-control programmes of all the diagnostic services.	CQI-3, b			0	0	0	1.2.3-1;			0	0	0
81		81	Monitoring includes medication management.	CQI-3, c			0	0	0	1.2.3-1;			0	0	0
82		82	Monitoring includes use of anaesthesia.	CQI-3, d			0	0	0	1.2.3-1;			0	0	0
83		83	Monitoring includes surgical services.	CQI-3, e			0	0	0	1.2.3-1;			0	0	0
84		84	Monitoring includes use of blood and blood components.	CQI-3, f			0	0	0	1.2.3-1;			0	0	0
85		85	Monitoring includes infection control activities.	CQI-3, g			0	0	0	1.2.3-1;			0	0	0
86		86	Monitoring includes review of mortality and morbidity indicators.	CQI-3, h			0	0	0	1.2.3-1;			0	0	0
87		87	Monitoring includes clinical research.	CQI-3, i			0	0	0	1.2.3-1;			0	0	0
88		88	Monitoring includes patient safety goals.	CQI-3, j			0	0	0	1.2.3-1;			0	0	0
89		89	The organisation identifies and monitors priority aspects of patient care.	CQI-3, k			0	0	0	1.2.3-1;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
90	The organisation identifies key indicators to monitor the managerial structures, processes and outcomes, which are used as tools for continual improvement.	90	Monitoring includes procurement of medication essential to meet patient needs.	CQI-4, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
91		91	Monitoring includes risk management.	CQI-4, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
92		92	Monitoring includes utilisation of space, manpower and equipment.	CQI-4, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
93		93	Monitoring includes patient satisfaction which also incorporates waiting time for services.	CQI-4, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
94		94	Monitoring includes employee satisfaction.	CQI-4, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
95		95	Monitoring includes adverse events and near misses.	CQI-4, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
96		96	Monitoring includes availability and content of medical records.	CQI-4, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
97		97	The organisation identifies and monitors priority managerial activities in the organisation.	CQI-4, h			0	0	0	1.2.4-1;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
98	There is a mechanism for validation and analysis of quality indicators to facilitate quality improvement.	98	There is a mechanism for validation of data.	CQI-5, a			0	0	0	1.2.3-4; 1.2.3-5;			0	0	0
99		99	There is a mechanism for analysis of data which results in identifying opportunities for improvement.	CQI-5, b			0	0	0	1.2.3-4; 1.2.3-5;			0	0	0
100		100	The opportunities for improvement are implemented and evaluated.	CQI-5, c			0	0	0	1.2.3-8; 1.2.3-9;			0	0	0
101		101	The organisation uses appropriate quality improvement, statistical and management tools in its quality improvement programme.	CQI-5, d			0	0	0	1.2.3-8; 1.2.3-9;			0	0	0
102		102	Feedback about care and service is communicated to staff.	CQI-5, e			0	0	0	1.2.3-7;			0	0	0
103	There is an established system for clinical audit.	103	Medical and nursing staff participates in this system.	CQI-7, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
104		104	The parameters to be audited are defined by the organisation.	CQI-7, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
105		105	Patient and staff anonymity is maintained.	CQI-7, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
106		106	All audits are documented.	CQI-7, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
107		107	Remedial measures are	CQI-7,			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			implemented.	e											
108	Incidents are collected and analysed to ensure continual quality improvement.	108	The organisation has an incident reporting system.	CQI-8, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
109		109	The organisation has established processes for analysis of incidents.	CQI-8, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
110		110	Corrective and preventive actions are taken based on the findings of such analysis.	CQI-8, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
111		111	The organisation shall have a process for informing various stakeholders in case of a near miss / adverse event.	CQI-8, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
112	Sentinel events are intensively analysed.	112	The organisation has defined sentinel events.	CQI-9, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
113		113	The organisation has established processes for intense analysis of such events.	CQI-9, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
114		114	Sentinel events are intensively analysed when they occur.	CQI-9, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
115		115	Corrective and preventive actions are taken based on the findings of such analysis.	CQI-9, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
116	Integrating governance clinical	116	Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Implementing policies and procedures for recognising and responding to acute deterioration b. Managing risks associated with recognising and responding to acute deterioration c. Identifying training requirements for recognising and responding to acute deterioration	0	0	0	CGS-8.1- a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
117	The patient is identified prior to any health activity.	117	There are guidelines for patient identification	0	0	0	CSS-6.6, a,b			1.2.7-1;			5.2.1-1;		
118		118	There are guidelines determining method and responsibility to ensure correct page and indication of right and left-sided image in accordance with referral before image is produced.	0	0	0	CSS-6.5, a,b			1.2.7-2;			0	0	0
119		119	The staff knows when to make patient identification.	0	0	0	CSS-6.6, a,b			1.2.7-3;			0	0	0
120		120	Patients are identified according to the described procedure and method.	0	0	0	CSS-6.6, a,b			1.2.7-4;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
121		121	Correct page and indication of right or left-sided image are secured in connection with imaging in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.2.7-5;			0	0	0
122		122	The policies and/or procedures require the use of two patient identifiers unique to the patient, not including the use of the patient's room number or locations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.1-2;		
123		123	Patients are identified before administering medications, blood or blood products.	0	0	0	CSS-6.5, a,b			0	0	0	5.2.1-3;		
124		124	Patients are identified before taking blood and other specimens for clinical testing.	0	0	0	CSS-6.5, a,b			0	0	0	5.2.1-4;		
125		125	Patients are identified before providing treatments and procedures.	0	0	0	CSS-6.5, a,b			0	0	0	5.2.1-5;		
126	The hospital develops an approach to improve the safety of verbal orders among caregivers.	126	Policies and procedures that address the accuracy of verbal and telephone orders are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.2-1;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
127		127	The complete verbal or telephone order or test result is written down by the receiver of the order or test result, who signs as having done so.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.2-2;	
128		128	The complete verbal and telephone order or test result is read back by a second person, who signs as having done so.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.2-3;	
129		129	The order is confirmed by the individual who gave it by signing the relevant document as per hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.2-4;	
130	Clinical handover	130	The health service organisation, in collaboration with clinicians, defines the: a. Minimum information content to be communicated at clinical handover, based on best-practice guidelines b. Risks relevant to the service context and the particular needs of patients, carers and families c. Clinicians who are involved in the clinical handover	0	0	0	CSS-6.7, a,b,c; CSS-6.6, a,b				0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
131		131	Clinicians use structured clinical handover processes that include: a. Preparing and scheduling clinical handover b. Having the relevant information at clinical handover c. Organising relevant clinicians and others to participate in clinical handover d. Being aware of the patient's goals and preferences e. Supporting patients, carers and families to be involved in clinical handover, in accordance with the wishes of the patient f. Ensuring that clinical handover results in the transfer of responsibility and accountability for care	0	0	0	CSS-6.8, a,b,c,d,e,f; CSS-6.6, a,b				0	0	0	0	0	0
132	The hospital develops an approach to improve the safety of high-alert medications.	132	Policies and/or procedures that address the identification, location, labelling and storage of high-alert medications are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.3-1;	
133		133	High-alert medications are available only in designated departments.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.3-2;	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
134		134	Measures to prevent the inadvertent administration of high-alert medications are implemented, e.g. hazard labels.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.3-3;		
135		135	Clinical practice guidelines are available to guide prescribing of high-alert medications.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.3-4;		
136		136	Patients prescribed high-alert medications are monitored for side effects or adverse drug reactions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.3-5;		
137		137	Policies and procedures that address the management of look-alike, sound-alike medications are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.3-6;		
138	The hospital develops an approach to ensuring correct site, correct procedure and correct patient surgery.	138	Policies and procedures that establish uniform processes to ensure the identification of the correct site, correct procedure and correct patient are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.4-1;		
139		139	The hospital uses a clearly understood mark for surgical site identification and involves the patient in the marking process.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.4-2;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
140		140	The mark is made using ink that will not be washed away when the patient's skin is prepared for surgery.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.4-3;		
141		141	The hospital uses a process to verify that all documents and items required to perform the marking are available, correct and functional.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.4-4;		
142	The hospital develops an approach to reduce the risk of patient harm resulting from falls.	142	Policies and procedures to reduce the risk of patient harm resulting from falls in the hospital are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.5-1;		
143		143	Patients identified as being at high risk of falls due to their condition, diagnosis or location undergo a falls risk assessment as part of their initial assessment and following a change in condition, medication, etc. according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.5-2;		
144		144	Measures are implemented to reduce fall risk for those assessed to be at risk.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.5-3;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
145		145	All falls are reported, recorded and monitored as part of the quality management system in each patient care unit.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.2.5-4;		
146	Quality control procedures are in place, followed and documented in Medical Physics and Radiation Oncology.	146	There is a quality control process for the medical physics imaging / Radiation Oncology service, which is implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.4.1-1; 34.4.1-1;		
147		147	Quality control of radiation treatments and planning are done according to accepted international and local standards.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.4.1-2; 34.4.1-2;		
148		148	Quality control includes validating test methods.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.4.1-3; 34.4.1-3;		
149		149	Quality control includes daily surveillance of imaging results.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.4.1-4; 34.4.1-4;		
150		150	Quality control includes rapid correction when a deficiency is identified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.4.1-5; 34.4.1-5;		
151		151	Quality control includes equipment maintenance/testing/safety.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.4.1-6; 34.4.1-6;		
152		152	Quality control includes documenting results and corrective actions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.4.1-7; 34.4.1-6;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
153		153	External audits for quality assurance are utilised to periodically evaluate the medical physics /Radiation Oncology service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.4.1-8; 34.4.1-8;		
154	Quality Improvement, Patient Safety and Performamnce Measurement	154	The health service organisation uses organisation-wide quality improvement systems that: a. Identify safety and quality measures, and monitor and report performance and outcomes b. Identify areas for improvement in safety and quality c. Implement and monitor safety and quality improvement strategies d. Involve consumers and the workforce in the review of safety and quality performance and systems	0	0	0	CGS-1.8- a,b,c,d			1.2.4-2; 1.2.4-3; 1.2.4-4; 1.2.4-5; 1.2.4-6; 1.2.4-7;			2.1.2-4; 2.1.2-5;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
155		155	The health service organisation ensures that timely reports on safety and quality systems and performance are provided to: a. The governing body b. The workforce c. Consumers and the local community d. Other relevant health service organisations	0	0	0	CGS-1.9-a,b,c,d			1.2.4-2; 1.2.4-3; 1.2.4-4; 1.2.4-5; 1.2.4-6; 1.2.4-7;			0	0	0
156		156	The health service organisation has valid and reliable performance review processes that: a. Require members of the workforce to regularly take part in a review of their performance b. Identify needs for training and development in safety and quality c. Incorporate information on training requirements into the organisation's training system	0	0	0	CGS-1.22-a,b,c			1.2.4-2; 1.2.4-3; 1.2.4-4; 1.2.4-5; 1.2.4-6; 1.2.4-7;			0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
157	Risk management (Incident Reports management systems)	157	The health service organisation: a. Identifies and documents organisational risks b. Uses clinical and other data collections to support risk assessments c. Acts to reduce risks d. Regularly reviews and acts to improve the effectiveness of the risk management system e. Reports on risks to the workforce and consumers f. Plans for, and manages, internal and external emergencies and disasters	0	0	0	CGS-1.10-a,b,c,d,e,f			0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
158		158	<p>The health service organisation has organisation-wide incident management and investigation systems, and:</p> <p>a. Supports the workforce to recognise and report incidents</p> <p>b. Supports patients, carers and families to communicate concerns or incidents</p> <p>c. Involves the workforce and consumers in the review of incidents</p> <p>d. Provides timely feedback on the analysis of incidents to the governing body, the workforce and consumers</p> <p>e. Uses the information from the analysis of incidents to improve safety and quality</p> <p>f. Incorporates risks identified in the analysis of incidents into the risk management system</p> <p>g. Regularly reviews and acts to improve the effectiveness of the incident management and investigation systems</p>	0	0	0	CGS-1.11-a,b,c,d,e,f,g			0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
159		159	The health service organisation: a. Uses an open disclosure program b. Monitors and acts to improve the effectiveness of open disclosure processes	0	0	0	CGS-1.12-a,b			0	0	0	0	0	0
160	Applying quality improvement systems	160	The health service organisation applies the quality improvement system from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Monitoring recognition and response systems b. Implementing strategies to improve recognition and response systems c. Reporting on effectiveness and outcomes of recognition and response systems	0	0	0	RRADS-8.2, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
161	There are documented quality management and improvement processes which are implemented throughout the hospital.	161	There is a system for the implementation of quality management and improvement processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.1-1;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
162		162	Managerial and clinical leaders and relevant stakeholders participate in the implementation of the quality management and improvement processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.1-2;		
163		163	The processes reflect the scope of service delivery in relation to managerial, clinical and support services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.1-3;		
164		164	The leaders identify priorities for monitoring activities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.1-4;		
165		165	The documented quality improvement processes include all components of quality management activities, i.e. standard and indicator selection, monitoring, evaluation and remedial action.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.1-5;		
166	The leaders coordinate the quality management and improvement processes and provide technological and other support.	166	Quality management and improvement processes are coordinated among all relevant services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.2-1;		
167		167	The leaders provide the required technology and support.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.2-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
168		168	There are relevant training processes to equip personnel with the necessary competencies for the design, implementation and evaluation of quality management and improvement processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.3.2-3;
169	Clinical processes are reviewed and the data obtained is used to drive improvements in patient care.	169	The leaders identify key measures to monitor the quality of clinical processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.1-1;
170		170	Leaders use clinical practice guidelines to guide patient care processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.1-2;
171		171	Clinical audits are performed to evaluate the quality of care provided, drive improvements in service provision and monitor performance over time.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.1-3;
172		172	Clinical processes are evaluated and the results used to drive improvements in patient care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.1-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
173		173	Medical, nursing and other clinical leaders use available and relevant clinical practice guidelines in clinical monitoring as part of a structured clinical audit.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.1-5;
174		174	Professional performance is monitored as part of clinical monitoring.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.1-6;
175	The quality of clinical record keeping is monitored by means of patient record audit.	175	Patient clinical records are reviewed regularly.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.2-1;
176		176	The review is conducted by medical, nursing and other personnel, who are authorised to make entries in patient records or to manage patient information.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.2-2;
177		177	Records of active and discharged patients are included in the review process.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.2-3;
178		178	Deficiencies in the quality of record keeping are addressed by appropriate interventions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.2-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
179		179	The effectiveness of these interventions is evaluated as part of the ongoing monitoring of the quality of patient records.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.2-5;
180		180	Where the use of abbreviations is permitted, a standardised abbreviation list is available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.2-6;
181		181	Standardised diagnosis and procedure codes are used as required by country-specific directives.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.2-7;
182	There are relevant managerial monitoring quality systems.	182	Appropriate data is collected and used to study areas targeted for improvement.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.3-1;
183		183	Appropriate data is collected and used to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of interventions implemented to achieve improvements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.3-2;
184		184	The results of these monitoring activities are communicated to the leaders and governance structure of the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.3-3;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
185	Analysed data is used to improve the quality of managerial and clinical services.	185	Clinical monitoring data is used to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of improvements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.4-1;		
186		186	Managerial monitoring data is used to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of improvements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.4-2;		
187		187	Clinical and managerial data and information are integrated as needed to support decision making.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.4-3;		
188		188	Comparisons are made over time within the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.4-4;		
189		189	Comparisons are made with similar hospitals, when possible.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.4-5;		
190		190	Comparisons are made with standards and desirable practices.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.4.4-6;		
191	Improvement in quality is achieved and sustained.	191	The hospital documents the improvements achieved and sustained over time.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.5.1-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
192		192	The data collected for monitoring and evaluation purposes is used to inform the development of processes to ensure that improvements are sustained over time.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.5.1-2;			

Table Number-20: Care of Patient (COP):

The Care of Patient has 45 Standards and 244 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	Uniform care to patients is provided in all settings of the organisation and is guided by the applicable laws, regulations and guidelines.	1	Care delivery is uniform for a given health problem when similar care is provided in more than one setting.	COP-1, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.2-1;		
2		2	Uniform care is guided by documented policies and procedures.	COP-1, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.2-2;		
3		3	These reflect applicable laws, regulations and guidelines.	COP-1, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4		4	The organisation adapts evidence-based medicine and clinical practice guidelines to guide uniform patient care.	COP-1, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
5	During all phases of care, there are qualified individuals responsible for the patient's care.	5	An appropriately qualified individual has clearly defined responsibilities and accountability for all aspects of the service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.2.1-1; 10.2.1-1; 11.2.1-1; 12.2.1-1; 13.2.1-1; 15.2.1-1; 16.2.1-1; 17.2.1-1; 19.1.2-1; 20.1.2-1;		
6		6	The individuals responsible for the patient's care are designated.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.2.1-2; 10.2.1-2; 11.2.1-2; 12.2.1-2; 13.2.1-2; 15.2.1-3; 16.2.1-2; 17.2.1-2; 19.1.2-2; 20.1.2-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
7		7	The individuals responsible for patient care are qualified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.2.1-3; 10.2.1-3; 11.2.1-3; 12.2.1-3; 13.2.1-3; 15.2.1-4; 16.2.1-3; 17.2.1-3; 19.1.2-3; 20.1.2-3;		
8		8	The individuals responsible for patient care are identified and made known to the patient and other personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.2.1-4; 10.2.1-4; 11.2.1-4; 12.2.1-4; 13.2.1-4; 15.2.1-5; 16.2.1-4; 17.2.1-4; 19.1.2-4; 20.1.2-4;		
9		9	The requirements of antenatal, labour and postnatal wards and nurseries are individually included in the staffing requirements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.2.1-5; 13.2.1-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
10		10	A registered midwife and/or medical practitioner is present at every birth.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13.2.1-6;		
11		11	Healthcare professionals, specifically doctors and nurses, indicate that they have access to adequate supervision.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13.2.1-7;		
12		12	Specialists are available for consultation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13.2.1-8;		
13		13	At least one person is available at all times who is qualified (medical practitioner or advanced midwife) in the management of maternal and neonatal emergencies.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13.2.1-9;		
14		14	Staffing of the service complies with accepted staffing norms for critical care services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15.2.1-2;		
15		15	During the hours of operation there is an adequate number of qualified professionals available to provide continuous cover to all sections at all times.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19.1.2-5; 20.1.2-5;		
16		16	Emergency services personnel maintain skills in advanced life support in accordance with hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20.1.2-6;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
17		17	Medical cover is reflected on a roster and each practitioner on the roster is contactable by telephone, pager or other two-way communication method.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19.1.2-6; 20.1.2-7;		
18		18	Arrangements are in place to ensure that specialist consultation services are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19.1.2-7; 20.1.2-8;		
19		19	Mechanisms for contacting medical practitioners who treat private patients in the hospital are known to personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19.1.2-8; 20.1.2-9;		
20	Clinical practice guidelines are used to guide patient care and reduce undesirable variation.	20	Evidence-based clinical practice guidelines relevant to the patients and services of the hospital are available to guide patient care processes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.2.2-1; 10.2.2-1; 11.2.2-1; 12.2.2-1; 13.2.2-1; 14.2.2-1; 15.2.2-1; 16.2.2-1; 17.2.2-1; 18.3.2-1; 19.2.2-1; 20.3.2-1; 26.2.2-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
21		21	The implementation of guidelines is monitored as part of a structured clinical audit.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.2.2-2; 10.2.2-2; 11.2.2-2; 12.2.2-2; 13.2.2-2; 14.2.2-2; 15.2.2-2; 16.2.2-2; 17.2.2-2; 18.3.2-3; 19.2.2-2; 20.3.2-2; 26.2.2-2;		
22		22	Guidelines are reviewed on a regular basis and updated when necessary and according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.2.2-3; 10.2.2-3; 11.2.2-3; 12.2.2-3; 13.2.2-3; 14.2.2-3; 15.2.2-3; 16.2.2-3; 17.2.2-3; 18.3.2-4; 19.2.2-3; 20.3.2-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
23		23	Clinical practice guidelines include protocols for time-critical states	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.3.2-2;
24		24	Guidelines are reviewed and adapted on a regular basis.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20.3.2-4; 26.2.2-3;
25	Documented policies and procedures guide the care of patients requiring cardiopulmonary resuscitation and it is performed according to clinical evidence based practice.	25	Documented policies and procedures guide the uniform use of resuscitation throughout the organisation.	COP-5, a			0	0	0	2.13.1-1;			0	0	0	
26		26	It is documented that the staff has completed training and maintains training in relation to cardiopulmonary resuscitation at the level which the management has decided.	COP-5, b			0	0	0	2.13.1-2; 2.13.1-4;			0	0	0	
27		27	The events during a cardiopulmonary resuscitation are recorded.	COP-5, c			0	0	0	2.13.1-1;			0	0	0	
28		28	A post-event analysis of all cardiopulmonary resuscitations is done by a multidisciplinary committee.	COP-5, d			0	0	0	2.13.1-1;			0	0	0	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
29		29	Corrective and preventive measures are taken based on the post-event analysis.	COP-5, e			0	0	0	2.13.1-1;			0	0	0
30		30	There are guidelines for cardiopulmonary resuscitation for adults, children and newborn babies which are common for the entire hospital. The guidelines are prepared in accordance with the latest national guidelines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.13.1-1;			6.1.1-11;		
31		31	The staff is familiar with its own tasks and responsibilities on cardiac arrest.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.13.1-3;			0	0	0
32	A resuscitation committee coordinates the management of resuscitation equipment, procedures and training systems.	32	The hospital identifies a resuscitation committee to advise on the resuscitation equipment required and the procedures to be followed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.1.1-1;		
33		33	Each committee member's responsibility for resuscitation is documented in a job description.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.1.1-2;		
34		34	A suitably qualified and experienced health professional is appointed as the resuscitation	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.1.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			coordinator.												
35		35	The medical equipment coordinator is on the committee.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.1.1-4;
36		36	A designated individual provides information, instruction and training on resuscitation to the personnel of the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.1.1-5;
37		37	The committee checks and documents that systems for the provision of emergency power are regularly checked according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.1.1-6;
38		38	The committee checks and documents that systems for the supply of gases and vacuum are regularly checked according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.1.1-7;
39		39	A member of the resuscitation committee visits all clinical departments where resuscitation equipment is kept at least monthly to monitor that requirements relating to resuscitation medication,	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.1.1-8;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			supplies and equipment are met.												
40		40	Records of these visits are kept, with reports on problems experienced, advice given and any remedial action taken.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.1.1-9;
41		41	Policies and procedures relating to the acquisition, maintenance and checking of resuscitation equipment are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.1.1-10;
42	Essential resuscitation equipment and medications are available in each patient care area.	42	The hospital has an updated list of equipment required for resuscitation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.2.1-1; 20.1.3-1;
43		43	Recommended appliances are available for specialised resuscitations	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20.1.3-2;
44		44	Diagnostic and vital sign monitoring equipment is available as per hospital policy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20.1.3-3;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
45		45	The committee ensures that resuscitation equipment is readily accessible to every patient care area in the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.2.1-2;		
46		46	The committee checks and documents that resuscitation equipment and drugs are checked daily, or immediately after use (whichever is the sooner), by persons identified to be responsible for this.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.2.1-3;		
47	All personnel are suitably trained and educated to provide resuscitation and competencies are regularly tested.	47	The resuscitation committee develops a continuing education strategy to ensure that all personnel in the hospital are trained in cardio-pulmonary resuscitation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.3.1-1;		
48		48	There is evidence that all members of the resuscitation committee, as well as relevant personnel, attend courses and seminars on resuscitation and that records of attendance are kept.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.3.1-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
49		49	New healthcare professionals employed in patient care areas are provided with resuscitation training within one month of appointment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.3.1-3;		
50		50	The continuing education strategy ensures that resuscitation training of personnel is kept current.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.3.1-4;		
51		51	Dated records are kept of attendance at in-service training programmes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.3.1-5;		
52		52	There is a mechanism whereby personnel show proficiency in resuscitation techniques.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.3.1-6;		
53	Documented policies and procedures guide nursing care.	53	There are documented policies and procedures for all activities of the nursing services.	COP-6, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
54		54	These reflect current standards of nursing services and practice, relevant regulations and purposes of the services.	COP-6, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
55		55	Assignment of patient care is done as per current good practice guidelines.	COP-6, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
56		56	Nursing care is aligned and integrated with overall patient care.	COP-6, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
57		57	Care provided by nurses is documented in the patient record.	COP-6, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
58		58	Nurses are provided with adequate equipment for providing safe and efficient nursing services.	COP-6, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
59		59	Nurses are empowered to take nursing-related decisions to ensure the timely care of patients.	COP-6, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
60	Documented procedures guide the performance of various procedures.	60	Documented procedures are used to guide the performance of various clinical procedures.	COP-7, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
61		61	Only qualified personnel order, plan, perform and assist in performing procedures.	COP-7, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
62		62	Documented procedures exist to prevent adverse events like a wrong site, wrong patient and wrong procedure.	COP-7, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
63		63	Informed consent is taken by the personnel performing the procedure, where applicable.	COP-7, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
64		64	Adherence to standard precautions and asepsis is adhered to during the conduct of the procedure.	COP-7, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
65		65	Patients are appropriately monitored during and after the procedure.	COP-7, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
66		66	Procedures are documented accurately in the patient record.	COP-7, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
67	Documented policies and procedures guide the care of patients in the intensive care and high dependency units.	67	Documented policies and procedures are used to guide the care of patients in the intensive care and high dependency units.	COP-9, a			0	0	0	2.12.1-1; 2.12.1-4;			0	0	0
68		68	The organisation has documented admission and discharge criteria for its intensive care and high dependency units.	COP-9, b			0	0	0	2.12.1-2; 2.12.1-3; 2.12.1-4; 2.12.1-6; 2.12.1-5;			0	0	0
69		69	Staff are trained to apply these criteria.	COP-9, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
70		70	Adequate staff and equipment are available.	COP-9, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
71		71	Defined procedures for the situation of bed shortages are followed.	COP-9, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
72		72	Infection control practices are documented and followed.	COP-9, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
73		73	A quality assurance programme is documented and implemented.	COP-9, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
74		74	Patients and families are counselled by the treating medical professional at periodic intervals and when there is a significant change in the condition of the patient, and same is documented.	COP-9, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
75		75	The hospital has targets for the quality of the access to services in intensive therapy units and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.				0	0	0	0	0	0	2.12.1-7;	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
76		76	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of access to services in intensive therapy units. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.12.1-8;			0	0	0
77	Treatment of patients admitted to intensive therapy units takes place according to clinical, evidence-based practices.	77	There are guidelines for diagnosis and treatment of sepsis and septic shock. The guidelines cover the hospital's overall efforts for treatment of these conditions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.2-1;			0	0	0
78		78	There are guidelines for prevention, diagnosis and treatment of ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP).	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.2-2;			0	0	0
79		79	There are guidelines for department specific (unit specific) antibiotic strategy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.2-3;			0	0	0
80		80	There are guidelines for intensive care delirium.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.2-4;			0	0	0
81		81	There are guidelines for department specific (unit	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.2-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			specific) sedation strategy.												
82		82	Diagnosis and treatment of sepsis and septic shock takes place in accordance with standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.2-6;			0	0	0
83		83	Prevention, diagnosis and treatment of ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) take place in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.2-7;			0	0	0
84		84	Treatment with antibiotics is in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.2-8;			0	0	0
85		85	Treatment of intensive care delirium takes place in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.2-9;			0	0	0
86		86	The patients are sedated in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.2-10;			0	0	0
87		87	The hospital has targets for the quality of the treatment in intensive therapy unit. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.2-11;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
88		88	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of treatment in intensive therapy unit. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. The hospital cannot deselect this element of the standard as not prioritised.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.2-12;			0	0	0
89	Documented policies and procedures guide the care of vulnerable patients.	89	Policies and procedures are documented and are in accordance with the prevailing laws and the national and international guidelines.	COP-10, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
90		90	Care is organised and delivered in accordance with the policies and procedures.	COP-10, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
91		91	The organisation provides for a safe and secure environment for the vulnerable group.	COP-10, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
92		92	A documented procedure exists for obtaining informed consent from the appropriate legal representative.	COP-10, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
93		93	Staff are trained to care for the vulnerable group.	COP-10, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
94	Documented policies and procedures guide obstetric care.	94	There is a documented policy and procedure for obstetric services.	COP-11, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
95		95	The organisation defines and displays whether high-risk obstetric cases can be cared for or not.	COP-11, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
96		96	Persons caring for high-risk obstetric cases are competent.	COP-11, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
97		97	Documented procedures guide the provision of ante-natal services.	COP-11, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
98		98	Obstetric patient's assessment also includes maternal nutrition.	COP-11, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
99		99	Appropriate pre-natal, perinatal and post-natal monitoring is performed and documented.	COP-11, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
100		100	The organisation caring for high-risk obstetric cases has the facilities to take care of neonates of such cases.	COP-11, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
101	Specific resources are available for the provision of safe care to patients in the obstetric and maternity unit/ward.	101	Current guidelines for the provision of obstetric/maternity care services and facilities are followed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.2-1;		
102		102	Staffing of the service complies with accepted staffing norms for obstetric/maternity care services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.1.2-2;		
103	Documented policies and procedures guide paediatric services.	103	There is a documented policy and procedure for paediatric services.	COP-12, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
104		104	The organisation defines and displays the scope of its paediatric services.	COP-12, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
105		105	The policy for care of neonatal patients is in consonance with the national/ international guidelines.	COP-12, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
106		106	Those who care for children have age-specific competency.	COP-12, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
107		107	Provisions are made for special care of children.	COP-12, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
108		108	Patient assessment includes detailed nutritional, growth, developmental and	COP-12, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			immunisation assessment.												
109		109	Documented policies and procedures prevent child/neonate abduction and abuse.	COP-12, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
110		110	The children's family members are educated about nutrition, immunisation and safe parenting and this is documented.	COP-12, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
111	Documented policies and procedures guide the care of patients undergoing surgical procedures.	111	The policies and procedures are documented.	COP-15, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
112		112	Surgical patients have a preoperative assessment and a provisional diagnosis documented prior to surgery.	COP-15, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
113		113	An informed consent is obtained by a surgeon prior to the procedure.	COP-15, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
114		114	Documented policies and procedures exist to prevent adverse events like wrong site, wrong patient and wrong surgery.	COP-15, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
115		115	Persons qualified by law are permitted to perform the procedures that they are entitled to perform.	COP-15, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
116		116	A brief operative note is documented prior to transfer out of patient from recovery.	COP-15, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
117		117	The operating surgeon documents the postoperative care plan.	COP-15, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
118		118	Patient, personnel and material flow conform to infection control practices.	COP-15, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
119		119	Appropriate facilities and equipment/ appliances/ instrumentation are available in the operating theatre.	COP-15, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
120		120	A quality assurance programme is followed for the surgical services.	COP-15, j			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
121		121	The quality assurance programme includes surveillance of the operation theatre environment.	COP-15, k			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
122	Documented policies and procedures guide organ transplant programme in the organisation.	122	The organ transplant program shall be in consonance with the legal requirements and shall be conducted in an ethical manner.	COP-16, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
123		123	Documented policies and procedures guide the organ transplant program.	COP-16, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
124		124	The organisation ensures education and counselling of recipient and donor through trained / qualified counsellors before organ transplantation.	COP-16, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
125		125	The organisation shall take measures to create awareness regarding organ donation.	COP-16, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
126	Documented policies and procedures guide the care of patients under restraints (physical and/or chemical).	126	Documented policies and procedures guide the care of patients under restraints.	COP-17, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
127		127	The policies and procedures include both physical and chemical restraint measures.	COP-17, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
128		128	The reasons for restraints are documented.	COP-17, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
129		129	Patients on restraints are more frequently monitored.	COP-17, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
130		130	Staff receives training and periodic updating in control and restraint techniques.	COP-17, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
131	Minimising restrictive practices: restraint	131	Where restraint is clinically necessary to prevent harm, the health service organisation has systems that: a. Minimise and, where possible, eliminate the use of restraint b. Govern the use of restraint in accordance with legislation c. Report use of restraint to the governing body	0	0	0	CCS-5.35, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
132	Preventing delirium and managing cognitive impairment	132	The health service organisation providing services to patients who have cognitive impairment or are at risk of developing delirium has a system for caring for patients with cognitive impairment to: a. Incorporate best-practice strategies for early recognition, prevention, treatment and management of cognitive impairment in the care plan, including the Delirium Clinical Care , where relevant b. Manage the use of antipsychotics and other psychoactive medicines, in accordance with best practice and legislation	0	0	0	CCS-5.29, a,b			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
133		133	Clinicians providing care to patients who have cognitive impairment or are at risk of developing delirium use the system for caring for patients with cognitive impairment to: a. Recognise, prevent, treat and manage cognitive impairment b. Collaborate with patients, carers and families to understand the patient and implement individualised strategies that minimise any anxiety or distress while they are receiving care	0	0	0	CCS-5.30, a,b			0	0	0	0	0	0
134	Predicting, preventing and managing selfharm and suicide	134	The health service organisation has systems to support collaboration with patients, carers and families to: a. Identify when a patient is at risk of self-harm b. Identify when a patient is at risk of suicide c. Safely and effectively respond to patients who are distressed, have thoughts of self-harm or suicide, or have self-harmed	0	0	0	CCS-5.31, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
135		135	The health service organisation ensures that follow-up arrangements are developed, communicated and implemented for people who have harmed themselves or reported suicidal thoughts	0	0	0	CCS-5.32			0	0	0	0	0	0
136	The hospital makes an active effort to prevent suicide among patients.	136	There are guidelines for prevention of suicides prepared by involving "The supportive and accompanying principle".	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.4-1;			0	0	0
137		137	Managers and staff are familiar with relevant parts of the guidelines and work accordingly.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.4-2;			0	0	0
138		138	Analyses of reasons for suicide and suicide attempts at the hospital are completed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.4-3;			0	0	0
139		139	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the monitoring of suicide risk or to maintain an already high level of quality.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.4-4;			0	0	0
140	Predicting, preventing and aggression managing and violence	140	The health service organisation has processes to identify and mitigate situations that may precipitate aggression	0	0	0	CCS-5.33			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
141		141	The health service organisation has processes to support collaboration with patients, carers and families to: a. Identify patients at risk of becoming aggressive or violent b. Implement de-escalation strategies c. Safely manage aggression, and minimise harm to patients, carers, families and the workforce	0	0	0	CCS-5.34, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
142	Minimising restrictive practices: seclusion	142	Where seclusion is clinically necessary to prevent harm and is permitted under legislation, the health service organisation has systems that: a. Minimise and, where possible, eliminate the use of seclusion b. Govern the use of seclusion in accordance with legislation c. Report use of seclusion to the governing body	0	0	0	CCS-5.36, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
143	Involuntary commitment and use of other coercion in psychiatry takes place according to current legislation.	143	There are guidelines for use of coercion which complies with current legislation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.3-1;			0	0	0
144		144	Involuntary commitment and other use of coercion are conducted and documented in accordance with the guidelines and current legislation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.3-2;			0	0	0
145		145	Every sixth month the hospital reviews patient health records from patients who have been exposed to involuntary commitment or other coercion. In connection with the review, it is clarified whether a protocol exists on use of coercive measures which complies with applicable rules and legislation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.3-3;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
146		146	Every sixth month the hospital reviews patient health records from patients who have been exposed to involuntary commitment or other use of coercion. The review clarifies whether it is documented that a follow-up conversation has been held with the patient after coercion.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.3-4;			0	0	0
147		147	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the involuntary commitment and use of other coercion in psychiatry. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.3-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
148	Where electro-convulsive therapy is provided, the service is managed and staffed to ensure patient safety.	148	A senior medical practitioner who is suitably qualified and experienced is in charge of the ECT service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.8.1-1;
149		149	The design of the ECT treatment area provides space for the reception, anaesthetic induction, treatment, recovery and observation of patients.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.8.1-2;
150		150	Policies and procedures relating to the activities in the ECT unit are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.8.1-3;
151		151	There is documented evidence that the patient has consented to the procedure.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.8.1-4;
152		152	Anaesthesia is administered only by qualified anaesthesiologists.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.8.1-5;
153		153	Emergency resuscitation equipment is available in the ECT unit according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.8.1-6;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
154		154	Resuscitation equipment and trolley contents are checked prior to each administration of ECT.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.8.1-7;		
155		155	There is a mechanism for summoning assistance in the event of an emergency.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.8.1-8;		
156	Documented policies and procedures appropriate management. guide pain	156	Documented policies and procedures guide the management of pain.	COP-18, a			0	0	0	2.7.5-1;			0	0	0		
157		157	All patients are screened for pain.	COP-18, b			0	0	0	2.7.5-2;			9.4.5-1; 10.4.5-1; 11.4.5-1; 12.4.5-1; 13.4.5-1; 15.4.5-1; 16.4.5-1; 17.4.5-1; 18.7.6-1; 19.5.4-1; 20.7.5-1;				

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
158		158	Patients with pain undergo detailed assessment and periodic reassessment.	COP-18, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.5-2; 10.4.5-2; 11.4.5-2; 12.4.5-2; 13.4.5-2; 15.4.5-2; 16.4.5-2; 17.4.5-2; 18.7.6-2; 19.5.4-2; 20.7.5-2;		
159		159	Pain alleviation measures or medications are initiated and treated according to patient's need and response.	COP-18, d			0	0	0	2.7.5-3;			9.4.5-3; 10.4.5-3; 11.4.5-3; 12.4.5-3; 13.4.5-3; 15.4.5-3; 16.4.5-3; 17.4.5-3; 18.7.6-3; 19.5.4-3; 20.7.5-3;		
160		160	The organisation respects and supports management of pain for such patients.	COP-18, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
161		161	Patient and family are educated on various pain management techniques, where appropriate.	COP-18, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.5-4; 10.4.5-4; 11.4.5-4; 12.4.5-4; 13.4.5-4; 15.4.5-4; 16.4.5-4; 17.4.5-4; 18.7.6-4; 19.5.4-4; 20.7.5-4;		
162		162	The hospital has processes to educate health professionals in assessing and managing pain.				0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.5-5; 10.4.5-5; 11.4.5-5; 12.4.5-5; 13.4.5-5; 15.4.5-5; 16.4.5-5; 17.4.5-5; 18.7.6-5; 19.5.4-5; 20.7.5-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
163		163	The hospital has targets for the quality of pain management. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. Data are analysed and assessed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.5-4;			0	0	0
164		164	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of pain management. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.5-5;			0	0	0
165	Documented policies and procedures guide appropriate rehabilitative services.	165	Documented policies and procedures guide the provision of rehabilitative services.	COP-19, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
166		166	These services are commensurate with the organisational requirements.	COP-19, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
167		167	Care is guided by functional assessment and periodic re-assessment which is done and documented by qualified individual(s).	COP-19, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
168		168	Care is provided adhering to infection control and safe practices.	COP-19, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
169		169	Rehabilitative services are provided by a multidisciplinary team.	COP-19, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
170		170	There is adequate space and equipment to perform these activities.	COP-19, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
171	Documented policies and procedures guide all research activities.	171	Documented policies and procedures guide all research activities in compliance with regulatory, national and international guidelines.	COP-20, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
172		172	The organisation has an ethics committee to oversee all research activities.	COP-20, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
173		173	The committee has the powers to discontinue a research trial when risks outweigh the potential benefits.	COP-20, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
174		174	Patient's informed consent is obtained before entering them in research protocols.	COP-20, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
175		175	Patients are informed of their right to withdraw from the research at any stage and also of the consequences (if any) of such withdrawal.	COP-20, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
176		176	Patients are assured that their refusal to participate or withdrawal from participation will not compromise their access to the organisation's services.	COP-20, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
177	Documented policies and procedures guide the end of life care. (NABH)	177	Documented policies and procedures guide the end of life care.	COP-22, a			CCS-5.15			2.19.1-1; 2.19.1-3; 2.19.1-4; 2.19.1-5;			9.4.6-1; 10.4.6-1; 11.4.6-1; 12.4.6-1; 13.4.6-1; 15.4.6-1; 16.4.6-1; 17.4.6-1;		
178		178	These policies and procedures are in consonance with the legal requirements.	COP-22, b			CCS-5.16			0	0	0	0	0	0
179		179	These also address the identification of the unique needs of such patient and family.	COP-22, c			0	0	0	2.19.1-2;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
180		180	Symptomatic treatment is provided and where appropriate measures are taken for the alleviation of pain.	COP-22, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
181		181	Staff are educated and trained in end of life care.	COP-22, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
182		182	The health service organisation has processes to ensure that current advance care plans: a. Can be received from patients b. Are documented in the patient's healthcare record				0	0	0	CCS-5.17			0	0	0
183		183	The health service organisation provides access to supervision and support for the workforce providing end-of-life care				0	0	0	CCS-5.18			0	0	0
184		184	The health service organisation has processes for routinely reviewing the safety and quality of end-of-life care that is provided against the planned goals of care				0	0	0	CCS-5.19			0	0	0
185		185	Clinicians support patients, carers and families to make shared decisions about end-of-life care.				0	0	0	CCS-5.20			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
186		186	The patient, family and significant other(s) are involved in care decisions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.6-2; 10.4.6-2; 11.4.6-2; 12.4.6-2; 13.4.6-2; 15.4.6-2; 16.4.6-2; 17.4.6-2;		
187		187	Pain and primary or secondary symptoms are managed according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.6-3; 10.4.6-3; 11.4.6-3; 12.4.6-3; 13.4.6-3; 15.4.6-3; 16.4.6-3; 17.4.6-3;		
188		188	Religious and cultural needs of patients and their families or significant others are identified and met.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.6-4; 10.4.6-4; 11.4.6-4; 12.4.6-4; 13.4.6-4; 15.4.6-4; 16.4.6-4; 17.4.6-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
189	Preventing and managing pressure injuries	189	The health service organisation providing services to patients at risk of pressure injuries has systems for pressure injury prevention and wound management that are consistent with best-practice guidelines	0	0	0	CCS-5.21			0	0	0	0	0	0
190		190	Clinicians providing care to patients at risk of developing, or with, a pressure injury conduct comprehensive skin inspections in accordance with best-practice time frames and frequency	0	0	0	CCS-5.22			0	0	0	0	0	0
191		191	The health service organisation providing services to patients at risk of pressure injuries ensures that: a. Patients, carers and families are provided with information about preventing pressure injuries b. Equipment, devices and products are used in line with best-practice guidelines to prevent and effectively manage pressure injuries	0	0	0	CCS-5.23, a,b			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
192	Preventing falls and harm from falls	192	The health service organisation providing services to patients at risk of falls has systems that are consistent with best-practice guidelines for: a. Falls prevention b. Minimising harm from falls c. Post-fall management	0	0	0	CCS-5.24, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
193		193	The health service organisation providing services to patients at risk of falls ensures that equipment, devices and tools are available to promote safe mobility and manage the risks of falls	0	0	0	CCS-5.25			0	0	0	0	0	0
194		194	Clinicians providing care to patients at risk of falls provide patients, carers and families with information about reducing falls risks and falls prevention strategies	0	0	0	CCS-5.26			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
195	Partnering with consumers-acute deterioration	195	Clinicians use organisational processes from the Partnering with Consumers Standard when recognising and responding to acute deterioration to: a. Actively involve patients in their own care b. Meet the patient's information needs c. Share decision-making	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
196	Recognising acute deterioration	196	Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Implementing policies and procedures for recognising and responding to acute deterioration b. Managing risks associated with recognising and responding to acute deterioration c. Identifying training requirements for recognising and responding to acute deterioration	0	0	0	RRAD S-8.1, a,b,c			2.10.1-1; 2.10.1-2; 2.10.1-3;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
197		197	The health service organisation has processes for clinicians to detect acute physiological deterioration that require clinicians to: a. Document individualised vital sign monitoring plans b. Monitor patients as required by their individualised monitoring plan c. Graphically document and track changes in agreed observations to detect acute deterioration over time, as appropriate for the patient	0	0	0	RRAD S-8.4, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
198		198	<p>The health service organisation has processes for clinicians to recognise acute deterioration in mental state that require clinicians to:</p> <p>a. Monitor patients at risk of acute deterioration in mental state, including patients at risk of developing delirium</p> <p>b. Include the person's known early warning signs of deterioration in mental state in their individualised monitoring plan</p> <p>c. Assess possible causes of acute deterioration in mental state, including delirium, when changes in behaviour, cognitive function, perception, physical function or emotional state are observed or reported</p> <p>d. Determine the required level of observation</p> <p>e. Document and communicate observed or reported changes in mental state</p>	0	0	0	RRAD S-8.5, a,b,c,d, e				0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
199	Escalating care	199	The health service organisation has protocols that specify criteria for escalating care, including: a. Agreed vital sign parameters and other indicators of physiological deterioration b. Agreed indicators of deterioration in mental state c. Agreed parameters and other indicators for calling emergency assistance d. Patient pain or distress that is not able to be managed using available treatment e. Worry or concern in members of the workforce, patients, carers and families about acute deterioration	0	0	0	RRAD S-8.6, a,b,c,d, e			0	0	0	0	0	0
200		200	The health service organisation has processes for patients, carers or families to directly escalate care	0	0	0	RRAD S-8.7			0	0	0	0	0	0
201		201	The health service organisation provides the workforce with mechanisms to escalate care and call for emergency	0	0	0	RRAD S-8.8			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			assistance												
202		202	The workforce uses the recognition and response systems to escalate care	0	0	0	RRAD S-8.9			0	0	0	0	0	0
203	Responding to deterioration	203	The health service organisation has processes that support timely response by clinicians with the skills required to manage episodes of acute deterioration	0	0	0	RRAD S-8.10			0	0	0	0	0	0
204		204	The health service organisation has processes to ensure rapid access at all times to at least one clinician, either on site or in close proximity, who can deliver advanced life support	0	0	0	RRAD S-8.11			0	0	0	0	0	0
205		205	The health service organisation has processes to ensure rapid referral to mental health services to meet the needs of patients whose mental state has acutely deteriorated	0	0	0	RRAD S-8.12			0	0	0	0	0	0
206		206	The health service organisation has processes for rapid referral to services that can provide definitive management of acute physical deterioration	0	0	0	RRAD S-8.13			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
207	The hospital prepares and uses guidelines concerning treatment of specific patient groups which are used as basis for treatment decisions. The guidelines are based on national guidelines, where they exist.	207	The hospital has a process ensuring the preparation of guidelines regarding treatment of specific patient groups for: the most frequent patient groups a) highly specialised treatment b) patient groups with complicated challenges in terms of assessment, c) treatment, rehabilitation, care or recovery.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.1-1;			0	0	0
208		208	The hospital has guidelines for how the guidelines for treatment of specific patient groups undergo a professional hearing and approval procedure prior to the final managerial approval.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.1-2;			0	0	0
209		209	There are guidelines prepared in accordance with the process and the determined professional hearing and approval procedure.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.1-3;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
210		210	Managers and staff are familiar with relevant parts of the guidelines regarding treatment of specific patient groups and work accordingly. In specific cases it may be well-founded to deviate from the guidelines. Specific de-selections are described and substantiated in the patient health record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.1-4;			0	0	0
211		211	The hospital has targets for the quality of the patient treatment. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.1-5;			0	0	0
212		212	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the patient treatment. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.1-6;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
213	The hospital prepares patient pathway descriptions concerning treatment of specific patient groups which are used as basis for the preparation of frequent and/or complex patient pathways.	213	The hospital has a process which ensures the preparation of pathway descriptions for: patients included by nationally integrated care pathways other complex and/or frequently occurring pathways	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.3-1;			0	0	0
214		214	There are agreements on the cross-sectorial collaboration between the primary sector and the secondary sector for patients with a chronic disease. As a minimum, the agreements describe: Tasks in the different phases of the pathway a) Unambiguous assignment of the responsibility for all the phases in the b) pathway	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.3-2;			0	0	0
215		215	There are pathway descriptions prepared in accordance with the process.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.3-3;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
216		216	There are specific pathway descriptions for patients with a chronic disease prepared as a result of the agreements on the cross-sectorial collaboration . As a minimum, the agreements include dementia, cardiac insufficiency, Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (COLD), type 2 diabetes and schizophrenia.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.3-4;			0	0	0
217		217	Managers and staff are familiar with the relevant pathway descriptions and work accordingly. In specific cases it may be well-founded to deviate from the pathway descriptions. Specific de-selections are described and substantiated in the patient health record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.3-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
218		218	The hospital has targets for the quality of its patient pathways. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. The targets include the nationally determined quality targets. Data are analysed and assessed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.3-6;			0	0	0
219		219	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of its patient pathways. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. The hospital cannot deselect this element of the standard as not prioritised. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals, including the nationally determined quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.12.3-7;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
220	Policies and procedures guide the care of high risk patients and the provision of high risk services.	220	Documented protocols, clinical guidelines or standard operating procedures for identified high risk patients and procedures are available and readily accessible.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.2.3-1; 10.2.3-1; 11.2.3-1; 12.2.3-1; 13.2.3-1; 15.2.3-1; 16.2.3-1; 17.2.3-1;		
221		221	In-service training is provided to personnel to ensure they understand the intent and content of the policies and procedures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.2.3-2; 10.2.3-2; 11.2.3-2; 12.2.3-2; 13.2.3-2; 15.2.3-2; 16.2.3-2; 17.2.3-2;		
222	Diversity and high-risk groups	222	The health service organisation: a. Identifies the diversity of the consumers using its services b. Identifies groups of patients using its services who are at higher risk of harm c. Incorporates information on the diversity of its consumers and higherrisk groups into the planning and delivery of care	0	0	0	CGS-1.15-a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
223	The care provided to each patient is planned and documented in the patient's record.	223	The planned care is provided and documented in the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.1-1; 10.4.1-1; 11.4.1-1; 12.4.1-1; 13.4.1-1; 15.4.1-1; 16.4.1-1; 17.4.1-1; 26.4.3-1;
224		224	The patient's response to care and therapeutic interventions is documented in the patient record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.1-2; 10.4.1-2; 11.4.1-2; 12.4.1-2; 13.4.1-2; 15.4.1-2; 16.4.1-2; 17.4.1-2;
225		225	All procedures and diagnostic tests ordered and performed are documented in the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.1-3; 10.4.1-3; 11.4.1-3; 12.4.1-3; 13.4.1-3; 15.4.1-3; 16.4.1-3; 17.4.1-3; 26.4.3-2;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
226		226	The results of procedures and diagnostic tests performed are available in the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.1-4; 10.4.1-4; 11.4.1-4; 12.4.1-4; 13.4.1-4; 15.4.1-4; 16.4.1-4; 17.4.1-4; 26.4.3-3;		
227		227	The maternal and foetal conditions and the progress of labour are recorded on a partogram in every labour.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13.4.1-5;		
228		228	Re-assessments are performed at appropriate, regular intervals and following a change in the patient's condition, and documented in the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.1-5; 10.4.1-5; 11.4.1-5; 12.4.1-5; 13.4.1-6; 15.4.1-5; 16.4.1-5; 17.4.1-5; 26.4.3-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
229		229	Care plans are revised when necessary in response to the findings of re-assessments.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.1-6; 10.4.1-6; 11.4.1-6; 12.4.1-6; 13.4.1-7; 15.4.1-6; 17.4.1-6; 26.4.3-5;		
230	Each healthcare professional supports patient, family and caregiver participation in care decisions and care processes	230	Patients and families indicate that they have received health education appropriate to their condition.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.2-1;		
231		231	Patients indicate that they have been informed about the clinical management of their condition.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.2-2;		
232		232	Patients are educated about their diagnosis relevant health risks, e.g. safe use of medication and medical equipment, medicine and food interaction, therapeutic diet and food interactions, defaulting on medication use, etc.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.2-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
233		233	Patients and families indicate that they have been informed about financial implications of care decisions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.2-4;		
234	Where observation and/or forensic services are provided, they comply with country-specific legislation.	234	Policies and procedures that guide the care and/or observation of forensic patients and the provision of forensic services are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.8.2-1;		
235		235	Security or correctional personnel are educated/trained regarding their responsibilities in relation to assisting with the management of patients.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.8.2-2;		
236		236	All seclusion or restraint, whether for clinical or non-clinical purposes, is documented in the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.8.2-3;		
237		237	There are mechanisms designed to facilitate communication and resolve conflict between judicial, correctional, penal, clinical and administrative agencies and those involved in an individual's care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.8.2-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
238	Integrating clinical governance	238	Clinicians use the safety and quality systems from the Clinical Governance Standard when: a. Implementing policies and procedures for comprehensive care b. Managing risks associated with comprehensive care c. Identifying training requirements to deliver comprehensive care	0	0	0	CCS-5.1, a,b,c				0	0	0	0	0	0
239	The hospital designs and implements processes to provide continuity of patient care services within the hospital and coordination among health professionals	239	Policies and procedures that guide the movement of patients within the hospital are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.1-1; 10.7.1-1; 11.7.1-1; 12.7.1-1; 13.7.1-1; 15.7.1-1; 17.7.1-1; 18.10.1-1; 19.8.4-1; 20.10.1-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
240		240	Individuals responsible for the patient's care and its coordination are identified for all phases of patient care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.1-2; 10.7.1-2; 11.7.1-2; 12.7.1-2; 13.7.1-2; 15.7.1-2; 16.7.1-2; 17.7.1-2; 18.10.1-2; 19.8.4-2; 20.10.1-2;		
241		241	Continuity and coordination are evident throughout all phases of patient care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.1-3; 10.7.1-3; 11.7.1-3; 12.7.1-3; 13.7.1-3; 15.7.1-3; 16.7.1-3; 17.7.1-3; 18.10.1-3; 19.8.4-3; 20.10.1-;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
242		242	When a patient is transferred within the hospital, they are accompanied by their patient record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.1-4; 10.7.1-4; 11.7.1-4; 12.7.1-4; 13.7.1-4; 15.7.1-4; 16.7.1-4; 17.7.1-4; 18.10.1-4; 19.8.4-4; 20.10.1-4;		
243		243	Patient handover between healthcare professionals is standardised according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.7.1-5; 10.7.1-5; 11.7.1-5; 12.7.1-5; 13.7.1-5; 15.7.1-5; 16.7.1-5; 17.7.1-5;		
244		244	Documentation regarding the transfer of a patient from the forensic service to another service within the hospital meets legal requirements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.7.1-6;		

Table Number-21: Anesthesia and Surgical Care (ASC):

The Anesthesia and Surgical Care Chapter has 15 Standards and 102 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
1	The operating theatre and anaesthetic services are managed and staffed to provide a safe and effective service.	1	A senior professional who is suitably qualified and experienced is in charge of the theatre and the recovery area.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.2.1-1;
2		2	During all phases of care, there are qualified individuals responsible for the patient's care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.2.1-2;
3		3	There is a theatre users' committee or equivalent, which meets regularly and consists of representatives from all relevant services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.2.1-3;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
4		4	Operating theatre rosters ensure that registered nurses with suitable qualifications and experience are present during all shifts for theatre duties, anaesthetic assistance and recovery room duties.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.2.1-4;
5		5	Anaesthesia is administered only by medical practitioners or other professionals who are privileged by the hospital to do so.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.2.1-5;
6		6	Trainee anaesthetists are under the supervision of trained anaesthesiologists.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.2.1-6;
7		7	The person administering anaesthesia is directly responsible for only one anaesthetised patient at a time.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.2.1-7;
8		8	Anaesthesia is commenced and terminated only in the presence of a member of personnel whose sole duty it is to assist the person administering anaesthesia until such time as the latter indicates that	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.2.1-8;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			assistance is no longer required.												
9		9	The surgeon performing the procedure(s) is present in the operating theatre before the anaesthetist commences the administration of the anaesthetic.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10		10	There is at least one suitably trained and/or experienced anaesthetic nurse per operating theatre.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11		11	Nursing personnel trained and/or experienced in recovery room care are available until the patient has fully recovered.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	Documented policies and procedures relating to the activities in the operating theatre are implemented.	12	Policies and procedures that guide the activities of the operating theatre services are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13		13	Policies and procedures relating to the anaesthetic service are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
14		14	In-service training is provided to personnel to ensure they understand the intent and content of the policies and procedures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.2.3-3;		
15	Policies and procedures that guide the care of patients undergoing moderate and deep sedation are implemented.	15	Policies and procedures regarding the care of patients undergoing moderate and deep sedation are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.10.2-1;			14.2.4-1;		
16		16	There is a pre-sedation assessment, according to hospital policy, to evaluate risk and appropriateness of sedation for the patient.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.10.2-2;			14.2.4-2;		
17		17	A qualified individual monitors the patient during sedation and during the period of recovery from sedation and documents the monitoring.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.10.2-3;			14.2.4-3;		
18		18	Moderate and deep sedation are administered according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.2.4-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
19	Documented policies and procedures guide the care of patients undergoing moderate sedation.	19	Documented procedures guide the administration of moderate sedation.	COP-13, a			0	0	0	2.10.2-1;			0	0	0
20		20	Informed consent for administration of moderate sedation is obtained.	COP-13, b			0	0	0	2.10.2-3;			0	0	0
21		21	Competent and trained persons perform sedation.	COP-13, c			0	0	0	2.10.2-3;			0	0	0
22		22	The person administering and monitoring sedation is different from the person performing the procedure.	COP-13, d			0	0	0	2.10.2-3;			0	0	0
23		23	Intra-procedure monitoring includes at a minimum the heart rate, cardiac rhythm, respiratory rate, blood pressure, oxygen saturation, level of sedation and end tidal carbon dioxide.	COP-13, e; COP-14, f			0	0	0	2.10.2-3;			0	0	0
24		24	Patients are monitored after sedation and the same documented.	COP-13, f			0	0	0	2.10.2-3;			0	0	0
25		25	Criteria are used to determine appropriateness of discharge from the observation/ recovery	COP-13, g			0	0	0	2.10.2-3;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			area.												
26		26	Equipment and manpower are available to manage patients who have gone into a deeper level of sedation than initially intended.	COP-13, h			0	0	0	2.10.2-3;			0	0	0
27		27	The hospital has targets for the quality of sedation of patients for procedures without the involvement of anaesthesiological staff, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year period. The goals include regular control of presence and function of monitoring and resuscitation equipment (e.g. oxygen, suction and bag) on the ward or in the immediate vicinity. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.				0	0	0	2.10.2-4;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
28		28	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of sedation of patients for procedures without the involvement of anaesthesiological staff. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.10.2-5;			0	0	0
29	Documented policies and procedures guide the administration of anaesthesia.	29	There is a documented policy and procedure for the administration of anaesthesia.	COP-14, a			0	0	0	2.11.1-1;			0	0	0
30		30	Patients for anaesthesia have a pre-anaesthesia assessment by a qualified anaesthesiologist.	COP-14, b			0	0	0	2.11.1-2;			0	0	0
31		31	The pre-anaesthesia assessment results in formulation of an anaesthesia plan which is documented.	COP-14, c			0	0	0	2.11.1-3;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
32		32	An immediate preoperative re-evaluation is performed and documented.	COP-14, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
33		33	Informed consent for administration of anaesthesia is obtained by the anesthesiologist.	COP-14, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
34		34	Patient's post-anaesthesia status is monitored and documented.	COP-14, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
35		35	The anaesthesiologist applies defined criteria to transfer the patient from the recovery area.	COP-14, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
36		36	The type of anaesthesia and anaesthetic medications used are documented in the patient record.	COP-14, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
37		37	Procedures shall comply with infection control guidelines to prevent crossinfection between patients.	COP-14, j			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
38		38	Adverse anaesthesia events are recorded and monitored.	COP-14, k			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
39		39	The hospital has targets for the quality of the assessment prior to the procedure in anaesthesia. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. Data are analysed and assessed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.1-4;			0	0	0
40		40	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the assessment prior to the procedure in anaesthesia. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.1-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
41	Pre-and post-procedural assessments are documented.	41	The patient's pre-anaesthetic medical assessment to determine fitness for anaesthesia is documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.4-1; 10.4.4-1; 11.4.4-1; 12.4.4-1; 13.4.4-1; 15.4.4-1; 16.4.4-1; 17.4.4-1;
42		42	Patients have a pre-procedural diagnosis recorded before anaesthesia.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.4-2; 10.4.4-2; 11.4.4-2; 12.4.4-2; 13.4.4-2; 15.4.4-2; 17.4.4-2;
43		43	A post-procedural diagnosis is documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.4-3; 10.4.4-3; 11.4.4-3; 12.4.4-3; 13.4.4-3; 15.4.4-3; 17.4.4-3;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
44		44	The name of the medical practitioner responsible for the procedure is documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.4-4; 10.4.4-4; 11.4.4-4; 12.4.4-4; 13.4.4-4; 15.4.4-4; 17.4.4-4;
45		45	The patient's physiological status is monitored during the post-procedural period.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.4.4-5; 10.4.4-5; 11.4.4-5; 12.4.4-5; 13.4.4-5; 15.4.4-5; 16.4.4-4; 17.4.4-5;
46	The hospital supports a surgical safety pathway by using WHO's Surgical Safety Check list.	46	There are guidelines which support safe implementation of operative, invasive procedure in general or local anaesthesia with anaesthetic involvement. The guidelines are based on WHO's "Surgical safety". Check lists have been prepared which can be adjusted to specific procedures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.5-1;			0	0	0	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
47		47	Managers and staff implement the initiatives in the hospital's check list in connection with operative, invasive procedures in general or local anaesthesia with anaesthetic involvement.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.5-2;			0	0	0
48		48	Implementation of "Surgical safety" is documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.5-3;			0	0	0
49		49	The hospital has targets for the quality for the implementation of "Surgical safety" and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.5-4;			0	0	0
50		50	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the documentation of informed consent. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.5-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.												
51	Each patient's physiological status is monitored and recorded during anaesthesia and surgery.	51	The patient's physiological status is continuously monitored during anaesthesia and surgery.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
52		52	The results of such monitoring are entered into the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
53		53	The anaesthetic agents used are entered into the patient's anaesthetic record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
54		54	Analgesia administered on conclusion of the surgical procedure is documented in the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
55		55	The patient's pre-anaesthetic medical assessment to determine fitness for anaesthesia is documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
56		56	The results of diagnostic tests performed on the patient are recorded prior to the administration of anaesthesia.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
57		57	The names of the anaesthetist, the medical practitioner who performs the ECT and other personnel, as required by law, are documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.4.5-3;
58		58	The patient's physiological status is monitored during the immediate post-ECT period.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.4.5-4;
59	The patients' post-anaesthetic monitoring is secured through a stipulated post-anaesthetic plan.	59	There are guidelines for planning of the post-anaesthetic monitoring.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.2-1;			0	0	0	
60		60	There are guidelines for termination of the post-anaesthetic monitoring.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.2-2;			0	0	0	
61		61	Post-anaesthetic monitoring is planned and implemented in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.2-3;			0	0	0	
62		62	Post-anaesthetic monitoring is terminated in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.2-4;			0	0	0	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
63		63	The hospital has targets for the quality of post-anaesthetic monitoring and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.2-5;			0	0	0
64		64	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the postanaesthetic monitoring. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.11.2-6;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
65	There is a system to monitor and document each patient's post-anaesthetic status and to discharge the patient from the recovery area according to accepted guidelines.	65	There are guidelines for assessment and initiation of recovery for relevant patient groups. If the effort is performed in collaboration with external parties, the division of responsibility and tasks will be described.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.1-1;			0	0	0
66		66	Patients who need recovery are offered a relevant recovery effort.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.1-2;			0	0	0
67		67	The hospital has target for the quality of the recovery effort and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.1-3;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
68		68	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the recovery effort. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.1-4;			0	0	0
69		69	The anaesthetist is responsible for supervising the recovery period.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.3.2-1;		
70		70	The qualifications and experience of personnel members who may monitor patients are documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.3.2-2;		
71		71	Monitoring is appropriate to the patient's condition during the post- anaesthetic recovery period.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.3.2-3;		
72		72	Monitoring findings are documented in the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.3.2-4;		
73		73	The individual responsible for discharging the patient and signs the discharge in the patient record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.3.2-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
74		74	Verbal orders are documented according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.3.2-6;		
75		75	Times of arrival in and discharge from the recovery area are recorded.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.3.2-7;		
76		76	Established criteria are used to make decisions to discharge patients from the recovery room.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.3.2-8;		
77		77	Patient safety is ensured by the correct implementation of the handover procedure from the recovery room personnel to the unit/ward personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.3.2-9;		
78		78	Signatures of those receiving the patient are recorded.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.3.2-10;		
79	Post-operative assessments are documented.	79	A post-operative diagnosis is documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.7.5-1; 20.7.4-1;		
80		80	The name of the surgeon and the names of other personnel are documented as required by law.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.7.5-2; 20.7.4-2;		
81		81	The patient's physiological status is monitored during the immediate post-surgical period.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.7.5-3; 20.7.4-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
82	Minor invasive procedures performed in the outpatient department are controlled by policy.	82	Policies and procedures govern invasive procedures performed in the outpatient department.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.7.3-1; 19.5.3-1; 20.7.3-1;
83		83	Protocols guide medication use for sedation, pain and anaesthesia.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.7.3-2; 19.5.3-2; 20.7.3-2;
84		84	Protocols address appropriate monitoring during and after the procedure.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.7.3-3; 19.5.3-3; 20.7.3-3;
85		85	The procedure and the name of the person performing the procedure are recorded in the patient's record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.7.3-4; 19.5.3-4; 20.7.3-4;
86		86	Unsuccessful or complicated procedures are recorded.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.7.3-5; 19.5.3-5; 20.7.3-5;
87	Anaesthetic equipment, supplies and medication comply with the recommendations of anaesthetic professional organisations or other authoritative sources.	87	Anaesthetic mixture components are available and used in accordance with hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.2-1;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
88		88	The recommendations of anaesthetic professional organisations or other authoritative sources guide the provision and use of breathing circuits.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.2-2;		
89		89	The recommendations of anaesthetic professional organisations or other authoritative sources guide the use of scavenging equipment for removing vapours and anaesthetic gases.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.2-3;		
90		90	The recommendations of anaesthetic professional organisations or other authoritative sources guide the provision and use of monitoring equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.2-4;		
91		91	The recommendations of anaesthetic professional organisations or other authoritative sources guide the provision and use of ancillary equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.2-5;		
92		92	Medication is available according to the requirements of the level of care provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.2-6;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
93		93	A medication trolley is available for the exclusive use of the anaesthetist in each theatre.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.2-7;		
94		94	A tracheostomy tray is available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.2-8;		
95	Medical equipment available meets the minimum requirements for the level of care provided.	95	Equipment and instrumentation for routine and emergency surgery must be available according to hospital policy for the level of care provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.3-1;		
96		96	Theatre personnel ensure that all equipment is included in the hospital's equipment replacement and maintenance programme.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.3-2;		
97	Resuscitation and personal protective equipment are provided in the operating theatre.	97	Standardised resuscitation equipment is available in all relevant areas of the operating theatre suite.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.4-1;		
98		98	Resuscitation equipment shows evidence of regular checking.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.4-2;		
99		99	Resuscitation equipment and supplies have clearly defined instructions for use.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.4-3;		
100		100	There is a mechanism for summoning assistance in an emergency.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.4-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
101		101	There is appropriate shielding and protective clothing in the presence of biohazards (including lasers) or radiographic equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.4-5;		
102		102	Hazard or warning notices are displayed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14.1.4-6;		

Table Number-22: Assessment of Patient (AOP):

The Assessment of Patient Chapter has 15 Standards and 110 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
1	Each patient has an initial assessment that complies with current policies, procedures and guidelines.	1	Each patient admitted has an initial assessment according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1.3-2; 9.3.2-1; 10.3.2-1; 11.3.2-1; 12.3.2-1; 13.3.2-1; 15.3.2-1; 16.3.2-1; 17.3.2-1;			
2		2	The initial assessment includes health history.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.2-2; 10.3.2-2; 11.3.2-2; 12.3.2-2; 13.3.2-2; 15.3.2-2; 16.3.2-3; 17.3.2-2;			

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
3		3	The initial assessment includes physical examination.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.2-3; 10.3.2-3; 11.3.2-3; 12.3.2-3; 13.3.2-3; 15.3.2-3; 16.3.2-4; 17.3.2-3;		
4		4	The initial assessment includes functional and nutritional examination, where applicable.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.2-4; 10.3.2-4; 11.3.2-4; 12.3.2-4; 13.3.2-4; 15.3.2-4; 16.3.2-5; 17.3.2-4;		
5		5	The initial assessment includes social and economic assessment, where applicable.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.2-5; 10.3.2-5; 11.3.2-5; 12.3.2-5; 13.3.2-5; 15.3.2-5; 16.3.2-6; 17.3.2-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
6		6	The initial assessment includes psychological assessment, where applicable.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.2-6; 10.3.2-6; 11.3.2-6; 12.3.2-6; 13.3.2-6; 15.3.2-6; 16.3.2-2; 17.3.2-6;		
7		7	The initial assessment includes cultural assessment, where applicable.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.2-7; 10.3.2-7; 11.3.2-7; 12.3.2-7; 13.3.2-7; 15.3.2-7; 16.3.2-7; 17.3.2-7;		
8		8	The initial assessment includes antenatal history.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13.3.2-8;		
9		9	The initial assessment includes maternal and foetal examination.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13.3.2-9;		

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
10		10	The initial assessment results in an initial diagnosis.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.2-8; 10.3.2-8; 11.3.2-8; 12.3.2-8; 13.3.2-10; 15.3.2-8; 16.3.2-8; 17.3.2-8;			
11		11	The patient's medical, nursing and other healthcare needs identified during the initial assessment are documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.2-9; 10.3.2-9; 11.3.2-9; 12.3.2-9; 13.3.2-11; 15.3.2-9; 16.3.2-9; 17.3.2-9;			
12		12	Discharge planning is commenced with the initial assessment and involves the patient and their family or carers.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.3.2-10;			
13		13	Where appropriate, treatment planning is done in collaboration with the patient's family and/or carers.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.3.2-11;			

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
14		14	Patients admitted to the unit against their will are assessed, admitted and cared for in accordance with legislative requirements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17.3.2-12;			
15	Allergy and intolerance	15	There are guidelines for documentation of known allergy	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.4-1;			0	0	0	
16		16	There are guidelines for documentation of known intolerance.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.4-2;			0	0	0	
17		17	Known allergy and intolerance are documented in the patient health record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.4-3;			0	0	0	
18		18	Known allergy and intolerance are communicated to relevant professionals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.4-4;			0	0	0	
19		19	The hospital has targets for the quality of documentation of allergy and intolerance. The hospital collects quantitative data which reflect the level of rating achievement of the targets. Data are analysed and assessed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.3.4-1;			0	0	0	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
20	Planning for comprehensive care	20	The health service organisation has processes relevant to the patients using the service and the services provided: a. For integrated and timely screening and assessment b. That identify the risks of harm in the 'Minimising patient harm' criterion	0	0	0	CCS-5.7, a,b			0	0	0	0	0	0
21		21	Patients are supported to document clear advance care plans	0	0	0	CCS-5.9			0	0	0	0	0	0
22		22	Clinicians use relevant screening processes: a. On presentation, during clinical examination and history taking, and when required during care b. To identify cognitive, behavioural, mental and physical conditions, issues, and risks of harm c. To identify social and other circumstances that may compound these risks	0	0	0	CCS-5.10, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
23		23	Clinicians comprehensively assess the conditions and risks identified through the screening	0	0	0	CCS-5.11			0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			process												
24		24	Clinicians document the findings of the screening and clinical assessment processes, including any relevant alerts, in the healthcare record	0	0	0	CCS-5.12			0	0	0	0	0	0
25		25	The workforce, patients, carers and families work in partnership to: a. Use the comprehensive care plan to deliver care b. Monitor the effectiveness of the comprehensive care plan in meeting the goals of care c. Review and update the comprehensive care plan if it is not effective d. Reassess the patient's needs if changes in diagnosis, behaviour, cognition, or mental or physical condition occur	0	0	0	CCS-5.14			0	0	0	0	0	0
26	Patients cared for by the organisation undergo an established initial assessment.	26	The organisation defines and documents the content of the initial assessment for the out-patients, in-patients and emergency patients.	ACC-4, a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
27		27	The organisation determines who can perform the initial assessment.	ACC-4, b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28		28	The organisation defines the time frame within which the initial assessment is completed based on patient's needs.	ACC-4, c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29		29	The initial assessment for in-patients is documented within 24 hours or earlier as per the patient's condition, as defined in the organisation's policy.	ACC-4, d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30		30	Initial assessment of in-patients includes nursing assessment which is done at the time of admission and documented.	ACC-4, e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31		31	Initial assessment includes screening for nutritional needs.	ACC-4, f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
32		32	The initial assessment results in a documented care plan.	ACC-4, g			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
33		33	The care plan reflects desired results of the treatment, care or service.	ACC-4, h			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
34		34	The care plan is countersigned by the clinician in-charge of the patient within 24 hours.	ACC-4, i			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
35	The patients' nutritional risk is assessed and they get an adjusted nutrition.	35	There are guidelines for nutritional screening with a view to identify patients with special nutritional risk.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.14.1-1;			0	0	0
36		36	There are guidelines for initiation of plan for nutrition and follow-up for patients in nutritional risk. If the effort is performed in collaboration with external parties, the division of responsibility and tasks will be described.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.14.1-2;			0	0	0
37		37	Nutritional screening is performed in accordance with the guidelines in element 1 of the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.14.1-3;			0	0	0
38		38	Patients in nutritional risk, which is directly significant for the treatment outcome, are offered relevant intervention (plan for nutrition). Other patients in nutritional risk are offered intervention or counselling on where to request intervention.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.14.1-4;			0	0	0
39		39	Nutrition plan and follow-up are documented in the patient health record.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.14.1-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
40		40	The hospital has targets for the quality of the effort for patients with nutritional risk, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.14.1-6;			0	0	0
41		41	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality for patients with nutritional risk. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.14.1-7;			0	0	0
42	The hospital identifies patients who need a rehabilitation plan and prepares rehabilitation plans for them.	42	There are guidelines for systematic assessment of the rehabilitation need.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.2-1;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
43		43	There are guidelines for preparation of rehabilitation plans for outpatient recovery in the municipality and outpatient specialised recovery at hospital. The guidelines describe how the recovery plans are passed on to the primary sector.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.2-2;			0	0	0
44		44	Relevant patients have their rehabilitation need assessed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.2-3;			0	0	0
45		45	Rehabilitation plans are prepared in accordance with the guidelines in element 2 of the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.2-4;			0	0	0
46		46	The hospital has targets for the preparation of the rehabilitation plans The hospital collects quantitative data which illustrate whether rehabilitation plans are prepared when it is relevant. Data are analysed and assessed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.2-5;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
47		47	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the preparation of rehabilitation plans. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.2-6;			0	0	0
48	All patients cared for by the hospital have their healthcare needs identified through an established assessment process.	48	Hospital policies and procedures for assessing patients on admission and during ongoing care are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.1-1; 10.3.1-1; 11.3.1-1; 12.3.1-1; 13.3.1-1; 15.3.1-1; 16.3.1-1; 17.3.1-1; 18.5.2-1; 20.5.2-1; 19.3.2-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
49		49	Only those individuals permitted by applicable laws and regulations or by registration perform the assessments.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.1-2; 10.3.1-2; 11.3.1-2; 12.3.1-2; 13.3.1-2; 15.3.1-2; 16.3.1-2; 17.3.1-2; 18.5.2-2; 20.5.2-2; 19.3.2-2; 26.4.1-3;			
50		50	The scope and content of assessment by each discipline is defined.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.1-3; 10.3.1-3; 11.3.1-3; 12.3.1-3; 13.3.1-3; 15.3.1-3; 16.3.1-3; 17.3.1-3; 18.5.2-3; 20.5.2-3; 19.3.2-3; 26.4.1-2;			

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
51		51	Assessments are performed within appropriate time frames and are comprehensively documented in the patients' records according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.1-4; 10.3.1-4; 11.3.1-4; 12.3.1-4; 13.3.1-4; 15.3.1-4; 16.3.1-4; 17.3.1-4; 18.5.2-4; 20.5.2-4; 19.3.2-4; 26.4.1-4;		
52		52	Agreements are in place with the nearest psychiatric unit to ensure appropriate, expedited care for psychiatric patients.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.5.2-5; 20.5.2-5;		
53		53	Assessments completed entirely outside the hospital are verified on admission to the service	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	26.4.1-5;		
54	Patients cared for by the organisation undergo a regular reassessment.	54	Patients are reassessed at appropriate intervals.	AOP-5. a			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
55		55	Out-patients are informed of their next follow-up, where appropriate.	AOP-5. b			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
56		56	For in-patients during reassessment the care plan is monitored and modified, where found necessary.	AOP-5. c			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
57		57	Staff involved in direct clinical care document reassessments.	AOP-5. d			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
58		58	Patients are reassessed to determine their response to treatment and to plan further treatment or discharge.	AOP-5. e			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
59		59	The organisation lays down guidelines and implements processes to identify early warning signs of change or deterioration in clinical conditions for initiating prompt intervention.	AOP-5. f			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
60	Healthcare professionals responsible for patient care collaborate to analyse and integrate assessment information.	60	Assessment findings are documented in the patient's record and are readily available to those responsible for the patient's care.				0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
61		61	Patient assessment data and information are analysed and integrated by those responsible for the patient's care and used to develop the treatment plan, which includes the goals of care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.3-2; 10.3.3-2; 11.3.3-2; 12.3.3-2; 15.3.3-2; 17.3.3-2; 18.7.1-2; 19.5.1-2; 20.7.1-2; 26.4.2-2;		
62		62	Patient needs are prioritised on the basis of assessment results.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.3-3; 10.3.3-3; 11.3.3-3; 12.3.3-3; 15.3.3-3; 17.3.3-3; 18.7.1-3; 19.5.1-3; 20.7.1-3; 26.4.2-3;		
63		63	The patient and/or the family participate in the decisions regarding the priority needs to be met.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.3-4; 10.3.3-4; 11.3.3-4; 12.3.3-4; 15.3.3-4; 17.3.3-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
64	The delivery of services is integrated and coordinated amongst care providers.	64	The patient's clinical records are completed according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.4-1; 10.3.4-1; 11.3.4-1; 12.3.4-1; 13.3.4-1; 15.3.4-1; 16.3.4-1; 17.3.4-1; 18.7.1-1; 19.5.1-1; 20.7.1-1;			
65		65	The patient's records are up to date to ensure the transfer of the latest information between care providers.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.4-2; 10.3.4-2; 11.3.4-2; 12.3.4-2; 13.3.4-2; 15.3.4-2; 16.3.4-2; 17.3.4-2; 18.7.1-2; 19.5.1-2; 20.7.1-2;			

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
66		66	Information exchanged includes a summary of the initial assessment, summary of care provided and the results of diagnostic tests.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.4-3; 10.3.4-3; 11.3.4-3; 12.3.4-3; 13.3.4-3; 15.3.4-3; 17.3.4-3; 18.7.1-3; 19.5.1-3; 20.7.1-3;			
67		67	Information exchanged includes the patient's progress.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.4-4; 10.3.4-4; 11.3.4-4; 12.3.4-4; 13.3.4-4; 15.3.4-4; 17.3.4-4; 18.7.1-4; 19.5.1-4; 20.7.1-4;			

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
68		68	The author can be identified for each patient record entry.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.4-5; 10.3.4-5; 11.3.4-5; 12.3.4-5; 13.3.4-5; 15.3.4-5; 17.3.4-5; 18.7.1-5; 19.5.1-5; 20.7.1-5;			
69		69	The date of each patient record entry can be identified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.4-6; 10.3.4-6; 11.3.4-6; 12.3.4-6; 13.3.4-6; 15.3.4-6; 17.3.4-6; 18.7.1-6; 19.5.1-6; 20.7.1-6;			
70		70	Patient handover between healthcare professionals is standardised according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.7.1-8; 19.5.1-8; 20.7.1-8;			

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
71		71	The time of each patient record entry can be identified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9.3.4-7; 10.3.4-7; 11.3.4-7; 12.3.4-7; 13.3.4-7; 15.3.4-7; 16.3.4-5; 17.3.4-7; 18.7.1-7; 19.5.1-7; 20.7.1-7;			
72		72	Patient care plans are formulated collaboratively by all healthcare professionals involved in the patient's care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.3.4-6;			
73		73	Patient needs are prioritised on the basis of assessment results.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.3.4-7;			
74		74	The team conducts periodic re-evaluation of each patient's plan of care to determine whether established goals are being or have been met and whether change in the patient's condition requires modification of goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75		75	A designated individual is responsible for the coordination and integration of care for each	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.3.4-10;			

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				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			patient.												
76		76	The multidisciplinary team meets regularly to coordinate patient care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
77		77	The care provided by the multidisciplinary team is documented according to hospital policy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
78		78	There is a multidisciplinary approach to the development and implementation of a therapeutic programme in accordance with a policy framework.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
79		79	The team consists of appropriately qualified personnel and includes representatives from all services offering care to the patient.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
80		80	Each patient's care is coordinated by a designated individual who is appointed by the team and made known to the patient.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
81		81	The team members' responsibilities include development and implementation of care plans for each patient, based on the assessment of the patient.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
82		82	The team conducts periodic re-evaluation of each patient's plan of care to determine whether established goals are being or have been met and whether change in the patient's condition requires modification of goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.3.4-8; 26.4.2-8;			
83		83	The team includes the patient and his/her family in the development and review of the plan of care, as appropriate.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.3.4-9; 26.4.2-9;			
84	The treatment of acute patients is managed by a treatment plan which is systematically adjusted based on an on-going assessment of the patient.	84	There are guidelines for which types of acute patients the hospital can receive. The guidelines describe any variations during day and night.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.6-1;			0	0	0	
85		85	There are guidelines for the preliminary assessment of the patient. The guidelines describe content and deadline for the assessment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.6-2;			0	0	0	

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
86		86	There are guidelines for preparation and content of the treatment plan for the individual acute patient, including observation plan for the following period. As far as possible, the plan is prepared by involving the patient and the relatives, if any.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.6-3;			0	0	0
87		87	The hospital's guidelines for which types of acute patients can be received are available for the referring part.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.6-4;			0	0	0
88		88	A preliminary assessment is performed of the patient at his/her arrival at the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.6-5;			0	0	0
89		89	There is a treatment plan for the individual patient. The treatment plan is prepared within the determined time frame stipulated by the hospital and includes observation plan.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.6-6;			0	0	0
90		90	The individual patient is re-assessed according to the hospital's guidelines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.6-7;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
91		91	The hospital has targets for the quality of the treatment of the individual acute patient, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.6-8;			0	0	0
92		92	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the treatment of the individual acute patient. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.7.6-9;			0	0	0
93	Patients' need for recovery is assessed and when needed an effort is offered.	93	There are guidelines for assessment and initiation of recovery for relevant patient groups. If the effort is performed in collaboration with external parties, the division of	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.1-1;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			responsibility and tasks will be described.												
94		94	Patients who need recovery are offered a relevant recovery effort.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.1-2;			0	0	0
95		95	The hospital has target for the quality of the recovery effort and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.1-3;			0	0	0
96		96	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the recovery effort. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented. This element of the standard is not relevant if the hospital meets the quality goals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.1-4;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
97	Documentation of information	97	The health service organisation has processes to contemporaneously document information in the healthcare record, including: a. Critical information, alerts and risks b. Reassessment processes and outcomes c. Changes to the care plan	0	0	0	CCS-6.11, a,b,c			0	0	0	0	0	0
98	The hospital identifies patients who need a rehabilitation plan and prepares rehabilitation plans for them.	98	There are guidelines for systematic assessment of the rehabilitation need.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.2-1;			0	0	0
99		99	There are guidelines for preparation of rehabilitation plans for outpatient recovery in the municipality and outpatient specialised recovery at hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.2-2;			0	0	0
100		100	Relevant patients have their rehabilitation need assessed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.2-3;			0	0	0
101		101	Rehabilitation plans are prepared in accordance with the standard.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.2-4;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
102		102	The hospital has targets for the preparation of the rehabilitation plans. The hospital collects quantitative data which illustrate whether rehabilitation plans are prepared when it is relevant. Data are analysed and assessed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.2-5;			0	0	0
103		103	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality of the preparation of rehabilitation plans. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.15.2-6;			0	0	0
104	Patients' health-related risk is assessed on the basis of life style factors. Relevant patients are offered intervention.	104	The hospital has a policy for prevention and health promotion describing defined goals and prioritisations for the effort at the area and how to clarify them for the staff, patients and relatives.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.16.2-1;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
105		105	There are guidelines for health-related risk assessment of patients describing how the hospital identifies patients, where an intervention in relation to life style factors is significant for the outcome of the patient pathway, or where life style factors otherwise pose a considerable risk for the patient.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.16.2-2;			0	0	0
106		106	There are guidelines for implementation of intervention regarding life style factors which are significant for the outcome of the patient pathway or where life style factors otherwise pose a risk for the patient. If the intervention takes place in collaboration with external parties, the division of responsibility and tasks will be described	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.16.2-3;			0	0	0
107		107	Patients with life style factors significant for the outcome of the patient pathway are offered intervention.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.16.2-4;			0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
108		108	Other patients in risk related to life style factors are offered intervention or counselling on where to request intervention.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.16.2-5;			0	0	0
109		109	The hospital has targets for the quality of the effort for prevention and health promotion, and the hospital assesses whether the target/s have been reached at least two times during a three-year-period. The assessment can be based on quantitative or qualitative methods or a combination of both.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.16.2-6;			0	0	0
110		110	The hospital has implemented initiatives to improve the quality for patients with nutritional risk. The effect of the initiatives has been assessed and it has either been concluded that they had the desired effect or new corrective initiatives have been implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.16.2-6;			0	0	0

Table Number-23: Nuclear Medicine:

The Nuclear Medicine Chapter has 9 Standards and 86 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
1	Where there is an arrangement with an outside service, this service meets applicable local and national standards, laws and regulations.	1	Adequate, convenient and regular nuclear medicine services are available to meet needs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.1.1-1;		
2		2	The selection of an outside source is based on an acceptable record and compliance with relevant laws and regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.1.1-2;		
3		3	Patients are informed about any relationships between the referring physician and outside sources of nuclear medicine services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.1.1-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
4		4	The nuclear medicine services provided meet applicable local and national standards, laws and regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.1.1-4;
5		5	The hospital has established the expected turnaround time for reports within a time frame to meet patient needs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.1.1-5;
6		6	Reports are clearly labelled with the name of the patient and the date and time of the procedures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.1.1-6;
7		7	Quality control results from outside sources are regularly reviewed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.1.1-7;
8		8	Qualified individuals review the quality control results.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.1.1-8;
9	Where the hospital provides on-site nuclear medicine services, the service is organised and managed in accordance with applicable laws, regulations and standards.	9	Nuclear medicine services are under the direction of one or more qualified individuals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.2.1-1;
10		10	All professional personnel are currently registered.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.2.1-2;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
11		11	There are qualified nuclear radiographers to provide services in keeping with the scope of their profession.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.2.1-3;
12		12	A qualified medical radiation physicist is available to fulfil the legal requirements of the regulations for the safe use of ionising radiation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.2.1-4;
13		13	The services of a qualified radiopharmacist or nuclear medicine radiographer are available for radiopharmaceutical preparations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.2.1-5;
14		14	Responsibilities include developing, implementing and maintaining policies and procedures	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.2.1-6;
15		15	The responsibilities of this person include administrative control.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.2.1-7;
16		16	The responsibilities of this person include maintaining quality control programmes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.2.1-8;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
17		17	The responsibilities of this person include monitoring and reviewing all nuclear medicine services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.2.1-9;
18	A radiation safety programme is in place, followed and documented.	18	A radiation safety programme is in place and is appropriate to the risks and hazards encountered.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.1-1;
19		19	The programme is coordinated with the hospitals safety management programme.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.1-2;
20		20	Personal dosimeters worn by personnel comply with the ionising radiation regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.1-3;
21		21	Appropriate radiation safety devices are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.1-4;
22		22	Documented records of radioactive stocks, calculation and preparation, administration and disposal details are kept.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.1-5;
23		23	A register is kept of sealed sources.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.1-6;
24		24	Contamination monitors are provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.1-7;
25		25	Area monitors are available where necessary.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.1-8;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
26	There are documented policies and procedures to guide personnel in all aspects of the provision of nuclear medicine services.	26	Documented policies and procedures that address compliance with applicable standards, laws and regulations are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-1;
27		27	The associated medical physicist is involved in the formulation of policies and radiation safety procedures applicable to nuclear medicine.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-2;
28		28	Policies and procedures that satisfy statutory requirements under the ionising radiation regulations are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-3;
29		29	A copy of the local rules relating to current ionising radiation regulations is available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-4;
30		30	Policies and procedures that relate to limiting the irradiation of patients to levels consistent with medical requirements are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-5;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
31		31	A strict policy on the conditions under which pregnant women may be subjected to a nuclear medicine examination is available and implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-6;
32		32	There is a procedure to ensure professional handling of a radiation emergency situation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-7;
33		33	Policies and procedures that relate to avoiding radioactive contamination, and controlling spread should it occur, are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-8;
34		34	A documented procedure is available for personnel to follow in the event of contamination.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-9;
35		35	Policies relating to monitoring the hands, clothing and body of every member of personnel leaving a controlled area are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-10;
36		36	Policies and procedures are implemented for the reporting of adverse reactions to therapy.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-11;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
37		37	Policies and procedures are implemented for clinical trials, where applicable.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-12;
38		38	Policies and procedures that address the handling and disposal of infectious and hazardous materials are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-13;
39		39	Nuclear medicine personnel are oriented to safety procedures and practices.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-14;
40		40	Personnel receive education with regard to new procedures and newly-acquired or recognised hazardous materials.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.2-15;
41	All diagnostic equipment is regularly inspected and maintained and appropriate records are kept of those activities.	41	There is a nuclear medicine equipment management programme.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.3-1;
42		42	The programme includes selecting and acquiring equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.3-2;
43		43	The programme includes taking an inventory of equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.3-3;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
44		44	The programme includes inspecting and testing the equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.3-4;		
45		45	The programme includes maintaining the equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.3-5;		
46		46	The programme includes monitoring and follow-up of the equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.3-6;		
47		47	Radiation monitors are calibrated regularly.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.3-7;		
48		48	Values are recorded in a log-book.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.3-8;		
49		49	The programme is implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.3-9;		
50		50	There is adequate documentation of all testing, maintenance and calibration of equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.3-10;		
51	Facilities ensure the safe, efficient and effective functioning of the nuclear medicine service.	51	Facilities ensure that radiation to personnel is kept as low as possible.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.4-1;		
52		52	At every entrance to a room where radioactive material is handled, a radiation warning sign is displayed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.4-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
53		53	Requirements laid down by the Department of Health regarding a controlled area are complied with.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.4-3;		
54		54	A copy of the most recent radiation safety inspection report is held by the nuclear physician responsible for the department, or the medical physics department or the medical physicist.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.4-4;		
55		55	There is a shower available in the event of contamination.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.4-5;		
56		56	Separate toilets for personnel and patients are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.4-6;		
57		57	Signs warning of the dangers of radiation to pregnant and breast-feeding women are prominently displayed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.4-7;		
58	Radiopharmaceuticals intended for administration to patients are prepared in a manner which satisfies both radiation safety and pharmaceutical quality requirements.	58	Appropriate aseptic precautions are taken.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.5-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
59		59	Regular and frequent gamma camera quality control procedures (e.g. flood uniformities, centre-of-rotation) are attended to or supervised by the medical physicist.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.5-2;		
60		60	The radiopharmacy is designed to ensure that the history of each radiopharmaceutical dose can be traced.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.5-3;		
61		61	Radiopharmaceuticals are only dispensed on written request.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.5-4;		
62		62	All details of each Tc-99m generator are recorded, including full details of each elution.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.5-5;		
63		63	Facilities are available for the quality control of all kits reconstituted on the premises.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.5-6;		
64		64	There are separate facilities for the radiolabelling of blood products.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.5-7;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
65		65	Blood products are labelled in a workstation with filtered air (at least a vertical laminar flow unit of biohazard type) to protect the product and designed to protect the operator against contamination.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.5-8;		
66		66	All containers with radioactivity are labelled according to specifications stating that the contents are radioactive and indicating the activity and the date.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.5-9;		
67	The management of organ disease using open radionuclides is practised, taking into account the safety and well-being of patients and personnel as a consequence of the high radiation levels.	67	Where radioactive material administered to the patient exceeds a level of 370 MBq (10mCi), it is administered by the nuclear physician or radiation oncologist only.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.6-1;		
68		68	Where radioactive material administered to the patient exceeds a level of 370 MBq (10mCi), there is an en-suite ward approved by the medical physicist for the isolation of the patient.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.6-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
69		69	In the event that the approved ward is not available, any alternative ward for the isolation of the patient receiving therapy is also approved by the medical physicist.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.6-3;		
70		70	A radiation survey of the ward used for the isolation of the patient and adjacent areas is conducted according to the requirements of the physicist immediately after the administration of the radioactive material.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.6-4;		
71		71	The isolated patient is monitored regularly during the isolation period.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.6-5;		
72		72	On discharge of the patient who has been isolated, the ward, the bedding and the bathroom are monitored according to the requirements of the physicist.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.6-6;		
73		73	Orally administered radioiodine is always in capsule form.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.6-7;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
74		74	Radioiodine by injection is administered only by the nuclear physician or radiation oncologist.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.6-8;		
75		75	A fume hood is used if liquid radioiodine is being prepared and the personnel preparing the radioiodine are adequately protected.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.6-9;		
76		76	Administration of all radionuclides for therapy purposes is done in consultation with the physicist and according to statutory radiation safety norms.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.3.6-10;		
77	Individuals with adequate training, skills, orientation and experience administer tests and interpret the results.	77	Examinations are performed only upon a formal request from a medical practitioner.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.4.1-1;		
78		78	Nuclear medicine procedure requests contain all relevant clinical information.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.4.1-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
79		79	If relevant radionuclides are available, all examinations are performed as soon as possible. Urgent scans are performed and reported on the same day.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.4.1-3;		
80		80	Those individuals who perform testing and those who direct or supervise testing are identified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.4.1-4;		
81		81	Tests are interpreted by appropriately trained and experienced personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.4.1-5;		
82		82	Only a nuclear medicine physician or a registrar under supervision of a nuclear medicine physician or a radiologist may report on the results of nuclear medicine procedures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.4.1-6;		
83		83	An effective mechanism exists whereby emergency nuclear medicine procedure results are brought to the attention of the doctor who requested the examination.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.4.1-7;		
84		84	Nuclear medicine procedure results are handled in a professional and confidential manner.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.4.1-8;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
85		85	Reports are appropriately filed and distributed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.4.1-9;		
86		86	Mechanisms are in place to ensure the results of procedures can be retrieved when necessary.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.4.1-10;		

Table Number-24: Central Sterile Supply Department (CSSD):

The Central Sterile Supply Department Chapter has 5 Standards and 23 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	CSSD is managed to ensure the provision of a safe and effective service.	1	A designated individual is responsible for the sterilising and disinfecting service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.1.1-1;		
2		2	The manager ensures that policies and procedures, which include the standard intent as a minimum, are available to guide personnel in the service and that they are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.1.1-2;		
3		3	The manager plans and implements an effective organisational structure to support his/her responsibilities and authority.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.1.1-3;		
4		4	The responsibilities of the unit manager are defined in writing.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.1.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
5	The unit is designed to allow for effective decontamination and sterilisation of medical equipment and supplies.	5	The design of the sterilising and disinfecting unit and the layout of equipment ensure the flow of work from the soiled to the clean side of the unit.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.1-1;		
6		6	There is a washing and decontamination area, with clean running water and a sink connected to the sewage system.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.1-2;		
7		7	There is a pre-packing area with storage facilities for clean materials.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.1-3;		
8		8	The autoclave area is equipped with loading and unloading trolleys at the correct height.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.1-4;		
9		9	There is a storage area for sterile packs with racks which allow for an adequate circulation of air.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.1-5;		
10		10	Adequate light and ventilation are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.1-6;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
11	Effective sterilising equipment is available.	11	There are one or more autoclaves or their equivalent capable of sterilising porous loads (gowns, drapes and dressings), as well as wrapped and unwrapped instruments.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.2-1;
12		12	Autoclaves/sterilising units are appropriate to their use and comply with licensing requirements.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.2-2;
13		13	Where liquids are sterilised, an autoclave with a fluid cycle and a reverse osmosis or distillation plant are also provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.2-3;
14		14	Where ethylene oxide is used as a sterilising agent, the installation complies with relevant safety standards and legislation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.2-4;
15		15	The sterilising ability of each autoclave is tested daily and the results recorded in a log book.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.2-5;
16		16	The sterility of each pack is shown on indicator tapes, which are suited to the processes used.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.2-6;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
17		17	Any incidents of failure of sterilisation procedures are recorded and investigated.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.2-7;
18		18	Sterilising and disinfecting unit personnel ensure that all equipment is included in the hospital's equipment replacement and maintenance programme.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.2-8;
19	The sterility of equipment and supplies is maintained.	19	There is a mechanism to ensure that sterile supplies are dated and used on a “first expired first out” basis.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.3-1;
20		20	The maintenance of sterility is checked before any sterile packs are issued.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.3-2;
21		21	There is a system for the ordering, storage, maintenance and distribution of sterile supplies.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.2.3-3;
22	A formalised proactive quality improvement approach is maintained in the service.	22	Indicators of performance are identified to evaluate the quality of the service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.3.1-2;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
23		23	The quality improvement cycle includes the monitoring and evaluation of the standards set, and the remedial action implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27.3.1-3;		

Table Number-25: Dietary Services:

The Dietary Services Chapter has 15 Standards and 83 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	The linen management service is managed to ensure the provision of a safe and effective service.	1	A designated individual is responsible for the linen management service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.1.1-1;
2		2	The linen management service manager ensures that policies and procedures are available to guide personnel and that they are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.1.1-2;
3		3	The manager plans and implements an effective organisational structure to support his/her responsibilities and authority.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.1.1-3;
4		4	The responsibilities of the service manager are documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.1.1-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
5	Where there is a laundry on site, the department is designed to allow for safe and effective processing of linen.	5	The space in the laundry is adequate to deal with the calculated or estimated dry weight of articles to be processed and the type of washing equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-1;		
6		6	The laundry facilities comply with the statement.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-2;		
7		7	The laundry provides a clear flow of laundry from the soiled to the clean side with no crossover of these lines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-3;		
8		8	Trolleys, bins, vehicles or other equipment used for the transport of linen bags are designed to avoid damage to linen and to be cleaned easily.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-4;		
9		9	Clean overalls, aprons, gloves and footwear for on-site sorting of used linen are provided and correctly used.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-5;		
10		10	Adequate hand washing facilities are provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-6;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
11		11	Washing machines are fitted with water level gauges or dip gauges and the quantity of water is regularly checked.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-7;		
12		12	The size and number of washing machines are adequate to meet the number of loads per hour, including peak loads.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-8;		
13		13	Ironers/laundry presses are adequate to ensure the processing of laundry items without undue delays.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-9;		
14		14	The machine cage volume is specified by the manufacturer.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-10;		
15		15	Loads are regularly weighed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-11;		
16		16	Washing machines are fitted with thermometers, which are tested every 6 weeks and calibrated every year.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-12;		
17	Where there is no on-site laundry, the linen-bank facilities allow for efficient handling of linen.	17	The arrangement between the hospital and the off-site laundry clearly states the responsibility for sorting, counting, collection and delivery of linen.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.2-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
18		18	Where sorting takes place on site, there is a clear flow of linen from the soiled to the clean side with no crossover of these lines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.2-2;
19		19	Trolleys, bins, vehicles or other equipment used for the transport of linen bags are designed to avoid damage to linen and to be cleaned easily.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.2-3;
20		20	Clean overalls, aprons, gloves and footwear for on-site sorting of used linen are provided and correctly used.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.2-4;
21		21	Soiled linen sent to the off-site laundry is sorted into bags (or other acceptable containers) which clearly indicate the contents.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.2-5;
22	Linen stock control mechanisms are implemented.	22	Access to the laundry/linen-bank is controlled.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-1;
23		23	There is a method of accounting for the numbers of different linen items sent for laundering.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-2;
24		24	There is a process to verify the numbers and physical condition of linen items sent and received.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-3;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
25		25	A record is kept of linen issued.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-4;		
26		26	Secure storage facilities are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-5;		
27		27	There is an inventory of all linen stored.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-6;		
28		28	Records are audited.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-7;		
29		29	All losses are investigated, reported and recorded.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-8;		

Table Number-26: Linen Services:

The Linen Services Chapter has 4 Standards and 29 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
1	The linen management service is managed to ensure the provision of a safe and effective service.	1	A designated individual is responsible for the linen management service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.1.1-1;
2		2	The linen management service manager ensures that policies and procedures are available to guide personnel and that they are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.1.1-2;
3		3	The manager plans and implements an effective organisational structure to support his/her responsibilities and authority.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.1.1-3;
4		4	The responsibilities of the service manager are documented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.1.1-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
5	Where there is a laundry on site, the department is designed to allow for safe and effective processing of linen.	5	The space in the laundry is adequate to deal with the calculated or estimated dry weight of articles to be processed and the type of washing equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-1;		
6		6	The laundry facilities comply with the standard statement.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-2;		
7		7	The laundry provides a clear flow of laundry from the soiled to the clean side with no crossover of these lines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-3;		
8		8	Trolleys, bins, vehicles or other equipment used for the transport of linen bags are designed to avoid damage to linen and to be cleaned easily.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-4;		
9		9	Clean overalls, aprons, gloves and footwear for on-site sorting of used linen are provided and correctly used.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-5;		
10		10	Adequate hand washing facilities are provided.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-6;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
11		11	Washing machines are fitted with water level gauges or dip gauges and the quantity of water is regularly checked.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-7;		
12		12	The size and number of washing machines are adequate to meet the number of loads per hour, including peak loads.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-8;		
13		13	Ironers/laundry presses are adequate to ensure the processing of laundry items without undue delays.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-9;		
14		14	The machine cage volume is specified by the manufacturer.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-10;		
15		15	Loads are regularly weighed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-11;		
16		16	Washing machines are fitted with thermometers, which are tested every 6 weeks and calibrated every year.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.1-12;		
17	Where there is no on-site laundry, the linen-bank facilities allow for efficient handling of linen.	17	The arrangement between the hospital and the off-site laundry clearly states the responsibility for sorting, counting, collection and delivery of linen.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.2-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
18		18	Where sorting takes place on site, there is a clear flow of linen from the soiled to the clean side with no crossover of these lines.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.2-2;		
19		19	Trolleys, bins, vehicles or other equipment used for the transport of linen bags are designed to avoid damage to linen and to be cleaned easily.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.2-3;		
20		20	Clean overalls, aprons, gloves and footwear for on-site sorting of used linen are provided and correctly used.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.2-4;		
21		21	Soiled linen sent to the off-site laundry is sorted into bags (or other acceptable containers) which clearly indicate the contents.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.2-5;		
22	Linen stock control mechanisms are implemented.	22	Access to the laundry/linen-bank is controlled.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-1;		
23		23	There is a method of accounting for the numbers of different linen items sent for laundering.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-2;		
24		24	There is a process to verify the numbers and physical condition of linen items sent and received.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-3;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
25		25	A record is kept of linen issued.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-4;		
26		26	Secure storage facilities are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-5;		
27		27	There is an inventory of all linen stored.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-6;		
28		28	Records are audited.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-7;		
29		29	All losses are investigated, reported and recorded.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29.2.3-8;		

Table Number-27: Housekeeping:

The Housekeeping Chapter has 4 Standards and 29 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
1	The housekeeping service is managed to ensure the provision of a safe and effective service.	1	A designated individual is responsible for the housekeeping service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.1.1-1;		
2		2	The housekeeping service manager ensures that policies and procedures are available to guide personnel and that they are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.1.1-2;		
3		3	The manager plans and implements an effective organisational structure to support his/her responsibilities and authority.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.1.1-3;		
4		4	The responsibilities of the service manager are defined in writing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.1.1-4;		
5		5	Pest control measures are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.1.1-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
6	Facilities and equipment are adequate to provide a safe and effective cleaning service.	6	Secure storage areas and well-maintained equipment are available to housekeeping personnel.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.2.1-1;		
7		7	Chemicals for cleaning are safely stored out of the reach of patients, children and visitors.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.2.1-2;		
8		8	Chemicals for cleaning are securely and accurately labelled.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.2.1-3;		
9		9	There is adequate storage place for brooms and mops.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.2.1-4;		
10		10	Mops and brooms are cleaned and dried before being stored.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.2.1-5;		
11		11	Cleaning cupboards are adequately ventilated.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.2.1-6;		
12		12	Soiled linen is placed in bags designated for that purpose.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.2.1-7;		
13		13	Soiled linen is stored in a secure facility.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.2.1-8;		
14		14	There is a mechanism whereby the manager of the housekeeping service can communicate the current state of housekeeping-related facilities and equipment to central facility management.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.2.1-9;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
15		15	Personal protective equipment (PPE) is available to housekeeping personnel to protect them from infection and the potentially harmful effects of chemicals used in the course of their duties.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.2.1-10;		
16	The housekeeping personnel work with the infection control committee to ensure safe waste disposal.	16	Waste is segregated in accordance with documented controls.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.4.1-1;		
17		17	Housekeeping personnel use colour-coded charts (or other suitable coding) to identify the colour of bag and type of container appropriate to the type of waste generated.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.4.1-2;		
18		18	Waste is protected from theft, vandalism or scavenging by animals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.4.1-3;		
19		19	Waste is collected at appropriate times so that hazards are not caused.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.4.1-4;		

Table Number-28: Medical Physics:

The Medical Physics Chapter has 10 Standards and 67 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	A medical physics service is provided by the hospital, or is readily available through arrangements with outside sources, to meet the needs of its catchment population.	1	Adequate, convenient and regular medical physics services are available to meet needs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.1-1;
2		2	An emergency medical physics service is available after normal hours.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.1-2;
3		3	The selection of an outside source is based on an acceptable record and compliance with laws and regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.1-3;
4		4	Patients are informed about any relationships between the referring physician and an outside source of medical physics services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.1-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
5	A qualified individual is responsible for managing the medical physics service.	5	A medical physicist, who is qualified by education, training and experience, manages the medical physics service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.2-1;		
6		6	The responsibilities of this person include developing, implementing and maintaining relevant policies and procedures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.2-2;		
7		7	The responsibilities of this person include administrative control.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.2-3;		
8		8	The responsibilities of this person include maintaining quality control programmes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.2-4;		
9		9	The responsibilities of this person include recommending outside sources of medical physics services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.2-5;		
10		10	The responsibilities of this person include monitoring and reviewing all medical physics services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.2-6;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
11	Individuals with adequate training, skills and experience perform medical physics procedures and interpret the results.	11	Those individuals, who may perform medical physics procedures and those who may interpret and report the results are identified.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.3-1;		
12		12	A mechanism exists which ensures that procedures are performed only by qualified medical physicists, or specially trained doctors and other persons authorised to do so by a radiation protection advisor.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.3-2;		
13		13	Medical physics procedures are done only upon a signed request from a qualified medical practitioner.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.3-3;		
14		14	There is an adequate number of qualified medical physicists to provide the services within the scope of their profession.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.3-4;		
15		15	Experts in specialised medical physics areas are contacted when needed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.3-5;		
16		16	A roster of experts for specialised medical physics areas is maintained.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.3-6;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
17	Personnel are provided with documented policies and guidelines for all aspects of the provision of medical physics services.	17	All radiation workers are oriented to safety procedures and practices.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.4-1;		
18		18	Personnel receive education for new procedures and newly acquired or recognised hazardous materials and apparatus.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.4-2;		
19		19	Policies and procedures relating to limiting the irradiation of patients and personnel to levels consistent with clinical requirements are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.4-3;		
20		20	Policies and procedures relating to the terms under which pregnant women may be subjected to any radiation exposure are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.4-4;		
21		21	Policies and procedures relating to avoiding radioactive contamination and controlling spread should it occur are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.4-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
22		22	Policies and procedures relating to procedures to be followed in the event of contamination, radiation emergency and overexposure are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.4-6;
23		23	Policies and procedures relating to monitoring the hands, clothing and body of every member of personnel leaving a controlled area are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.4-7;
24		24	Policies and procedures relating to all trials, clinical or other, involving ionising radiations are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.4-8;
25		25	Policies and procedures addressing the handling and disposal of infectious and hazardous materials are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.1.4-9;
26	Individuals with adequate training, skills, orientation and experience administer all tests and treatments.	26	Diagnostic and therapeutic procedures utilising radiation and/or radiation treatments are planned and performed only upon a formal written prescription from a qualified physician.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.2.1-1;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
27		27	A radiation oncologist or nuclear medicine physician, or a registrar under the supervision of such a physician, prescribes and monitors the treatment of the patient.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.2.1-2;
28		28	An effective mechanism exists whereby emergency medical physics services are initiated promptly.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.2.1-3;
29		29	Documents are appropriately filed and/or distributed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.2.1-4;
30		30	Mechanisms exist whereby records of procedures can be retrieved when necessary.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.2.1-5;
31	A radiation safety programme is in place, is implemented and is documented.	31	A qualified medical radiation physicist is available to fulfil the legal requirements of the regulations for the safe use of ionising radiation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.1-1;
32		32	A copy of the local rules relating to current ionising radiation regulations is available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.1-2;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
33		33	A radiation safety programme is in place and is appropriate to the risks and possible hazards encountered.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.1-3;		
34		34	The programme is coordinated with the hospitals risk management programme.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.1-4;		
35		35	Personal dosimeters worn by personnel comply with the ionising radiation regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.1-5;		
36		36	Appropriate radiation safety devices are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.1-6;		
37		37	Written records of radioactive stocks, calculation and preparation, administration and disposal details are kept.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.1-7;		
38		38	A register of sealed sources is kept.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.1-8;		
39		39	Facilities are available for testing the integrity of all sealed sources.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.1-9;		
40		40	Contamination monitors and safety mechanisms are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.1-10;		
41		41	Area monitors are available where necessary.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.1-11;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
42	All medical physics related equipment is regularly inspected and maintained and appropriate records are kept of these activities.	42	The medical physicist is a member of the hospitals Healthcare Technology Advisory Committee.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.2-1;		
43		43	Policies and procedures relating to medical physics equipment safety and management complying with current applicable legislation and standards are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.2-2;		
44		44	There is a medical physics equipment management programme.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.2-3;		
45		45	The programme includes selecting and maintaining the equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.2-4;		
46		46	The programme includes taking an inventory of equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.2-5;		
47		47	The programme includes the inspecting, testing, quality control and continuous monitoring of equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.2-6;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
48		48	The programme ensures that all equipment used complies with the requirements of the regulations of the Radiation Authorities including regular and recorded calibration of all radiation monitoring equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.2-7;
49	Facilities ensure the safe, efficient and effective functioning of the medical physics service.	49	Facilities ensure that radiation to all personnel is kept as low as possible.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.3-1;
50		50	Signs warning of the dangers of radiation are prominently displayed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.3-2;
51		51	Requirements laid down by the Department of Health or other authority regarding controlled and supervised areas are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.3-3;
52		52	A copy of the most recent radiation safety inspection report(s) is available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.3-4;
53		53	There is a shower available in the event of contamination.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.3-5;
54		54	Separate toilets for personnel and patients are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.3-6;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
55	Radioactive materials (open and sealed sources) intended for administration to, or implantation into, patients are prepared in a manner which satisfies both radiation safety and pharmaceutical quality requirements.	55	Appropriate aseptic precautions are taken for each application.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.4-1;
56		56	The radio-pharmacy is designed to ensure the history of each radio-pharmaceutical dose can be traced.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.4-2;
57		57	Radio-pharmaceuticals and radioactive implants are only dispensed or prepared on the written request of a qualified medical practitioner.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.4-3;
58		58	Each preparation of sealed sources is recorded with the dose plan, calculations and all relevant details.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.4-4;
59		59	All containers with radioactivity are labelled according to specifications, stating that the contents are radioactive and indicating the radio-nuclide, the activity and	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.4-5;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			the date.												
60	The management and treatment of organ disease using radio-nuclides is practised taking into account the safety and well-being of patients and personnel as a consequence of the high radiation levels.	60	The administration of all radio-nuclides for therapy purposes is done by a qualified nuclear medicine physician or radiation oncologist in consultation with a medical physicist and according to statutory radiation safety norms.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
61		61	Where the quantity of radioactive material administered to the patient equals or exceeds 370MBq (10mCi), there is an en-suite ward approved by a medical physicist for the isolation of the patient.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
62		62	In the event that the approved ward is not available, any alternative ward for the isolation of patients is also approved by a medical physicist.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
63		63	A radiation survey of the ward used for the isolation of the patient and adjacent areas is conducted according to the requirements of the medical physicist immediately after the administration of the radioactive material.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.5-4;		
64		64	The isolated patient is monitored regularly during the isolation period and the exposure values are recorded.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.5-5;		
65		65	On discharge of the patient who has been isolated, the ward, the bedding and the bathroom and toilet are monitored according to the requirements of the medical physicist.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.5-6;		
66		66	Orally administered radio-iodine is always in capsule form.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.5-7;		
67		67	A fume hood is used if liquid radio-iodine is being prepared and personnel preparing the radio-iodine are adequately protected.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.3.5-8;		

Table Number-29: Radiation Oncology:

The Radiation Oncology Chapter has 9 Standards and 75 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	A radiation oncology service is provided by the hospital, or is readily available through arrangements with outside sources, to meet the needs of its patient population.	1	Adequate, convenient and regular radiation oncology services are available to meet needs.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.1-1;
2		2	An emergency radiation oncology service is available after normal hours.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.1-2;
3		3	The selection of an outside source is based on an acceptable record of accurate, timely service and compliance with laws and regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.1-3;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
4		4	Patients are informed about any relationships between the referring physician and outside sources of services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.1-4;
5	A qualified individual is responsible for managing the Radiation Oncology Service.	5	A radiation oncologist, who is qualified by education, training and experience, manages the service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.2-1;
6		6	The responsibilities of this person include developing, implementing and maintaining relevant policies and procedures.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.2-2;
7		7	The responsibilities of this person include administrative control.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.2-3;
8		8	The responsibilities of this person include maintaining quality control programmes.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.2-4;
9		9	The responsibilities of this person include recommending outside sources of radiation oncology services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.2-5;
10		10	The responsibilities of this person include monitoring and reviewing all radiation oncology services.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.2-6;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
11		11	There are qualified radiation therapists (radiographers) to provide services in keeping with the scope of their profession.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.2-7;		
12		12	A qualified medical radiation physicist is available to fulfil the legal requirements of the regulations for the safe use of ionising radiation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.2-8;		
13		13	The service(s) of a legally qualified person(s) is/are available for open and sealed source preparation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.2-9;		
14	Personnel are provided with documented policies and guidelines for all aspects of the provision of radiation oncology services.	14	Radiation oncology personnel are orientated to safety procedures and practices.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.3-1;		
15		15	Personnel receive education for new procedures and newly-acquired or recognised hazardous materials and apparatus.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.3-2;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
16		16	The associated medical physicist is involved in the formulation of policies and radiation safety procedures applicable to radiation oncology medicine.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.3-3;
17		17	Policies and procedures relating to limiting the irradiation of patients and personnel to levels consistent with clinical requirements are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.3-4;
18		18	Policies and procedures relating to the conditions under which pregnant women may be subjected to any radiation exposure are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.3-5;
19		19	Policies and procedures relating to avoiding radioactive contamination and controlling spread should it occur are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.3-6;
20		20	Policies and procedures relating to procedures to be followed in the event of contamination, radiation emergency and overexposure are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.3-7;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
21		21	Policies and procedures relating to monitoring the hands, clothing and body of every member of personnel leaving a controlled area are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.3-8;
22		22	Policies and procedures relating to all trials, clinical or other, involving ionising radiations are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.3-9;
23		23	Policies and procedures addressing the handling and disposal of infectious and hazardous materials are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.3-10;
24		24	Policies and procedures relating to the reporting of adverse reactions to therapy are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.1.3-11;
25	Individuals with adequate training, skills, orientation and experience administer all tests and treatments.	25	Diagnostic and therapeutic procedures utilising radiation and/or radiation treatments are planned and performed only upon a formal written prescription from a qualified physician.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.2.1-1;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
26		26	A radiation oncologist or nuclear medicine physician or a registrar under the supervision of such a physician prescribes and monitors the treatment of the patient.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.2.1-2;
27		27	Radiation oncology prescriptions contain relevant clinical information.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.2.1-3;
28		28	If all relevant treatment modalities are available, all treatments are initiated as soon as possible.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.2.1-4;
29		29	An effective mechanism exists whereby emergency radiation oncology services are initiated promptly.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.2.1-5;
30		30	Documents are appropriately filed and distributed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.2.1-6;
31		31	Mechanisms exist whereby records of procedures can be retrieved when necessary.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.2.1-7;
32	A radiation safety programme is in place, is implemented and documented.	32	A qualified medical radiation physicist is available to fulfil the legal requirements of the regulations for the safe use of ionising radiation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.1-1;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
33		33	A copy of the local rules relating to current ionising radiation regulations is available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.1-2;		
34		34	A radiation safety programme is in place and is appropriate to the risks and possible hazards encountered.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.1-3;		
35		35	The programme is coordinated with the hospitals risk management programme.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.1-4;		
36		36	Personal dosimeters worn by personnel comply with the ionising radiation regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.1-5;		
37		37	Appropriate radiation safety devices are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.1-6;		
38		38	Documented records of radioactive stocks, calculation and preparation, administration and disposal details are maintained.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.1-7;		
39		39	A register of sealed sources is maintained.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.1-8;		
40		40	Facilities for testing the integrity of all sealed sources are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.1-9;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA						
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M				
41		41	Contamination monitors and safety mechanisms are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.1-10;			
42		42	Area monitors are available where necessary.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.1-11;			
43	Facilities ensure the safe, efficient and effective functioning of the Radiation Oncology Service.	43	Facilities ensure that radiation to all personnel is kept as low as possible.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.2-1;			
44		44	Signs warning of the dangers of radiation are prominently displayed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.2-2;			
45		45	Requirements regarding controlled and supervised areas laid down by the Department of Health or other authority are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.2-3;		
46		46	A copy of the most recent radiation safety inspection report(s) of department(s) serviced by the radiation oncology department is/(are) held by the person responsible for the department, the Radiation Oncology Department, or the medical physicist.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.2-4;		
47		47	There is a shower available in the event of contamination.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.2-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
48		48	Separate toilets for personnel and patients are available.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.2-6;		
49	All therapy-related equipment is regularly inspected and maintained and appropriate records are kept of these activities.	49	Policies and procedures relating to radiation oncology equipment safety and management complying with current applicable legislation and standards are implemented.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.3-1;		
50		50	There is a medical equipment management programme which includes selecting and maintaining the equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.3-2;		
51		51	The programme includes taking an inventory of equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.3-3;		
52		52	The programme includes the inspecting, testing, quality control and continuous monitoring of equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.3-4;		
53		53	The programme ensures that all equipment used complies with the regulations and requirements of the Radiation Authorities including regular and recorded calibration of all radiation monitoring equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.3-5;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
54		54	Radiation monitors are calibrated regularly.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.3-6;		
55		55	Values are recorded in a log book.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.3-7;		
56		56	There is documentation of all testing, maintenance and calibration of equipment.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.3-8;		
57		57	All linear accelerators are calibrated and subjected to a constancy output on a regular and frequent basis.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.3-9;		
58		58	All equipment is checked on a daily basis.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.3-10;		
59		59	The accuracy of the computer control of all 'After Loading High Dose Rate' units is checked at regular intervals and the results recorded.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.3-11;		
60	Radioactive materials (open and sealed sources) intended for administration to, or implantation into, patients are prepared in a manner which satisfies both radiation safety and pharmaceutical quality requirements.	60	Appropriate aseptic precautions are implemented for each application.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.4-1;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
61		61	The radio-pharmacy is designed to ensure the history of each radio-pharmaceutical dose can be traced.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.4-2;
62		62	Radio-pharmaceuticals and radioactive implants are only dispensed or prepared on the written request of a qualified medical practitioner.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.4-3;
63		63	Each preparation of sealed sources is recorded with the dose plan, calculations and all relevant details.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.4-4;
64		64	All containers with radioactivity are labelled according to specifications, stating that the contents are radioactive and indicating the radio-nuclide, the activity and the date.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.4-5;
65	The management of organ disease using radionuclides is practised taking into account the safety and well-being of patients and personnel as a consequence of the high radiation levels.	65	The administration of all radionuclides for therapy purposes is done by a qualified nuclear medicine physician or radiation oncologist in consultation with a medical physicist and according to statutory radiation safety norms.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.5-1;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
66		66	Where radioactive material administered to the patient equals or exceeds a level of 370MBq (10mCi), it is administered by the radiation oncologist only.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.5-2;
67		67	Where radioactive material administered to the patient equals or exceeds a level of 370MBq (10mCi), there is an en-suite ward approved by the medical physicist for isolation of the patient.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.5-3;
68		68	In the event that the approved ward is not available, any alternative ward for isolation of the patient is also approved by the medical physicist.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.5-4;
69		69	A radiation survey of the ward used for isolation of the patient and adjacent areas is conducted according to the requirements of the physicist immediately after administration of the radioactive material.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.5-5;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
70		70	The isolated patient is monitored regularly during the isolation period and exposure values are recorded.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.5-6;
71		71	On discharge of the patient who has been isolated, the ward, the bedding and the bathroom are monitored according to the requirements of the physicist.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.5-7;
72		72	Orally administered radio-iodine 10mCi and above is always in capsule form.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.5-8;
73		73	Open source nuclides by injection are administered only by the radiation oncologist.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.5-9;
74		74	A fume hood is used if liquid radio-iodine is being prepared and the personnel preparing the radio-iodine are adequately protected.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.5-10;
75		75	Administration of all radionuclides for therapy purposes is done in consultation with the physicist and according to statutory radiation safety norms.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34.3.5-11;

Table Number-30: Occupational Health:

The Occupational Health Chapter has 9 Standards and 55 Measurable Elements. In the below table, each measurable elements are compared with NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa respectively. The comparison is done by using the terminology used in the national and international healthcare accreditations such as FM= Fully Met, PM=Partially Met and NM=Not Met. The number zero “0” is used to show the non compliance and to show the compliance of relevant Standards (NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA), Standard Number and Measurable Numbers are mentioned in the columns against each measurable elements.

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
1	The Occupational Health Service is managed to provide the personnel and resources required for an effective service.	1	A designated person is responsible and accountable for the management of the Occupational Health Service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.3.1-1;
2		2	There is an adequate number of personnel to provide for the needs of the Occupational Health Service.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.3.1-2;
3		3	Occupational health personnel have the necessary and appropriate training, credentials and skills to carry out their responsibilities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.3.1-3;
4		4	Occupational health personnel participate in continuing medical education in occupational health.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.3.1-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
5		5	Occupational health personnel have appropriate access to a physician with expertise and credentials in occupational health care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.3.1-5;
6	The mission statement and overall policy of the Occupational Health Service reflect current international best practice.	6	The Occupational Health Service has an overall policy that contains as a minimum a mission statement.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.3.2-1;
7		7	The policy is authorised by senior management.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.3.2-2;
8		8	The policy is clearly displayed within the department, communicated to all employees and available to all interested parties.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.3.2-3;
9		9	The policy is reviewed at appropriate intervals as determined by the department, but at least every three years.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.3.2-4;
10		10	The services to be offered are consistent with the mission of the department.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.3.2-5;
11		11	The services to be provided are described in the strategic plans of the department.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.3.2-6;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
12	Where students are trained as part of undergraduate or postgraduate programmes, the Occupational Health Service ensures formal training.	12	There is a designated member of the personnel of the Occupational Health Service who coordinates student training.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.3.3-1;
13		13	The training programme is structured in accordance with the guidelines of the appropriate registration body and training facilities.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.3.3-2;
14		14	Training periods are recorded and evaluated.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.3.3-3;
15	The functions of the occupational health practitioners are provided in accordance with ethical and professional practices and legal requirements	15	Occupational Health Services are provided in accordance with relevant standards promulgated by local, provincial and national guidelines, laws and regulations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.1-1;
16		16	Copies of relevant laws and regulations are available and readily accessible.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.1-2;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
17		17	Legislation is reviewed regularly at a frequency determined by the hospital but at least every three years and the reference records updated accordingly.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.1-3;
18		18	When outdated legislation is retained for future reference or research purposes, it is clearly marked as outdated, removed from the current reference documentation and stored in such a way as to guard against unintended use.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.1-4;
19	The hospital provides appropriate medical care to the employees of the hospital and/or organisation.	19	Occupational Health Service personnel are informed of the potential workplace hazards for each employee.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.2-1;
20		20	Occupational Health Service personnel have ready access to appropriate reference materials regarding occupational health care.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.2-2;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
21		21	Where routine medical care is offered to employees by the Occupational Health Service, medical complaints by employees are differentiated in terms of workplace-related complaints and other medical conditions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.2-3;
22		22	The management of medical conditions includes consideration of the relationship of the employee and the medical condition to the workplace environment and work practices.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.2-4;
23		23	The management of medical complaints includes consideration of the employee's fitness to continue present work practices.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.2-5;
24		24	The management of medical complaints includes consideration of any disability that may have been sustained.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.2-6;
25		25	The management of an acute injury includes measures to minimise disability and return the employee to an optimal functional state as soon as	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.2-7;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			possible.												
26		26	Employees are screened for mental health issues that may arise from working conditions, illness or disability and are managed appropriately.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
27		27	Records reflect both screening for and management of mental health issues.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28	Details of the hospital's and/or organisation's absenteeism and sickness rates are recorded and analysed to allow for informed decision making by the senior management team.	28	Employees who are absent from work are evaluated to ensure that they have regained sufficient health to be returned to their particular work place.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29		29	Such evaluation includes, but is not limited to, the extent and duration of the condition that caused the absence from work.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30		30	Such evaluation includes, but is not limited to, the extent and duration of potential hazards that may affect the employee's health.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA			
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	
31		31	Analysis of employee absenteeism and sickness provides data for risk management planning, for example analysis of back injuries causing employee sickness and absenteeism.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.3-4;
32	The Occupational Health Service has an appropriate medical surveillance programme, which meets the needs of the population served.	32	The health surveillance programme is appropriate for the health risks to which employees are exposed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.4-1;
33		33	The data collection process is designed to provide information that can be used in determining measures to eliminate, control and minimise the health risks to which employees are exposed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.4-2;
34		34	There is an effective employee recall system to ensure that employees are seen at appropriate intervals.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.4-3;
35		35	Personnel responsible for the development and implementation of the health surveillance programme are appropriately trained and	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.4-4;

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			updated.												
36		36	Records of each employee under surveillance are appropriately stored and managed in accordance with hospital policy relating to management of information and appropriate legislation.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
37		37	Records are available to the employee upon request.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
38		38	Employees are aware of their right to access their records relating to the health surveillance programme.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
39		39	Pre-employment examinations are conducted that consider the health of the individual and the requirements of the prospective workplace.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
40		40	Pre-termination examinations are conducted when employees leave the employ of the hospital and/or organisation to provide accurate information on their state of health on departure.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA					
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M			
41		41	Lifestyle habits (weight, diet, exercise, alcohol and/or tobacco use, etc.) are assessed when potential exposure to hazardous agents may be affected by those habits.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.4.4-10;		
42	The Occupational Health Service builds capacity in the workplace through the provision of information, education and counselling services.	42	The Occupational Health Service works with the personnel of other health services, non-governmental organisations and local governmental structures to provide health education and build capacity within the workforce.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.5.1-1;		
43		43	Posters are displayed in relevant areas within the hospital.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.5.1-2;		
44		44	HIV counselling and screening services are offered with due regard for confidentiality.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.5.1-3;		
45		45	Information provided is appropriate for the language/s and comprehension of the population served.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.5.1-4;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA				
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M		
46	There is a system to ensure that reports and records are efficiently managed with due regard for confidentiality.	46	There is documented evidence that occupational health practitioners write reports on occupational health-related issues.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.7.1-1;		
47		47	There is documented evidence that occupational health practitioners write letters and serve notices to remedy occupational health problems.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.7.1-2;		
48		48	There is documented evidence that occupational health practitioners record and file health-related statistics and evaluate trends.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.7.1-3;		
49		49	There is documented evidence that occupational health practitioners complete questionnaires from an occupational health perspective.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.7.1-4;		
50		50	There is documented evidence that occupational health practitioners provide reports and comments on inspections, complaints, investigations.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.7.1-5;		
51		51	There is documented evidence that occupational health practitioners compile	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.7.1-6;		

Sr. No.	Standards	Sr. No.	Measurable Elements (ME's)	NABH			NSQHS			DDKM			COHSASA		
				FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M	FM	P M	N M
			occupational health report forms.												
52		52	There is documented evidence that occupational health practitioners utilise standard or prescribed occupational health report forms or recording systems in respect of inspections, investigations and work of a recurring nature, e.g. notifiable medical conditions.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.7.1-7;		
53		53	Personal information about an employee that is unrelated to the ability to perform the specified job safely is handled in a confidential manner.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.7.1-8;		
54		54	Signed consent is obtained from employees prior to the release of any employee-related information.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.7.1-9;		
55		55	Current versions of relevant documents and information are available at all locations where operations essential to the effective functions of the Occupational Health Service are performed.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21.7.2-1;		

Hypothesis Testing:

Table Number- 31: Comparison between before and after mapping, filtration and merging of Chapters, Standards and Measurable Elements in NABH, DDKM, NSQHS and COHSASA standards for hospitals.

Before and After	Number of Chapters	Number of Standards	Number of Measurable Elements
Before Filtration	79	776	4778
After Filtration	24	466	2678
Decrease in percentage	30.37%	60.05%	56.04%

Table Number 31 is the comparison of NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards and Measurable Elements before and after mapping, filtration and merging. It is evident that after merging-filtration the percentages are decreased by 30.37% in number of chapters, 60.05% in number of Standards and 56.04% in number of Measurable Elements. It also depicts that 69.63% chapters were duplicated, 39.95% of the standards were duplicated and 43.96% of the Measurable Elements were duplicated.

Figure 2: Comparison between before and after filtration of Chapters, Standards and Measurable Elements in NABH, DDKM, NSQHS and COHSASA standards for hospitals.

Figure number 2 depicts that there is 30.37% decrease in number of chapters, 60.05% decrease in number of standards and 56.04% decrease in measurable elements after the filtration of Chapters, Standards and Measurable Elements in NABH, DDKM, NSQHS and COHSASA standards for hospitals.

Hypothesis Number-1:

H1₀: There is a decrease in the number of Chapters, Standards and Measurable Elements after mapping, filtration and merging of Standards and Measurable Elements in NABH, DDKM, NSQHS and COHSASA standards for hospitals.

H1₁: There is no decrease in the number of Chapters, Standards and Measurable Elements after mapping, filtration and merging of Standards and Measurable Elements in NABH, DDKM, NSQHS and COHSASA standards for hospitals.

Hypothesis Number-1 Result:

H1₀ hypothesis was accepted, which means there is a decrease in the number of Chapters, Standards and Measurable Elements after mapping, filtration and merging of Standards and Measurable Elements in NABH, DDKM, NSQHS and COHSASA standards for hospitals.

Table Number -32: Comparison of Fully Met (FM) and Not Met (NM) Measurable Elements in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards

Sr. No.	Chapters / Standards	NABH (India)		NSQHS (Australia)		DDKM (Denmark)		COHSASA (South Africa)	
		FM	NM	FM	NM	FM	NM	FM	NM
1	Facility Management and Safety (FMS)	56	269	5	320	50	275	222	103
2	Access to Care and Continuity of Care (ACC)	34	79	4	109	36	77	52	61
3	Emergency Department (ED)	24	31	0	55	0	55	33	22
4	Management of Information (MOI)	45	58	3	100	32	71	44	59
5	Patient and Family Rights (PFR)	56	67	10	113	31	92	49	74
6	Patient and Family Education (PFE)	6	32	10	28	14	24	14	24
7	Laboratory (LAB)	28	104	10	122	17	115	81	51
8	Radiology (RAD)	24	81	0	105	20	85	61	44
9	Human Resource (HR)	61	67	1	127	23	105	63	65
10	Pharmacy	77	90	14	153	38	129	68	99
11	Prevention and Control of Infection (PCI)	54	88	15	127	35	107	84	58
12	Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI)	63	129	21	171	43	149	110	82
13	Governance Leadership and Direction (GLD)	35	127	15	147	25	137	96	66
14	Care of Patients (COP)	94	150	33	211	53	191	86	158
15	Anesthesia and Surgical Care (ASC)	18	84	0	102	33	69	65	37
16	Assessment of Patient (AOP)	15	95	7	103	44	66	43	67
17	Nuclear Medicine	0	86	0	86	0	86	86	0
18	Central Sterile Supply Department (CSSD)	0	23	0	23	0	23	23	0
19	Dietary Services	6	77	2	81	8	75	73	10
20	Linen Services	0	29	0	29	0	29	29	0
21	Housekeeping Services	0	19	0	19	0	19	19	0

Sr. No.	Chapters / Standards	NABH (India)		NSQHS (Australia)		DDKM (Denmark)		COHSASA (South Africa)	
		FM	NM	FM	NM	FM	NM	FM	NM
22	Medical Physics	0	67	0	67	0	67	67	0
23	Radiation Oncology	0	75	0	75	0	75	75	0
24	Occupation Health	0	55	0	55	0	55	55	0

As identified by the ANOVA, FM, $F(3, 95) = 21.69$ and NM, $F(3, 95) = 5.24$ differed between countries. Considering the FM or the fully met standards, COHSASA had significantly higher FM compared with NABH ($MD = 37.58, p < .05$) NSQHS ($MD = 60.33, p < .05$) and DDKM ($MD = 45.67, p < .05$). NABH had significantly higher FM compared to NSQHS ($MD = 22.75, p < .05$). NABH (India) and DDKM (Denmark) had statistically equal level of FM ($MD = 8.08, p > .05$). Considering the NM, NSQHS (Australia) had significantly higher NM compared to COHSASA ($MD = 60.33, p < .05$). Further, NSQHS (Australia), DDKM (Denmark) and NABH (India) had statistically equal level of NM. *See Appendix 1 to confirm the results.*

Table-33-ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
FM	Between Groups	47616.458	3	15872.153	21.690	.000
	Within Groups	67322.167	92	731.763		
	Total	114938.625	95			
NM	Between Groups	47616.458	3	15872.153	5.244	.002
	Within Groups	278448.500	92	3026.614		
	Total	326064.958	95			

Figure3-: Mean plot of Fully Met (FM) and Not Met (NM) Measurable Elements in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards

Hypothesis Number-2:

H₂₀: The national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa are the same.

H₂₁: The national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa are not the same.

Hypothesis Number-2 Result:

H₂₁ hypothesis was accepted and it means that the national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa are not the same.

Hypothesis Number-3:

H₃₀: The NABH Standards for Hospitals of India are the best amongst the selected countries' Healthcare Standards for Hospitals.

H₃₁: The NABH Standards for Hospitals of India are not the best amongst the selected countries' Healthcare Standards for Hospitals.

Hypothesis Number-3 Result:

H₃₁ was accepted, it means that the NABH Standards for Hospitals of India are not the best amongst the selected countries' Healthcare Standards for Hospitals.

Table-34- Common Measurable Elements in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA standards for hospitals

Sr. No.	Chapters and Standards	NABH (India)	NSQHS (Australia)	DDKM(Denmark)	COHSASA (South Africa)
1	Facility Management and Safety (FMS)	8	0	12	4
2	Access to Care and Continuity of Care (ACC)	8	0	12	4
3	Emergency Department (ED)	2	0	0	2
4	Management of Information (MOI)	11	2	21	8
5	Patient and Family Rights (PFR)	18	1	16	10
6	Patient and Family Education (PFE)	5	5	8	0
7	Laboratory (LAB)	5	0	5	0
8	Radiology (RAD)	0	0	0	0
9	Human Resource (HR)	12	1	13	11
10	Pharmacy	16	1	22	8
11	Prevention and Control of Infection (PCI)	22	7	23	30
12	Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI)	22	10	40	17
13	Governance Leadership and Direction (GLD)	3	0	6	9
14	Care of Patients (COP)	17	3	15	8
15	Anesthesia and Surgical Care (ASC)	11	0	14	3
16	Assessment of Patient (AOP)	0	0	0	0
17	Nuclear Medicine	0	0	0	0
18	Central Sterile Supply Department (CSSD)	0	0	0	0
19	Dietary Services	4	1	6	1
20	Linen Services	0	0	0	0
21	Housekeeping Services	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Chapters and Standards	NABH (India)	NSQHS (Australia)	DDKM(Denmark)	COHSASA (South Africa)
22	Medical Physics	0	0	0	0
23	Radiation Oncology	0	0	0	0
24	Occupation Health	0	0	0	0

As identified from the ANOVA, NABH (India) had a higher Common Measurable Elements compared to NSQHS (Australia) (MD = 5.54, $p < .05$). DDKM (Denmark) had significantly higher Common Measurable Elements compared to NSQHS (Australia) (MD = 2.04, $p < .05$). NABH, DDKM and COHSASA were statistically equal in Common Measurable Elements. *See multiple comparison table in appendix 2 for more details.*

Table- 35:ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	F	<i>Sig.</i>
Between Groups	752.865	3	250.955	4.530	.005
Within Groups	5096.875	92	55.401		
Total	5849.740	95			

Figure-4: Mean plot of Common Measurable Elements in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA standards for hospitals

Hypothesis Number-4:

H₄₀: The highest numbers of common Measurable Elements are not in COHSASA standards.

H₄₁: The highest numbers of common Measurable Elements are in COHSASA Standards.

Hypothesis Number-4 Result:

H₄₀ was accepted, which means the highest numbers of common measurable elements are not in COHSASA standards.

Table-36- Repeated Measurable Elements in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards

Sr. No.	Chapters and Standards	NABH (India)	NSQHS (Australia)	DDKM (Denmark)	COHSASA (South Africa)
1	Facility Management and Safety (FMS)	2	0	7	21
2	Access to Care and Continuity of Care (ACC)	0	0	7	35
3	Emergency Department (ED)	0	0	0	23
4	Management of Information (MOI)	0	0	4	5
5	Patient and Family Rights (PFR)	0	1	1	9
6	Patient and Family Education (PFE)	0	0	4	4
7	Laboratory (LAB)	0	0	2	8
8	Radiology (RAD)	0	0	0	8
9	Human Resource (HR)	0	0	6	0
10	Pharmacy	0	0	3	22
11	Prevention and Control of Infection (PCI)	0	1	3	19
12	Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI)	0	2	15	20
13	Governance Leadership and Direction (GLD)	0	0	3	1
14	Care of Patients (COP)	0	0	5	36
15	Anesthesia and Surgical Care (ASC)	0	0	0	14
16	Assessment of Patient (AOP)	0	0	0	28
17	Nuclear Medicine	0	0	0	0
18	Central Sterile Supply Department (CSSD)	0	0	0	0
19	Dietary Services	0	0	1	8
20	Linen Services	0	0	0	0
21	Housekeeping Services	0	0	0	0

Sr. No.	Chapters and Standards	NABH (India)	NSQHS (Australia)	DDKM (Denmark)	COHSASA (South Africa)
22	Medical Physics	0	0	0	0
23	Radiation Oncology	0	0	0	0
24	Occupation Health	0	0	0	0

ANOVA indicated that COHSASA has significantly higher repeated measurable elements compared to other three, COHSASA vs. NABH (MD = 10.79, $p < .05$), COHSASA vs NSCHS (MD = 10.71, $p < .05$), COHSASA vs DDKM (MD = 8.33, $p < .05$). NSCHS, NABH and DDKM had statistically equal level of repeated measurable elements. *See appendix 3 for more details.*

Table-37 -ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	F	<i>Sig.</i>
Between Groups	1873.583	3	624.528	16.436	.000
Within Groups	3495.750	92	37.997		
Total	5369.333	95			

Figure-5: Mean plot of Repeated Measurable Elements in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards

Hypothesis Number-5:

H5₀: The highest numbers of repeated Measurable Elements are not in COHSASA standards.

H5₁: The highest numbers of repeated Measurable Elements are in COHSASA Standards.

Hypothesis Number-5 Result:

H5₁ was accepted, which means the highest number of repeated measurable elements are in COHSASA standards.

Table-38- Common Chapter (based on the score -Fully Met) in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards

Sr. No.	Chapters / Standards	NABH (India)	NSQHS (Australia)	DDKM (Denmark)	COHSASA (South Africa)
1	Facility Management and Safety (FMS)	56	5	50	222
2	Access to Care and Continuity of Care (ACC)	34	4	36	52
3	Management of Information (MOI)	45	3	32	44
4	Patient and Family Rights (PFR)	56	10	31	49
5	Patient and Family Education (PFE)	6	10	14	14
6	Laboratory (LAB)	28	10	17	81
7	Human Resource (HR)	61	1	23	63
8	Pharmacy	77	14	38	68
9	Prevention and Control of Infection (PCI)	54	15	35	84
10	Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI)	63	21	43	110
11	Governance Leadership and Direction (GLD)	35	15	25	96
12	Care of Patients (COP)	94	33	53	86
13	Assessment of Patient (AOP)	15	7	44	43
14	Dietary Services	6	2	8	73

The table number 38 depicts that there are 14 chapters (58%) out of 24 chapters which are common in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards based on the score -Fully Met as described in the above table. It is very evident from the above table that all 14 chapters have fully met measurable elements. Hence, these 14 chapters are common in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards for Hospitals.

Table-39- Uncommon Chapter (based on the score -Fully Met) in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards

Sr. No.	Chapters / Standards	NABH (India)	NSQHS (Australia)	DDKM (Denmark)	COHSASA (South Africa)
1	Nuclear Medicine	0	0	0	86
2	Central Sterile Supply Department (CSSD)	0	0	0	23
3	Linen Services	0	0	0	29
4	Housekeeping Services	0	0	0	19
5	Medical Physics	0	0	0	67
6	Radiation Oncology	0	0	0	75
7	Occupation Health	0	0	0	55
8	Emergency Department (ED)	24	0	0	33
9	Radiology (RAD)	24	0	20	61
10	Anesthesia and Surgical Care (ASC)	18	0	33	65

The table number 39 depicts that there are 10 chapters (42%) out of 24 chapters which are uncommon in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards based on the score -Fully Met as described in the above table. It is very evident from the above table that there are 7 chapters in NABH, 10 chapters in NSQHS and 8 Chapters in DDKM which are common based on the scoring method. However, these all 10 chapters are only available in COHSASA Standards of South Africa.

Table-40- Common and Un-common Chapter in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards

Standards	Common Chapter in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards	Uncommon Chapter in NABH, NSQHS and DDKM Standards	Uncommon Chapter in NSQHS Standards	Uncommon Chapter in NSQHS and DDKM Standards
Numbers of Chapters	14	7	2	1

The table number 40 depicts that there are 14 chapters (58%) out of 24 chapters which are common in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards based on the score -Fully Met as described in the above table, 7 chapters are uncommon in NABH, NSQHS and DDKM Standards, 2 chapters are Uncommon Chapter in NSQHS Standards and 1 chapter is uncommon in NSQHS and DDKM Standards.

Figure-6: Common and Un-common Chapter in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards

The figure number-6 depicts that there are 14 chapters out of 24 chapters which are common in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards based on the score -Fully Met as described in the above table, 7 chapters are uncommon in NABH, NSQHS and DDKM Standards, 2 chapters are Uncommon Chapter in NSQHS Standards and 1 chapter is uncommon in NSQHS and DDKM Standards.

Appendix 1: Multiple comparisons – Fully Met (FM) and Not Met (NM) Measurable Elements in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards

Dependent Variable	(I) Country	(J) Country	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
FM	NABH (India)	NSQHS (Australia)	22.750*	7.809	.023
		DDKM (Denmark)	8.083	7.809	.729
		COHSASA (South Africa)	-37.583*	7.809	.000
	NSQHS (Australia)	NABH (India)	-22.750*	7.809	.023
		DDKM (Denmark)	-14.667	7.809	.245
		COHSASA (South Africa)	-60.333*	7.809	.000
	DDKM (Denmark)	NABH (India)	-8.083	7.809	.729
		NSQHS (Australia)	14.667	7.809	.245
		COHSASA (South Africa)	-45.667*	7.809	.000
	COHSASA (South Africa)	NABH (India)	37.583*	7.809	.000
		NSQHS (Australia)	60.333*	7.809	.000
		DDKM (Denmark)	45.667*	7.809	.000
NM	NABH (India)	NSQHS (Australia)	-22.750	15.881	.483
		DDKM (Denmark)	-8.083	15.881	.957
		COHSASA (South Africa)	37.583	15.881	.091
	NSQHS (Australia)	NABH (India)	22.750	15.881	.483
		DDKM (Denmark)	14.667	15.881	.792

Dependent Variable	(I) Country	(J) Country	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
		COHSASA (South Africa)	60.333*	15.881	.001
DDKM (Denmark)	NABH (India)	8.083	15.881	.957	
	NSQHS (Australia)	-14.667	15.881	.792	
	COHSASA (South Africa)	45.667*	15.881	.025	
COHSASA (South Africa)	NABH (India)	-37.583	15.881	.091	
	NSQHS (Australia)	-60.333*	15.881	.001	
	DDKM (Denmark)	-45.667*	15.881	.025	

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Appendix 2: Multiple comparisons – Common Measurable Elements in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards for Hospitals

(I) Country	(J) Country	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
NABH (India)	NSQHS (Australia)	5.542	2.149	.055
	DDKM (Denmark)	-2.042	2.149	.778
	COHSASA (South Africa)	2.042	2.149	.778
NSQHS (Australia)	NABH (India)	-5.542	2.149	.055
	DDKM (Denmark)	-7.583*	2.149	.004
	COHSASA (South Africa)	-3.500	2.149	.368
DDKM (Denmark)	NABH (India)	2.042	2.149	.778
	NSQHS (Australia)	7.583*	2.149	.004
	COHSASA (South Africa)	4.083	2.149	.235
COHSASA (South Africa)	NABH (India)	-2.042	2.149	.778
	NSQHS (Australia)	3.500	2.149	.368
	DDKM (Denmark)	-4.083	2.149	.235

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Appendix 3: Multiple comparisons – Repeated Measurable Elements in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards for Hospitals

(I) Country	(J) Country	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
NABH (India)	NSQHS (Australia)	-.083	1.779	1.000
	DDKM (Denmark)	-2.458	1.779	.514
	COHSASA (South Africa)	-10.792*	1.779	.000
NSQHS (Australia)	NABH (India)	.083	1.779	1.000
	DDKM (Denmark)	-2.375	1.779	.543
	COHSASA (South Africa)	-10.708*	1.779	.000
DDKM (Denmark)	NABH (India)	2.458	1.779	.514
	NSQHS (Australia)	2.375	1.779	.543
	COHSASA (South Africa)	-8.333*	1.779	.000
COHSASA (South Africa)	NABH (India)	10.792*	1.779	.000
	NSQHS (Australia)	10.708*	1.779	.000
	DDKM (Denmark)	8.333*	1.779	.000

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

CHAPTER- 4

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this chapter, the researcher has recapitulated the main findings or conclusions on the present research “A Critical Comparative Study on the National Accreditation Standards for Hospitals of India, Australia, Denmark and South Africa” in an orderly manner based on the objectives of the research.

After analyzing the data the researcher has come to the following conclusions and recommendations:

CONCLUSIONS:

1. In National Accreditation Board for Hospitals and Healthcare Providers (NABH), India there are 10 Chapters, 105 Standards and 795 Measurable Elements based on which the hospitals are assessed for the national healthcare accreditation.
2. In National Safety and Quality Health Service (NSQHS), Australia there are 8 Chapters, 30 Standards and 148 Measurable Elements based on which the hospitals are assessed for the national healthcare accreditation.
3. In Danish Healthcare Quality Programme (DDKM), Denmark there are 27 Chapters, 80 Standards and 461 Measurable Elements based on which the hospitals are assessed for the national healthcare accreditation.
4. In Council for Health Service Accreditation of Southern Africa (COHSASA), South Africa there are 34 Chapters, 561 Standards and 3374 Measurable Elements based on which the hospitals are assessed for the national healthcare accreditation.
5. It was revealed after mapping, filtration and merging of duplicated or common chapters, standards and measurable elements that in NABH, DDKM, NSQHS and COHSASA standards there are 24 chapters, 466 standards and 2678 measurable elements which are unique.
6. The comparison of NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards and Measurable Elements before and after mapping, filtration and merging revealed that after merging-filtration the percentages are decreased by 30.37% in number of chapters, 60.05% in number of Standards and 56.04% in number of Measurable Elements. It also depicts that 69.63% chapters were duplicated,

39.95% of the standards were duplicated and 43.96% of the Measurable Elements were duplicated.

7. The comparison of Fully Met (FM) and Not Met (NM) Measurable Elements in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards revealed that the national healthcare accreditation standards for hospitals of India (NABH), Australia (NSQHS), Denmark (DDKM) and South Africa (COHSASA) are not the same. Also, the NABH Standards for Hospitals of India are not the best amongst the selected countries' Healthcare Standards for Hospitals.
8. The common Measurable Elements in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA standards for hospitals analysis revealed that the highest numbers of common measurable elements are not in COHSASA standards.
9. The repeated Measurable Elements in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards revealed that the highest numbers of repeated measurable elements are not in the COHSASA standards.
10. There are 14 common chapters (58%) [based on the score -Fully Met] out of 24 chapters which are common in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards based on the score -Fully Met as described in the above table.
11. There are 10 chapters (42%) out of the 24 chapters which are uncommon in NABH, NSQHS, DDKM and COHSASA Standards based on the score -Fully Met (7 chapters in NABH, 10 chapters in NSQHS and 8 Chapters in DDKM). However, these all 10 chapters are only available in COHSASA Standards of South Africa.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

1. The International Society for Quality in Health Care (ISQua) should stringent their national healthcare accreditation standards approval mechanism for hospitals.
2. The World Health Organization should come up with set of healthcare accreditation standards for all hospitals in the world.
3. The national healthcare accreditation organizations should revise their standards based on the researches and evidences.
4. The NABH, NSQHS, DDMK and COHSASA should revise the standards for hospitals based on this research.

ADVANCE THE KNOWLEDGE IN THE FIELD OF HEALTHCARE QUALITY:

The researcher has developed and submitted “The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals” as one of the objective of this research along with this thesis. It will be applicable for all the general hospitals in all continents and countries of the world. Moreover, it will be a great help for NABH, WHO and ISQua to improve the NABH Standards, to develop the global standards for all the countries of the world and to standardize the ISQua accredited national standards respectively. The Universal Healthcare Quality Standards for General Hospitals will be unique in the world which will be applicable for all the general hospitals across the globe.

GLOSSARY

A

Access:

Person's ability to get necessary medical care and services when needed. The ease of access is determined by components such as the availability of medical services and their acceptability to the individual and community, the locale of healthcare facilities, transportation, and hours of operation.

Accountability:

The ability of a system to track an individual's actions, or the acknowledgment and assumption of responsibility for actions, products, decisions, and policies.

Accreditation:

Act of granting recognition by an external evaluation organization of the achievement of accreditation standards, demonstrated through an independent external peer assessment of that organisation's level of performance in relation to the standards.

Accreditation assessment:

The evaluation process for assessing the compliance of an organisation with the applicable standards for determining its accreditation status.

Accreditation standard:

A standard which describes requirements and makes the basis for accreditation.

Accreditation surveys:

An evaluation of an organization to assess compliance with applicable standards and International Patient Safety Goals and to determine its accreditation status. The JCI accreditation survey includes the following:

- Evaluation of documents provided by the organization
- Verbal information about the implementation of standards or examples of their implementation that enables compliance to be determined.
- On-site observations by surveyors
- Tracking of patients through the care process using tracer methodology
- Education about standards compliance and performance improvement

A survey of all hospital standards throughout an entire organization is considered a full survey.

An initial survey, triennial survey, and validation survey are full surveys:

Initial survey:

The first full on-site survey of a hospital.

Triennial survey:

The survey of a hospital after a three-year cycle of accreditation.

Validation survey:

A second full survey that JCI may conduct in volunteer organizations as a component of JCI's internal quality improvement monitoring processes. This survey has no impact on the hospital's accreditation status and is conducted at no charge to the hospital. Other types of JCI surveys are limited in scope, content, and length and designed to gather information on specific issues, standards, or measurable elements. These types of JCI surveys are called *follow-up surveys*:

Extension survey:

A survey that may be conducted when the hospital has changes in core information, services, and/or other factors. **Examples** include a change in name, ownership, or licensing; construction and renovation; and adding or eliminating a service(s); among other examples. The hospital notifies JCI within 30 days of the effective date of the change(s).

For-cause survey:

A survey conducted when JCI learns of potentially serious standards noncompliance, serious patient care or safety issues, regulatory issues or sanctions, or other serious issues within an accredited hospital or certified program that may have placed the hospital At Risk for Denial of Accreditation.

Achievement of goals:

Compliance of requirements of the accreditation standards or elements of the standard

Action plan:

In general it includes actions which are initiated on the basis of an evaluation. Action plans usually describe the following

- a) Specific goals for the effort, including effect which is requested
- b) Initiatives to be implemented
- c) Time frame for implementation
- d) Who is responsible for the implementation
- e) Monitoring of achievement of goals
- f) Who is responsible for follow-up

Activity goals:

Activity goals describe the expected production of services which a department has to deliver during a calendar year for a given budget.

Acute care:

A level of health care in which a patient is treated for a brief but severe episode of illness; for conditions that are the result of disease or trauma; and during recovery from surgery. Many hospitals are acute care facilities with the goal of discharging the patient as soon as the patient is deemed healthy and stable, with appropriate discharge instructions.

Acute deterioration:

Physiological, psychological or cognitive changes that may indicate a worsening of the patient's health status; this may occur across hours or days.

Administration of medicine:

The staff's distribution and assistance with the patient's intake of medicine, including required observation of the patient

Advance care plan:

A plan that states preferences about health and personal care, and preferred health outcomes. An advance care planning discussion will often result in an advance care plan. Plans should be made on the person's behalf and prepared from the person's perspective to guide decisions about care.

Advance life support:

Emergency medical care for sustaining life, including defibrillation, airway management, and drugs and medications.

Adverse event:

Any untoward medical occurrence that may present during treatment with a pharmaceutical product but which does not necessarily have a causal relationship with this treatment.

Adverse Drug Reaction:

A response to a drug which is noxious and unintended and which occurs at doses normally used in man for prophylaxis, diagnosis, or therapy of disease or for the modification of physiologic function.

Therefore ADR = Adverse Event with a causal link to a drug.

Adverse drug event: The FDA recognises the term adverse drug event to be a synonym for adverse event.

In the patient-safety literature, the terms adverse drug event and adverse event usually denote a causal association between the drug and the event, but there is a wide spectrum of definitions for these terms, including harm caused by a

- a) drug
- b) harm caused by drug use, and
- c) a medication error with or without harm

Adverse event:

An injury related to medical management, in contrast to complications of disease. Medical management includes all aspects of care, including diagnosis and treatment, failure to diagnose or treat, and the systems and equipment used to deliver care. Adverse events may be preventable or non-preventable. (WHO Draft Guidelines for Adverse Event Reporting and Learning Systems)

Agreement:

Something two or several parties have agreed upon. In DDKM, agreements include i.a. healthcare agreements.

Alert:

Warning of a potential risk to a patient.

Allergy:

Occurs when a person's immune system reacts to allergens in the environment that are harmless for most people. Typical allergens include some medicines, foods and latex. An allergen may be encountered through inhalation, ingestion, injection or skin contact. A medicine allergy is one type of adverse drug reaction.

Ambulance:

Patient carrying vehicle having facilities to provide unless otherwise indicated at least basic life support during the process of transportation of patient. There are various types of ambulances that provide special services viz. coronary care ambulance, trauma ambulance, air ambulance, etc.

Ambulatory care:

Types of health care services provided to individuals on an outpatient basis. Ambulatory care services are provided in many settings ranging from freestanding surgical facilities to cardiac catheterization centers.

American society of health-system pharmacists (ASHP):

A professional organization of pharmacists and pharmacy technicians in the United States of America. It has been on the forefront of efforts to improve medication use and enhance patient safety.

Anaesthesia:

Loss of bodily sensation with or without loss of consciousness.

Anaesthesia Death:

It is defined as death occurring within 24 hours of administration of anaesthesia due to cases related to anaesthesia. However death may occur even afterwards due to the complications.

Antibiogram:

The result of a laboratory testing for the sensitivity of an isolated bacterial strain to different antibiotics. It is also known as in-vitro sensitivity.

Antimicrobial:

A chemical substance that inhibits or destroys bacteria, viruses or fungi, and can be safely administered to humans and animals.

Antimicrobial resistance:

Failure of an antimicrobial to inhibit a microorganism at the antimicrobial concentrations usually achieved over time with standard dosing regimens.

Antimicrobial stewardship:

An ongoing effort by a health service organisation to reduce the risks associated with increasing antimicrobial resistance and to extend the effectiveness of antimicrobial treatments. It may incorporate several strategies, including monitoring and review of antimicrobial use.

Appointment:

The process of reviewing an initial applicant's credentials to decide if the individual is qualified to provide patient care services that the hospital's patients need and the hospital can support with qualified staff and technical capabilities.

Appraisal:

Regularly completed conversation between the employee and his/her immediate manager about assessment and discussion of the staff development plan.

Appropriateness:

Extent to which a particular procedure, treatment, test or service is effective, clearly indicated, not excessive, adequate in quantity, and provided in the setting best suited to the client needs.

Approved identifiers:

Items of information accepted for use in identification, including family and given names, date of birth, sex, address, healthcare record number and Individual Healthcare Identifier. Health service organisations and clinicians are responsible for specifying the approved items for identification and procedure matching. Identifiers such as room or bed number should not be used.

Aseptic technique:

A technique that aims to prevent microorganisms on hands, surfaces and equipment from being introduced to susceptible sites. Unlike sterile techniques, aseptic techniques can be achieved in typical ward and home settings.

Assessment:

All activities including history taking, physical examination, laboratory investigations that contribute towards determining the prevailing clinical status of the patient.

Audit (clinical):

A systematic review of clinical care against a predetermined set of criteria.

Assigned to clinical privileges:

Types of tasks which are reserved authorised health professionals, including doctors, midwives, dentists and chiropractors. These tasks can, with a few exceptions, be delegated to an assistant.

Automatic Stop Order:

A type of medication orders that originates not with the physician but with the hospital pharmacy. Medication orders for certain types of drugs (e.g., controlled substances) are only valid for a certain number of days as determined by the hospital's Pharmacy Committee while the patient is in the hospital. After that time, the pharmacy automatically stops sending the drug to the patient's nursing unit, and the attending physician must write an entirely new order if the patient is to continue to receive that drug. It is known as "Hard Stop "in electronic pharmacy profiles

Authorization:

A process where the hospital, for a range of clinical services involved with special risks for the patient, determines who is allowed to deliver this service. This means that these services may not just be delivered by all the persons who, because of their education and authorisation, are formally qualified to this.

Autopsy:

1. An examination of a cadaver in order to determine the cause of death or to study pathologic changes.

2. A surgical procedure performed after death to examine body tissues and determine the cause of death.

Availability:

The degree to which appropriate care is available to meet the individual patient needs.

B

Baseline assessment:

The first systematic self-assessment of the level of rating achievement of the requirements in the accreditation standards. It is recommended to carry out the baseline assessment within three months after reception of the accreditation standards.

Basic life support:

Basic life support (BLS) is the level of medical care which is used for patients with life-threatening illnesses or injuries until the patient can be given full medical care.

Benchmarking:

A continuous process of measuring products, services, and/or practices against the competition in order to find and implement the best practices.

Best possible medication history:

A list of all the medicines a patient is using at presentation. The list includes the name, dose, route and frequency of the medicine, and is documented on a specific form or in a specific place. All prescribed, over-the-counter and complementary medicines should be included. This history is obtained by a trained clinician interviewing the patient (and/or their carer) and is confirmed, where appropriate, by using other sources of medicines information.

Best practice:

When the diagnosis, treatment or care provided is based on the best available evidence, which is used to achieve the best possible outcomes for patients.

Best-practice guidelines:

A set of recommended actions that are developed using the best available evidence. They provide clinicians with evidence-informed recommendations that support clinical practice, and guide clinician and patient decisions about appropriate health care in specific clinical practice settings and circumstances.

Blanket Order:

A summary order to resume previous medications. Blanket orders can be confusing or imprecise and are not indicating a safe practice (e.g., resume previous medications, for a patient post-operation).

Blood management:

A process that improves outcomes for patients by improving their medical and surgical management in ways that boost and conserve their own blood, and ensure that any blood and blood products patients receive are appropriate and safe.

Blood products:

The products derived from fresh blood – red blood cells and platelets, fresh frozen plasma, cryoprecipitate and cryodepleted plasma, plasma-derived blood products, and recombinant blood products.

Breakdown maintenance:

Activities which are associated with the repair and servicing of site infrastructure, buildings, plant or equipment within the site's agreed building capacity allocation which have become inoperable or unusable because of the failure of component parts.

Barrier nursing:

The nursing of patients with infectious diseases in isolation to prevent the spread of infection.

As the name implies, the aim is to erect a barrier to the passage of infectious pathogenic organisms between the contagious patient and other patients and staff in the hospital, and thence to the outside world. The nurses wear gowns, masks, and gloves, and they observe strict rules that minimise the risk of passing on infectious agents.

Business decision-making:

Decision-making regarding service planning and management for a health service organisation. It covers the purchase of building finishes, equipment and plant; program maintenance; workforce training for safe handling of equipment and plant; and all issues for which business decisions are taken that might affect the safety and wellbeing of patients, visitors and the workforce.

Bylaws:

A rule governing the internal management of an organisation. It can supplement or complement the government law but cannot countermand it, e.g. municipal bylaws for construction of hospitals/nursing homes, for disposal of hazardous and/or infectious waste.

C

Capital cost:

The cost of investing in the development of new or improved facilities, services, or equipment. Does not include operational costs.

Care pathway:

A complex intervention that supports mutual decision-making and organisation of care processes for a well-defined group of patients during a well-defined period.

Carer:

A person who provides personal care, support and assistance to another individual who needs it because they have a disability, medical condition (including a terminal or chronic illness) or mental illness, or they are frail or aged. An individual is not a carer merely because they are a spouse, de facto partner, parent, child, other relative or guardian of an individual, or live with an individual who requires care. A person is not considered a carer if they are paid, a volunteer for an organisation, or caring as part of a training or education program.

Case Fatality Rate:

The reported case fatality rate (CFR) is a measure of the severity of a disease and is defined as the proportion of reported cases of a specified disease or condition which are fatal within a specified time.

Certification:

The procedure and action by which an authorized organization evaluates and certifies that an individual, institution, or program meets requirements, such as standards. Certification differs from accreditation in that certification can also be applied to individuals (**for example**, a medical specialist).

Check list:

A list of items which are necessary to perform for a given task to be completed.

Citizens:

In this connection citizens include present patients and relatives and other persons who are interested in the hospital's services and the quality of the services.

Cleaning:

Removal of visible soil from objects and surfaces, which is normally accomplished manually or mechanically using water with detergents or enzymatic products.

Clinical audit:

A quality improvement process that seeks to improve patient care and outcomes through systematic review of care against explicit criteria and the implementation of change.

Clinical care standards:

Nationally relevant standards developed by the Australian Commission on Safety and Quality in Health Care, and agreed by health ministers, that identify and define the care people should expect to be offered or receive for specific conditions.

Clinical communication:

The exchange of information about a person's care that occurs between treating clinicians, patients, carers and families, and other members of a multidisciplinary team. Communication can be through several different channels, including face-to-face meetings, telephone, written notes or other documentation, and electronic means. See also effective clinical communication, clinical communication process

Clinical communication process:

The method of exchanging information about a person's care. It involves several components, and includes the sender (the person who is communicating the information), the receiver (the person receiving the information), the message (the information that is communicated) and the channel of communication. Various channels of communication can be used, including verbal (face to face, over the phone, through Skype), written and electronic. Sending and receipt of the information can occur at the same time, such as verbal communication between two clinicians, or at different times, such as non-verbal communication during which a clinician documents a patient's goals, assessments and comprehensive care plan in the healthcare record, which is later read by another clinician.

Clinical department:

All departments involved in patient treatment

Clinical governance:

An integrated component of corporate governance of health service organisations. It ensures that everyone – from frontline clinicians to managers and members of governing bodies, such as boards – is accountable to patients and the community for assuring the delivery of safe, effective and high-quality services. Clinical governance systems provide confidence to the community and the healthcare organisation that systems are in place to deliver safe and high-quality health care.

Clinical handover:

The transfer of professional responsibility and accountability for some or all aspects of care for a patient, or group of patients, to another person or professional group on a temporary or permanent basis.

Clinical information system:

A computerised healthcare record and management system that is used by clinicians in healthcare settings. Clinical information systems are typically organisation-wide, have high levels of security and access, and have roles and rights (for example, prescribing medicines, reviewing laboratory results, administering intravenous fluids) specified for each clinical and administrative user. Clinical information systems enable electronic data entry and data retrieval by clinicians.

Clinical leaders:

Clinicians with management or leadership roles in a health service organisation who can use their position or influence to change behaviour, practice or performance. Examples are directors of clinical services, heads of units and clinical supervisors.

Clinician:

A healthcare provider, trained as a health professional, including registered and non-registered practitioners. Clinicians may provide care within a health service organisation as an employee, a contractor or a credentialed healthcare provider, or under other working arrangements. They include nurses, midwives, medical practitioners, allied health practitioners, technicians, scientists and other clinicians who provide health care, and students who provide health care under supervision.

Clinical quality:

The quality of the services which professionals perform in connection with the clinical work

Clinical staff:

Staff involved in patient treatment, e.g. doctors, nurses, physiotherapists and occupational therapists, midwives and social and health care assistants (healthcare professionals)

Clinical practice guidelines:

Clinical practice guidelines are systematically developed statements to assist practitioner and patient decisions about appropriate health care for specific clinical circumstances.

Clinical pathology:

Services relating to solving clinical problems, particularly using laboratory methods in clinical diagnosis. Includes clinical chemistry, bacteriology and mycology, parasitology, virology, clinical microscopy, hematology, coagulation immunohematology, immunology, serology, and radiobioassay.

Clinical trial:

Testing of drugs, devices, or techniques in three or sometimes four stages depending on the purpose, size, and scope of the test. "Phase I" trials evaluate the safety of diagnostic, therapeutic, or prophylactic drugs, devices, or techniques to determine the safe dosage range (if appropriate). They involve a small number of healthy subjects. The trial usually lasts about one year. "Phase II" trials are usually controlled to assess the effectiveness and dosage (if appropriate) of the drugs, devices, or techniques. These studies involve several hundred volunteers, including a limited number of patients with the target disease or disorder. The trial usually lasts about two years. "Phase III" trials verify the effectiveness of the drugs, devices, or techniques determined in Phase II studies. Phase II patients are monitored to identify any adverse reactions from long-term use. These studies involve groups of patients large enough to identify clinically significant responses. The trial usually lasts about three years. "Phase IV" trials study the drugs, devices, or techniques that have been approved for general sale. These studies are often conducted to obtain more data about a product's safety and efficacy.

Code of Conduct:

A set of principles and expected behaviors that are expectations of employee performance within a healthcare setting or as defined by the leadership group.

Cognitive impairment:

Deficits in one or more of the areas of memory, communication, attention, thinking and judgement. This can be temporary or permanent. It can affect a person's understanding, their ability to carry out tasks or follow instructions, their recognition of people or objects, how they relate to others and how they interpret the environment. Dementia and delirium are common forms of cognitive impairment seen in hospitalised older patients. Cognitive impairment can also be a result of several other conditions, such as acquired brain injury, a stroke, intellectual disability, licit or illicit drug use, or medicines.

Cold chain management:

The system of transporting and storing temperature-sensitive medicines and other therapies, such as blood and blood products, within their defined temperature range at all times, from point of origin (manufacture) to point of administration, to ensure that the integrity of the product is maintained.

Collaborative Work:

An organizational culture characterized by a shared vision, shared leadership, empowered workers, and cooperation among organizational units as they work to improve processes.

Competency:

Knowledge, skills, and attitudes required to perform the job. Knowledge is the understanding of facts and procedures. Skill is the ability to perform specific actions.

Committee:

A multidisciplinary body of persons officially delegated to consider, investigate, take action on, or report on some matter or perform a specified function.

Competence:

A determination of an individual's skills, knowledge, and capability to meet defined expectations, as frequently described in a job description.

Communication:

Exchange of information or messages.

Competence development:

All kinds of development and learning, including internal and external courses, further training and other competence developing activities for all managers and staff

Communicable:

An infection that can be transferred from one person or host to another.

Competence:

Demonstrated ability to apply knowledge and skills.

Knowledge is the understanding of facts and procedures. Skill is the ability to perform specific action. For example, a competent gynecologist knows about the patho-physiology of the female genitalia and can conduct both normal as well as abnormal deliveries.

Comprehensive care:

Health care that is based on identified goals for the episode of care. These goals are aligned with the patient's expressed preferences and healthcare needs, consider the impact of the patient's health issues on their life and wellbeing, and are clinically appropriate.

Comprehensive care plan:

A document describing agreed goals of care, and outlining planned medical, nursing and allied health activities for a patient. Comprehensive care plans reflect shared decisions made with patients, carers and families about the tests, interventions, treatments and other activities needed to achieve the goals of care. The content of comprehensive care plans will depend on the setting and the service that is being provided, and may be called different things in different health service organisations. For example, a care or clinical pathway for a specific intervention may be considered a comprehensive care plan.

Confidentiality:

The restricted access to data and information to health care practitioners and clinical staff who have a need, a reason, and permission for such access. An individual's right to personal and informational privacy, including for his or her medical records.

Contamination:

The presence of an unwanted material or organism, such as an infectious agent, bacteria, parasite, or other contaminant, that is introduced to an environment, surface, object, or substance, such as water, food, or sterile medical supplies.

Continuity of care:

The degree to which the care of individuals is coordinated among practitioners, among organizations, and over time.

Continuum of care:

Matching the individual's ongoing needs with the appropriate level and type of care, treatment, and services within an organization or across multiple organizations.

Contracted services:

Services provided through a written agreement with another organization, agency, or individual. The agreement specifies the services or staff to be provided on behalf of the applicant organization and the fees to provide these services or staff.

Consumer:

A person who has used, or may potentially use, health services, or is a carer for a patient using health services. A healthcare consumer may also act as a consumer representative to provide a consumer perspective, contribute consumer experiences, advocate for the interests of current and potential health service users, and take part in decision-making processes.

Consent:

1. Willingness of a party to undergo examination/procedure/ treatment by a healthcare provider. It may be implied (e.g. patient registering in OPD), expressed which may be written or verbal. Informed consent is a type of consent in which the healthcare provider has a duty to inform his/her patient about the procedure, its potential risk and benefits, alternative procedure with their risk and benefits so as to enable the patient to take an
 1. Informed decision of his/her health care.
 2. In law, it means active acquiescence or silent compliance by a person legally capable of consenting. In India, legal age of consent is 18 years. It may be evidenced by words or acts or by silence when silence implies concurrence. Actual or implied consent is necessarily an element in every contract and every agreement.

Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI):

The culture, strategies and methods necessary for continual improvement in meeting and exceeding customer expectations. Patients and their families, staff, contractors, and visitors are all examples of internal and external customers of a hospital.

Continuous Quality Improvement Tools:

Tools focusing on the process rather than the individual, and promote the need to analyze and improve that process.

Consultant:

A person who is specialised within an area and who handles tasks within this area of shorter or longer duration.

Contemporaneously (documenting information):

Recording information in the healthcare record as soon as possible after the event that is being documented.

Control Charts:

Statistical tool used in quality control to (1) analyze and understand process variables, (2) determine process capabilities, and to (3) monitor effects of the variables on the difference between target and actual performance. Control charts indicate upper and lower control limits, and often include a central (average) line, to help detect trend of plotted values. If all data points are within the control limits, variations in the values may be due to a common cause and process is said to be 'in control'. If data points fall outside the control limits, variations may be due to a special cause and the process is said to be out of control.

Continuity:

That the patient experiences a patient pathway which proceeds without professional unfounded waiting time

Coordination:

The means to continuity; process of getting different activities to fit together

Credentialing:

The process of obtaining, verifying and assessing the qualification of a healthcare provider.

Credentials:

Evidence of competence, current and relevant licensure, education, training, and experience. Other criteria may be added by a health care organization.

Criteria:

Expected level(s) of achievement or specifications against which performance can be assessed.

Critical path method (CPM):

The critical path method (CPM) is a step-by-step technique for process planning that defines critical and non-critical tasks with the goal of preventing time-frame problems and process bottlenecks.

The CPM is ideally suited to projects consisting of numerous activities that interact in a complex manner. In applying the CPM, there are several steps that can be summarized as follows:

- Define the required tasks and put them down in an ordered (sequenced) list.
- Create a flowchart or other diagram showing each task in relation to the others.
- Identify the critical and non-critical relationships (paths) among tasks.
- Determine the expected completion or execution time for each task.
- Locate or devise alternatives (backups) for the most critical paths.

Critical equipment:

Items that confer a high risk for infection if they are contaminated with any microorganism, and must be sterile at the time of use. They include any objects that enter sterile tissue or the vascular system, because any microbial contamination could transmit disease.

Critical information:

Information that has a considerable impact on a patient's health, wellbeing or ongoing care (physical or psychological). The availability of critical information may require a clinician to reassess or change a patient's comprehensive care plan.

Critical observation findings:

Observation findings which indicate a deterioration of the patient's condition or deviate from the expected course

Cross-disciplinary clinical department:

Department which undertakes tasks across the clinical specialities, e.g. diagnostic imaging department

Cross-sectorial patient pathway:

Patient pathway which proceeds in two sectors at the same time, e.g. primary and secondary sector.

Culture of safety:

Also known as a *safe culture*, a collaborative environment in which skilled clinicians treat each other with respect, leaders drive effective teamwork and promote psychological safety, teams learn from errors and near misses, caregivers are aware of the inherent limitations of human performance in complex systems (stress recognition), and there is a visible process of learning and driving improvement through debriefings.

Curative services:

Services provided to overcome disease and to promote recovery. Curative services or therapy are different from palliative services, which give relief but not cure.

D

Data:

Facts or information used usually to calculate analyse or plan something.

Database:

An organized, comprehensive collection of stored data.

Department:

An umbrella term for parts of a hospital, including section, clinic, centre etc.

Department/service leaders:

The individuals who manage and direct the “subgroups” of the hospital, commonly referred to as *departments, services, units, and/or wards*.

Description of pathway:

Description of ideal, clinical practice for patient pathways, activities, contacts and events for selected patient groups

Decision support tools:

Tools that can help clinicians and consumers to draw on available evidence when making clinical decisions. The tools have a number of formats. Some are explicitly designed to enable shared decision making (for example, decision aids). Others provide some of the information needed for some components of the shared decision-making process (for example, risk calculators, evidence summaries), or provide ways of initiating and structuring conversations about health decisions (for example, communication frameworks, question prompt lists). See also shared decision making

De-escalation strategies:

Psychosocial techniques that aim to reduce violent or disruptive behaviour. They are intended to reduce or eliminate the risk of violence during the escalation phase, using verbal and non-verbal communication skills. De-escalation is about establishing rapport to gain the patient’s trust, minimising restriction to protect their self-esteem, appearing externally calm and self-aware in the face of aggressive behaviour, and intuitively identifying creative and flexible interventions that will reduce the need for aggression. Disease or disorder that has been chosen as the best one for the patient after all other choices have been considered.

Delirium:

An acute disturbance of consciousness, attention, cognition and perception that tends to fluctuate during the day. It is a serious condition that can be prevented in 30–40% of cases, and should be treated promptly and appropriately. Hospitalised older people with existing dementia are at the greatest risk of developing delirium. Delirium can be hyperactive (the person has heightened arousal; or can be restless, agitated and aggressive) or hypoactive (the person is withdrawn, quiet and sleepy).

Deterioration in mental state:

A negative change in a person’s mood or thinking, marked by a change in behaviour, cognitive function, perception or emotional state. Changes can be gradual or acute; they can be observed by members of the workforce, or reported by the person themselves, or their family or carers. Deterioration in a person’s mental state can be related to several predisposing or precipitating factors, including mental illness, psychological or existential stress, physiological changes, cognitive

impairment (including delirium), intoxication, withdrawal from substances, and responses to social context and environment.

Diagnostic department:

Department which primary task is to diagnose, e.g. diagnostic imaging department

Dialogue:

Exchange of information, points of view and/or messages

Dialogue meeting:

Meeting for mutual information and evaluation between parties

Discharge:

The point at which an individual's active involvement with an organization or program ends and the organization or program no longer maintains active responsibility for the care of the individual.

Discharge criterion:

A set of objective requirements which need to be met before the patient is ready for discharge. There are recognised criteria or the hospital itself may prepare the criteria for the patient categories found.

Discharge letter:

A short summary containing the information of a patient's case history and hospitalisation which is necessary for the recipient.

Discharge summary:

A part of a patient record that summarises the reasons for admission, significant clinical findings, procedures performed, treatment rendered, patient's condition on discharge and any specific instructions given to the patient or family (for example follow-up medications).

Disciplinary proceedings:

Sequence of activities to be carried out when staff does not conform to the laid-down norms, rules and regulations of the healthcare organisation.

Disinfection:

A process that eliminates many or all pathogenic microorganisms, except bacterial spores, on inanimate objects, usually by using liquid chemicals or wet pasteurization.

Dispensing of medicine:

The processes where the staff counts or prepares prescribed medicine for administration, i.e. measures, pours or absorbs medicine in another container and adds agents for solution or mixture.

Diversity:

The varying social, economic and geographic circumstances of consumers who use, or may use, the services of a health service organisation, as well as their cultural backgrounds, religions, beliefs, practices, languages spoken and sexualities (diversity in sexualities is currently referred to as lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and intersex, or LGBTI).

Document management:

Management or administration of documents

Document management system:

System which supports the document management; may with advantage be IT-based.

Documenting:

Presentation of documents/notes which substantiate an element of the standard or a service

Do-not-use list:

A written catalog of abbreviations, acronyms, and symbols that are not to be used throughout an organization—whether handwritten or entered as free text into a computer—due to their potentially confusing nature.

Dosage of medicine:

Determination of dosage plan, volume of medicine and dosage

Dose dispensing of medicine:

A medicinal product at a pharmacy or a hospital pharmacy is filled up with a dosage container which has been adjusted to the medicine's specific use. The dosage container can include one or several dosages of one or several medicinal products.

Dosimeter:

Device used to measure an individual's exposure to a hazardous environment, particularly when the hazard is cumulative over long intervals of time or one's lifetime.

Downtime:

Unavoidable data system interruptions and failures.

Planned downtime:

Scheduled data system interruption for the purpose of conducting maintenance, repairs, upgrades, and other changes to the system.

Unplanned downtime:

Unexpected data system interruption as a result of power or equipment failures, heating/cooling system failures, natural disasters, human error, or interruptions to Internet or intranet services, among other disruptions. Unplanned downtime can have a negative impact on data systems, such as data loss, hardware failures, and data corruption.

Drug dispensing:

The preparation, packaging, labeling, record keeping, and transfer of a prescription drug to a patient or an intermediary, who is responsible for administration of the drug

Drug Administration:

The giving of a therapeutic agent to a patient, e.g. by infusion, inhalation, injection, paste, suppository or tablet. It includes aerosol, oral, transtracheal infusion, subcutaneous, intramuscular, intravenous, intrauterine, intraperitoneal, intraarticular, intramammary, intrathecal, subconjunctival, percutaneous, percutaneous intraruminal, gas inhalation. Mass medication is per feed or drinking water or, in the case of captive fish, in the tank water. For feral animals individual dosing by projectile dart is usual, for group therapy administration by bait is possible.

Drug Utilization Evaluation (DUE):

A system of ongoing, systematic, criteria-based evaluation of drug use that will help ensure that medicines are used appropriately (at the individual patient level). DUE is drug or disease-specific and can be structured so that it will assess the actual process of prescribing, dispensing or administering a drug (indications, dose, drug interactions, etc.).

E

Effective clinical communication:

Two-way, coordinated and continuous communication that results in the timely, accurate and appropriate transfer of information. Effective communication is critical to, and supports, the delivery of safe patient care.

Effective communication:

A two way information sharing process which involves the communicator, communicating a message that is easily understood by the recipient. Good medical care depends upon effective communication between patients and providers. Effective

communication with persons who have limited language proficiency or understanding of the subject due to lack of familiarity, often requires interpreters, special efforts or other services.

Effectiveness:

The degree to which care is provided in the correct manner, given the current state of knowledge, to achieve the desired or projected outcome for the patient.

Efficiency:

The relationship between the outcomes (results of care) and the resources used to deliver care. **For example**, when two programs use the same amount of resources, the one that achieves a higher immunization coverage rate is the more efficient. Increasing efficiency involves achieving the same outputs with fewer resources or more outputs with the same amount of resources.

Elective patients:

Patients who are received for planned treatment

Element of the standard:

A measurable variable used to monitor and evaluate the quality

Emergency assistance:

Clinical advice or assistance provided when a patient's condition has deteriorated severely. This assistance is provided as part of the rapid response system, and is additional to the care provided by the attending clinician or team.

Emergency department:

Physical department at a hospital to which acutely ill or injured patients are referred or brought in; see also "Joint emergency department"

Emergency plan:

A plan describing purpose, organisation of the preparedness, core tasks plus division of role and responsibility in connection with external emergency events. The public health preparedness consists of the hospital preparedness, including the pre-hospital preparedness plus the medication preparedness and preparedness in the primary health service.

Emergency room:

Department receiving, examining and treating patients with acute injuries or diseases

Emergency tray:

A local well-defined collection of medicine for use in connection with acute events, e.g. cardiac arrest or anaphylactic reaction

Emergent:

A classification of acuity used in the triage systems to signify that the patient's condition is life-threatening and requires immediate intervention.

Employees:

All members of the healthcare organisation who are employed full time and are paid suitable remuneration for their services as per the laid-down policy.

Employment practices:

Analysis, screening, or other methods used to recruit, hire, select, transfer, promote, provide benefits, or similarly affect staff or future staff.

Electronic medical record (EMR):

An electronic record of a patient's health-related information that can be created, gathered, managed, and consulted by authorized health care practitioners.

End of life:

The period when a patient is living with, and impaired by, a fatal condition, even if the trajectory is ambiguous or unknown. This period may be years in the case of patients with chronic or malignant disease, or very brief in the case of patients who suffer acute and unexpected illnesses or events, such as sepsis, stroke or trauma.

End of life Care:

Helps all those with advanced, progressive, incurable illness to live as well as possible until they die. It enables the supportive and palliative care needs of both patient and family to be identified and met throughout the last phase of life and into bereavement. It includes management of pain and other symptoms and provision of psychological, social, spiritual and practical support.

Environment:

The physical surroundings in which health care is delivered, including the building, fixtures, fittings, and services such as air and water supply. Environment can also include other patients, consumers, visitors and the workforce.

Episode of care:

A phase of treatment. There may be more than one episode of care within the one hospital stay. An episode of care ends when the principal clinical intent changes or when the patient is formally separated from the facility.

ESBL:

Extended Spectrum Beta-Lactamase (ESBL) is enzymes which can degrade a range of beta-lactam antibiotics, including penicillins (ampicillin) plus cephalosporin such as cefuroxime, cefoxatime, ceftazidime and ceftriaxone. There are more than hundreds of different types of ESBL.

Escalation protocol:

The protocol that sets out the organisational response required for different levels of abnormal physiological measurements or other observed deterioration. The protocol applies to the care of all patients at all times.

Ethics:

Moral principles that govern a person's or group's behaviour.

Evaluate:

Systematically documenting the assessment of a process to see if it meets the determined goals or requirements.

Evidence:

Best existing scientific knowledge/prove

Evidence-based:

Medical basis for decision based on the best existing, empirical evidence or – for lack of empirical evidence – expert consensus

Evidence-based medicine:

Evidence-based medicine is the conscientious, explicit, and judicious use of current best evidence in making decisions about the care of individual patients.

Evidence-based guidelines:

Making clinical decisions based on empirical evidence or, in the absence of empirical evidence, expert consensus (such as consensus statements promoted by professional societies). The approach requires understanding conflicting results and assessing the quality and strength of evidence. Finally, practitioners must know how this applies to patient care and health care policy.

External patient transport:

Transport of patients which requires that the patients are transferred between sites or hospitals

Extemporaneous Preparations:

The timely non-sterile preparation of a drug product according to a physician's prescription, a drug formula, or a recipe in which calculated amounts of ingredients

are made into a homogenous (uniform) mixture under the direct supervision of a pharmacist. Extemporaneous compounding is performed when certain medical needs of individual patients cannot be met by the use of an approved commercial drug product.

F

Fall:

An event that results in a person coming to rest inadvertently on the ground or floor, or another lower level.

Familiar with:

Is used in a number of elements of the standard at step 2 about knowing that there is a document which concerns a specific topic plus having relevant knowledge about the content in the document to be able to carry out a relevant procedure.

Family:

The person(s) with a significant role in the patient's life. It mainly includes spouse, children and parents. It may also include a person not legally related to the patient but can make healthcare decisions for a patient if the patient loses decision-making ability.

Facility management program(s):

The organization's written document describing the process it has in place for the following areas of its operations: safety and security, hazardous materials, disaster preparedness, fire safety, medical equipment, and utility systems. The plan identifies specific procedures that describe mitigation, preparedness, response and recovery strategies, actions, and responsibilities.

Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA):

A common process used to prospectively identify error risk within a particular process. FMEA begins with a complete process mapping that identifies all the steps that must occur for a given process to occur (e.g., programming an infusion pump or preparing an intravenous medication in the pharmacy). With the process mapped out, the FMEA then continues by identifying the ways in which each step can go wrong (i.e., the failure modes for each step), the probability that each error will be detected (i.e., so that it can be corrected before causing harm), and the consequences or impact of the error not being detected. The estimates of the likelihood of a particular process failure, the chance of detecting such failure, and its impact are combined numerically to produce a criticality index. This criticality index provides a rough quantitative estimate of the magnitude of hazard posed by each step in a high-risk process. Assigning a criticality index to each step allows prioritization of targets for improvement. For instance, an FMEA analysis of the medication-dispensing process

on a general hospital ward might break down all steps from receipt of orders in the central pharmacy to filling automated dispensing machines by pharmacy technicians. Each step in this process would be assigned a probability of failure and an impact score, so that all steps could be ranked according to the product of these two numbers. Steps ranked at the top (i.e., those with the highest criticality indices) would be prioritized for error proofing.

Falsification (of information):

Fabrication, in whole or in part, of any information provided by an applicant or accredited organization to JCI.

Fire drills:

Drills training in development of fire, alarm in case of fire plus handling of fire-fighting equipment

Formulary:

An approved list of drugs. Drugs contained on the formulary are generally those that are determined to be cost effective and medically effective. The list is compiled by professionals and physicians in the field and is updated at regular intervals. Changes may be made depending on availability or market.

Functional Status:

The ability of individuals to take care of themselves physically and psychologically.

Framework:

An outline, overview, or “skeleton” of interconnected items that can be modified at any time by adding or deleting items.

Full operation:

Criteria indicating the hospital’s readiness for comprehensive on-site evaluation against all relevant JCI standards, based on a list of all clinical services currently provided for inpatients and outpatients; utilization statistics for clinical services showing consistent inpatient and outpatient activity levels and types of services provided for at least four months or more prior to submission of the hospital’s electronic application (E-App); and all inpatient and outpatient clinical services, units, and departments.

Functional status:

The ability of individuals to take care of themselves physically and emotionally according to the expected norms of their age group. Functional status may be divided into “social,” “physical,” and “psychological” functions. Functional

status may be assessed by asking questions during periodic health examinations or using formal screening instruments. easure.

G

General practice:

Includes general practitioners and practice coordinators and –consultants

Goal:

A broad statement describing a desired future condition or achievement without being specific about how much and when. The term —goals refers to a future condition or performance level that one intends to attain. Goals can be both short- and longer-term. Goals are ends that guide actions.

Goals of care:

Clinical and other goals for a patient’s episode of care that are determined in the context of a shared decision-making process.

Governance:

The set of relationships and responsibilities established by a health service organisation between its executive, workforce and stakeholders (including patients and consumers). Governance incorporates the processes, customs, policy directives, laws and conventions affecting the way an organisation is directed, administered or controlled. Governance arrangements provide the structure for setting the corporate objectives (social, fiscal, legal, human resources) of the organisation and the means to achieve the objectives. They also specify the mechanisms for monitoring performance. Effective governance provides a clear statement of individual accountabilities within the organisation to help align the roles, interests and actions of different participants in the organisation to achieve the organisation’s objectives. In the NSQHS Standards, governance includes both corporate and clinical governance.

Governing body:

A board, chief executive officer, organisation owner, partnership or other highest level of governance (individual or group of individuals) that has ultimate responsibility for strategic and operational decisions affecting safety and quality in a health service organisation.

Grievance handling procedures:

Sequence of activities carried out to address the grievances of patients, visitors, relatives and staff.

Guidelines: clinical practice guidelines are systematically developed statements to assist clinician and consumer decisions about appropriate health care for specific circumstances.

H

Haemovigilance:

A set of surveillance procedures covering the entire blood transfusion chain, from the donation and processing of blood and its components, to their provision and transfusion to patients, to their follow-up. It includes monitoring, reporting, investigating and analysing adverse events related to the donation, processing and transfusion of blood, as well as development and implementation of recommendations to prevent the occurrence or recurrence of adverse events.

HAI-BA:

National database for monitoring of hospital-acquired infections which are in preparation

Hand hygiene: a general term referring to any action of hand cleansing.

Handover:

The transfer of responsibility for a patient and patient care that occurs in the health care setting. **For example**, in the hospital from one health care practitioner to another, from one level of care to another level, from an inpatient unit to a diagnostic or other treatment unit, and from staff to patients/families at discharge, among other examples. Also known as a *handoff*.

Harvesting, of organs:

Removal of an organ for means of transplantation.

Hazardous materials:

Substances dangerous to human and other living organisms. They include radioactive or chemical materials.

Hazardous waste:

Waste materials dangerous to living organisms. Such materials require special precautions for disposal. They include biologic waste that can transmit disease (for example, blood, tissues) radioactive materials, and toxic chemicals. Other examples are infectious waste such as used needles, used bandages and fluid soaked items.

Hazard vulnerability analysis:

A tool used for the identification of potential emergencies and the direct and indirect effects those emergencies may have on the organization's operations and demand for its services.

Health care:

The prevention, treatment and management of illness and injury, and the preservation of mental and physical wellbeing through the services offered by clinicians, such as medical, nursing and allied health professionals.

Health care-associated infection(s) (HAIs):

Any infection(s) acquired by an individual while receiving care or services in a health care organization. Common HAIs are urinary infections, surgical wound infections, pneumonia, and bloodstream infections.

Health care organization:

A general term used to describe many types of organizations that provide health care services. This includes ambulatory care centers, behavioral/mental health institutions, home care organizations, hospitals, laboratories, and long term care organizations.

Health care practitioner:

Any person who has completed a course of study and is skilled in a field of health care. This includes a nurse, physician, dentist, pharmacist, respiratory therapist, physical therapist, and dietitian, among others. Health care practitioners are licensed by a government agency or certified by a professional organization.

Health literacy:

The Australian Commission on Safety and Quality in Health Care separates health literacy into two components – individual health literacy and the health literacy environment. Individual health literacy is the skills, knowledge, motivation and capacity of a consumer to access, understand, appraise and apply information to make effective decisions about health and health care, and take appropriate action. The health literacy environment is the infrastructure, policies, processes, materials, people and relationships that make up the healthcare system, which affect the ways in which consumers access, understand, appraise and apply health-related information and services.

Healthcare activity:

Healthcare-related activity targeted at one patient

Health promotion:

Healthcare-related activities which aim at improving the individual's health and public health by making it possible to mobilising the patient's and other citizens' action competences.

Healthcare professional contact person:

Health professional person who is attached to the individual patient and who is specifically responsible for coordination of the patient pathway during hospitalisation and during outpatient programmes; the decisive factor is not the person's profession but that he/she is part of the provision of one or several health professional service during the course

Health service organisation:

A separately constituted health service that is responsible for implementing clinical governance, administration and financial management of a service unit or service units providing health care at the direction of the governing body. A service unit involves a group of clinicians and others working in a systematic way to deliver health care to patients. It can be in any location or setting, including pharmacies, clinics, outpatient facilities, hospitals, patients' homes, community settings, practices and clinicians' rooms.

Healthcare associated infection:

Healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) are infections caused by a wide variety of common and unusual bacteria, fungi, and viruses during the course of receiving medical care. This was earlier referred to as Nosocomial/hospital-acquired/hospital-associated infection(s).

Healthcare organization:

Generic term is used to describe the various types of organization that provide healthcare services. This includes ambulatory care centres, hospitals, laboratories, etc.

Healthcare record:

Includes a record of the patient's medical history, treatment notes, observations, correspondence, investigations, test results, photographs, prescription records and medication charts for an episode of care.

High Dependency Unit (HDU):

A high-dependency unit (HDU) is an area for patients who require more intensive observation, treatment and nursing care than are usually provided for in a ward. It is a standard of care between the ward and full intensive care.

High Risk /High Alert Medications:

High-risk / high-alert medications can be defined as those drugs that have a heightened risk for adverse events or have heightened risk of catastrophic harm whenever there is an error. These drugs include generally have low therapeutic index

Higher risk (patients at higher risk of harm):

A patient with multiple factors or a few specific factors that result in their being more vulnerable to harm from health care or the healthcare system. Risk factors may include having chronic clinical conditions; having language barriers; being of Aboriginal or Torres Strait Islander background; having low health literacy; being homeless; or being of diverse gender identities and experiences, bodies, relationships and sexualities (currently referred to as lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and intersex, or LGBTI).

High-risk equipment:

High-risk equipment could be x-ray apparatus, respirators, linear accelerators, syringe pumps, pain pumps and defibrillators.

Hospital:

An umbrella term for hospitals/mental hospitals and private hospitals having a joint top management who is head of operations.

Hospital management:

Top management at a hospital

Hospital leadership:

A group of individuals who typically report to the chief executive of the hospital and most frequently include a chief medical officer representing the medical staff, a chief nursing officer representing all levels of nursing in the hospital, senior administrators, and any other individuals the hospital selects, such as a chief quality officer, vice president of human resources, chief operating officer, and so on.

Human subjects research:

Research involving living individuals about whom an investigator obtains data through intervention or interaction with individuals and/or identifiable personal information. Research protocols involving human subjects are reviewed by an Institutional Review Board (IRB) or other research ethics review mechanism and receive ongoing oversight as necessary.

Hygienic environment: an environment in which practical prevention and control measures are used to reduce the risk of infection from contamination by microbes.

I

Imaging Safety:

Includes safety measures to be taken while performing an MRI, Radiological interventions, Sedation, Anaesthesia, Transfer of patients, Monitoring patients during imaging procedure etc.

Implantable medical device:

A device that is permanently placed into a surgically or naturally formed cavity of the body to continuously assist, restore, or replace a function or structure of the body throughout the useful life of the device. Examples include a prosthesis (such as a hip), a stent, a pacemaker, and an infusion pump, among other examples.

Important conversations:

Dialogue conveying an important/serious message

Incident (clinical):

an event or circumstance that resulted, or could have resulted, in unintended or unnecessary harm to a patient or consumer; or a complaint, loss or damage. An incident may also be a near miss. See also near miss

Incidents:

Events that are unusual, unexpected, may have an element of risk, or that may have a negative effect on patients, staff, or the hospital.

Incident reporting:

It is defined as written or verbal reporting of any event in the process of patient care, that is inconsistent with the deserved patient outcome or routine operations of the healthcare facility.

Indicator of Performance:

Measurement tool which is used as a guide to monitor, evaluate and improve the quality of patient care and service.

Infection:

the invasion and reproduction of pathogenic (disease-causing) organisms inside the body. This may cause tissue injury and disease.

Infection hygiene:

Knowledge which can counteract infection and dispersion of it

Information management:

The creation, use, sharing, and disposal of data or information across an organization. This practice is critical to the effective and efficient operation of

organization activities. It includes the role of management to produce and to control the use of data and information in work activities, information resources management, information technology, and information services.

Informed consent:

A process of communication between a patient and clinician about options for treatment, care processes or potential outcomes. This communication results in the patient's authorisation or agreement to undergo a specific intervention or participate in planned care. The communication should ensure that the patient has an understanding of the care they will receive, all the available options and the expected outcomes, including success rates and side effects for each option.

Injury:

Damage to tissues caused by an agent or circumstance.

Innovation:

Activity, which based on new knowledge, develops new possibilities, which by utilisation generates an increased value

Institute of Medicine:

An injury resulting from medical intervention related to a drug, which has been simplified to —an injury resulting from the use of a drug. Adverse drug events extend beyond adverse drug reactions to include harm from overdoses and underdoses usually related to medication errors. A minority of adverse drug events is medication errors, and medication errors rarely result in adverse drug events.

Integrated care pathway:

Patient pathway where the individual steps are prepared as well-defined events in term of time and content following a course booked in advance.

Inpatient:

In general, a person who is admitted to and housed in a health care organization at least overnight.

In service education/training:

Organised education/training usually provided in the workplace for enhancing the skills of staff members or for teaching them new skills relevant to their jobs/tasks.

Instruction:

Specific instruction of how the staff is going to carry out specific tasks.

Indicator:

A statistical measure of the performance of functions, systems or processes overtime. For example, hospital acquired infection rate, mortality rate, caesarean section rate, absence rate, etc.

Information:

Processed data which lends meaning to the raw data.

Intent:

A brief explanation of the rationale, meaning and significance of the standards laid down in a particular chapter.

Integrated care pathway:

Patient pathway where the individual steps are prepared as well-defined events in term of time and content following a course booked in advance.

Integrated system:

A health care organization that offers a broad corporate system for managing a diversified health care delivery system. The system typically includes one or more hospitals, a large group practice, a health plan, and other health care operations. Health care practitioners are employed by the system or in a tightly affiliated practitioner group. The system can provide several levels of health care to patients in the same geographic areas.

Intensive therapy:

Observation, diagnostics, treatment and care of patients suffering from potential reversible failure of one or several organ systems which is so severe that treatment cannot be carried out at a regular ward.

Intervals, at regular:

Used in a number of elements of the standard at step 3 requiring evaluation. The hospital itself determines the interval. However, at least one evaluation must have been made within each accreditation period.

Intervention:

An intervention, involvement or influence, e.g. conversation in connection with prevention and health promotion

Intolerance:

Intolerance is defined as a non-allergic hypersensitivity and can be described as the inability of tolerating a specific drug or food.

Introductory conversation:

Conversation between new employee and immediate manager where mutual expectations are presented and adjusted

Invasive medical devices:

devices inserted through skin, mucosal barrier or internal cavity, including central lines, peripheral lines, urinary catheters, chest drains, peripherally inserted central catheters and endotracheal tubes.

Invasive procedure:

Procedure involving penetration of skin or natural meatus, e.g. arthroscopies; include surgical and non-surgical invasive procedures

Inventory control:

The method of supervising the intake, use and disposal of various goods in hands. It relates to supervision of the supply, storage and accessibility of items in order to ensure adequate supply without stock-outs/excessive storage. It is also the process of balancing ordering costs against carrying costs of the inventory so as to minimise total costs.

Isolation:

Separation of an ill person who has a communicable disease (e.g. measles, chickenpox, mumps, SARS) from those who are healthy. Isolation prevents transmission of infection to others and also allows the focused delivery of specialised health care to ill patients. The period of isolation varies from disease-to-disease. Isolation facilities can also be extended to patients for fulfilling their individual, unique needs.

J

Job description:

1. It entails an explanation pertaining to duties, responsibilities and conditions required to perform a job.
2. A summary of the most important features of a job, including the general nature of the work performed (duties and responsibilities) and level (i.e., skill, effort, responsibility and working conditions) of the work performed. It typically includes **job specifications** that include employee characteristics required for competent performance of the job. A job description should describe and focus on the job itself and not on any specific individual who might fill the job.

Job specification:

1. The qualifications/physical requirements, experience and skills required to perform a particular job/task.
2. A statement of the minimum acceptable qualifications that an incumbent must possess to perform a given job successfully.

Joint emergency departments:

That place at an acute hospital where a team of medical specialists and other health care professionals are ready day and night to ensure prompt assessment and treatment of all acute patients.

Jurisdictional requirements:

systematically developed statements from state and territory governments about appropriate healthcare or service delivery for specific circumstances. Jurisdictional requirements encompass a number of types of documents from state and territory governments, including legislation, regulations, guidelines, policies, directives and circulars. Terms used for each document may vary by state and territory.

L

Large equipment:

Large equipment for clinical use could be: x-ray equipment, respirators, laboratory equipment, ECG equipment, defibrillators and droppers.

Laws:

Legal document setting forth the rules of governing a particular kind of activity, e.g. organ transplantation act, which governs the rules for undertaking organ transplantation.

Laws and regulations:

Statements or directions specifying required decisions and actions. Penalties, legal or otherwise, are normally assessed when laws and regulations are not followed.

Leadership:

having a vision of what can be achieved, and then communicating this to others and evolving strategies for realising the vision. Leaders motivate people, and can negotiate for resources and other support to achieve goals.

Levels of care:

A classification of health care service levels. They are divided by the kind of care given, the number of people served, and the people providing the care. The main levels of care are primary, secondary, and tertiary. Levels of care classified by the

acuity of the patient or intensity of the services provided are emergency, intensive, and general.

Licensed independent practitioner:

An individual qualified by education and training and permitted by license and law (when applicable) and the organization to provide care and services, without direction or supervision, within the scope of the individual's practice. In many countries, licensed independent practitioners include physicians, dentists, some categories of nurses, podiatrists, optometrists, and chiropractors.

Licensure:

A legal right that is granted by a government agency in compliance with a statute governing an occupation (such as physicians, dentists, nurses, psychiatry, or clinical social work, or the operation of a health care facility).

Limited prescription:

The doctor assigns other professional groups to initiate treatment with selected medicine for groups of patients with thoroughly described diseases or symptoms. Limited prescriptions are clearly described in an instruction which has been updated and approved. The instruction must include information about what can be prescribed, who can prescribe and which patients/groups medicine can be prescribed for.

List of medicine:

List of the patient's prescribed medicine

Lists of training:

Lists of those who have participated in the training and when they participated

Local community:

The people living in a defined geographic region or from a specific group who receive services from a health service organisation.

Logbook:

Includes systematic recording of relevant data either in writing or electronically

Look-Alike Sound-Alike (LASA) Medications:

Medications with generic or proprietary names that look or sound like other medication names.

M

Maintenance:

The combination of all technical and administrative actions, including supervision actions, intended to retain an item in, or restore it to, a state in which it can perform a required function.

Management:

Includes managers in a hospital/department

Manager:

A person employed at a hospital/department to manage employees; staff = managers and staff

Mandatory:

Required by law or mandate in regulation, policy or other directive; compulsory.

Measure:

1. A quantitative and/or qualitative tool, instrument, or item used to ascertain the degree, extent, or quality of something;
2. The act of collecting quantifiable data about a structure, outcome, or process.

Medical device:

An instrument, apparatus, or machine that is used in the prevention, diagnosis, or treatment of illness or disease, or for detecting, measuring, restoring, correcting, or modifying the structure or function of the body for health care purposes. Typically, the purpose of a medical device is not achieved by pharmacological, immunological, or metabolic means.

Medical equipment:

Any fixed or portable non-drug item or apparatus used for diagnosis, treatment, monitoring and direct care of patient.

Medical record:

A written or electronic documentation of varied patient health information, such as assessment findings, treatment details, progress notes, and discharge summary. This record is created by health care practitioners.

Medical research:

Basic, clinical, and health services research that includes many types of research studies, such as clinical trials, therapeutic interventions, development of new medical technologies, and outcomes research, among others.

Medical staff:

All physicians, surgeons, dentists, and other medical practitioners who are licensed to practice independently (without supervision) and who provide preventive, curative, restorative, surgical, rehabilitative, or other medical or dental services to patients; this also includes those who provide interpretive services for patients, such as pathology and radiology; all are considered medical staff regardless of the organization's classification of appointment, employment status, contract, or other arrangements with the individual to provide such patient care services.

Medical student:

An individual enrolled in a medical educational institution.

Medication:

Any prescription medications; sample medications; herbal remedies; vitamins; nutraceuticals; over-the-counter drugs; vaccines; diagnostic and contrast agents used on or administered to persons to diagnose, to treat, or to prevent disease or other abnormal conditions; radioactive medications; respiratory therapy treatments; parenteral nutrition; blood derivatives; and intravenous solutions (plain, with electrolytes and/or drugs).

Medication error:

A medication error is any preventable event that may cause or lead to inappropriate medication use or patient harm while the medication is in the control of the health care professional, patient, or consumer. Such events may be related to professional practice, health care products, procedures, and systems, including prescribing; order communication; product labeling, packing and nomenclature; compounding; dispensing; distribution; administration; education; monitoring; and use.

Medical expertise:

Technical devices which either runs on power or gas and which falls within consolidated act no 1268 of 12 December 2005 on medical equipment ("the medical directive"). For example: Patient monitors, defibrillators, lifesaving equipment, x-ray equipment, PCs which make up an integral part of equipment and automated endoscope reproprocessors.

Medication management:

Practices used to manage the provision of medicines. Medication management has also been described as a cycle, pathway or system, which is complex and involves a number of different clinicians. The patient is the central focus. The system includes manufacturing, compounding, procuring, dispensing, prescribing, storing, administering, supplying and monitoring the effects of medicines. It also includes

decision-making, and rules, guidelines, support tools, policies and procedures that are in place to direct the use of medicines.

Medications, high-alert:

Medications involved in a high percentage of errors and/or sentinel events, as well as medications that carry a higher risk for abuse or other adverse outcomes. **Examples** of high-alert medications include investigational medications, controlled medications, anticoagulants, and lookalike/sound-alike medications.

Medicine:

Product compounded by one or several agents in a specific pharmaceutical form and –potency

Medication Order:

A written order by a physician, dentist, or other designated health professional for a medication to be dispensed by a pharmacy for administration to a patient. (Reference: Mosby's Medical Dictionary, 9th edition, Elsevier).

Primary difference between Prescription & Medication Order is that the medication order is used after Prescription, to get medicines issued/ dispensed from Pharmacy. Medication Order is an active Record, while Prescription is a Document.

Medication reconciliation:

A formal process of obtaining and verifying a complete and accurate list of each patient's current medicines, and matching the medicines the patient should be prescribed to those they are actually prescribed. Any discrepancies are discussed with the prescriber, and reasons for changes to therapy are documented and communicated when care is transferred. Medication review may form part of the medication reconciliation process.

Medication review:

A systematic assessment of medication management for an individual patient that aims to optimise the patient's medicines and outcomes of therapy by providing a recommendation or making a change. Medication review may be part of medication reconciliation.

Medicine:

A chemical substance given with the intention of preventing, diagnosing, curing, controlling or alleviating disease, or otherwise improving the physical or mental wellbeing of people. These include prescription, non-prescription, investigational, clinical trial and complementary medicines, irrespective of how they are administered.

Medicine-related problem:

Any event involving treatment with a medicine that has a negative effect on a patient's health or prevents a positive outcome. Consideration should be given to disease-specific, laboratory test-specific and patient-specific information.

Medicines list:

Prepared by a clinician, a medicines list contains, at a minimum: All medicines a patient is taking, including over-the-counter, complementary, prescription and non-prescription medicines; for each medicine, the medicine name, form, strength and directions for use must be included.

Any medicines that should not be taken by the patient, including those causing allergies and adverse drug reactions; for each allergy or adverse drug reaction, the medicine name, the reaction type and the date on which the reaction was experienced should be included.

Ideally, a medicines list also includes the intended use (indication) for each medicine. It is expected that the medicines list is updated and correct at the time of transfer (including clinical handover) or when services cease, and that it is tailored to the audience for whom it is intended (that is, patient or clinician).

Minimum information content:

The content of information that must be contained and transferred in a particular type of clinical handover. What is included as part of the minimum information content will depend on the context and reason for the handover or communication.

Mission:

An organisation's purpose. This refers to the overall function of an organisation. The mission answers the question, —What is this organisation attempting to accomplish? The mission might define patients, stakeholders, or markets served, distinctive or core competencies, or technologies used.

Monitoring:

The performance and analysis of routine measurements aimed at identifying and detecting changes in the health status or the environment, e.g. monitoring of growth and nutritional status, air quality in operation theatre. It requires careful planning and use of standardised procedures and methods of data collection.

MSDS (Material Safety Data Sheet):

A form containing data regarding the hazardous properties of chemicals and other hazardous agents.

Multidisciplinary:

A generic term which includes representatives from various disciplines, professions or service areas.

Multidisciplinary team:

A team including clinicians from multiple disciplines who work together to deliver comprehensive care that deals with as many of the patient's health and other needs as possible. The team may operate under one organisational umbrella or may be from several organisations brought together as a unique team. As a patient's condition changes, the composition of the team may change to reflect the changing clinical and psychosocial needs of the patient. Multidisciplinary care includes interdisciplinary care.

My Health Record (formerly known as a personally controlled electronic device):

The secure online summary of a consumer's health information, managed by the System Operator of the national My Health Record system (the Australian Digital Health Agency). Clinicians are able to share health clinical documents to a consumer's My Health Record, according to the consumer's access controls. These may include information on medical history and treatments, diagnoses, medicines and allergies.

N

National patient identifier:

A unique 16-digit number that is used to identify individuals who receive or may receive health care in the Australian healthcare system. Also known as an Individual Healthcare Identifier (IHI).

National provider identifier:

A unique 16-digit number that is used to identify individual clinicians or organisations that deliver health care in the Australian healthcare setting. For individuals, it is also known as a Healthcare Provider Identifier – Individual (HPI-I); for organisations, it is also known as a Healthcare Provider Identifier – Organisation (HPI-O).

National surveys of patient experiences:

Include the Danish National Survey of Patient Experiences (LUP) and the Danish National Survey of Psychiatric Experiences

Nearest relatives:

Person, who a patient allows to be involved in connection with a patient contact. The relatives could be a kinsman or kinswoman but it may also be a good friend

Near-miss:

A near-miss is an unplanned event that did not result in injury, illness, or damage--but had the potential to do so. Errors that did not result in patient harm, but could have, can be categorised as near-misses.

No harm:

This is used synonymously with near miss. However, some authors draw a distinction between these two phrases. A near-miss is defined when an error is realised just in the nick of time and abortive action is instituted to cut short its translation. In no harm scenario, the error is not recognised and the deed is done but fortunately for the healthcare professional, the expected adverse event does not occur. The distinction between the two is important and is best exemplified by reactions to administered drugs in allergic patients. A prophylactic injection of cephalosporin may be stopped in time because it suddenly transpires that the patient is known to be allergic to penicillin (near-miss). If this vital piece of information is overlooked and the cephalosporin administered, the patient may fortunately not develop an anaphylactic reaction (no harm event).

Non-diagnostic department:

All clinical departments except diagnostic departments

Nosocomial infections:

Hospital-acquired infections

Nutritional risk:

Includes malnutrition due to inadequate or unsuitable food, including patients with under- over weight.

Nutritional interventions:

Care and counseling to promote appropriate nutrition intake. This activity is based on nutrition and information about food, other sources of nutrients, and meal preparation. It includes the patient's cultural background and socioeconomic status.

Nutritional therapy:

Medical treatment which includes enteral and parenteral nutrition

Notifiable disease:

Certain specified diseases, which are required by law to be notified to the public health authorities. Under the international health regulation (WHO's International Health Regulations 2005) the following diseases are notifiable to WHO:

- (a) Smallpox
- (b) Poliomyelitis due to wild-type poliovirus
- (c) Human influenza caused by a new subtype

- (d) Severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS).
- b) In India, the following is a indicative list of diseases which are also notifiable, but may vary from state to state:
 - (a) Polio
 - (b) Influenza
 - (c) Malaria
 - (d) Rabies
 - (e) HIV/AIDS
 - (f) Louse-born typhus
 - (g) Tuberculosis
 - (h) Leprosy
 - (i) Leptospirosis
 - (j) Viral hepatitis
 - (k) Dengue fever

The various diseases notifiable under the factories act lead poisoning, byssinosis, anthrax, asbestosis and silicosis.

Nutrition care plan:

A plan to meet the nutrition and hydration needs of a patient. The nutrition care plan is developed for the patient after their nutrition and hydration needs have been assessed.

Nutritional risk:

Includes malnutrition due to inadequate or unsuitable food, including patients with under- over weight.

Nutritional therapy:

Medical treatment which includes enteral and parenteral nutrition

O

Objective:

A specific statement of a desired short-term condition or achievement includes measurable end-results to be accomplished by specific teams or individuals within time limits.

Objective element:

It is that component of standard which can be measured objectively on a rating scale. The acceptable compliance with the measureable elements will determine the overall compliance with the standard.

Observation:

The time during which a patient is watched closely by a health care practitioner(s).

Occupational health hazard:

The hazards to which an individual is exposed during the course of performance of his job. These include physical, chemical, biological, mechanical and psychosocial hazards.

Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA):

A government agency under the United States Department of Labor that helps employers reduce injuries, illnesses, and deaths in the workplace.

Off-Label:

Where prescribing or supply of a licensed medication is outside the indications named in its license or summary of product characteristics. There are a number of circumstances where medicines may be prescribed or supplied for the purposes for which they are not licensed e.g. children.

Open disclosure:

An open discussion with a patient and carer about an incident that resulted in harm to the patient while receiving health care. The criteria of open disclosure are an expression of regret, and a factual explanation of what happened, the potential consequences, and the steps taken to manage the event and prevent recurrence.

Operational plan:

Operational plan is the part of your strategic plan. It defines how you will operate in practice to implement your action and monitoring plans--what your capacity needs are, how you will engage resources, how you will deal with risks, and how you will ensure sustainability of the organisation's achievements.

Organisation chart:

Plan describing the functions/job categories which are part of a certain organisation.

Organisation-wide: intended for use throughout the health service organisation.

Organisational quality:

Planning of patient pathway so it appears coordinated plus rational resource utilisation.

Orientation:

A formal process of informing and training a worker starting in a new position or beginning work for an organisation, which covers the policies, processes and procedures applicable to the organisation.

Organogram:

A graphic representation of reporting relationship in an organisation.

Outcome:

The status of an individual, group of people or population that is wholly or partially attributable to an action, agent or circumstance.

Outpatient:

Generally, persons who do not need the level of care associated with the more structured environment of an inpatient or a residential program. In many countries, outpatient care is also known as “ambulatory care.” In some countries, outpatients are considered “admitted” to a health care organization; in others, outpatients are considered “registered.”

Outsourcing:

Hiring of services and facilities from other organisation based upon one’s own requirement in areas where such facilities are either not available or else are not cost-effective. For example, outsourcing of house-keeping, security, laboratory/certain special diagnostic facilities with other institutions after drawing a memorandum of understanding that clearly lays down the obligations of both organisations: the one which is outsourcing and the one which is providing the outsourced facility. It also addresses the quality-related aspects.

P

Palliative effort:

Effort to improve the quality of life for patients and families facing problems associated with life-threatening diseases by preventing and relieving the disease by early diagnosis and immediate assessment and treatment of pain and other problems of physical, emotional, psychosocial and spiritual character.

Palliative services:

Treatments and support services intended to alleviate pain and suffering rather than to cure illness. Palliative therapy may include surgery or radiotherapy undertaken to reduce or to shrink tumors compressing vital structures and thereby to improve the quality of life. Palliative services include attending to the patient’s psychological and spiritual needs and supporting the dying patient and his or her family.

Para-clinical examination:

Assessment and analysis of samples from patients plus imaging performed by staff working at diagnostic imaging departments.

Partner:

A person who is part of a collaboration or a decision

Partnership:

A situation that develops when patients and consumers are treated with dignity and respect, when information is shared with them, and when participation and collaboration in healthcare processes are encouraged and supported to the extent that patients and consumers choose. Partnerships can exist in different ways in a health service organisation, including at the level of individual interactions; at the level of a service, department or program; and at the level of the organisation. They can also exist with consumers and groups in the community. Generally, partnerships at all levels are necessary to ensure that the health service organisation is responsive to patient and consumer input and needs, although the nature of the activities for these different types of partnership will depend on the context of the health service organisation.

Patient: a person who is receiving care in a health service organisation.

Patient-care setting:

The location where a patient is provided health care as per his needs, e.g. ICU, specialty ward, private ward and general ward.

Patient care process:

The act of providing accommodations, comfort, and treatment to an individual. This implies responsibility for safety, including treatment, services, habilitation, rehabilitation, or other programs requested by the organization or network for the individual.

Patient-centered care:

Care that is respectful of, and responsive to, individual patient preferences, needs, and values. Ensures that patient values guide clinical decisions.

Patient critical supplies:

Technical supplies (e.g. power and gas) which may cause a critical condition for the patient if this function lacks

Patient health record:

Include all data concerning the patient treatment, including recordings from non-health professionals

Patient pathway:

The sum of the activities, contacts and events in the healthcare system which a patient or a defined group of patients experience in relation to the healthcare professional service.

Patient record/ medical record/ clinical record:

A document which contains the chronological sequence of events that a patient undergoes during his stay in the healthcare organisation. It includes demographic data of the patient, assessment findings, diagnosis, consultations, procedures undergone, progress notes and discharge summary. (Death certificate, where required)

Patient safety:

Protection of the patient against injuries or risk of injuries due to the healthcare system's effort and services or lack of same.

Patient satisfaction:

Is a measure of the extent to which a patient is content with the health care which they received from their health care provider. Patient satisfaction is thus a proxy but a very effective indicator to measure the success of Health care providers.

Patient Experience:

Is the sum of all interactions, shaped by an organisation's culture, that influence patient perceptions across the continuum of care. It is a holistic perception that the patient forms about the healthcare provider based on the overall interactions/ care touch points.

Patient-perceived quality:

The quality a given patient experiences in the contact with the healthcare system

Patterns and tendencies:

Patterns are defined as conditions which are present when data are reviewed "across". There could e.g. be problems with several aspects of the quality at a given department or there may be problems with a process which is monitored in several different contexts, e.g. evaluation of pain. Tendencies are defined as development over time.

PDCA:

A scientific method utilized to improve processes. Acronym components: PLAN the improvement, DO the improvement, collect and analyze data, CHECK and study the results, ACT to improve the process and hold gains. Also known as the Shewart cycle, Deming cycle, or learning cycle of change.

Performance appraisal:

It is the process of evaluating the performance of employees during a defined period of time with the aim of ascertaining their suitability for the job, potential for growth as well as determining training needs.

Person-centred care:

An approach to the planning, delivery and evaluation of health care that is founded on mutually beneficial partnerships among clinicians and patients. Person-centred care is respectful of, and responsive to, the preferences, needs and values of patients and consumers. Key dimensions of person-centred care include respect, emotional support, physical comfort, information and communication, continuity and transition, care coordination, involvement of carers and family, and access to care. Also known as patient-centred care or consumer-centred care.

Person identifiable data:

Data which can be identified/related directly to a patient, examples could be civil registry numbers and data where diagnoses are connected with civil registry numbers.

Person responsible for pathway:

Healthcare professional person responsible for coordination of patient pathway for a group of patients, e.g. patients with diabetes and cardiac insufficiency.

Person responsible for treatment:

Managers and/or staff responsible for the patient treatment.

Pharmaceutical Care:

A patient-centered pharmaceutical practice in which the pharmacist assumes responsibility for a patient's medication management issues and is held accountable for this commitment.

Pharmacovigilance:

The science and activities relating to the detection, assessment, understanding and prevention of the adverse effects of pharmaceutical products.

Physiologic-based criteria:

Criteria centered on the branch of biology dealing with the functions of the living organism and its parts of the physical and chemical factors and processes involved.

Plan:

Description of specific initiatives to obtain a given goal, e.g. implementation of a policy or guideline.

Point of care: the time and location of an interaction between a patient and a clinician for the purpose of delivering care.

Point of care equipment:

Medical Equipments that are used to deliver care / intervene at or near the site of patient care. These are primarily Point-of-care testing (POCT), or bedside testing equipments that helps in reducing turnaround times. POCT Machine examples; Glucometer, ABG Analyzer, Stat Lab at ICU/ ER, portable USG etc.

Point-of-care testing:

Analytical testing performed at sites outside the traditional laboratory environment, usually at or near where care is delivered to individuals.

Policy:

A set of principles that reflect the organisation's mission and direction. All procedures and protocols are linked to a policy statement.

Policies:

They are the guidelines for decision-making, e.g. admission, discharge policies, antibiotic policy, etc.

Post-anaesthetic monitoring:

The pathway from the patient arrives at the recovery ward until he/she is discharged or transferred to a bed unit

Preoperative medical assessment:

A clinical risk assessment that assesses the health of a patient to determine if the patient is safe to undergo anesthesia and surgery.

Prescription of medicine:

Part of medication where it is planned which medicine a patient is going to be supplied with

Prevention:

Health-related activity which aims to prevent the start and development of diseases, psychosocial problems or accidents and thus promotes the public health

Preventive maintenance:

It is a set of activities that are performed on plant equipment, machinery, and systems before the occurrence of a failure in order to protect them and to prevent or eliminate any degradation in their operating conditions. The maintenance carried out

at predetermined intervals or according to prescribed criteria and intended to reduce the probability of failure or the degradation of the functioning of an item.

Preventive services:

Interventions to promote health and prevent disease. These include identification of and counseling on risk factors (**for example**, smoking, lack of physical activity), screening to detect disease (**for example**, breast cancer, sexually transmitted diseases), and immunizations.

Primary sector:

The primary sector is that part of the healthcare system which has the primary contact to the citizen, including general practitioner, the municipal home care/visiting nurses and any specialist physicians

Primary source verification:

Verification of an individual health care practitioner's reported qualifications by the original source or an approved agent of that source. Methods for conducting primary source verification of credentials include direct correspondence, documented telephone verification, secure electronic verification from the original qualification source, or reports from credentials verification organizations that meet JCI requirements.

Prescription:

A prescription is a document given by a physician or other healthcare practitioner in the form of instructions that govern the care plan for an individual patient. Legally, it is a written directive, for compounding or dispensing and administration of drugs, or for other service to a particular patient.

Pressure injuries:

Injuries of the skin and/or underlying tissue, usually over a bony prominence, caused by unrelieved pressure, friction or shearing. They occur most commonly on the sacrum and heel, but can develop anywhere on the body. Pressure injury is a synonymous term for pressure ulcer.

Principal site:

The site at which an academic medical center hospital provides the majority of medical specialty programs for postgraduate medical trainees (**for example**, residents or interns) and not just one specialty, as in a single-specialty hospital (**for example**, an ophthalmologic hospital, dental hospital, or orthopedic hospital). *See* General Eligibility Requirements in this manual.

Privileging:

It is the process for authorising all medical professionals to admit and treat patients and provide other clinical services commensurate with their qualifications and skills.

PRN (Pro Re Nata) Order:

Orders acted upon based on the occurrence of specific indication or symptom (e.g., acetaminophen 500 mg PO Q4H, PRN for fever $\geq 38.5^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Procedural sedation:

A technique of administering sedatives or dissociative agents with or without analgesics to induce a state that allows the patient to tolerate unpleasant procedures while maintaining cardiorespiratory function.

Procedure:

1. A specified way to carry out an activity or a process
2. A series of activities for carrying out work which when observed by all help to ensure the maximum use of resources and efforts to achieve the desired output.

Procedure matching:

The processes of correctly matching patients to their intended care.

Process:

A set of interrelated or interacting activities which transforms inputs into outputs

Program:

An initiative, or series of initiatives, designed to deal with a particular issue, with resources, a time frame, objectives and deliverables allocated to it.

Programme:

A sequence of activities designed to implement policies and accomplish objectives.

Professional quality:

The quality of the services which professionals perform in connection with the clinical work

Project Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT):

PERT is a method to analyze the involved tasks in completing a given project, especially the time needed to complete each task, and to identify the minimum time needed to complete the total project. PERT breaks down the project into events and activities, and lays down their proper sequence, relationships, and duration in the form

of a network. Lines connecting the events are called paths, and the longest path resulting from connecting all events is called the critical path. The length (duration) of the critical path is the duration of the project, and any delay occurring along it delays the whole project. PERT is a scheduling tool, and does not help in finding the best or the shortest way to complete a project.

Prospective:

A focus on the potential for something to happen in the future.

Protocol:

A plan or a set of steps to be followed in a study, an investigation or an intervention.

Public health preparedness training:

Training so a healthcare professional gains the competences which are needed to handle the tasks which the person is responsible for in connection with the public health preparedness

Purpose-driven communication:

Communication in which all the parties involved in the communication process have a shared understanding of why the communication is taking place (for example, to gather, share, receive or check information), what action needs to be taken and who is responsible for taking that action.

Q

Qualified individual:

An individual or staff member who can participate in one or all of the organization's care activities or services. Qualification is determined by the following, as applicable: education, training, experience, competence, applicable licensure, laws or regulations, registration, or certification.

Quality:

1. Degree to which a set of inherent characteristics fulfil requirements.
2. Characteristics imply a distinguishing feature .Requirements are a need or expectation that is stated, generally implied or obligatory.
3. Degree of adherence to pre-established criteria or standards.

Quality assurance:

Part of quality management focused on providing confidence that quality requirements will be fulfilled

Quality flaw:

That a given activity does not meet the required or determined quality goals

Quality goal:

Goal for the requested quality

Quality improvement:

Ongoing response to quality assessment data about a service in ways that improve the process by which services are provided to consumers/patients.

Quality monitoring plan:

Plan describing the hospital's overall quality monitoring, including how and when the hospital will monitor the quality of different services

Quality of care:

The degree to which health services for individuals and populations increase the likelihood of desired health outcomes and are consistent with current professional knowledge. Dimensions of performance include the following: patient perspective issues; safety of the care environment; and accessibility, appropriateness, continuity, effectiveness, efficacy, efficiency, and timeliness of care.

Quality organization:

Organisation in the hospital which plans the systems and working procedures which support the implementation and monitoring of the quality policy. The quality organisation could include a quality council and cross-disciplinary, counselling committee

R

Radiation safety:

Refers to safety issues and protection from radiation hazards arising from the handling of radioactive materials or chemicals and exposure to Ionizing & Non-Ionizing Radiation. This is implemented by taking steps to ensure that people will not receive excessive doses of radiation and by monitoring all sources of radiation to which they may be exposed.(Reference: McGraw-Hill Dictionary of Scientific & Technical Terms) In a Healthcare setting, this commonly refers to X-ray machines, CT/ PET CT Scans, Electron microscopes, Particle accelerators, Cyclotrone etc. Radioactive substances &radioactive waste are also potential Hazards.

Range Order:

Order in which the dose or dosing intervals varies over a prescribed range, depending on the situation or patient's status (e.g., pethidine 50-100 mg IM Q3-4H, PRN for pain).

Referral:

The process by which a patient is sent (1) from one clinician to another clinician or specialist; or (2) from one setting or service to another, either for consultation or care that the referring source is not prepared or qualified to provide.

Rational pharmacotherapy:

Evidence-based and in accordance with good clinical practice. Rational use of the available medication samples based on effect as well as on economic point of views

Reappointment:

The process of reviewing the medical staff member's file to verify a continued licensure; that the medical staff member is not compromised by disciplinary actions of licensing and certification agencies; that the file contains sufficient documentation for seeking new or expanded privileges or duties in the hospital; and that the medical staff member is physically and mentally able to provide patient care and treatment without supervision.

Re-assessment:

It implies continuous and ongoing assessment of the patient which is recorded in the medical records as progress notes.

Recruitment:

Seeking—usually new—staff or other members of an organization.

Reconciliation of medications:

Medication reconciliation is the process of creating the most accurate list possible of all medications a patient is taking — including drug name, dosage, frequency, and route — and comparing that list against the physician's admission, transfer, and/or discharge orders, with the goal of providing correct medications to the patient at all transition points within the hospital. (Reference: Institute for Healthcare Improvement).

Recovery:

A range of efforts which help the individual patient in obtaining and maintaining the best possible physical, sensory, intellectual, psychological and social functional capacity. Recovery provides people with a reduced functional capacity with the tools which are necessary to gain independence and self-determination.

Reference/contract laboratory:

A laboratory owned and operated by an organization other than the hospital, with which the hospital contacts for testing.

Regularly:

Occurring at recurring intervals. The specific interval for regular review, evaluation, audit or monitoring needs to be determined for each case. In the NSQHS Standards (2nd ed.), the interval should be consistent with best practice, risk based, and determined by the subject and nature of the activity.

Rehabilitation:

Rehabilitation is defined according to the Danish Health Act and the Danish Social Services Act as a targeted and time-limited process of collaboration between a patient/citizen, any relatives and staff so the patient/citizen get the same degree of functional capacity as previous or the best possible functional capacity, in terms of motion-, activity as well as cognitive, emotionally and socially.

Rehabilitation plan:

Rehabilitation plan is based on a specific, individual assessment of the individual patient's needs for rehabilitation.

Rehabilitation services:

The use of medical, social, educational, and vocational measures together for training or retraining individuals disabled by disease or injury. The goal is to enable patients to achieve their highest possible level of functional ability.

Responsibility and accountability for care:

Accountability includes the obligation to report and be answerable for consequences. Responsibility is the acknowledgement that a person has to take action that is appropriate to a patient's care needs and the health service organisation.

Reliability:

A characteristic of a measure that indicates how accurately and consistently the measure produces similar results. **For example**, a reliable measure or measurement tool yields accurate and consistent results when used by different individuals, across different settings, with different patients, and so on, as applicable.

Relatives:

Person who is related to a patient in connection with a patient contact; see also "nearest relatives"

Representative sample:

As it relates to JCI standards, a representative sample of medical records is reviewed as part of an organization's monitoring and performance improvement activities. Representative sample means medical records from all services of the hospital, both inpatient and outpatient medical records, and both active and discharged medical records. The number of medical records should make sense for

the organization. **For example**, random sampling and selecting approximately 5% of medical records may achieve a representative sample.

Responsible physician:

The physician who has overall responsibility for the care and management of an individual patient at a specific point in time during the patient's hospital stay.

Responsible surgeon:

In cases of surgical procedures, the person who performs the surgery. Different titles used for the responsible surgeon include *attending surgeon* and *consultant surgeon*, among other titles.

Resources:

It implies all inputs in terms of men, material, money, machines, minutes (time), methods, metres (space), skills, knowledge and information that are needed for efficient and effective functioning of an organisation.

Restraint:

The restriction of an individual's freedom of movement by physical or mechanical means.

Restraints:

Devices used to ensure safety by restricting and controlling a person's movement. Many facilities are —restraint free or use alternative methods to help modify behaviour. Restraint may be physical or chemical (by use of sedatives).

Retrospective tracing:

As it relates to supply chain management, the process of identifying and tracking unstable, contaminated, defective, or counterfeit supplies after they have entered the hospital. When applicable, the hospital notifies the manufacturer and/or distributor about the unstable, contaminated, defective, or counterfeit supply.

Reusable device:

A medical device that is designated by its manufacturer as suitable for reprocessing and reuse.

Risk:

The chance of something happening that will have a negative impact. Risk is measured by the consequences of an event and its likelihood.

Risk assessment:

Risk assessment is the determination of quantitative or qualitative value of risk related to a concrete situation and a recognised threat (also called hazard). Risk assessment is a step in a risk management procedure.

Risk management:

Clinical and administrative activities to identify evaluate and reduce the risk of injury.

Risk reduction:

The conceptual framework of elements considered with the possibilities to minimise vulnerabilities and disaster risks throughout a society to avoid (prevention) or to limit (mitigation and preparedness) the adverse impacts of hazards, within the broad context of sustainable development. It is the decrease in the risk of a healthcare facility, given activity, and treatment process with respect to patient, staff, visitors and community.

Root Cause Analysis (RCA):

Root Cause Analysis (RCA) is a structured process that uncovers the physical, human, and latent causes of any undesirable event in the workplace. Root cause analysis (RCA) is a method of problem solving that tries to identify the root causes of faults or problems that cause operating events. RCA practice tries to solve problems by attempting to identify and correct the root causes of events, as opposed to simply addressing their symptoms. By focusing correction on root causes, problem recurrence can be prevented. The process involves data collection; cause charting, root cause identification and recommendation generation and implementation.

Routine maintenance:

The performance of basic safety checks—that is, the visual, technical, and functional evaluations of equipment—to identify obvious deficiencies before they have a negative impact. It normally includes inspections of the case, power cord, structural frame, enclosure, controls, indicators, and so on.

S

Safety:

The degree to which the organization's buildings, grounds, and equipment do not pose a hazard or risk to patients, staff, or visitors.

Safety data sheet (SDS):

A formal document with information about the characteristics and actual or potential hazards of a substance; includes instructions related to first aid, spills, and

safe storage, among other information. Previously named material safety data sheet (MSDS).

Scope of practice:

The range of activities performed by a practitioner in a health care organization. The scope is determined by training, tradition, laws or regulations, or the organization.

Scope of services:

The range of activities performed by governance, managerial, clinical, and support staff.

Screening criteria:

A set of standardized rules or tests applied to patient groups on which to base a preliminary judgment that further evaluation or interventions are warranted, such as the need for a nutritional evaluation based on nutritional screening.

Second victim:

A health care practitioner involved in an unanticipated adverse patient event, medical error, and/or a patient-related injury who becomes victimized in the sense that the practitioner is traumatized by the event. The practitioner's emotional response, which may include remorse, anxiety, and moral distress, may have an impact on the quality and safety of patient care if health care organizations do not acknowledge and provide support for the health care practitioner.

Secondary sector:

That part of the healthcare system which can takeover or carry on the treatment from the primary sector, including hospitals.

Security:

Protection from loss, destruction, tampering, or unauthorized access or use.

Sedation:

Causing a condition of tranquillity, relaxation, drowsiness and freedom for anxiety with pharmaceutical agents. Sedation is a spectrum of conditions with varying degrees of affection of the patient.

Self-assessment:

The hospital's assessment of the level of rating achievement of the requirements in the accreditation standards plus an assessment of whether the action plans are followed.

Sentinel event:

An unanticipated occurrence involving death or serious physical or psychological injury. *See* QPS.7 for an operational definition.

Service context:

The particular context in which care is delivered. Health service delivery occurs in many different ways, and the service context will depend on the organisation's function, size and organisation of care regarding service delivery mode, location and workforce.

Service goal:

Service goals are politically determined goals for the service which the citizen may expect in his/her contact with the healthcare system

Serious Adverse Drug Reaction:

An adverse drug reaction which results in death, is life-threatening, requires inpatient hospitalization or prolongation of existing hospitalization, results in persistent or significant disability or incapacity.

Side effect:

Pharmacological effect of a drug, normally adverse, other than the one(s) for which the drug is prescribed.

Shared decision making:

A consultation process in which a clinician and a patient jointly participate in making a health decision, having discussed the options, and their benefits and harms, and having considered the patient's values, preferences and circumstances.

Specialist:

Staff specialised within a given field; often a medical specialist, but it may include other groups with special competence, e.g. within imaging

Specialty laboratory programs:

Programs that include laboratory disciplines, such as chemistry (including toxicology, therapeutic drug testing, and drugs of abuse testing), clinical cytogenetics, immunogenetics, diagnostic immunology, embryology, hematology (including coagulation testing), histocompatibility, immunohematology, microbiology (including bacteriology, mycobacteriology, mycology, virology, and parasitology), molecular biology, pathology (including surgical pathology, cytopathology, and necropsy), and radiobioassay.

Staff:

The total number of persons employed at a hospital/department; staff = managers and employees

Staff development plan:

Plan for each employee describing a development and education, if any, which has been agreed between each employee and his/her immediate manager; is developed on the basis of the appraisal

Stakeholder:

Anyone who shows an interest in the hospital. Includes hence managers, staff, patients and relatives and other visitors plus citizens.

Standard:

Agreed attributes and processes designed to ensure that a product, service or method will perform consistently at a designated level.

Standard national terminologies:

A structured vocabulary used in clinical practice to accurately describe the care and treatment of patients. Healthcare providers around the world use specialised vocabulary to describe diseases, operations, clinical procedures, findings, treatments and medicines. In Australia, terminologies include SNOMED CT-AU and Australian Medicines Terminology. Standard national terminologies are also referred to as clinical terminologies.

Standard precautions:

Work practices that provide a first-line approach to infection prevention and control, and are used for the care and treatment of all patients.

Sterilization:

The use of a physical or chemical procedure to destroy all microbial life, including highly resistant bacterial endospores.

Structured clinical handover:

A structured format used to deliver information (the minimum information content), enabling all participants to know the purpose of the handover, and the information that they are required to know and communicate.

Strategic Planning:

A management tool to help an organization do a better job. It is a disciplined effort to produce fundamental decisions and actions that shape what an organization is, what it does, and why it does it, with a focus on the future direction.

Substitute decision-maker:

A person appointed or identified by law to make health, medical, residential and other personal (but not financial or legal) decisions on behalf of a patient whose decision-making capacity is impaired. A substitute decision-maker may be appointed by the patient, appointed for (on behalf of) the person, or identified as the default decision-maker by legislation, which varies by state and territory.

Surgical confusions:

All started invasive procedures performed either on the wrong patient, at the wrong place or the wrong organ, include also confusion of types of interventions, procedures or implants.

Supply chain:

The steps in moving a finished product (drug, medical equipment, medical device, or medical supply) from its source (a manufacturer) to its customer (a hospital). Key considerations in the supply chain are the risks to the product (**for example**, protection from losing stability, becoming contaminated, and becoming defective); the potential risk points in the steps of the supply chain (**for example**, quality of product, storage conditions, customs, delivery methods); and the selection of vendor, distributor, and so on, based on the risks in the supply chain.

Surgery:

Those procedures that investigate and/or treat diseases and disorders of the human body through cutting, removing, altering, or insertion of diagnostic/therapeutic scopes.

Surgical/invasive procedure:

A procedure involving puncture or incision of the skin or insertion of an instrument or foreign material into the body.

Symptom, primary:

First or most prominent indication of an illness, disease, or other disorder.

Symptom, secondary:

An indication of illness, disease, or other disorder that appears after or because of a primary symptom.

Survey:

Systematic assessment of level of rating achievement of the requirements in the accreditation standards performed by on-site surveyors from other hospitals

Surveyor:

Professional who, after having completed a special training, assesses the hospital's compliance of the accreditation standards.

Surveillance:

An epidemiological practice that involves monitoring the spread of disease to establish progression patterns. The main roles of surveillance are to predict and observe spread; to provide a measure for strategies that may minimise the harm caused by outbreak, epidemic and pandemic situations; and to increase knowledge of the factors that might contribute to such circumstances.

Safety:

The degree to which the risk of an intervention/procedure, in the care environment is reduced for a patient, visitors and healthcare providers

Safety culture:

A commitment to safety that permeates all levels of an organisation, from the clinical workforce to executive management. Features commonly include acknowledgement of the high-risk, error-prone nature of an organisation's activities; a blame-free environment in which individuals are able to report errors or near misses without fear of reprimand or punishment; an expectation of collaboration across all areas and levels of an organisation to seek solutions to vulnerabilities; and a willingness of the organisation to direct resources to deal with safety concerns.

Safety programme:

A programme focused on patient, staff and visitor safety.

Scope of services:

Range of clinical and supportive activities that are provided by a healthcare organisation.

Scope of clinical practice:

The extent of an individual clinician's approved clinical practice within a particular organisation, based on the clinician's skills, knowledge, performance and professional suitability, and the needs and service capability of the organisation.

Screening:

A process of identifying patients who are at risk, or already have a disease or injury. Screening requires enough knowledge to make a clinical judgement.

Seclusion:

The confinement of a patient, at any time of the day or night, alone in a room or area from which free exit is prevented.

Security:

Protection from loss, destruction, tampering, and unauthorized access or use.

Sedation:

The administration to an individual, in any setting for any purpose, by any route, moderate or deep sedation. There are three levels of sedation:

Minimal sedation (anxiolysis):

A drug-induced state during which patients respond normally to verbal commands. Although cognitive function and coordination may be impaired, ventilatory and cardiovascular functions are not affected.

Moderate sedation/analgesia (conscious sedation):

A drug-induced depression of consciousness during which patients respond purposefully to verbal commands either alone or accompanied by light tactile stimulation. No interventions are needed to maintain a patent airway.

Deep sedation/analgesia:

A drug-induced depression of consciousness during which patients cannot be easily aroused but respond purposefully after repeated or painful stimulation. Patients may need help in maintaining a patent airway.

Self-harm:

Includes self-poisoning, overdoses and minor injury, as well as potentially dangerous and life-threatening forms of injury. Self-harm is a behaviour and not an illness. People self-harm to cope with distress or to communicate that they are distressed.

Semi-critical equipment:

Items that come into contact with mucous membranes or non-intact skin, and should be single use or sterilised after each use. If this is not possible, high-level disinfection is the minimum level of reprocessing that is acceptable.

Sentinel events:

A relatively infrequent, unexpected incident, related to system or process deficiencies, which leads to death or major and enduring loss of function for a recipient of healthcare services. Major and enduring loss of function refers to sensory, motor, physiological, or psychological impairment not present at the time services were sought or begun. The impairment lasts for a minimum period of two weeks and is not related to an underlying condition.

Social responsibility:

A balanced approach for organisation to address economic, social and environmental issues in a way that aims to benefit people, communities and society, e.g. adoption of villages for providing health care, holding of medical camps and proper disposal of hospital wastes.

Special Educational needs of the patient:

In addition to routine carried by the healthcare professionals, patients and family have special educational needs depending on the situation. eg: a post surgical patient who has to take care of his wound, NG tube feeding, Patient on tracheostomy getting discharged who has to be taken care by the family etc. The special educational needs are also greatly influenced by the literacy, educational level, language, emotional barriers and physical and cognitive limitations. Hence it is important for the staff to determine the special educational needs and the challenges influencing the effective education.

Staff:

All personnel working in the organisation including employees, —fee for-service medical professionals, part-time workers, contractual personnel and volunteers.

Standard precautions:

1. A method of infection control in which all human blood and other bodily fluids are considered infectious for HIV, HBV and other blood-borne pathogens, regardless of patient history. It encompasses a variety of practices to prevent occupational exposure, such as the use of personal protective equipment (PPE), disposal of sharps and safe housekeeping
2. A set of guidelines protecting first aiders or healthcare professionals from pathogens. The main message is: "Don't touch or use anything that has the victim's body fluid on it without a barrier." It also assumes that all body fluid of a patient is infectious, and must be treated accordingly.

Standard Precautions apply to blood, all body fluids, secretions, and excretions (except sweat) regardless of whether or not they contain visible blood, non-intact skin and mucous membranes.

Standards:

A statement of expectation that defines the structures and process that must be substantially in place in an organisation to enhance the quality of care.

Strategic plan:

Strategic planning is an organisation's process of defining its strategy or direction and making decisions on allocating its resources to pursue this strategy,

including its capital and people. Various business analysis techniques can be used in strategic planning, including SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) e.g. Organisation can have a strategic plan to become market leader in provision of cardiothoracic and vascular services.

Surveillance:

The continuous scrutiny of factors that determines the occurrence and distribution of diseases and other conditions of ill health. It implies watching over with great attention, authority and often with suspicion. It requires professional analysis and sophisticated interpretation of data leading to recommendations for control activities.

T

Tapering Order:

Order in which the dose is decreased by a particular amount with each dosing interval. Taper orders shall include the starting dose, the entire taper, the medication amount for each step of the taper, and frequency of the taper (e.g., Prednisone 20 mg PO for 2 days, then taper dose on successive days to give 15 mg for 1 day, then 10 mg for 1 day, then stop).

Terms of reference:

Formulation of an organisation/group/committee's tasks

Therapeutic duplication:

One person using two drugs, usually unnecessarily, from the same therapeutic category at the same time.

Time-out:

A pause, just prior to performing a surgical or other procedure, during which any unanswered questions or confusion about patient, procedure, or site are resolved by the entire surgical or procedural team. Even when there is only one person doing the procedure, a brief pause to confirm the correct patient, procedure, and site is appropriate.

Timely (communication):

Communication of information within a reasonable time frame. This will depend on how important or time critical the information is to a patient's ongoing care or wellbeing, the context in which the service is provided and the clinical acuity of the patient.

Titration Order:

Order in which the dose is either progressively increased or decreased in response to the patient's status. Titrated orders shall include the starting medication dose, assessment parameters, and final endpoint (e.g., Dopamine 5mcg/kg/min. Titrate infusion rate every 15 minutes to maintain MAP of 60-80 mmHg).

Traceability:

The ability to trace the history, application or location of reusable medical devices. Some professional groups may refer to traceability as tracking.

Tracer methodology:

A process that JCI surveyors use during the on-site survey to analyze an organization's processes and systems by following individual patients through the organization's health care process in the sequence experienced by the patients. Depending on the health care setting, this may require surveyors to visit multiple care units, departments, or areas within an organization or a single care unit to "trace" the care rendered to a patient.

Patient tracer:

These occur during the on-site survey and focus on evaluating an individual patient's total care experience within a health care organization.

System tracer:

These occur during the on-site survey and focus on evaluating high-priority safety and quality-of-care issues on a system wide basis throughout the organization. Examples of such issues may include infection prevention and control, medication management, facility management, and the use of data.

Trainee:

An individual training in medical service after graduation from a medical educational institution. Different titles used for trainee include *intern*, *resident*, *house officer*, and *fellow*.

Training:

The development of knowledge and skills.

Transfer:

When a patient moves department, hospital or sector

Transcribing:

Any act by which medicinal products are written from one form of direction to administer to another is "transcribing" (whether hand written or computer generated).

Team A group of five to eight people consisting of a leader, facilitator, and members who are addressing an issue that impacts the operations of a process.

Transfusion history:

A list of transfusions a patient has had before presentation, including details of any adverse reactions to the transfusion and any special transfusion requirements. The completeness of the history will depend on the availability of information. It is expected that information will be obtained by reviewing any available referral information and interviewing the patient or their carer.

Transfusion reaction:

A transfusion reaction is a problem that occurs after a patient receives a transfusion of blood.

Transitions of care:

Situations when all or part of a patient's care is transferred between healthcare locations, providers, or levels of care within the same location, as the patient's conditions and care needs change.

Transmission-based precautions:

Extra work practices used in situations when standard precautions alone may not be enough to prevent transmission of infection. Transmission-based precautions are used in conjunction with standard precautions.

Treatment:

Examination, diagnosing, treatment of disease, obstetric aid, rehabilitation, care plus prevention and health promotion in relation to the individual patient.

Treatment goal:

The result/goal which is aimed to be obtained through initiation of treatment.

Treatment plan:

Recorded plan for assessment, treatment and care according to a specific disposition

Trending:

The evaluation of data collected over a period of time for the purpose of identifying patterns or changes.

Triage:

Triage is a process of prioritising patients based on the severity of their condition so as to treat as many as possible when resources are insufficient for all to be treated immediately.

Turn-around time for laboratory test:

A parameter of a clinical lab's efficiency, defined as the time between ordering a test / submitting a specimen to the lab till the time the results are made available.

Turn-around time for Blood banking services:

Time taken to be calculated from the time the request/ sample is received in the blood bank till the blood is cross matched/ reserved and available for transfusion. Blood Bank shall set upper limits for routine and emergency issues separately.

Turn-around time for Radiology services:

A parameter to monitor the efficiency of Radiological services, defined as the time between ordering the test/performing the test till the time results are made available.

U

Unified pharmaceutical documentation system:

Use of a joint prescription scheme (written/electronic) in the institution. The doctor registers his/her prescriptions in the scheme and the staff uses the same scheme for dispensing and drug administration.

Unstable patient:

A patient whose vital parameters need external assistance for their maintenance.

Urgent:

A classification of acuity used in triage systems to signify that the patient's condition is potentially life-threatening and requires timely assessment and possible intervention.

USP <797>:

A general chapter in the United States Pharmacopoeia that describes requirements for the preparation of sterile drugs. USP is a nongovernmental, scientific body responsible for setting standards for drug quality and related practices.

Utility system;

Organization wide systems and equipment that support the following: electrical distribution; emergency power; water; vertical and horizontal transport; heating, ventilating, and air conditioning; plumbing, boiler, and steam; piped gases; vacuum systems; or communication systems, including data-exchange systems. May also include systems for life support; surveillance, prevention, and control of infection; and environment support.

Utilization:

The use, patterns of use, or rates of use of a specified health care service. Overuse occurs when a health care service is provided under circumstances in which its potential for harm exceeds the possible benefits for a patient. Underuse is the failure to use a health care service that may have been necessary for a patient and may have produced a favorable outcome for a patient. Misuse occurs when an appropriate service has been selected but a preventable complication occurs. All three reflect a problem in quality of health care. They can increase mortality risk and diminish quality of life.

Utilization management:

The planning, organization, direction, and control of resources. How this relates to patient care by a health care organization is significant.

V

Validation:

Confirmation through the provision of objective evidence that the requirements for a specific intended use or application have been fulfilled. The checking of data for correction or for compliance with applicable standards, rules or conventions. These are the tests to determine whether an implemented system fulfills its requirements. It also refers to what extent does a test accurately measure what it purports to measure.

Values:

The fundamental beliefs that drive organisational behaviour and decision-making.

This refers to the guiding principles and behaviours that embody how an organisation and its people are expected to operate. Values reflect and reinforce the desired culture of an organisation.

Variation:

The differences in results obtained in measuring the same event more than once. The sources of variation can be grouped into two major classes: common causes and special causes. Too much variation often leads to waste and loss, such as the occurrence of undesirable patient health outcomes and increased cost of health services.

Ventilator Associated Adverse Events:

The new term, ventilator-associated event (VAE), groups all the conditions that result in a significant and sustained deterioration in oxygenation, (defined as a greater than 20% increase in the daily minimum fraction of inspired oxygen or an increase of at least 3 cm H₂O in the daily minimum positive end-expiratory pressure

(PEEP) to maintain oxygenation). It is imperative to understand that both infectious conditions (such as tracheitis, tracheobronchitis, and pneumonia) and non-infectious conditions (such as atelectasis, pulmonary embolism, pulmonary edema, ventilator-induced lung injury, and others) may fulfil this VAE definition. The definition is 3 tiered, as follows:

Tier 1: ventilator-associated condition (VAC) —the patient develops hypoxemia (as defined above) for a sustained period of more than 2 days. The etiology of the hypoxemia is not considered.

Tier 2: infection-related ventilator-associated complication (IVAC) —hypoxemia develops in the setting of generalized infection or inflammation, and antibiotics are instituted for a minimum of 4 days.

Tier 3: probable or possible ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) —additional laboratory evidence of white blood cells on Gram stain of material from a respiratory secretion specimen of acceptable quality, or (=possible)/and (=probable) presence of respiratory pathogens on quantitative cultures, in patients with IVAC. Additional criteria are also available for use in meeting the possible or Probable VAP (PVAP) definitions.

Verification:

The process of checking the validity and completeness of a clinical or other credential from the source that issued the credential.

Vision:

An overarching statement of the way an organisation wants to be, an ideal state of being at a future point. This refers to the desired future state of an organisation. The vision describes where the organisation is headed, what it intends to be, or how it wishes to be perceived in the future.

Vulnerable patient:

Those patients who are prone to injury and disease by virtue of their age, sex, physical, mental and immunological status, e.g. infants, elderly, physically- and mentally-challenged, semiconscious/ unconscious, those on immunosuppressive and/or chemotherapeutic agents.

W

Workforce:

All people working in a health service organisation, including clinicians and any other employed or contracted, locum, agency, student, volunteer or peer workers. The workforce can be members of the health service organisation or medical company

representatives providing technical support who have assigned roles and responsibilities for care of, administration of, support of, or involvement with patients in the health service organisation. See also clinician.

Written document:

A printed or electronic document furnishing information of a formal or informal nature for a specific purpose.